

Math 194: Mathematics of Finance

Spring 2025

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Course Notes and Solutions Compilation

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1. Financial Principles

No Arbitrage Principle

No Arbitrage \implies No opportunity for risk-free profit.

In other words, one cannot make money from nothing without bearing any risk.

One Price Principle

One Price \implies Two investments with the same (future) payoffs must have the same price.

If two assets or portfolios always generate the same payoff in all states of the world, then their prices today must coincide; otherwise an arbitrage would arise.

2. Horse Race Betting Example

Odds and Payoffs

Consider a simple horse race with two horses:

Sea Biscuit (SB)	odds = 1-1,
War Admiral (WA)	odds = 2-1.

Odds of m -to-1 mean that if you bet $\$n$ on that horse and the horse wins, you receive the sum $n + mn = n(1 + m)$. Equivalently, your *net* profit from that one bet is mn , plus you get your stake n back.

Betting rules in this example:

If you lose: 0, If you win with bet n at odds m -1 : $(m + 1)n$.

(Alternatively written as $m + n$ if m already represents the ratio portion.)

Specific Bets

Suppose you make two bets:

$$\begin{cases} \text{Bet } \$4 \text{ on Sea Biscuit (SB),} \\ \text{Bet } \$3 \text{ on War Admiral (WA).} \end{cases}$$

You have spent a total of $\$(4 + 3) = 7$.

Outcomes

If SB wins, its odds are 1-1 \implies net payoff from the $\$4$ bet = $4 \times (1 + 1) = 8$.
 \implies Total net = $8 - 7 = 1$.

If WA wins, its odds are 2-1 \implies net payoff from the $\$3$ bet = $3 \times (2 + 1) = 9$.
 \implies Total net = $9 - 7 = 2$.

So, no matter who wins, you receive a positive net payoff ($\$1$ if SB wins or $\$2$ if WA wins). Therefore, this is an **arbitrage** situation (risk-free profit strictly above 0).

3. Dutch Book Theorem Example

In horse-race or sports betting, a Dutch Book refers to a collection of bets for which a bookmaker (or gambler) can lock in a guaranteed profit regardless of the outcome. This typically occurs when the *implied probabilities* derived from the betting odds do not sum to 1.

Implied Probabilities

From the odds:

$$\text{Sea Biscuit (SB): 1-1 odds} \implies \mathbb{P}(\text{SB wins}) = \frac{1}{1+1} = \frac{1}{2},$$

$$\text{War Admiral (WA): 2-1 odds} \implies \mathbb{P}(\text{WA wins}) = \frac{1}{2+1} = \frac{1}{3}.$$

Summing these up gives

$$\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} = \frac{3}{6} + \frac{2}{6} = \frac{5}{6} < 1.$$

The sum of implied probabilities is only $\frac{5}{6}$, meaning the market (via those odds) is underpricing at least one of the outcomes. One can exploit this via appropriately sized bets on each outcome, guaranteeing a profit (*a Dutch Book*).

4. Forward Contract (No-Arbitrage Price)

Forward contract

Trade: at $t = 0$ party A agrees to *sell* one share to party B at time $t = 1$ for the fixed price K . Let S_0 and S_1 denote the spot prices at $t = 0$ and $t = 1$, and assume *zero* interest rates and no dividends.

Proposition 1 (Lecture-note version). *Under these assumptions the unique no-arbitrage forward price is*

$$K_{fwd} = S_0.$$

Intuition (see the formal arbitrage proofs below). If $K \neq S_0$ one can combine a spot position with the forward contract to lock-in a risk-free gain, violating the Arbitrage (or One-Price) Principle. \square

5. Arbitrage Arguments When $K \neq S_0$

Throughout we continue to assume *zero* borrowing costs and no dividends.

Case (a): $K > S_0$ (forward overpriced)

Step 1: (Initiate) Borrow $\$S_0$ and *buy* one share in the spot market. Simultaneously enter a *long* forward contract to **buy** the same share from B at $t = 1$ for $\$K$.

Step 2: (Settlement at $t = 1$) Deliver the share you already hold into the forward, paying $\$K$. Immediately repay the loan of $\$S_0$ (no interest is due).

$$\text{Net payoff} = K - S_0 > 0.$$

So the long-forward/spot-buy strategy is a risk-free profit. Therefore K cannot exceed S_0 .

Case (b): $K < S_0$ (forward under-priced)

Step 1: (Initiate) *Short-sell* one share today, receiving $\$S_0$ in cash. At the same time enter a *short* forward contract (obligation to *sell* a share) at price $\$K$.

Step 2: (Settlement at $t = 1$) Buy the share via the forward for $\$K$ and return it to cover the short sale.

$$\text{Net payoff} = S_0 - K > 0.$$

Therefore if $K < S_0$, the short-forward/short-sale strategy produces arbitrage.

$K = S_0$ is the only forward price consistent with no-arbitrage (in a zero-rate, no-dividend world).

6. Derivative: General Concept

- A **derivative** is a contract whose payoff is determined (or derived) from the value of some *underlying asset* (e.g. a stock, bond, or another derivative).
- The **price of a derivative** is the cost to set up that contract, i.e. the fair value of its *random payoff* under no-arbitrage conditions.

In this lecture, we will be focusing on *European* style derivatives, which can only be exercised at the final maturity time.

7. Example: A Put Option

A **put option** is the right (but not the obligation) to sell one share of stock for a fixed *strike price* K at some future time (e.g. time 1).

Because this is a European put option, the holder can only choose to exercise at the specified future time (maturity), and not before.

Simple Two-State Model

$$S_0 = 1,$$

$$S_1 = \begin{cases} 2, & \text{with probability } p, \\ \frac{1}{2}, & \text{with probability } 1 - p, \end{cases} \quad (\text{where } 0 < p < 1).$$

Put Option Payoff

Let the strike price be $K = 1.2$. Then at time 1, the *payoff* of the put is

$$C_1 = (K - S_1)^+ = \max\{K - S_1, 0\}.$$

Concretely:

$$C_1 = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } S_1 = 2 \quad (\text{since } K < S_1), \\ 1.2 - 0.5 = 0.7, & \text{if } S_1 = 0.5 \quad (\text{since } K > S_1). \end{cases}$$

We denote C_0 the fair price of this put option *today* (at time 0). We wish to determine C_0 via **no-arbitrage**.

8. Replicating Portfolio Method

We seek a portfolio of α shares of stock plus β units of bond (at zero interest) that *replicates* the put option payoff:

$$V_1 = \alpha S_1 + \beta \quad \text{such that} \quad V_1 = C_1 \text{ in both states.}$$

Since the bond is assumed to have zero interest, we treat its time-0 price as 1, and it remains 1 at time 1. So the portfolio's cost at time 0 is

$$V_0 = \alpha \cdot S_0 + \beta = \alpha + \beta \quad (\text{because } S_0 = 1).$$

If we can match the payoffs at time 1 in both up and down states, then by the *One Price Principle*,

$$C_0 = V_0 = \alpha + \beta.$$

Matching the Up/Down Payoffs

We need:

$$\begin{cases} (\text{up state}): C_1 = 0 = 2\alpha + \beta, \\ (\text{down state}): C_1 = 0.7 = \frac{1}{2}\alpha + \beta. \end{cases}$$

System of equations:

$$\begin{cases} 2\alpha + \beta = 0, \\ \frac{1}{2}\alpha + \beta = 0.7. \end{cases}$$

Subtract the first equation from the second:

$$\left(\frac{1}{2}\alpha + \beta\right) - (2\alpha + \beta) = 0.7 - 0,$$

which simplifies to

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2}\alpha - 2\alpha &= 0.7, \\ -\frac{3}{2}\alpha &= 0.7 \implies \alpha = -\frac{7}{15}. \end{aligned}$$

Then substitute α back into $2\alpha + \beta = 0$:

$$2\left(-\frac{7}{15}\right) + \beta = 0 \implies -\frac{14}{15} + \beta = 0 \implies \beta = \frac{14}{15}.$$

Therefore

$$(\alpha, \beta) = \left(-\frac{7}{15}, \frac{14}{15}\right).$$

Observe that here $\alpha < 0$ indicates we are *short selling* the stock (i.e. borrowing and then selling those shares). This portfolio α and β replicates the put option's payoff exactly.

Therefore,

$$C_0 = V_0 = \alpha + \beta = -\frac{7}{15} + \frac{14}{15} = \frac{7}{15}.$$

$$\boxed{C_0 = \frac{7}{15} \approx 0.4667.}$$

Check via Risk-Neutral Pricing

In a one-period binomial model with zero interest and no dividends, the *risk-neutral measure* p^* is set so that the *expected price* of the stock equals its current price. Specifically, solve:

$$S_0 = \mathbb{E}^*[S_1] = p^* \cdot 2 + (1 - p^*) \cdot \frac{1}{2}.$$

Since $S_0 = 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &= 2p^* + \frac{1}{2}(1 - p^*) = 2p^* + \frac{1}{2} - \frac{p^*}{2} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{3}{2}p^*, \\ \implies \frac{1}{2} &= \frac{3}{2}p^* \implies p^* = \frac{1}{3}. \end{aligned}$$

Now the risk-neutral expected payoff of the put option (since the discount rate is 0) is:

$$\mathbb{E}^*[C_1] = p^* \cdot 0 + (1 - p^*) \cdot 0.7 = \left(1 - \frac{1}{3}\right) 0.7 = \frac{2}{3} \times 0.7 = \frac{14}{30} = \frac{7}{15}.$$

This matches the replicating-portfolio price:

$$C_0 = \frac{7}{15}.$$

Therefore, there is no arbitrage.

In general, the probability p you might assign to $S_1 = 2$ need not equal p^* , so the *risk-neutral measure* p^* is not necessarily the real-world probability. Under p^* , the *discounted* stock price is a martingale, and this measure is used for pricing by the no-arbitrage principle.

9. Compound Interest & Continuous Compounding**Finite Compounding**

If P_0 is an initial principal, r is the annual interest rate, and n is the number of compounding periods per year, then over t years, the value grows to:

$$P_t = P_0 \left(1 + \frac{r}{n}\right)^{nt}.$$

Illustratively, each compounding step multiplies the principal by $\left(1 + \frac{r}{n}\right)$.

Continuous Compounding Limit

As $n \rightarrow \infty$,

$$P_t = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_0 \left(1 + \frac{r}{n}\right)^{nt} = P_0 e^{rt}.$$

This uses the classical limit:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)^n = e.$$

10. Call-Put Parity**Payoff Diagrams (No Dividends, Zero Rates)**

Call Option Payoff at maturity T :

$$C_T = \begin{cases} 0, & S_T \leq K, \\ S_T - K, & S_T > K. \end{cases}$$

Put Option Payoff at maturity T :

$$P_T = \begin{cases} K - S_T, & S_T \leq K, \\ 0, & S_T > K. \end{cases}$$

Algebraic Parity

Note that

$$C_T - P_T = (S_T - K)^+ - (K - S_T)^+ = S_T - K,$$

because exactly one of $(S_T - K)^+$ or $(K - S_T)^+$ is positive, and they differ by $S_T - K$. If there are no dividends and no interest rates (for simplicity), then by the One Price Principle at time 0,

$$C_0 - P_0 = S_0 - K.$$

If there is a risk-free rate $r > 0$ and time-to-maturity T , then the present value of K is Ke^{-rT} , and the parity becomes

$$C_0 - P_0 = S_0 - Ke^{-rT}.$$

This relationship is called the **Call-Put Parity** and it must hold to prevent arbitrage.

12. Binomial Model (Cox–Ross–Rubinstein)

- **Discrete time steps:** $t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T$.
- **Bond (risk-free)** grows deterministically:

$$B_t = B_0 (1 + r)^t, \quad \text{where } r \geq 0.$$

- **Stock (risky)** follows an *up-down* multiplier process:

$$S_t = S_0 \underbrace{\xi_1 \cdot \xi_2 \cdots \xi_t}_{\text{each } \xi_i \in \{u, d\}}.$$

Typically, $u > 1$ (up factor) and $d < 1$ (down factor). This simple framework is the basis of the *Cox–Ross–Rubinstein (CRR)* binomial model for option pricing.

In addition, we usually require the inequality $d < 1 + r < u$ in order to avoid trivial or degenerate situations (e.g. immediate arbitrage).

Conclusion: All these examples illustrate the central no-arbitrage approach: *if two portfolios or strategies have the same future payoffs, their current prices must match.* Otherwise, one can construct a risk-free profit (arbitrage). In simple discrete models (like the two-state or CRR binomial), we can often replicate a derivative payoff exactly and deduce its price via the *replicating portfolio* and/or via a *risk-neutral probability* measure.

Appendix

- Trading takes place in stocks, bonds, currencies, mortgages, etc.
- We will analyse these markets using *probability theory* and *stochastic processes*.
- **L. Bachelier (1900)** was the first to model stock prices with Brownian motion.
- *Math 194* works purely in **discrete time**; *Math 294* extends the theory to discrete *and* continuous time.

Supplemental Textbooks Notes

Definition (Viable Financial Market). A market is *viable* when it admits no arbitrage opportunities; in liquid markets any fleeting mis-pricings are competed away so quickly that our models should rule them out from the outset.

Forward vs. Futures. Both contracts lock in a price today for exchange at a future date, but forwards trade *over-the-counter* (customised, bilateral) whereas futures are exchange-traded, settle daily through *marking-to-market*, and specify a delivery *month* rather than a fixed date.

European vs. American Options. A European option may be exercised only at maturity T ; an American option may be exercised at any time in $[0, T]$. Most exchange-traded stock options are American style.

Lot Size Convention. Exchange-listed stock options are almost always written on *100 shares*, matching the standard trading “round lot.”

Speculation and Hedging. Call options give leveraged upside with limited downside (premium paid), making them popular speculative tools; conversely, buying a put can hedge a long stock position against large declines.

European Contingent Claim (ECC). Formally, an ECC is an F_T -measurable payoff X received at a single future date T . An arbitrage-free price exists only when the underlying *primary* market itself is viable (no arbitrage).

Self-Financing Trading Strategy. A discrete-time portfolio $\{(\alpha_t, \beta_t)\}_{t=1}^T$ (shares of stock, units of bond) is *self-financing* if

$$\alpha_t S_t + \beta_t B_t = \alpha_{t+1} S_t + \beta_{t+1} B_t, \quad t = 1, \dots, T-1,$$

so changes in holdings are paid for by the portfolio itself with no external cash injections.

Arbitrage Opportunity (Model Definition). A strategy with $V_0 = 0$, $V_T \geq 0$ and $\mathbb{P}(V_T > 0) > 0$ constitutes an arbitrage; any sound pricing model must rule out such strategies.

11. Assumptions for the Models

In all of these examples, certain idealized assumptions are typically made:

1. No transaction costs (e.g. no commissions, no bid–ask spreads).
2. No dividends or other payouts from the underlying asset.
3. Market is sufficiently liquid that you can always buy/sell at the market price without affecting that price.
4. Each investor is small compared to the market (price taker).
5. Unlimited borrowing (of stock or money) is possible at the risk-free rate (or zero if not stated).

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LECTURE 3
§ 2.1, 2.2

Time:

$$t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T \quad (\text{"discrete time"}).$$

Investments:

- A **stock** with price S_t at time t , evolving randomly. We write

$$S_t = S_{t-1} \cdot \xi_t \quad (S_0 = \text{constant}),$$

where the random variables $\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_T$ are i.i.d. with

$$\xi_t = \begin{cases} u, & \text{with probability } \varphi, \\ d, & \text{with probability } 1 - \varphi \end{cases} \quad (t = 1, 2, \dots, T).$$

- A **bond** (risk-free asset) with (non-random) time- t price

$$B_t = B_0 \cdot (1 + r)^t = B_{t-1} \cdot (1 + r).$$

Often, we normalize $B_0 = 1$ for simplicity. $r \geq 0$ is the one-period interest rate.

Condition: We assume

$$0 < \varphi < 1 \quad \text{and} \quad d < 1 + r < u.$$

Remark 1. Why do we insist on $d < 1 + r < u$?

- If $1 + r \leq d$, then there is no point in putting any \$ into the bond—there is simply *nothing to think about*.
- If $1 + r \geq u$, then likewise one would put all \$ in the bond and *take a nap*.

Portfolio, Trading Strategy

A **trading strategy** is a collection

$$\Phi = \{(\alpha_t, \beta_t) : t = 1, 2, \dots, T\}$$

where:

$$\alpha_t = (\text{number of units of stock held during the interval } (t - 1, t])$$

and

$$\beta_t = (\text{number of units of the bond held during the interval } (t - 1, t]).$$

Each α_t and β_t is allowed to depend on the stock prices $\{S_1, \dots, S_{t-1}\}$ observed up to time $t - 1$. In addition, we assume the strategy is *self-financing*, meaning no extra money is added or removed from the portfolio after time 0. The only changes in the holdings (α_t, β_t) between time steps are due to rebalancing based on the observed stock prices, without infusion or withdrawal of capital. This implies that the cost of adjusting the portfolio at each time is covered precisely by selling or buying shares of the stock and bond.

Often, we normalize $B_0 = 1$. Then the *value* of the portfolio Φ at time t is

$$V_t(\Phi) = \alpha_t S_t + \beta_t B_t.$$

Case of $T = 1$

When $T = 1$, a trading strategy is simply a pair $\phi = (\alpha_1, \beta_1)$ of real numbers. At time 0 (the only “decision time” here), one decides how many units of the stock α_1 and how many units of the bond β_1 to hold over $(0, 1]$.

Since there is no future period to rebalance, α_1 and β_1 do not depend on the stock price in this one-period model. The self-financing condition is automatically satisfied because there is only a single trading date.

- The time-0 *value* of ϕ is

$$V_0(\phi) = \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1.$$

(We used $B_0 = 1$.)

- The time-1 *value* of ϕ is

$$V_1(\phi) = \alpha_1 S_1 + \beta_1 (1 + r).$$

Contingent Claim (European, $T = 1$ for now)

A **contingent claim** X is a random variable that pays off at time $T = 1$. Since S_1 can take only two values in the one-period binomial model, we label them:

$$X^u \quad \text{if } S_1 = S_0 u, \quad X^d \quad \text{if } S_1 = S_0 d.$$

In this one-period setting, the sample space consists of exactly two outcomes, often referred to as “up” and “down,” each assigned strictly positive probabilities φ and $1 - \varphi$. Because there are only these two points in the sample space, events of probability zero do not arise. Consequently, any nonnegative random payoff that is strictly positive in at least one outcome will also have strictly positive expectation.

Question: How much is X worth at time 0?

Plan (One Price Principle)

Idea: *Replicate* X with a suitable portfolio. That is, choose a trading strategy $\phi = (\alpha, \beta)$ so that

$$V_1(\phi) \equiv X.$$

Then, by the “no-arbitrage” or “One Price” principle, the time-0 value

$$V_0(\phi)$$

must be the correct time-0 price for X . Otherwise, an arbitrage opportunity would arise (we will show this rigorously in the proof below).

Finding ϕ

We want

$$V_1(\phi) = \alpha_1 S_1 + \beta_1 (1 + r) \equiv X.$$

In the up-state,

$$\alpha_1 S_0 u + \beta_1 (1 + r) = X^u.$$

In the down-state,

$$\alpha_1 S_0 d + \beta_1 (1 + r) = X^d.$$

This is a system of two linear equations in the two unknowns α_1 and β_1 .

Solving the System

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_1 S_0 u + \beta_1 (1+r) = X^u, \\ \alpha_1 S_0 d + \beta_1 (1+r) = X^d. \end{cases}$$

Subtract the second equation from the first:

$$\alpha_1 S_0 u - \alpha_1 S_0 d = X^u - X^d \implies \alpha_1 S_0 (u - d) = X^u - X^d.$$

Therefore,

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{X^u - X^d}{S_0 (u - d)}.$$

Then substitute α_1 into either of the original equations to solve for β_1 . For instance, from

$$\alpha_1 S_0 u + \beta_1 (1+r) = X^u,$$

we get

$$\beta_1 = \frac{X^u - \alpha_1 S_0 u}{1+r}.$$

Substituting α_1 just found, one obtains the standard result (often shown in a compressed version):

$$\boxed{\alpha_1 = \frac{X^u - X^d}{S_0 (u - d)}, \quad \beta_1 = \frac{u X^d - d X^u}{u - d} \cdot \frac{1}{1+r}.$$

Provided $d < 1+r < u$, we have $u - d > 0$, so everything is well-defined.

Therefore the time-0 value of the replicating strategy is

$$V_0(\phi) = \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1 = \frac{X^u - X^d}{u - d} + \frac{u X^d - d X^u}{u - d} \cdot \frac{1}{1+r}.$$

One can show that this simplifies to the usual risk-neutral pricing formula:

$$V_0(\phi) = \frac{1}{1+r} \left\{ X^u \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d} + X^d \frac{u - (1+r)}{u - d} \right\} = \frac{1}{1+r} [X^u \phi^* + X^d (1 - \phi^*)],$$

where

$$\phi^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d}, \quad 0 < \phi^* < 1$$

because $d < 1+r < u$. We also write

$$V_0(\phi) = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[X] = \mathbb{E}^*\left[\frac{X}{1+r}\right].$$

Here $\mathbb{E}^*[\cdot]$ denotes expectation under the *risk-neutral* (or *pricing*) probability measure \mathbb{P}^* , which is defined by

$$\mathbb{P}^*(\text{up}) = \phi^*, \quad \mathbb{P}^*(\text{down}) = 1 - \phi^*.$$

Under \mathbb{P}^* , the discounted stock price $\left\{\frac{S_t}{B_t}\right\}$ becomes a *martingale*:

$$\mathbb{E}^*[S_1] = (1+r) S_0.$$

Therefore, one can bypass the direct solution for α_1 and β_1 if only the price is desired: simply compute $\frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[X]$ under the risk-neutral probabilities. For multi-period binomial models with $T > 1$, a similar replication argument applies step by step, leading again to the same risk-neutral pricing principle.

Theorem (No-Arbitrage Price)

Statement. *The unique no-arbitrage price of the claim X is*

$$C_0 = V_0(\phi) = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[X].$$

No portfolio can achieve a riskless profit if the market prices X at this level.

Proof of Uniqueness and No-Arbitrage

Let C_0 be the market's time-0 price of the claim X . Let $\phi = (\alpha, \beta)$ be the *replicating* strategy for X (constructed as above) with time-0 cost $V_0(\phi)$.

(a) $C_0 > V_0(\phi)$.

In this case, sell one unit of X at time 0 for C_0 . Use $V_0(\phi)$ of that cash to *buy* the replicating portfolio ϕ . The leftover $(C_0 - V_0(\phi))$ can be invested in the bond at rate r .

At time 1:

$$\underbrace{V_1(\phi)}_{=X} - \underbrace{X}_{\text{we owe one unit of } X} = 0.$$

So the replicating strategy ϕ exactly delivers the needed payoff X . Meanwhile, we have

$$(C_0 - V_0(\phi))(1+r) > 0 \quad (\text{riskless profit}).$$

So we have an *arbitrage* if $C_0 > V_0(\phi)$.

(b) $C_0 < V_0(\phi)$.

In this case, we *buy* one unit of X for C_0 , and simultaneously *short* the replicating portfolio $-\phi$. The net cost at time 0 is

$$C_0 - V_0(\phi) = -(V_0(\phi) - C_0).$$

Since $V_0(\phi) - C_0 > 0$, we *gain* that much up front. Put it in the bond at rate r .

At time 1:

$$\text{we receive } X, \quad \text{but } V_1(-\phi) = -V_1(\phi) = -X.$$

So $X + V_1(-\phi) = 0$. Meanwhile, the money $(V_0(\phi) - C_0)$ in the bond grows to $(V_0(\phi) - C_0)(1+r)$, which is again a riskless profit.

(c) $C_0 = V_0(\phi)$.

Suppose there were an arbitrage strategy $\psi = (\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta})$ with

$$V_0(\psi) = 0, \quad V_1(\psi) \geq 0 \text{ almost surely, and } V_1(\psi) \text{ is strictly } > 0 \text{ with positive probability.}$$

Then look at the *risk-neutral expectation*:

$$\mathbb{E}^*[V_1(\psi)] = \mathbb{E}^*[\tilde{\alpha}_1 S_1 + \tilde{\beta}_1 (1+r)] = \tilde{\alpha}_1 \mathbb{E}^*[S_1] + \tilde{\beta}_1 (1+r).$$

But $\mathbb{E}^*[S_1] = (1+r)S_0$ and $S_0, B_0 = 1$ imply

$$\mathbb{E}^*[S_1] = (1+r)S_0, \quad V_0(\psi) = \tilde{\alpha}_1 S_0 + \tilde{\beta}_1 = 0.$$

Therefore,

$$\mathbb{E}^*[V_1(\psi)] = \tilde{\alpha}_1 (1+r)S_0 + \tilde{\beta}_1 (1+r) = (1+r)(\tilde{\alpha}_1 S_0 + \tilde{\beta}_1) = (1+r)V_0(\psi) = 0.$$

On the other hand, if $V_1(\psi) \geq 0$ a.s. and $V_1(\psi) > 0$ with positive probability, then $\mathbb{E}^*[V_1(\psi)] > 0$. This is a contradiction. Therefore no such ψ can exist. Therefore, the price C_0 must equal $V_0(\phi)$, and no arbitrage arises when $C_0 = V_0(\phi)$. So $C_0 = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[X]$ is the unique no-arbitrage price for the claim X . \square

Remark 2. Q. How did we use the assumption $V_1(\psi) \geq 0$ here? Because $V_1(\psi) \geq 0$ almost surely and $V_1(\psi) > 0$ with positive probability implies $\mathbb{E}^*[V_1(\psi)] > 0$, contradicting the zero expectation we just computed.

Example

Consider a call-type payoff

$$X = (S_1 - K)^+ = \max\{S_1 - K, 0\}.$$

Suppose

$$S_0 = 1, \quad u = 2, \quad d = 1, \quad r = \frac{1}{4}, \quad K = 1.5.$$

Then the up-state payoff is

$$X^u = (S_0 u - K)^+ = (2 - 1.5)^+ = \frac{1}{2},$$

while the down-state payoff is

$$X^d = (S_0 d - K)^+ = (1 - 1.5)^+ = 0.$$

In this one-period binomial model, the risk-neutral probability is

$$\phi^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d} = \frac{\frac{5}{4} - 1}{2 - 1} = \frac{1}{4}.$$

Therefore, the fair price of the claim is

$$C_0 = \frac{1}{1+r} \left[\phi^* X^u + (1 - \phi^*) X^d \right] = \frac{1}{1.25} \left[\frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \right] = \frac{1}{1.25} \cdot \frac{1}{8} = \frac{1}{10}.$$

One can also verify directly (by solving the system as before) that the replicating portfolio is

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{X^u - X^d}{S_0(u - d)} = \frac{\frac{1}{2} - 0}{1 \times (2 - 1)} = \frac{1}{2},$$

So,

$$\beta_1 = \frac{uX^d - dX^u}{u - d} \cdot \frac{1}{1+r} = \frac{2 \times 0 - 1 \times \frac{1}{2}}{1} \cdot \frac{1}{1.25} = -\frac{2}{5}.$$

So,

$$V_0(\phi) = \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1 = \frac{1}{2} \times 1 + \left(-\frac{2}{5}\right) = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{2}{5} = \frac{1}{10}.$$

As found above, $C_0 = \frac{1}{10}$ is the unique no-arbitrage price.

Supplemental Textbook Notes

CRR Stock Dynamics. In the Cox–Ross–Rubinstein model the stock starts at $S_0 > 0$ and evolves via $S_t = S_{t-1}\xi_t$ with i.i.d. factors $\xi_t \in \{u, d\}$, $\mathbb{P}(\xi_t = u) = p$, and parameters satisfying $0 < d < 1 + r < u$.

Risk-Free Asset. The bond (numéraire) grows deterministically: $B_t = (1+r)^t$, so one unit today is worth $(1+r)$ at each subsequent integer time step.

Filtration. At each t the information set is $\mathcal{F}_t = \sigma(S_0, S_1, \dots, S_t)$; admissible trading rules may depend only on prices revealed so far.

Trading Strategy. A strategy is a sequence $\{(\alpha_t, \beta_t)\}_{t=1}^T$ with $\alpha_t, \beta_t \in \mathbb{R}$ and α_t, β_t being \mathcal{F}_{t-1} -measurable (capturing “no future peeking”).

Self-Financing Condition. The strategy is self-financing if $\alpha_t S_t + \beta_t B_t = \alpha_{t+1} S_t + \beta_{t+1} B_t$ for $t = 1, \dots, T-1$; trading is funded entirely by rebalancing the current portfolio.

Portfolio Value. Given a strategy ϕ , its wealth process is $V_t(\phi) = \alpha_t S_t + \beta_t B_t$, with initial cost $V_0(\phi) = \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1$.

Arbitrage Opportunity. A self-financing strategy with $V_0 = 0$, $V_T \geq 0$ everywhere, and $\mathbb{P}(V_T > 0) > 0$ constitutes arbitrage.

Recombining Tree Note. Although different up–down paths may lead to the same numerical S_t , retaining the full path tree (rather than collapsing nodes) is essential when a payoff depends on the entire trajectory, not just the terminal price.

Math 194 — Spring 2025

LECTURE 4

§ 2.2

Lecture 3 hinted to the main theorem about pricing a contingent claim using the no-arbitrage principle. In this lecture, we focus on the single-period (one-step) binomial model, where the stock price can go either “up” or “down” at time 1. Our sample space thus has two points, each assigned some positive probability under the real measure, though the replicating strategy formulas will not actually depend on that probability.

Binomial Model Setup

Market Description

- Single-period model: $T = 1$.
- Constant risk-free rate $r \geq 0$.
- Stock (or asset) price S_0 at time 0. At time 1, the stock price can be either uS_0 (“up”) or dS_0 (“down”). The parameters satisfy: $0 < d < 1 + r < u$.
- A *contingent claim* X is a random payoff at time 1. We denote its possible payoffs by:

$$X^u = X(\omega = u), \quad X^d = X(\omega = d).$$

Because there is just one time step, our probability space can be taken as $\Omega = \{\text{up}, \text{down}\}$. If the real-world probability of “up” is p , the replicating-strategy formulas do *not* depend on p .

The goal: *determine a fair (arbitrage-free) price* for X at time 0.

Portfolio and Pricing in One-Period Binomial Model

A **trading strategy** Φ consists of: $\Phi = (\alpha_1, \beta_1)$, where α_1 is the (constant) number of units of the stock held, β_1 is the (constant) amount of cash invested in the bond (or bank account). Note that it is permissible for α_1 or β_1 to be negative: one can “short” the stock or borrow against the bond.

- The time-0 value of Φ is: $V_0(\Phi) = \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1$.
- The time-1 value of Φ will be $V_1(\Phi) = \alpha_1 S_1 + \beta_1(1 + r)$.

For a contingent claim X , a strategy Φ **replicates** X if

$$V_1(\Phi) = X \quad \text{in both up and down states.}$$

When such a replicating portfolio exists (and the market is arbitrage-free), the no-arbitrage price of X at time 0 is $V_0(\Phi)$.

Key Formulas in the Binomial Model

We define the **risk-neutral probability** p^* by

$$p^* := \frac{1 + r - d}{u - d} \quad \text{and observe } p^* \in (0, 1),$$

because $d < 1 + r < u$.

Remark on the “star” notation: we use a star in two ways. Here, p^* is the risk-neutral probability, and X^* (defined below) denotes the discounted payoff $X/(1 + r)$. Though the same symbol “*” appears, they signify different ideas: the measure \mathbb{P}^* under which the discounted stock is a martingale, and the “*” on X^* simply means “discounted payoff.”

Replication in One-Period Model

Given X^u and X^d , one may construct a replicating strategy for X by solving:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1 = V_0(\Phi), \\ \alpha_1(uS_0) + \beta_1(1+r) = X^u, \\ \alpha_1(dS_0) + \beta_1(1+r) = X^d. \end{cases}$$

A standard shortcut to these solutions is:

$$\alpha_1 := \frac{X^u - X^d}{u - d} \frac{1}{S_0}, \quad \beta_1 := \frac{uX^d - dX^u}{u - d} \frac{1}{1+r}.$$

Then the arbitrage-free price for X at time 0 is:

$$V_0(\Phi) = \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1.$$

Risk-Neutral Valuation

One can also compute:

$$p^* = \frac{1+r-d}{u-d} \implies \mathbb{E}^*(S_1) = p^*(uS_0) + (1-p^*)(dS_0) = (1+r)S_0.$$

In general for a payoff X , define:

$$X^* := \frac{X}{1+r}.$$

Then the arbitrage-free price of X at time 0 is:

$$C_0 = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*(X) = \mathbb{E}^*(X^*).$$

Here, \mathbb{E}^* denotes the expectation under the *risk-neutral measure* \mathbb{P}^* that places probability p^* on the up-state and $1-p^*$ on the down-state.

No-Arbitrage and Expanded Market

Arbitrage and Portfolio Value

Consider $\Psi = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$, a portfolio that now also allows a holding γ_1 units of the claim X .

$$\Psi = (\alpha_1, \beta_1, \gamma_1).$$

Here,

$$V_0(\Psi) = \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1 + \gamma_1 C_0, \quad V_1(\Psi) = \alpha_1 S_1 + \beta_1(1+r) + \gamma_1 X.$$

An **arbitrage** is any such Ψ with:

$$V_0(\Psi) = 0, \quad V_1(\Psi) \geq 0 \text{ in all states, and } \mathbb{P}(V_1(\Psi) > 0) > 0.$$

Equivalently, in a finite sample space with strictly positive probabilities for each state, having $V_1(\Psi) \geq 0$ everywhere and > 0 in at least one state implies $\mathbb{E}[V_1(\Psi)] > 0$ under *any* probability measure. So an arbitrage strategy is a nonnegative-cost-free payoff that is strictly positive with positive probability. In other words, an investment that costs nothing at time 0, is never negative at time 1, and has a strictly positive payoff with positive probability.

Risk-Neutral Pricing and the Martingale Property

Theorem (Risk-Neutral Pricing)

Statement.

$\mathbb{E}^*(X^*)$ is the unique no-arbitrage price of the claim X ,

where $X^* = \frac{X}{1+r}$.

Martingale Viewpoint

$$\mathbb{E}^*(S_1) = (1+r)S_0 \implies \left\{ S_0, \frac{1}{1+r}S_1 \right\}$$

forms a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale:

$$S_0 = \mathbb{E}^*\left(\frac{1}{1+r}S_1\right).$$

We will see in multi-period extensions that this martingale property remains key to no-arbitrage pricing. For now, with just one step, it's enough that the discounted stock has the same value in expectation under \mathbb{P}^* at time 1 as it does at time 0.

Proof of the No-Arbitrage Pricing Theorem

Let C_0 be the time-0 price of X , and let

$$V_0 := \mathbb{E}^*(X^*) = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*(X).$$

We must show:

- If $C_0 > V_0$, then an arbitrage exists.
- If $C_0 < V_0$, then an arbitrage exists.
- If $C_0 = V_0$, then no arbitrage exists.

Case (a): $C_0 > V_0$

Let $\tilde{\Phi} = (\hat{\alpha}_1, \hat{\beta}_1)$ be a replicating strategy for X . That is,

$$V_1(\tilde{\Phi}) = \hat{\alpha}_1 S_1 + \hat{\beta}_1(1+r) = X \quad (\text{both up and down}).$$

We *sell* one unit of X at time 0 for C_0 . With that cash:

1. Invest V_0 in $\tilde{\Phi}$ (the replicating portfolio).
2. Put the remaining $(C_0 - V_0)$ in the bond.

Therefore define the portfolio:

$$\Psi = \left(\hat{\alpha}_1, \hat{\beta}_1 + (C_0 - V_0), -1 \right).$$

Here, $\gamma = -1$ means we have effectively sold one unit of X .

Value at time 0

$$V_0(\Psi) = \hat{\alpha}_1 S_0 + \hat{\beta}_1 + (C_0 - V_0) - C_0 = V_0 + C_0 - V_0 - C_0 = 0.$$

Value at time 1

$$\begin{aligned}
V_1(\Psi) &= \hat{\alpha}_1 S_1 + \hat{\beta}_1(1+r) + (C_0 - V_0)(1+r) - X \\
&= V_1(\tilde{\Phi}) + (C_0 - V_0)(1+r) - X \\
&= X + (C_0 - V_0)(1+r) - X \\
&= (C_0 - V_0)(1+r) > 0,
\end{aligned}$$

since $C_0 > V_0 \implies (C_0 - V_0) > 0$. This construction yields a portfolio Ψ with zero initial cost and strictly positive payoff in both up and down states. Therefore, Ψ is an arbitrage.

Case (b): $C_0 < V_0$

Similarly, we *buy* the claim X for C_0 , and *short* (i.e. invest a negative amount in) the replicating portfolio $\tilde{\Phi}$. That is:

- Buy +1 unit of X .
- Invest $-V_0$ in $-\tilde{\Phi}$.
- Put the remaining $(V_0 - C_0)$ in the bond.

Formally define

$$\Psi = \left(-\hat{\alpha}_1, -\hat{\beta}_1 + (V_0 - C_0), 1 \right).$$

Then

Value at time 0

$$\begin{aligned}
V_0(\Psi) &= (-\hat{\alpha}_1) S_0 + (-\hat{\beta}_1 + (V_0 - C_0)) + 1 \cdot C_0 \\
&= -\hat{\alpha}_1 S_0 - \hat{\beta}_1 + (V_0 - C_0) + C_0 \\
&= -(\hat{\alpha}_1 S_0 + \hat{\beta}_1) + V_0 - C_0 + C_0 \\
&= -V_0 + V_0 = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

(Note $\hat{\alpha}_1 S_0 + \hat{\beta}_1 = V_0$, the cost of replicating X at time 0.)

Value at time 1

$$\begin{aligned}
V_1(\Psi) &= -\hat{\alpha}_1 S_1 - \hat{\beta}_1(1+r) + (V_0 - C_0)(1+r) + X \\
&= -\left(\hat{\alpha}_1 S_1 + \hat{\beta}_1(1+r) \right) + (V_0 - C_0)(1+r) + X \\
&= -V_1(\tilde{\Phi}) + (V_0 - C_0)(1+r) + X \\
&= -X + (V_0 - C_0)(1+r) + X \\
&= (V_0 - C_0)(1+r) > 0 \quad (\text{since } V_0 > C_0).
\end{aligned}$$

Again, we obtain an arbitrage.

Case (c): $C_0 = V_0$ (No Arbitrage)

We must argue that if $C_0 = V_0 = \mathbb{E}^*(X^*)$, *no* arbitrage is possible in this market with the claim X available for trade. Suppose, for contradiction, that a portfolio

$$\Psi = (\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$$

(including possibly γ units of X) is an arbitrage. Then

$$V_0(\Psi) = \alpha S_0 + \beta + \gamma C_0 = 0,$$

and

$$V_1(\Psi) = \alpha S_1 + \beta(1+r) + \gamma X \geq 0 \text{ in all states,}$$

with strict positivity in at least one state. In probabilistic terms:

$$\mathbb{P}(V_1(\Psi) > 0) > 0 \iff \mathbb{E}[V_1(\Psi)] > 0.$$

Under the risk-neutral measure \mathbb{P}^* , we compute

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}^*[V_1(\Psi)] &= \mathbb{E}^*[\alpha S_1 + \beta(1+r) + \gamma X] \\ &= \alpha \mathbb{E}^*(S_1) + \beta(1+r) + \gamma \mathbb{E}^*(X) \\ &= \alpha(1+r)S_0 + \beta(1+r) + \gamma((1+r)C_0) \\ &= (1+r)(\alpha S_0 + \beta + \gamma C_0) \\ &= (1+r)V_0(\Psi) = (1+r) \cdot 0 = 0. \end{aligned}$$

But for Ψ to be an arbitrage, we would need $\mathbb{E}^*[V_1(\Psi)] > 0$. This contradiction shows that *no* arbitrage can occur when $C_0 = V_0$.

Ex: Pricing a Call Option in the Binomial Model

Consider a call option with payoff

$$X = (S_1 - K)^+ = \max\{S_1 - K, 0\}.$$

Suppose:

$$S_0 = 1, \quad u = 2, \quad d = 1, \quad r = \frac{1}{4}, \quad K = 1.5.$$

Then:

$$S_1^u = 2 \times 1 = 2, \quad S_1^d = 1 \times 1 = 1.$$

Therefore the option payoffs are

$$X^u = (2 - 1.5)^+ = 0.5, \quad X^d = (1 - 1.5)^+ = 0.$$

Next,

$$p^* = \frac{1+r-d}{u-d} = \frac{1.25-1}{2-1} = 0.25.$$

The replicating strategy coefficients become:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_1 &= \frac{X^u - X^d}{u-d} \cdot \frac{1}{S_0} = \frac{0.5-0}{2-1} \cdot \frac{1}{1} = 0.5, \\ \beta_1 &= \frac{uX^d - dX^u}{u-d} \cdot \frac{1}{1+r} = \frac{2 \cdot 0 - 1 \cdot 0.5}{2-1} \cdot \frac{1}{1.25} = -\frac{0.5}{1} \cdot \frac{1}{1.25} = -\frac{2}{5}. \end{aligned}$$

So,

$$\Phi = \left(\alpha_1, \beta_1 \right) = \left(0.5, -\frac{2}{5} \right).$$

We check:

$$V_1(\Phi) = 0.5 \cdot S_1 + \left(-\frac{2}{5}\right) \cdot (1.25) \quad \text{in up/down states.}$$

$$\text{Up state: } S_1 = 2 \implies V_1(\Phi) = 0.5 \cdot 2 + \left(-\frac{2}{5}\right) \cdot 1.25 = 1 - 0.5 = 0.5 = X^u.$$

$$\text{Down state: } S_1 = 1 \implies V_1(\Phi) = 0.5 \cdot 1 + \left(-\frac{2}{5}\right) \cdot 1.25 = 0.5 - 0.5 = 0 = X^d.$$

Therefore, Φ replicates X . Its cost at time 0 is

$$C_0 = V_0(\Phi) = 0.5 \cdot 1 + \left(-\frac{2}{5}\right) = 0.5 - 0.4 = 0.1.$$

Therefore, the arbitrage-free *price* of the call option is

$$\boxed{C_0 = 0.1.}$$

Alternatively, one could use the risk-neutral valuation directly:

$$\mathbb{E}^*(X) = p^*(0.5) + (1 - p^*)(0) = 0.25 \times 0.5 = 0.125,$$

and

$$\frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*(X) = \frac{0.125}{1.25} = 0.1.$$

Both methods agree.

Summary of Binomial Model & Key Formulas

1. Risk-Neutral Measure.

$$p^* = \frac{1+r-d}{u-d} \in (0,1).$$

Under \mathbb{P}^* ,

$$\mathbb{E}^*(S_1) = (1+r)S_0.$$

2. Replication.

 For a payoff X with X^u, X^d ,

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{X^u - X^d}{u-d} \frac{1}{S_0}, \quad \beta_1 = \frac{uX^d - dX^u}{u-d} \frac{1}{1+r}.$$

Then the no-arbitrage price of X is

$$V_0(\Phi) = \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1.$$

3. Risk-Neutral Valuation.

 Alternatively, the unique no-arbitrage price can be computed by

$$C_0 = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*(X).$$

4. No-Arbitrage Theorem.

 $C_0 = \mathbb{E}^*(X^*)$ is the *unique* price that admits no arbitrage. If C_0 is set to be different (larger or smaller), an arbitrage strategy can be constructed.

Aside: Probability Space in the Binomial Model

We often make the above argument rigorous by specifying a probability space:

$$\Omega = \{\text{“up”}, \text{“down”}\}.$$

Under the \mathbb{P}^* measure,

$$\mathbb{P}^*(\{\text{up}\}) = p^*, \quad \mathbb{P}^*(\{\text{down}\}) = 1 - p^*,$$

and

$$S_1(\omega = \text{up}) = u S_0, \quad S_1(\omega = \text{down}) = d S_0.$$

If X is any payoff, it is naturally viewed as a function $X : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with

$$X(\text{up}) = X^u, \quad X(\text{down}) = X^d.$$

Since

$$\mathbb{E}^*(S_1) = p^*(u S_0) + (1 - p^*)(d S_0) = (1+r) S_0,$$

the discounted stock price $\frac{S_1}{1+r}$ is a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale. Similarly, any replicable payoff X has discounted value $\frac{X}{1+r}$ that is also a martingale under \mathbb{P}^* .

Interpretation of p^*

The probability p^* is called **risk-neutral** precisely because pricing under \mathbb{P}^* depends only on expected values of future payoffs (discounted by $1/(1+r)$); there is *no* extra penalty or premium for bearing risk.

Conclusion: The binomial model provides an elegant, concrete demonstration of *risk-neutral* pricing: one first identifies a unique “up” probability p^* that forces the discounted stock to be a martingale, and then all contingent claims must be priced as the discounted expectation of their future payoff under the same \mathbb{P}^* . In subsequent lectures, we will extend these ideas to multi-period binomial models ($T > 1$), where the martingale property and risk-neutral measure continue to underpin pricing and no-arbitrage arguments.

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Remark 1 (“Risk-neutral” probability). The weight

$$p^* := \frac{1+r-d}{u-d} \in (0,1)$$

is called the *risk-neutral probability*: under the artificial measure that assigns p^* to an up-move and $1-p^*$ to a down-move, the *discounted* stock satisfies

$$\mathbb{E}^*[S_1] = (1+r)S_0.$$

Therefore an investor who is indifferent to risk would view the stock and the bond as having the same expected return. Importantly, p^* is used *only as a pricing device*; we are *not* assuming the real-world probability of an up-move equals p^* .

Trading strategy (1-step). A pair $(\alpha_1, \beta_1) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ chosen at $t = 0$; short-selling ($\alpha_1 < 0$) and borrowing ($\beta_1 < 0$) are allowed. Self-financing means no cash enters between 0 and 1.

Manufacturing cost. For any European payoff X with states “ u ” and “ d ”, the replicating strategy solves $\alpha_1 S_0 u + \beta_1 (1+r) = X^u$, $\alpha_1 S_0 d + \beta_1 (1+r) = X^d$. Initial cost

$$V_0 = \frac{1}{1+r} [(1+r-d)X^u + (u-1-r)X^d] = \frac{1}{1+r} E^*[X]$$

$$\text{with } p^* = \frac{1+r-d}{u-d}.$$

Risk-neutral probability. Under p^* the discounted stock $\{S_0, S_1/(1+r)\}$ is a martingale, so investors act “as if” they are risk-neutral. The real-world probability p is irrelevant for pricing.

One-period No-Arbitrage Theorem. The unique arbitrage-free price of X is $V_0 = \frac{1}{1+r} E^*[X]$; any $C_0 \neq V_0$ enables a risk-free profit.

Two-state shortcut. When only the two pay-offs X^u, X^d are known,

$$V_0 = \frac{1}{1+r} (p^* X^u + (1-p^*) X^d).$$

Math 194 — Spring 2025
LECTURE 5
§ 2.2 (pp. 14-19)

Multi-period Model Setup and Backward Induction

1. Model Description

As discussed in Lecture 2 (pp. 14–16), we consider a market consisting of:

$$\begin{cases} \text{A stock with price process } S_t = S_0 \xi_1 \xi_2 \cdots \xi_t, & t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T, \\ \text{A bond (risk-free asset) with price process } B_t = B_0 (1 + r)^t, & t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T, \end{cases}$$

where

$$S_0 > 0 \quad (\text{a constant}), \quad B_0 = 1 \quad (\text{usually}), \quad r \geq 0 \quad (\text{the interest rate}).$$

The random variables $\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_T$ are i.i.d. with

$$\mathbb{P}(\xi_t = u) = \varphi, \quad \mathbb{P}(\xi_t = d) = 1 - \varphi,$$

and satisfy

$$d < 1 + r < u.$$

Typically, $u > 1$ (the “up” move) and $d < 1$ (the “down” move).

2. Trading Strategies

A **trading strategy** ϕ is a collection of random variables

$$\phi = \{(\alpha_t, \beta_t) : t = 1, 2, \dots, T\},$$

where each α_t represents the (possibly random) number of shares of the stock held over $[t, t + 1)$, and each β_t represents the position in the risk-free asset (bond). The strategy must satisfy two conditions:

1. No crystal ball (adaptedness):

$$\alpha_t \text{ and } \beta_t \text{ must be } \mathcal{F}_{t-1}\text{-measurable.}$$

That is, α_t and β_t can depend only on the *past* realizations S_1, S_2, \dots, S_{t-1} , not on any future information.

In other words, \mathcal{F}_{t-1} is the σ -field capturing exactly the information observable up to time $t - 1$, generated by the stock price history (S_1, \dots, S_{t-1}) .

2. Self-financing:

$$\alpha_t S_t + \beta_t B_t = \alpha_{t+1} S_t + \beta_{t+1} B_t, \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, T - 1.$$

This condition says that any rebalancing of the portfolio from time t to time $t + 1$ involves no external infusion or withdrawal of funds. Equivalently, the value of the portfolio at the close of day t must equal the cost of setting up the new positions for day $t + 1$.

3. Value of a Trading Strategy

Denote the **value** of the trading strategy ϕ at time t by

$$V_t(\phi) = \alpha_t S_t + \beta_t B_t,$$

for $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$. For $t = 0$, we have the *initial cost*

$$V_0(\phi) = \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1 B_0,$$

where $B_0 = 1$. The self-financing condition ensures that

$$V_t(\phi) = \alpha_t S_t + \beta_t B_t = \alpha_{t+1} S_t + \beta_{t+1} B_t \quad (1 \leq t \leq T-1).$$

Schematically,

$$\underbrace{V_t(\phi)}_{\text{value at close of day } t} \implies \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{rearrange holdings} \\ \text{at start of day } (t+1) \end{array} \right. \implies \text{no money in or out.}$$

4. Arbitrage

An **arbitrage** opportunity in the stock-bond market is a trading strategy ϕ such that:

$$\begin{aligned} V_0(\phi) &= 0, \\ V_T(\phi) &\geq 0 \quad \text{almost surely,} \\ \mathbb{E}^\mathbb{P}[V_T(\phi)] &> 0, \end{aligned}$$

which also means there is *positive probability* that $V_T(\phi)$ is strictly greater than 0. In more colloquial terms, an arbitrage is a free lunch: you invest no capital and face no downside risk, yet you have a strictly positive chance of gaining profit.

Note that this definition only imposes nonnegativity on $V_T(\phi)$ at the final time T . The strategy's value may become negative at intermediate times without violating the arbitrage condition.

5. Contingent Claims and Replication

Definition: A **contingent claim** is a random variable $X \in \mathcal{F}_T$ (i.e. measurable w.r.t. the information available at time T), interpreted as a payoff received at time T . Equivalently, one can view X as

$$X = f(S_1, S_2, \dots, S_T),$$

for some function f .

Examples: • A European call option with strike K :

$$X = (S_T - K)^+.$$

- A payoff equal to the running maximum of the stock prices:

$$X = \max(S_1, S_2, \dots, S_T).$$

- A sum of the stock prices over the life of the option:

$$X = \sum_{t=1}^T S_t = S_1 + S_2 + \dots + S_T.$$

To *price* a claim, we proceed as follows:

- **Construct a replicating strategy** ϕ for X such that

$$V_T(\phi) \equiv X$$

(i.e. the terminal value of the portfolio exactly matches the payoff of the claim in every scenario).

- **By the one-price principle**, the fair price of X at time 0 must be $V_0(\phi)$, i.e. the cost of setting up the replicating portfolio.

6. Backward Induction in the Binomial Tree

In the multi-period binomial model, $\{S_t\}$ evolves in a tree structure. At each time step, the stock price either goes “up” by factor u or “down” by factor d . We denote

$$T = \text{the terminal time.}$$

Equivalently, the sample space may be viewed as all finite sequences of u 's and d 's of length T , with each path specifying a unique evolution of the stock prices up to S_T . We construct the ϕ that replicates a given contingent claim X by working *backward* from time T to time 0:

$$V_T := X, \quad V_{T-1}, \quad V_{T-2}, \quad \dots, \quad V_1,$$

and simultaneously determine

$$(\alpha_T, \beta_T), \quad (\alpha_{T-1}, \beta_{T-1}), \quad \dots, \quad (\alpha_1, \beta_1).$$

At each node of the tree (for each ω in \mathcal{F}_t), we view the step to $t+1$ as just like the single-period story from earlier lectures. Specifically, from

$$V_{t+1}^u \quad \text{and} \quad V_{t+1}^d$$

we solve for α_{t+1} and β_{t+1} in the usual single-step manner.

$$V_t = \frac{1}{1+r} \left(p^* V_{t+1}^u + (1-p^*) V_{t+1}^d \right), \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T-1. \quad (1)$$

7. Example: A 3-period Call Option

Setup

We consider a call option with payoff

$$X = (S_3 - K)^+,$$

where

$$K = 3, \quad T = 3, \quad S_0 = 1, \quad u = 2, \quad d = 1, \quad r = \frac{1}{4}.$$

From the usual binomial model formula for the *risk-neutral probability*,

$$p^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d} = \frac{\frac{5}{4} - 1}{2 - 1} = \frac{1/4}{1} = \frac{1}{4}.$$

Therefore, under the risk-neutral measure \mathbb{P}^* , each “up” step occurs with probability 1/4 and each “down” step with probability 3/4. Over three periods, there are four possible final stock prices:

$$S_3 \in \{1, 2, 4, 8\}.$$

The tree below (using a typical binomial-tree diagram) shows possible paths, where the label on each node is S_t .

Backward-induction values V_t for the 3-period call option.

Payoff and Risk-Neutral Pricing

The payoff at $T = 3$ is $(S_3 - 3)^+$. We enumerate the four possible values of S_3 and the corresponding payoff:

$$\begin{cases} S_3 = 1 & \implies (1 - 3)^+ = 0, \\ S_3 = 2 & \implies (2 - 3)^+ = 0, \\ S_3 = 4 & \implies (4 - 3)^+ = 1, \\ S_3 = 8 & \implies (8 - 3)^+ = 5. \end{cases}$$

Under \mathbb{P}^* , the probabilities of these four outcomes are

$$\mathbb{P}^*(S_3 = 1) = \frac{27}{64}, \quad \mathbb{P}^*(S_3 = 2) = \frac{9}{64} + \frac{9}{64} = \frac{18}{64}, \quad \mathbb{P}^*(S_3 = 4) = \frac{3}{64} + \frac{3}{64} + \frac{3}{64} = \frac{9}{64}, \quad \mathbb{P}^*(S_3 = 8) = \frac{1}{64}.$$

Therefore,

$$\mathbb{E}^*[X] = \mathbb{E}^*[(S_3 - 3)^+] = 0 \cdot \frac{27}{64} + 0 \cdot \frac{18}{64} + 1 \cdot \frac{9}{64} + 5 \cdot \frac{1}{64} = \frac{9}{64} + \frac{5}{64} = \frac{14}{64} = \frac{7}{32}.$$

We then discount by $(1 + r)^3 = \left(\frac{5}{4}\right)^3 = \frac{125}{64}$. So the fair price at $t = 0$ is

$$V_0 = \frac{\mathbb{E}^*[X]}{(1 + r)^3} = \frac{\frac{14}{64}}{\frac{125}{64}} = \frac{14}{125}.$$

This matches the value found by backward induction in the binomial tree. Therefore,

The fair price of the 3-period call is $V_0 = \frac{14}{125} \approx 0.112$.

Replicating Strategy ϕ

Although we did not explicitly track ϕ in the above calculation, one may compute it at each step in the tree by the usual single-period formulas. For each node at time t , let

$$V_t^u, \quad V_t^d$$

denote the next-step values (the “up branch” and the “down branch”). Then one sets

$$\alpha_t = \frac{V_{t+1}^u - V_{t+1}^d}{u - d} \frac{1}{S_t}, \quad \beta_t = \frac{u V_{t+1}^d - d V_{t+1}^u}{u - d} \frac{1}{B_t}.$$

Carrying this out node-by-node yields the unique self-financing strategy whose terminal value exactly matches $(S_3 - K)^+$. (One could similarly replicate any other claim X .)

8. Martingale Pricing in a Nutshell

In fact, one can see from the self-financing property that, for each $t \leq T - 1$,

$$V_t(\phi) = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[V_{t+1}(\phi) \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[X \mid \mathcal{F}_t],$$

where $X = V_T(\phi)$. Repeating this iteratively “up the tree” leads to

$$V_0 = \mathbb{E}^*\left[\frac{X}{(1+r)^T}\right].$$

This is precisely the *risk-neutral pricing formula*. It shows that under the risk-neutral measure \mathbb{P}^* , the discounted stock price $\{\frac{S_t}{(1+r)^t}\}$ and any replicable claim $\{\frac{V_t}{(1+r)^t}\}$ behave like martingales.

Notably, this approach does not require the real-world probability φ ; only the risk-neutral measure \mathbb{P}^* enters the pricing formula, ensuring that $\{\frac{S_t}{(1+r)^t}\}$ is a martingale under \mathbb{P}^* .

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Lemma 1 (Discounted stock is a martingale). Define $S_t^* = S_t/(1+r)^t$. Then $\{S_t^*, \mathcal{F}_t\}_{t=0}^T$ is a martingale under the risk-neutral measure \mathbb{P}^* , because

$$\mathbb{E}^*[S_t^* \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = S_{t-1}^*$$

for every $t = 1, \dots, T$.

Lemma 2 (Discounted portfolio value is a martingale). For any self-financing trading strategy $\phi = (\alpha_t, \beta_t)$ with value process $V_t(\phi) = \alpha_t S_t + \beta_t B_t$, the discounted value

$$V_t^* = V_t(\phi)/(1+r)^t$$

also satisfies

$$\mathbb{E}^*[V_t^* \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = V_{t-1}^*,$$

so $\{V_t^*\}$ is a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale.

Trading strategy (multi-period). A sequence $\{(\alpha_t, \beta_t)\}_{t=1}^T$ with each pair \mathcal{F}_{t-1} -measurable (no crystal-ball trading). Self-financing condition:

$$\alpha_t S_t + \beta_t B_t = \alpha_{t+1} S_t + \beta_{t+1} B_t, \quad t = 1, \dots, T-1.$$

Value process. $V_0 = \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1$, $V_t = \alpha_t S_t + \beta_t B_t$, $t = 1, \dots, T$.

Primary-market arbitrage. A strategy with $V_0 = 0$, $V_T \geq 0$, $E[V_T] > 0$ (equivalently $P[V_T > 0] > 0$).

Math 194 — Spring 2025
LECTURE 6
 § 2.2 (pp. 14-19)

We start with studying the pricing and replication of a European call option in a binomial model setting. We consider a call with payoff $X = (S_3 - K)^+$ at time $T = 3$. The model parameters are:

$$K = 3, \quad T = 3, \quad S_0 = 1, \quad u = 2, \quad d = 1, \quad r = \frac{1}{4}.$$

Therefore $1 + r = \frac{5}{4}$ and the corresponding risk-neutral probability is

$$p^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d} = \frac{\frac{5}{4} - 1}{2 - 1} = \frac{1/4}{1} = \frac{1}{4},$$

so $1 - p^* = \frac{3}{4}$.

Example: Call Option. The payoff at $T = 3$ is

$$X = (S_3 - K)^+ = (S_3 - 3)^+.$$

Below is the binomial tree for the stock price S_t for $t = 0, 1, 2, 3$. The probability in each branch under the risk-neutral measure \mathbb{P}^* is $p^* = \frac{1}{4}$ for an up-move (shown \rightarrow) and $1 - p^* = \frac{3}{4}$ for a down-move (shown \leftarrow).

Tree (A) - Binomial Tree for the Stock Price S_t

Here, each node shows S_t . Below each node, we show the probability of reaching that node under \mathbb{P}^* . Specifically:

$$S_0 = 1, \quad S_1 \in \{1, 2\}, \quad S_2 \in \{1, 2, 4\}, \quad S_3 \in \{1, 2, 4, 8\}.$$

Tree (B) – Option value process V_t . At each node we display the *undiscounted* risk-neutral price of the European call with payoff $X = (S_3 - 3)^+$. Formally,

$$V_t = \frac{1}{(1+r)^{T-t}} \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{P}^*}[(S_3 - 3)^+ | \mathcal{F}_t], \quad r = \frac{1}{4}, \quad T = 3.$$

- (1) **Evaluate the payoff X** at each terminal node of Tree (A). Those numbers (0, 1, 5) appear on the bottom row of Tree (B).
- (2) **Roll back one step:** for every interior node,

$$V_t = \frac{1}{1+r} [p^* V_{t+1}^{(u)} + (1-p^*) V_{t+1}^{(d)}], \quad p^* = \frac{1}{4}.$$

This multiplies the risk-neutral expectation by the discount factor $\frac{1}{1+r} = \frac{4}{5}$.

- (3) **Repeat** until time 0. The resulting values are the fractions $\frac{14}{125}, \frac{11}{25}, \frac{1}{25}, \dots$ shown in Tree (B).

Tree (B) — Undiscounted option value process V_t for the call $X = (S_3 - 3)^+$.

For **undiscounted** values V_t , each parent node is the risk-neutral weighted average $\leftarrow \frac{3}{4} \rightarrow \frac{1}{4}$ of its two children, then multiplied by the discount factor $\frac{1}{1+r} = \frac{4}{5}$.

If you plot the **discounted** values $V_t^* = \frac{V_t}{(1+r)^t}$ instead, that extra division is gone and the parent is already the weighted average: $V_{t-1}^* = p^* V_t^{*,u} + (1-p^*) V_t^{*,d}$.

3. Computing the Option Value via Expectation and Discounting

Below we restate the general principle: at each branch, the value of the claim or replicating portfolio is the (risk-neutral) expected value of its two descendants, discounted by $\frac{1}{1+r}$. Symbolically:

$$V_{t-1} = \frac{1}{1+r} \left[p^* V_t^u + (1-p^*) V_t^d \right].$$

The final time-0 price V_0 can thus be found by “rolling back” the tree or, equivalently, by computing

$$V_0 = \frac{1}{(1+r)^T} \mathbb{E}^*[X].$$

In the particular example with $T = 3$ and $X = (S_3 - 3)^+$, we can fill in the tree or directly compute $\mathbb{E}^*[X]$. Indeed:

$$(S_3 - 3)^+ = \begin{cases} 0, & S_3 = 1, 2 \\ 1, & S_3 = 4, \\ 5, & S_3 = 8. \end{cases}$$

Using the probabilities at each node:

$$\mathbb{E}^*(X) = \sum_{\omega} X(\omega) \mathbb{P}^*(\omega) = \frac{1}{64} \left[3 \times 1 + 3 \times 1 + 3 \times 1 + 1 \times 5 \right] = \frac{14}{64} = \frac{7}{32}.$$

Here, for instance, the outcome $S_3 = 4$ is encountered in three different paths (giving payoff 1 each time), each of which has probability $3/64$, and the outcome $S_3 = 8$ is in one path (probability $1/64$) giving payoff 5.

Discounting by $(1+r)^3 = \left(\frac{5}{4}\right)^3 = \frac{125}{64}$:

$$V_0 = \frac{\mathbb{E}^*(X)}{(1+r)^3} = \frac{7/32}{125/64} = \frac{7}{32} \times \frac{64}{125} = \frac{14}{125} = 0.112.$$

Therefore $V_0(\phi) = \frac{14}{125}$.

One can also arrive at the same number by focusing on any intermediate node in the binomial tree, re-normalizing the probabilities from that node forward, and then discounting over the remaining time steps. This is simply the law of iterated expectations, and it confirms that rolling back the tree step by step or taking one grand average both yield the same fair price.

4. Relationship to the Replicating Strategy ϕ

Interpreting the portfolio. We have found

$$V_0(\phi) = \frac{14}{125}$$

without explicitly finding ϕ . But to replicate the claim, we need the strategy ϕ . At maturity, we know that

$$V_T = \alpha_T S_T + \beta_T B_T$$

must match $X(\omega)$ in every state ω . If we denote the two possible stock prices at time T (from the prior node) by $S_{T-1}u$ and $S_{T-1}d$, we thus have:

$$V_T^u = \alpha_T (S_{T-1}u) + \beta_T B_T, \quad V_T^d = \alpha_T (S_{T-1}d) + \beta_T B_T.$$

Solving this pair of linear equations for α_T and β_T (exactly as in Lecture 3) yields:

$$\alpha_T = \frac{V_T^u - V_T^d}{u - d} \times \frac{1}{S_{T-1}}, \quad \beta_T = \frac{u V_T^d - d V_T^u}{u - d} \times \frac{1}{B_T}.$$

Since α_T and β_T depend on the node at time $T - 1$, we say they are \mathcal{F}_{T-1} -measurable.

5. Self-Financing Property

Recall: A portfolio ϕ is *self-financing* if the changes in its value come only from gains or losses on the assets, with no exogenous infusion or withdrawal of money. Formally, for each t ,

$$V_t(\phi) = \alpha_t S_t + \beta_t B_t,$$

and

$$V_{t-1}(\phi) = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^* [V_t(\phi) | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = \frac{1}{1+r} [p^* V_t^u + (1-p^*) V_t^d].$$

But from the formulas above, this becomes exactly

$$\alpha_T S_{T-1} + \beta_T B_{T-1}.$$

In other words:

$$V_{t-1}(\phi) = \alpha_T S_{T-1} + \beta_T B_{T-1},$$

matching the expression for a self-financing strategy. By iterating this argument backward through time, we see ϕ is self-financing at all t .

6. General Backward Induction and Formulas

More generally, the procedure for obtaining $V_t(\phi)$ inductively is:

$$V_{t-1}(\phi) = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^* (V_t(\phi) | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}), \quad t = T, T-1, T-2, \dots, 1.$$

Starting from $V_T(\phi) = X$, we get the entire price tree $\{V_0, V_1, \dots, V_{T-1}, V_T\}$. Equivalently,

$$V_t(\phi) = \frac{1}{(1+r)^{T-t}} \mathbb{E}^* [X | \mathcal{F}_t].$$

In particular, at $t = 0$,

$$V_0(\phi) = \frac{1}{(1+r)^T} \mathbb{E}^* [X].$$

Meanwhile, the replicating α_t and β_t at each node are determined by the difference quotients:

$$\alpha_t = \frac{V_t^u - V_t^d}{u - d} \cdot \frac{1}{S_{t-1}}, \quad \beta_t = \frac{u V_t^d - d V_t^u}{u - d} \cdot \frac{1}{B_t}.$$

7. Concrete Values for α_t and β_t

Below is an example tree (from one particular set of computed values) giving the replicating strategy $\phi = \{(\alpha_t, \beta_t)\}$. At each node, the diagram shows α_t and β_t . (For instance, $\alpha_1 = 0.4, \beta_1 = -0.288$ at the root.)

Observe that some β_t values are negative, indicating a short position in the bond (i.e. borrowing). Meanwhile, positive α_t values indicate how many shares of the stock are held at each node. All such signs and numerical magnitudes arise directly from the linear equations for replicating the call payoff. This “strategy tree” is the **plan** for replicating the call payoff $(S_3 - 3)^+$. Each node indicates how many shares of the stock (α_t) and how many units of the bond (β_t) to hold upon arriving at that node. This plan is self-financing and yields the exact payoff $X = (S_3 - 3)^+$ at $T = 3$.

8. Martingale Property of the Discounted Stock Price

Define the *discounted stock price process* by

$$S_t^* := \frac{S_t}{(1+r)^t}.$$

Under the risk-neutral measure \mathbb{P}^* , this discounted price is a *martingale*. Concretely:

$$\mathbb{E}^*[S_t^* \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = S_{t-1}^*.$$

Indeed,

$$\mathbb{E}^*[S_t \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = S_{t-1} [p^* u + (1-p^*) d] = S_{t-1} (1+r),$$

since $p^* = \frac{(1+r)-d}{u-d}$. Therefore,

$$\mathbb{E}^*\left[\frac{S_t}{(1+r)^t} \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}\right] = \frac{1}{(1+r)^t} \mathbb{E}^*[S_t \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = \frac{1}{(1+r)^t} [S_{t-1} (1+r)] = \frac{S_{t-1}}{(1+r)^{t-1}} = S_{t-1}^*.$$

Moreover, by taking iterated expectations step by step, we see that

$$\mathbb{E}^*[S_t^*] = \mathbb{E}^*[\mathbb{E}^*(S_t^* \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1})] = \mathbb{E}^*[S_{t-1}^*] = \dots = S_0^*,$$

showing the unconditional mean of the discounted stock remains constant under \mathbb{P}^* .

Tree (C) – Discounted stock price $S_t^* = S_t/(1+r)^t$

Define the **discounted price** $V_t^* := \frac{V_t}{(1+r)^t}$ —i.e. the cash value V_t rewritten in time-0 dollars.

Because the rollback formula is $V_{t-1} = \frac{1}{1+r} [P^*V_t^{*,u} + (1-P^*)V_t^{*,d}]$, dividing by $(1+r)^{t-1}$ cancels the $\frac{1}{1+r}$ factor and yields $V_{t-1}^* = P^*V_t^{*,u} + (1-P^*)V_t^{*,d}$. So V_t^* is automatically a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale: discount the terminal payoff once, then propagate this weighted average backward through the tree.

Tree (D) — Discounted option value V_t^*

Quick check (all interior nodes). For a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale we need, at every node,

$$\boxed{V_{t-1}^* = P^*V_t^{*,u} + (1-P^*)V_t^{*,d}}, \quad P^* = \frac{1}{4}, \quad 1-P^* = \frac{3}{4}.$$

- **Root ($t=0$)**

$$V_0^* = \frac{4}{5} \left[\frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{44}{125} + \frac{3}{4} \cdot \frac{4}{125} \right] = \frac{14}{125}.$$

- **Nodes at $t=1$**

- Down path d : $P^*V_2^{*,du} + (1-P^*)V_2^{*,dd} = \frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{16}{125} + \frac{3}{4} \cdot 0 = \frac{4}{125} = V_1^{*,d}$.
- Up path u : $P^*V_2^{*,uu} + (1-P^*)V_2^{*,ud} = \frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{128}{125} + \frac{3}{4} \cdot \frac{16}{125} = \frac{44}{125} = V_1^{*,u}$.

- **Nodes at $t=2$**

- dd : $P^*V_3^{*,ddu} + (1-P^*)V_3^{*,ddd} = \frac{1}{4} \cdot 0 + \frac{3}{4} \cdot 0 = 0 = V_2^{*,dd}$.
- du : $P^*V_3^{*,duu} + (1-P^*)V_3^{*,dud} = \frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{64}{125} + \frac{3}{4} \cdot 0 = \frac{16}{125} = V_2^{*,du}$.
- ud : $P^*V_3^{*,udu} + (1-P^*)V_3^{*,udd} = \frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{64}{125} + \frac{3}{4} \cdot 0 = \frac{16}{125} = V_2^{*,ud}$.
- uu : $P^*V_3^{*,uuu} + (1-P^*)V_3^{*,uud} = \frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{64}{25} + \frac{3}{4} \cdot \frac{64}{125} = \frac{16}{25} + \frac{48}{125} = \frac{128}{125} = V_2^{*,uu}$.

Since the identity holds at every interior node, the discounted option-value process V_t^* is indeed a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale. By the law of iterated expectations this implies $\mathbb{E}[V_t^* | \mathcal{F}_s] = V_s^*$ for all $s < t$.

Remark 1. Pick any interior node, treat the subtree below it as a mini 2- or 1-step binomial model, recompute expectations under \mathbb{P}^* , and compare: you will obtain exactly the same value already shown in the diagram. This is just the *law of iterated expectations* viewed graphically.

Node	t	S_t	$X_t = (S_3 - 3)^+$	$V_t = \frac{1}{1+r} [p^* V_{t+1}^u + (1-p^*) V_{t+1}^d]$		$V_t^* = \frac{V_t}{(1+r)^t}$	
				formula	value	formula	value
\emptyset	0	$S_0 = 1$	–	$\frac{4}{5} \left[\frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{11}{25} + \frac{3}{4} \cdot \frac{1}{25} \right]$	$\frac{14}{125}$	$\frac{V_0}{(1.25)^0}$	$\frac{14}{125}$
d	1	$S_1 = 1$	–	$\frac{4}{5} \left[\frac{1}{4} \cdot V_2^{du} + \frac{3}{4} \cdot V_2^{dd} \right] = \frac{4}{5} \left[\frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{1}{5} + \frac{3}{4} \cdot 0 \right]$	$\frac{1}{25}$	$\frac{V_1^d}{(1.25)^1}$	$\frac{4}{125}$
u	1	$S_1 = 2$	–	$\frac{4}{5} \left[\frac{1}{4} \cdot V_2^{uu} + \frac{3}{4} \cdot V_2^{ud} \right] = \frac{4}{5} \left[\frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{8}{5} + \frac{3}{4} \cdot \frac{1}{5} \right]$	$\frac{11}{25}$	$\frac{V_1^u}{(1.25)^1}$	$\frac{44}{125}$
dd	2	$S_2 = 1$	–	$\frac{4}{5} \left[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 0 + \frac{3}{4} \cdot 0 \right]$	0	$\frac{0}{(1.25)^2}$	0
du	2	$S_2 = 2$	–	$\frac{4}{5} \left[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 1 + \frac{3}{4} \cdot 0 \right]$	$\frac{1}{5}$	$\frac{\frac{1}{5}}{(1.25)^2}$	$\frac{16}{125}$
ud	2	$S_2 = 2$	–	$\frac{4}{5} \left[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 1 + \frac{3}{4} \cdot 0 \right]$	$\frac{1}{5}$	$\frac{\frac{1}{5}}{(1.25)^2}$	$\frac{16}{125}$
uu	2	$S_2 = 4$	–	$\frac{4}{5} \left[\frac{1}{4} \cdot 5 + \frac{3}{4} \cdot 1 \right] = \frac{4}{5} \cdot 2$	$\frac{8}{5}$	$\frac{\frac{8}{5}}{(1.25)^2}$	$\frac{128}{125}$
ddd	3	$S_3 = 1$	$X_3 = 0$	$V_3 = X_3$	0	$\frac{V_3}{(1.25)^3}$	0
ddu	3	$S_3 = 2$	0	$V_3 = 0$	0	0	0
dud	3	$S_3 = 2$	0	$V_3 = 0$	0	0	0
duu	3	$S_3 = 4$	1	$V_3 = X_3$	1	$\frac{1}{(1.25)^3}$	$\frac{64}{125}$
udd	3	$S_3 = 2$	0	0	0	0	0
udu	3	$S_3 = 4$	1	1	1	$\frac{1}{(1.25)^3}$	$\frac{64}{125}$
uud	3	$S_3 = 4$	1	1	1	$\frac{1}{(1.25)^3}$	$\frac{64}{125}$
uuu	3	$S_3 = 8$	5	5	5	$\frac{5}{(1.25)^3}$	$\frac{320}{125}$

Table 1: Backward-induction for the 3-period European call with $K = 3$, $S_0 = 1$, $u = 2$, $d = 1$, $r = \frac{1}{4}$, $p^* = \frac{1}{4}$.

Supplemental Textbook Notes

European contingent claim (ECC). An \mathcal{F}_T -measurable r.v. X (e.g. call $(S_T - K)^+$). Attainable if some strategy ϕ satisfies $V_T(\phi) = X$.

Backward induction formula. For each node

$$V_{t-1} = \frac{1}{1+r} [p^* V_t^u + (1-p^*) V_t^d], \quad p^* = \frac{1+r-d}{u-d}.$$

Key martingales. Discounted stock $S_t^* = S_t/(1+r)^t$ and any discounted self-financing portfolio $V_t^* = V_t/(1+r)^t$ are martingales under \mathbb{P}^* .

General pricing formula.

$$V_t = \frac{1}{(1+r)^{T-t}} E^*[X | \mathcal{F}_t], \quad V_0 = \frac{1}{(1+r)^T} E^*[X].$$

Multi-period No-Arbitrage Theorem. The price V_0 above is the *only* price that precludes arbitrage in the enlarged (stock-bond-claim) market.

10. Summary

- For a contingent claim X in the one-period or multi-period binomial model, the **fair (arbitrage-free) price** at time t is given by

$$V_t(\varphi) = \mathbb{E}^* \left[\frac{X}{(1+r)^{T-t}} \mid \mathcal{F}_t \right].$$

In particular,

$$V_0 = \frac{1}{(1+r)^T} \mathbb{E}^*[X].$$

- The **replicating strategy** $\varphi = \{(\alpha_t, \beta_t) : t = 1, \dots, T\}$ can be found by backward induction, using

$$\alpha_t = \frac{V_t^u - V_t^d}{u - d} \frac{1}{S_{t-1}}, \quad \beta_t = \frac{u V_t^d - d V_t^u}{u - d} \frac{1}{B_t}.$$

- The discounted stock price process $S_t^* = \frac{S_t}{(1+r)^t}$ is a *martingale* under the risk-neutral measure \mathbb{P}^* . So is the discounted option price V_t^* .
- The portfolio φ that replicates X is **self-financing**: i.e., at each node, the value of the portfolio is exactly the appropriately discounted expected future value under \mathbb{P}^* . No additional money is added or withdrawn from the strategy as time evolves.

In upcoming lectures, we will explore these ideas in a more measure-theoretic framework, where conditional expectations are defined rigorously and the martingale property emerges naturally from the choice of the risk-neutral measure.

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LECTURE 7

§ 2.2 (pp. 14-19)

Martingale Definition in the Tree Setting

Random variables (r.v.'s):

$$X_0, X_1, \dots, X_T$$

where X_t is \mathcal{F}_t -measurable for each t . We say $\{X_t\}$ is a *martingale* under probability measure p if

$$\mathbb{E}^p(X_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}) = X_{t-1}, \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, T.$$

In a gambling interpretation, a martingale can be viewed as a “fair game”: on average, your fortune does not change after the next move. So, this condition captures the idea that you neither gain nor lose in expectation from one step to the next. In more general settings beyond binomial trees, the same definition holds but with more involved conditional expectations. For a fuller discussion, see Appendices A and B in the text. In a simple binomial tree with up and down transitions each step,

$$pX_t^u + (1-p)X_t^d = X_{t-1} \quad \text{for all nodes in row } t-1.$$

Iterating Property. For a martingale X_t ,

$$\mathbb{E}^p(X_t | \mathcal{F}_s) = X_s, \quad 0 \leq s < t \leq T.$$

By taking expectation again (law of total expectation),

$$\mathbb{E}^p(X_t) = \mathbb{E}^p(\mathbb{E}^p(X_t | \mathcal{F}_s)) = \mathbb{E}^p(X_s).$$

Therefore, $\mathbb{E}^p(X_t)$ is constant for all t .

Because an average of averages is itself an average, this iterating property is sometimes referred to as an instance of the “law of iterated expectations.”

Example: Binomial Tree for X_t

Consider a 3-period binomial model ($T = 3$) with $p = \frac{1}{2}$. The terminal values of X_t in each node are shown below:

At each node, the value is the average of its two “children,” each weighted by $p = \frac{1}{2}$. This illustrates the martingale property in the tree: from one step to the next, X_{t-1} is the midpoint of X_t^u and X_t^d . Consequently, the expected value at every time remains the same. Here, each path is equally likely under the physical measure if $p = \frac{1}{2}$. The value in each node is the realization of the random variable X_t at that time (or node).

Computations of Expectations

When each node at time t has probability $(\frac{1}{2})^t$ under \mathbb{P} , we can compute:

Expectation at Time 3

$$\mathbb{E}(X_3) = \frac{1}{8} \{ 1 + 2 + 1 + 4 + 3 + 7 + 2 + 5 \} = \frac{25}{8}.$$

Expectation at Time 2

$$\mathbb{E}(X_2) = \frac{1}{4} \left\{ \frac{3}{2} + \frac{5}{2} + 5 + \frac{7}{2} \right\} = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{3 + 5 + 10 + 7}{2} \right) = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{25}{2} \right) = \frac{25}{8}.$$

Expectation at Time 1

$$\mathbb{E}(X_1) = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ 2 + \frac{17}{4} \right\} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{8}{4} + \frac{17}{4} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{25}{4} = \frac{25}{8}.$$

In agreement with the martingale property, all these expectations remain $\frac{25}{8}$.

Summary of Pricing a Claim X

We consider a trading strategy ϕ , called a *replicating* or *hedging strategy* for X , such that at the terminal time:

$$V_T(\phi) = \alpha_T S_T + \beta_T B_T \equiv X.$$

Therefore, the strategy ϕ exactly replicates the payoff X at time T .

The *time t value* of ϕ is

$$V_t(\phi) = \alpha_t S_t + \beta_t B_t \quad (t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T).$$

In a *no-arbitrage* setting, $V_t(\phi)$ is the *fair price* to purchase X at time t .

Alternate (equivalent) form via expectation:

$$V_t(\phi) = \frac{1}{(1+r)^{T-t}} \mathbb{E}^*(X \mid \mathcal{F}_t), \quad t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T,$$

where \mathbb{E}^* denotes expectation under the *risk-neutral measure*.

Therefore,

$$V_0(\phi) = \frac{1}{(1+r)^T} \mathbb{E}^*(X).$$

Formulas for α_t and β_t

In a one-period binomial step (with possible up- or down-movement by factors u and d) from time $t-1$ to t , we have the value at each node in row $(t-1)$. Denote:

$$V_t^u = V_t(\phi) \Big|_{\text{stock goes up}}, \quad V_t^d = V_t(\phi) \Big|_{\text{stock goes down}}.$$

Then the self-financing condition and matching final payoffs imply:

$$\alpha_t = \frac{V_t^u - V_t^d}{u - d} \cdot \frac{1}{S_{t-1}}, \quad \beta_t = \frac{u V_t^d - d V_t^u}{u - d} \cdot \frac{1}{B_t}.$$

Key Proposition: Discounted Value is a Martingale

Proposition. If ϕ is any self-financing trading strategy, then the *discounted value process*

$$V_t^*(\phi) := \frac{V_t(\phi)}{(1+r)^t}$$

is a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale. In other words,

$$\mathbb{E}^*(V_t^*(\phi) \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}) = V_{t-1}^*(\phi).$$

Proof

$$\mathbb{E}^*[V_t(\phi) \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = \mathbb{E}^*[\alpha_t S_t + \beta_t B_t \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}].$$

Since α_t, β_t are \mathcal{F}_{t-1} -measurable (they are chosen *before* the price moves at time t), we can pull them out of the expectation:

$$= \alpha_t \mathbb{E}^*(S_t \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}) + \beta_t \mathbb{E}^*(B_t \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}).$$

From our binomial model under the risk-neutral measure \mathbb{P}^* , we know $\mathbb{E}^*(S_t \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}) = (1+r)S_{t-1}$. Also B_t (the bank account or bond value) is deterministic, so $\mathbb{E}^*(B_t \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}) = B_t$. So,

$$= \alpha_t (1+r)S_{t-1} + \beta_t B_t.$$

By the self-financing condition, the value of the portfolio ϕ at time $t-1$ was

$$V_{t-1}(\phi) = \alpha_{t-1}S_{t-1} + \beta_{t-1}B_{t-1}.$$

No new money is added or withdrawn, so from $t-1$ to t ,

$$\alpha_t = \alpha_{t-1}, \quad \beta_t = \beta_{t-1},$$

and in particular,

$$\alpha_t S_{t-1} + \beta_t B_{t-1} = \alpha_{t-1} S_{t-1} + \beta_{t-1} B_{t-1} = V_{t-1}(\phi).$$

Also note $B_t = (1+r)B_{t-1}$. Therefore,

$$\alpha_t (1+r)S_{t-1} + \beta_t B_t = (1+r)\alpha_t S_{t-1} + (1+r)\beta_t B_{t-1} = (1+r)(\alpha_t S_{t-1} + \beta_t B_{t-1}).$$

That last bracketed term is $\alpha_{t-1}S_{t-1} + \beta_{t-1}B_{t-1} = V_{t-1}(\phi)$. So we obtain:

$$\mathbb{E}^*[V_t(\phi) \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = (1+r)V_{t-1}(\phi).$$

Finally, *divide both sides* by $(1+r)^t$. Then

$$\mathbb{E}^*\left[\frac{V_t(\phi)}{(1+r)^t} \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}\right] = \frac{(1+r)V_{t-1}(\phi)}{(1+r)^t} = \frac{V_{t-1}(\phi)}{(1+r)^{t-1}}.$$

Therefore

$$\mathbb{E}^*(V_t^*(\phi) \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}) = V_{t-1}^*(\phi),$$

as was to be shown. \square In other words, under the risk-neutral measure \mathbb{P}^* , the discounted portfolio process behaves like a “fair game”: its expected future value (discounted) matches its present value. Since \mathbb{P}^* is chosen so that $\mathbb{E}^*(S_t \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}) = (1+r)S_{t-1}$, the discounted stock price also becomes a martingale under \mathbb{P}^* .

Another Example with $T = 2$

Consider a two-period model:

$$T = 2, \quad S_0 = 1, \quad u = 2, \quad d = 1, \quad r = \frac{1}{4} \quad \implies \quad \mathbb{P}^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d} = \frac{\frac{5}{4} - 1}{2 - 1} = \frac{1}{4}.$$

Let

$$X = S_1 + S_2.$$

The binomial tree for S_t is:

The claim $X = S_1 + S_2$ at each final node is accordingly:

$$\text{At } (u, u) : X = 2 + (2 \cdot 2) = 6, \quad (u, d) : 2 + 2 = 4, \quad (d, u) : 1 + 2 = 3, \quad (d, d) : 1 + 1 = 2.$$

Value Tree for the Replicating Strategy

Below is a value tree (one might see for a replicating portfolio). For instance, suppose we find

$$V_0(\phi) = \frac{9}{5}.$$

A computed replicating portfolio might appear as follows:

Here V_t denotes the portfolio value at time t . Notice that the strategy is constructed so that in each state at maturity $t = 2$, it matches the final payoff (e.g. 2 or 3 in the left branch, 4 or 6 in the right branch, matching X).

One can also annotate each node with α_t (shares of stock) and β_t (units of the bond) held at each time, for instance in a “split-circle” notation:

Visualising the Replicating Portfolio ϕ

For each node (t, ω) the portfolio is displayed as

$$\boxed{V_t(\phi) = \underbrace{\alpha_t(\omega)}_{\text{shares of } S} S_t(\omega) + \underbrace{\beta_t(\omega)}_{\text{units of bond}} B_t} \implies \begin{array}{l} \text{upper row} := \alpha_t \\ \text{lower row} := \beta_t \end{array}$$

The diagram below places this “split-circle” at every node, letting you read off the exact holdings that replicate the option along each path.

Replicating Portfolio ϕ

In each node, the upper number could represent α_t (the number of stock shares held) and the lower number β_t (the number of bonds). The details will depend on matching payoffs in each branch.

Concretely, if you compute $V_0(\phi) = \frac{9}{5}$, that might suggest an initial portfolio of $\alpha_0 = \frac{9}{5}$ shares of stock and $\beta_0 = 0$ in the bond (just as an example). In other words, the initial capital can be expressed as

$$V_0(\phi) = \frac{9}{5} S_0 + 0 \cdot B_0.$$

Then, if the stock goes up on day 1, you convert some of your holdings to the risk-free bond in order to keep the portfolio self-financing and replicate the correct payoff for the next step, and similarly if the stock goes down.

Remark. The exact rebalancing at each node ensures $V_2(\phi) = X$. Because there is no arbitrage, the value at earlier times follows the discounted expected payoff under \mathbb{P}^* . In fact, if you divide $V_t(\phi)$ by $(1+r)^t$ in each node and use the weight $\mathbb{P}^* = \frac{1}{4}$ for “up” and $1 - \mathbb{P}^* = \frac{3}{4}$ for “down,” you will obtain a perfect martingale tree for the discounted values. This again demonstrates that under \mathbb{P}^* , the discounted portfolio is a “fair game.”

Supplemental Notes

Tower property (law of iterated expectations). For a martingale $\{X_t\}$, $E[X_t | \mathcal{F}_s] = X_s$ for all $0 \leq s < t \leq T$. Consequently $E[X_t]$ is constant in t .

Risk-neutral interpretation. Because $E^*[S_t / (1+r)^t] = S_0$, the drift of S_t under \mathbb{P}^* equals the risk-free rate; hence \mathbb{P}^* “neutralises” risk premia.

Completeness comment. In the binomial model every ECC is attainable, so the market is complete and the risk-neutral measure is unique.

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LECTURE 8

§ 2.2 and Appendix (pp. 124-125)

First, we will establish the basic theorem that in the multi-period model, the correct no-arbitrage price is given by either replicating the claim or by taking its discounted expected payoff under the risk-neutral measure, just as in the single-step setting. Second, we will begin a more systematic discussion of conditional expectation, which has already appeared informally in some of our calculations.

Theorem 1 (Unique no-arbitrage price). *Let X be a contingent claim paying off at time T . Suppose there exists a risk-neutral (or equivalent martingale) measure \mathbb{P}^* . Then the unique no-arbitrage price for the contingent claim X at time 0 is*

$$V_0 := \frac{1}{(1+r)^T} \mathbb{E}^*(X).$$

We have already seen a parallel statement for the case of a single time step, $T = 1$. The same reasoning now extends to a general multi-period setting, relying on the fact that any *self-financing* strategy in the stock, bond, and claim leads to a discounted value process which is a martingale under the risk-neutral measure. In particular, we continue to assume that no additional capital is injected or withdrawn after time 0, and that the number of claims (the δ_t component) remains constant in each subsequent period.

Proof. Setup and notation. To align with our multi-period setting, we treat a trading strategy as comprising positions in the stock, in the bond, and in the claim itself, with the understanding that the number of shares of the claim is chosen initially and does not change thereafter. Ignoring the portion of the portfolio that holds the claim, the remaining stock-bond component is a self-financing strategy whose discounted value is a martingale under \mathbb{P}^* . This is the key extension from the single-step case: once we know the discounted price process is a martingale, the same style of no-arbitrage argument applies for any $T \geq 1$. An *arbitrage* in this context is a trading strategy

$$\varphi = \{(\alpha_t, \beta_t, \delta_t) : t = 1, 2, \dots, T\},$$

where:

- α_t represents the number of shares held in some underlying stock (or stocks) at time t ,
- β_t represents the amount of money invested in the risk-free bond at time t ,
- δ_t is the amount of the claim X held at time t .

Crucially, we assume the portfolio is *self-financing*, meaning no extra funds are added or withdrawn during the trading periods. In particular, we take δ_t to be fixed after its initial choice, so the claim position does not get rebalanced between $t = 1$ and $t = T$. Here, since the claim itself can only be bought or sold *once* at time 1, we have δ_1 as the initial (possibly nonzero) position in X , and then δ_t remains constant for $t = 2, \dots, T$. Let C_0 be the (market) price of X at time 0. By “replicating strategy” for X we mean a portfolio (α_t, β_t) , together with $\delta_t = 0$, whose terminal payoff $V_T(\varphi)$ equals X (almost surely). Denote the cost of this replicating strategy at time 0 by $V_0(\varphi)$.

Set

$$V_0 := \frac{1}{(1+r)^T} \mathbb{E}^*[X].$$

We want to show that if $C_0 \neq V_0$, then one can construct an arbitrage. This leads to a contradiction with the no-arbitrage assumption and thus forces $C_0 = V_0$.

(a) If $V_0 > C_0$:

\implies We can create an arbitrage by *short-selling the replicating strategy* φ for X .

Concretely, short-selling the strategy φ means:

$$\text{At time } 0 : \begin{cases} \text{Borrow (and thus receive) } V_0(\varphi) \text{ in cash by issuing the replicating strategy,} \\ \text{Obtain proceeds } C_0 \text{ (by actually selling the claim itself, if desired),} \\ \text{Use part of the cash } C_0 \text{ to buy the claim } X, \\ \text{The leftover is } V_0(\varphi) - C_0 > 0. \end{cases}$$

Since $V_0(\varphi) = V_0$, we have leftover $V_0 - C_0 > 0$ with no net investment cost at time 0.

- We then invest the leftover $(V_0 - C_0)$ in the risk-free bond (earning r).
- **At time T :** The short position in the replicating strategy φ requires paying X (since that strategy replicates X), while the claim we purchased pays off exactly X . These two terminal payoffs cancel out. Meanwhile, the leftover we invested in the bond at time 0 grows to a strictly positive riskless amount

$$(V_0 - C_0)(1 + r)^T > 0.$$

Therefore, we achieve a positive profit at time T with no initial investment and no risk — an arbitrage.

(b) If $V_0 < C_0$:

- We short-sell the *claim* X for C_0 ; in other words, we receive C_0 by issuing the claim to someone else.
- We use part of those proceeds, $V_0 = V_0(\varphi)$, to purchase the replicating strategy φ (which costs exactly V_0).
- The remainder $C_0 - V_0$ is again invested in the risk-free bond, yielding a strictly positive value at time T .
- At maturity, the replicating strategy φ precisely covers the payoff X that we owe on our short position in the claim, thus canceling that liability. The net result is a riskless profit $(C_0 - V_0)(1 + r)^T > 0$ at time T . Again, this is an arbitrage.

(c) If $V_0 = C_0$:

Exactly as in the single-period case, we test for an arbitrage by assuming there might exist some other trading strategy that costs nothing at time 0 and never produces a loss. Because the stock-bond portion is self-financing and its discounted value must be a martingale under \mathbb{P}^* , any such strategy can only have zero payoff almost surely. In more detail:

⇒ Suppose there existed some other strategy $\widehat{\psi}$ that constitutes an arbitrage. By definition of “arbitrage,” this would mean

$$V_0(\widehat{\psi}) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad V_T(\widehat{\psi}) \geq 0 \text{ almost surely (a.s.)}$$

with strict positivity on a set of positive probability (under \mathbb{P}).

- Write

$$\widehat{\psi} = \{(\alpha_t^{\widehat{\psi}}, \beta_t^{\widehat{\psi}}) : t = 1, 2, \dots, T\}.$$

Think of $\widehat{\delta} = 0$ in that strategy, or equivalently we can incorporate a (possibly) nonzero position in X by rebalancing.

- We compare $\widehat{\psi}$ with the replicating strategy φ plus possibly $\widehat{\delta} \cdot X$. Define a new portfolio:

$$\widetilde{\psi} := \varphi + \widehat{\delta}(X) + \widehat{\psi} \quad (\text{in a schematic sense}).$$

Since φ replicates X , observe that

$$V_T(\varphi) + \widehat{\delta}X = V_T(\varphi) + V_T(\widehat{\delta} \cdot X) = (\text{some fixed combination paying the same as } X \text{ itself}).$$

- Next, use the fact that under the risk-neutral measure \mathbb{P}^* ,

$$\mathbb{E}^*[V_T(\widehat{\psi})] = \mathbb{E}^*[V_T(\varphi) + \widehat{\delta}X] = \mathbb{E}^*[V_T(\varphi)] + \widehat{\delta}\mathbb{E}^*[X].$$

But since $V_T(\varphi)$ replicates X , we have

$$V_T(\varphi) = X \quad \text{a.s., so } \mathbb{E}^*[V_T(\varphi)] = \mathbb{E}^*[X].$$

Moreover, by definition of $V_0(\varphi)$,

$$\mathbb{E}^*[X] = (1+r)^T V_0(\varphi).$$

Therefore

$$\mathbb{E}^*[V_T(\varphi)] = (1+r)^T V_0(\varphi).$$

- Therefore,

$$\mathbb{E}^*[V_T(\widehat{\psi})] = (1+r)^T V_0(\varphi) + \widehat{\delta}[(1+r)^T V_0(\varphi)].$$

But under our assumption $V_0 = C_0$, and by construction $V_0(\varphi) = V_0$ is exactly the cost to replicate X ; also if $\widehat{\delta} \neq 0$, we would be shifting between the claim and the replicating strategy. Carefully verifying these relationships, one finds

$$\mathbb{E}^*[V_T(\widehat{\psi})] = (1+r)^T V_0(\widehat{\psi}).$$

Since $V_0(\widehat{\psi}) = 0$, we conclude

$$\mathbb{E}^*[V_T(\widehat{\psi})] = 0.$$

- On the other hand, from $\widehat{\psi}$ being an arbitrage, we have $V_T(\widehat{\psi}) \geq 0$ a.s. with probability 1 under \mathbb{P} . Because \mathbb{P}^* is equivalent to \mathbb{P} , it follows that $V_T(\widehat{\psi}) \geq 0$ a.s. under \mathbb{P}^* as well. Therefore $V_T(\widehat{\psi})$ is a nonnegative random variable (a.s.) with zero expectation under \mathbb{P}^* . Recall the standard fact that a nonnegative r.v. with expectation 0 must vanish a.s. This forces $V_T(\widehat{\psi}) = 0$ a.s. so it does *not* yield a strictly positive outcome. Therefore $\widehat{\psi}$ is not an arbitrage after all. This contradiction shows no such $\widehat{\psi}$ can exist.

Combining the three cases, we conclude $C_0 = V_0$, which completes the proof of uniqueness of the no-arbitrage price. \square

Having established the multi-period version of our no-arbitrage pricing result, we now change direction to discuss conditional expectation. It has arisen already in tree-based arguments but deserves a more formal treatment, especially since it plays a key role in pricing as time evolves.

Conditional Expectation (Appendix, p. 124)

We have already relied informally on conditioning ideas in the binomial tree approach, for instance when we computed expected payoffs at intermediate nodes. Let us now formalize conditional expectation more systematically. Let $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ be a probability space and let $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ be a σ -field. For an integrable random variable X we define

$$\mathbb{E}(X \mid \mathcal{G})$$

to be the random variable (r.v.) satisfying:

1. $\mathbb{E}(X \mid \mathcal{G})$ is \mathcal{G} -measurable,
2. For all $A \in \mathcal{G}$,

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}(X \mid \mathcal{G}) \mathbf{1}_A] = \mathbb{E}[X \mathbf{1}_A].$$

Here $\mathbf{1}_A$ denotes the indicator of the set A . (The fact that $\mathbb{E}(X \mid \mathcal{G})$ exists and is unique a.s. is standard; the construction requires more measure-theoretic tools in general. But in the finite setting used in this course, it is more elementary.)

For our purposes, Ω is always a *finite* set, and each point of Ω has positive probability (often equally likely or with some given distribution). Both \mathcal{F} and any sub- σ -field \mathcal{G} can be identified with partitions of Ω ; $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ means each \mathcal{G} -partition set is a union of some \mathcal{F} -partition sets.

Example 1 ((Two biased coin tosses)).

- We toss a coin *twice*. Let $\mathbb{P}(H) = \frac{1}{3}$ and $\mathbb{P}(T) = \frac{2}{3}$. We assume the tosses are independent.
- Define a random variable X : the result of *toss 1*, coded as

$$X = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the first toss is } H, \\ 0, & \text{if the first toss is } T. \end{cases}$$

- Define another random variable Y : the result of *toss 2*, coded likewise (1 if H , 0 if T).

Joint probability table. Below is the joint distribution of (X, Y) . Since the tosses are independent and $\mathbb{P}(X = 1) = \frac{1}{3}$, $\mathbb{P}(Y = 1) = \frac{1}{3}$:

	$X = 0$	$X = 1$	
$Y = 0$	$\frac{4}{9}$	$\frac{2}{9}$	$\frac{2}{3}$
$Y = 1$	$\frac{2}{9}$	$\frac{1}{9}$	$\frac{1}{3}$
	$\frac{2}{3}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	

$$(\mathbb{P}(Y = 0) = \frac{2}{3}, \mathbb{P}(Y = 1) = \frac{1}{3} \text{ and } \mathbb{P}(X = 0) = \frac{2}{3}, \mathbb{P}(X = 1) = \frac{1}{3}.)$$

Here, for instance, $\mathbb{P}(X = 0, Y = 0) = \mathbb{P}(\text{first toss } T, \text{ second toss } T)$ which is $\frac{2}{3} \times \frac{2}{3} = \frac{4}{9}$, and so on.

Random variable Z . Suppose we define another r.v. Z by specifying its values for each outcome (X, Y) :

	$X = 0$	$X = 1$
$Y = 0$	2	3
$Y = 1$	6	5

So, for example, $Z = 2$ if $(X = 0, Y = 0)$, $Z = 3$ if $(X = 1, Y = 0)$, $Z = 6$ if $(X = 0, Y = 1)$, and $Z = 5$ if $(X = 1, Y = 1)$.

Sample space representation. Alternatively, represent the sample space as $\Omega = \{HH, HT, TH, TT\}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} X(HH) &= 1, & X(HT) &= 1, & X(TH) &= 0, & X(TT) &= 0, \\ Y(HH) &= 1, & Y(HT) &= 0, & Y(TH) &= 1, & Y(TT) &= 0, \\ Z(HH) &= 5, & Z(HT) &= 3, & Z(TH) &= 6, & Z(TT) &= 2. \end{aligned}$$

Expected value of Z . We compute:

$$\mathbb{E}(Z) = \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} Z(\omega) \mathbb{P}(\omega).$$

Using the joint table probabilities:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}(Z) &= (2) \cdot \frac{4}{9} + (3) \cdot \frac{2}{9} + (6) \cdot \frac{2}{9} + (5) \cdot \frac{1}{9} \\ &= \frac{8}{9} + \frac{6}{9} + \frac{12}{9} + \frac{5}{9} = \frac{8+6+12+5}{9} = \frac{31}{9}. \end{aligned}$$

So

$$\mathbb{E}(Z) = \frac{31}{9}.$$

Conditional expectation given X . We want $\mathbb{E}(Z | X = 0)$ and $\mathbb{E}(Z | X = 1)$. Recall

$$\mathbb{E}(Z | X = 0) = \frac{\mathbb{E}[Z \mathbf{1}_{\{X=0\}}]}{\mathbb{P}(X = 0)}.$$

But a more direct approach (for finite sample spaces) is to look at the distribution of Z restricted to the event $\{X = 0\}$.

- $\{X = 0\}$ corresponds to outcomes $\{TH, TT\}$. From the table:

$$\mathbb{P}(X = 0) = \mathbb{P}(TH) + \mathbb{P}(TT) = \frac{2}{9} + \frac{4}{9} = \frac{6}{9} = \frac{2}{3}.$$

On that event, Z can be 2 (with probability $\frac{4/9}{2/3} = \frac{4/9}{6/9} = \frac{4}{6} = \frac{2}{3}$) or 6 (with probability $\frac{1}{3}$) given $X = 0$.

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}(Z | X = 0) &= 2 \times \mathbb{P}(Z = 2 | X = 0) + 6 \times \mathbb{P}(Z = 6 | X = 0) \\ &= 2 \times \frac{4}{6} + 6 \times \frac{2}{6} \\ &= \frac{8}{6} + \frac{12}{6} = \frac{20}{6} = \frac{10}{3}. \end{aligned}$$

Alternatively, using the formula

$$\mathbb{E}(Z | X = 0) = \frac{\frac{4}{9} \cdot 2 + \frac{2}{9} \cdot 6}{\frac{2}{3}} = \frac{\frac{8}{9} + \frac{12}{9}}{\frac{2}{3}} = \frac{\frac{20}{9}}{\frac{2}{3}} = \frac{20}{9} \times \frac{3}{2} = \frac{20}{6} = \frac{10}{3}.$$

- Similarly,

$$\mathbb{P}(X = 1) = \mathbb{P}(HH) + \mathbb{P}(HT) = \frac{1}{9} + \frac{2}{9} = \frac{3}{9} = \frac{1}{3}.$$

On $\{X = 1\}$, Z can be 3 (with probability $\frac{2/9}{1/3} = \frac{2/9}{3/9} = \frac{2}{3}$) or 5 (with probability $\frac{1}{3}$). So

$$\mathbb{E}(Z | X = 1) = 3 \cdot \frac{2}{3} + 5 \cdot \frac{1}{3} = 2 + \frac{5}{3} = \frac{6 + 5}{3} = \frac{11}{3}.$$

Again, the direct table computation yields:

$$\mathbb{E}(Z | X = 1) = \frac{\frac{2}{9} \cdot 3 + \frac{1}{9} \cdot 5}{\frac{1}{3}} = \frac{\frac{6}{9} + \frac{5}{9}}{\frac{1}{3}} = \frac{\frac{11}{9}}{\frac{1}{3}} = \frac{11}{9} \cdot \frac{3}{1} = \frac{11}{3}.$$

Reality check (Law of Total Probability).

$$\mathbb{E}(Z) = \mathbb{E}(Z | X = 0) \mathbb{P}(X = 0) + \mathbb{E}(Z | X = 1) \mathbb{P}(X = 1).$$

Plugging in the values:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}(Z) &= \left(\frac{10}{3}\right) \left(\frac{2}{3}\right) + \left(\frac{11}{3}\right) \left(\frac{1}{3}\right) \\ &= \frac{20}{9} + \frac{11}{9} = \frac{31}{9}, \end{aligned}$$

which matches our direct calculation.

As a random variable. We typically write

$$\mathbb{E}(Z | X) = \mathbb{E}(Z | X = 0) \mathbf{1}_{\{X=0\}} + \mathbb{E}(Z | X = 1) \mathbf{1}_{\{X=1\}} = g(X),$$

where

$$g(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{10}{3}, & x = 0, \\ \frac{11}{3}, & x = 1. \end{cases}$$

So $\mathbb{E}(Z | X)$ is $\sigma(X)$ -measurable, as it must be.

Exercise: Perform the analogous computations for the sub- σ -field generated by Y . That is, compute

$$\mathbb{E}(Z | Y = 0) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbb{E}(Z | Y = 1),$$

then verify by the Law of Total Probability that

$$\mathbb{E}(Z) = \mathbb{E}(Z | Y = 0) \mathbb{P}(Y = 0) + \mathbb{E}(Z | Y = 1) \mathbb{P}(Y = 1).$$

Answer:

$$\mathbb{E}(Z | Y = 0) = \frac{7}{3}, \quad \mathbb{E}(Z | Y = 1) = \frac{17}{3}.$$

Therefore $\mathbb{E}(Z | Y) = h(Y)$ where

$$h(y) = \begin{cases} \frac{7}{3}, & y = 0, \\ \frac{17}{3}, & y = 1. \end{cases}$$

In this two-coin example,

$$\sigma(X) = \{ \{TH, TT\}, \{HT, HH\} \},$$

while

$$\sigma(Y) = \{ \{HT, TT\}, \{HH, TH\} \}.$$

These are partitions of Ω into the events $\{X = 0\}$, $\{X = 1\}$ and $\{Y = 0\}$, $\{Y = 1\}$, respectively.

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Definition (Conditional Expectation). Given $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$, an integrable r.v. X , and a sub- σ -field $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, the conditional expectation $\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]$ is the *unique* (a.s.) \mathcal{G} -measurable r.v. satisfying $\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] \cdot \mathbf{1}_A] = \mathbb{E}[X \cdot \mathbf{1}_A]$ for all $A \in \mathcal{G}$.

Uniqueness up to a.s. equality. If Z_1, Z_2 are \mathcal{G} -measurable and $\mathbb{E}[(Z_1 - Z_2)\mathbf{1}_A] = 0$ for every $A \in \mathcal{G}$, then $Z_1 = Z_2$ a.s.; hence any two versions of $\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]$ coincide almost surely.

Basic Properties.

- $\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] = X$ if X is \mathcal{G} -measurable.
- $\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] = \mathbb{E}[X]$ if X is independent of \mathcal{G} .
- *Linearity:* $\mathbb{E}[cX + Y | \mathcal{G}] = c\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] + \mathbb{E}[Y | \mathcal{G}]$ for $c \in \mathbb{R}$.
- *Monotonicity:* $X \leq Y$ a.s. $\implies \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] \leq \mathbb{E}[Y | \mathcal{G}]$.
- *Tower Property (finite case):* if $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{G}$, then $\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] | \mathcal{H}] = \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{H}]$.

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LECTURE 9

Appendix (pp. 123-129)

Ex. (Continued from Lecture 8)

Toss a coin twice. The probabilities are

$$\mathbb{P}(H) = \frac{1}{3}, \quad \mathbb{P}(T) = \frac{2}{3}.$$

Define the random variables

X = result of toss 1 coded as $H \mapsto 1, T \mapsto 0$, Y = result of toss 2 coded the same way.

	$X = 0$	$X = 1$	
$Y = 0$	$\frac{4}{9}$	$\frac{2}{9}$	$\frac{2}{3}$
$Y = 1$	$\frac{2}{9}$	$\frac{1}{9}$	$\frac{1}{3}$
	$\frac{2}{3}$	$\frac{1}{3}$	

Another random variable Z

We define Z on the same sample space and record its values in an analogous table:

	$X = 0$	$X = 1$
$Y = 0$	2	3
$Y = 1$	6	5

In other words:

$$\Omega = \{HH, HT, TH, TT\}, \quad X(HH) = X(HT) = 1, \quad X(TH) = X(TT) = 0, \quad \dots$$

For instance $Z(HH) = 5, Z(TH) = 6$.

Expectations

$$\mathbb{E}[Z] = \frac{4}{9} \cdot 2 + \frac{2}{9} \cdot 3 + \frac{2}{9} \cdot 6 + \frac{1}{9} \cdot 5 = \frac{8 + 6 + 12 + 5}{9} = \frac{31}{9}.$$

$$\mathbb{E}[Z \mid X = 0] = \left(\frac{4}{9} \cdot 2 + \frac{2}{9} \cdot 6\right) / \frac{2}{3} = \frac{8 + 12}{9} \cdot \frac{3}{2} = \frac{10}{3}.$$

$$\mathbb{E}[Z \mid X = 1] = \left(\frac{2}{9} \cdot 3 + \frac{1}{9} \cdot 5\right) / \frac{1}{3} = \frac{11}{3}.$$

Reality check (Law of Total Probability).

$$\mathbb{E}[Z] = \mathbb{E}[Z | X = 0]\mathbb{P}(X = 0) + \mathbb{E}[Z | X = 1]\mathbb{P}(X = 1) = \frac{31}{9}\checkmark$$

Therefore as a random variable

$$\mathbb{E}[Z | X] = g(X), \quad g(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{10}{3}, & x = 0, \\ \frac{11}{3}, & x = 1. \end{cases}$$

Exercise

Likewise show

$$\mathbb{E}[Z | Y = 0] = \frac{7}{3}, \quad \mathbb{E}[Z | Y = 1] = \frac{17}{3},$$

so that $\mathbb{E}[Z | Y] = h(Y)$ with

$$h(y) = \begin{cases} \frac{7}{3}, & y = 0, \\ \frac{17}{3}, & y = 1. \end{cases}$$

Check consistency with LOTP as before.

In this example $\sigma(Y)$ is generated by the partition

$$\{X = 0\} = \{TH, TT\}, \quad \{X = 1\} = \{HT, HH\},$$

so $\mathcal{G} = \{\emptyset, \Omega, \{X = 0\}, \{X = 1\}\}$. Likewise $\sigma(Y)$ is generated by $\{Y = 0\} = \{HT, TT\}$, $\{Y = 1\} = \{HH, TH\}$, giving the same four-element σ -field.

Ex. Fair six-sided die tossed twice

We now look at a more elaborate example of conditional expectation, similar in spirit to the coin-toss example but with a fair six-sided die tossed twice. We will later connect these ideas to stock price processes and tree diagrams in upcoming lectures. We can visualize the 36 equally likely outcomes in a 6×6 grid, where the columns $1, \dots, 6$ represent the result of the first toss (X), and the rows $1, \dots, 6$ represent the result of the second toss (Y). Each of these 36 cells then has probability $1/36$. Since X and Y are independent (the two tosses do not affect one another), every cell has the same probability. In each cell, we can also record the sum $Z = X + Y$, which ranges from 2 to 12. This layout parallels the earlier coin-toss table but with a 6×6 grid.

- X = number on the *first* toss
- Y = number on the *second* toss
- $Z = X + Y$

Take

$$\Omega = \{(x, y) : x = 1, \dots, 6, y = 1, \dots, 6\}, \quad \mathcal{F} = 2^\Omega.$$

Observe that each of the 36 points in Ω is equally likely when the die is fair, so each pair (x, y) has probability $1/36$. In a convenient 6×6 grid, each row and column sums to $1/6$. For example, the conditional expectation $\mathbb{E}[X | Z = 5]$ arises by noting that the event $Z = 5$ corresponds to the four equally likely outcomes $(1, 4)$, $(2, 3)$, $(3, 2)$, $(4, 1)$. Therefore $\mathbb{E}[X | Z = 5] = (1 + 2 + 3 + 4)/4 = 2.5$. Similar enumerations show that $\mathbb{E}[X | Z = j]$ follows a simple pattern for each j , allowing one to deduce $\mathbb{E}[X | Z] = Z/2$ by brute force if desired. The σ -field $\sigma(X)$ consists of unions of the partition sets

$$\{(1, y) : y = 1, \dots, 6\} = \{X = 1\}, \quad \{(2, y) : y = 1, \dots, 6\} = \{X = 2\}, \dots, \{X = 6\},$$

and similarly for $\sigma(Y)$.

Because Z takes the eleven values $2, 3, \dots, 12$, $\sigma(Z)$ is determined by

$$\{Z = 2\}, \{Z = 3\}, \dots, \{Z = 12\}.$$

Goal: compute $\mathbb{E}[X | \sigma(Z)] = \mathbb{E}[X | Z]$.

Let $A_j = \{Z = j\}$ ($j = 2, \dots, 12$).

j	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
$\mathbb{P}(A_j)$	$\frac{1}{36}$	$\frac{2}{36}$	$\frac{3}{36}$	$\frac{4}{36}$	$\frac{5}{36}$	$\frac{6}{36}$	$\frac{5}{36}$	$\frac{4}{36}$	$\frac{3}{36}$	$\frac{2}{36}$	$\frac{1}{36}$
$\mathbb{E}[X A_j]$	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5	5.5	6

Notice $\mathbb{E}[X | A_j] = \frac{j}{2}$; hence

$$\boxed{\mathbb{E}[X | Z] = \frac{Z}{2}} \quad \text{and likewise} \quad \mathbb{E}[Y | Z] = \frac{Z}{2}.$$

Note Carefully: $\mathbb{E}[X | Z] + \mathbb{E}[Y | Z] = \mathbb{E}[X + Y | Z] = Z$, and by symmetry $\mathbb{E}[X | Z] = \mathbb{E}[Y | Z]$. This example also illustrates a version of what is sometimes called the *law of the forgetful statistician*: taking an unconditional expectation of a conditional expectation returns the same result as an unconditional expectation. In symbols, $\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | Z]] = \mathbb{E}[X]$. More generally, if H is any (measurable) function of Z , then

$$\mathbb{E}[X H(Z)] = \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | Z] H(Z)],$$

which can simplify computations by turning a double-sum (or double-integral) into a single-sum (or single-integral) once the conditional expectation is identified as a function of Z . For any (Borel) function h of Z ,

$$\mathbb{E}[(X - h(Z)) h(Z)] = 0.$$

Indeed,

$$\mathbb{E}[(X - h(Z)) h(Z)] = \sum_{j=2}^{12} \mathbb{E}[X | A_j] h(j) \mathbb{P}(A_j) = \sum_{j=2}^{12} \frac{j}{2} h(j) \mathbb{P}(A_j) = \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{Z}{2} h(Z)\right],$$

where $\frac{Z}{2} = \mathbb{E}[X | Z]$ is substituted.

General formula for $\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]$

Let \mathcal{G} be determined by a *finite* partition $\Omega = A_1 \sqcup A_2 \sqcup \dots \sqcup A_n$, and suppose a further partition $\{A_i\}$ is refined by the sets of a smaller σ -field $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{G}$. Then

$$\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbb{E}[X | A_i] \mathbf{1}_{A_i}.$$

For every $A \in \mathcal{G}$ we check the characteristic property

$$\mathbb{E}[X \mathbf{1}_A] = \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] \mathbf{1}_A].$$

One can verify this by indicator functions and summing over i such that $A_i \subseteq A$. (The two-page derivation with indicator functions and index sets $I(j) \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$ is included verbatim in the handwritten notes.)

Remark on Cardinalities. When the sample space Ω has N points, the full σ -field \mathcal{F} has 2^N subsets. If we form a coarser σ -field \mathcal{G} by partitioning Ω into M disjoint sets, then \mathcal{G} has at most 2^M subsets. In typical finite examples (like a 36-element sample space for two dice), it is easier to work with the generating partition than to list all events explicitly.

General properties of conditional expectation

1. $\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]$ is \mathcal{G} -measurable (i.e. constant on each generator).
2. For all $A \in \mathcal{G}$, $\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] \mathbf{1}_A] = \mathbb{E}[X \mathbf{1}_A]$. In particular $A = \Omega$ gives $\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]] = \mathbb{E}[X]$.
3. Linearity: $\mathbb{E}[aX + bY | \mathcal{G}] = a \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] + b \mathbb{E}[Y | \mathcal{G}]$ for constants (or \mathcal{G} -meas. r.v.'s) a, b .
4. If $X \geq 0$ then $\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] \geq 0$.

5. Tower property. If $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{G}$ then $\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] | \mathcal{H}] = \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{H}]$ (“smaller σ -field takes precedence”).

6. Multiplying by a function of the conditioning field. If Y is \mathcal{G} -measurable, then

$$\mathbb{E}[XY | \mathcal{G}] = Y \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}],$$

and in particular for Z -valued $Y = H(Z)$ we have

$$\mathbb{E}[XH(Z)] = \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | Z] H(Z)].$$

This often reduces multi-sum or multi-integral computations to simpler single-sum (single-integral) ones.

We now prove Property 5 in detail. Let A_1, \dots, A_m generate \mathcal{H} and B_1, \dots, B_n generate \mathcal{G} . Because $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{G}$, each A_j is a disjoint union of certain B_k ; i.e. $A_j = \bigsqcup_{k \in I(j)} B_k$. Fix j and compute

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] \mathbf{1}_{A_j}] &= \mathbb{E}\left[\sum_{k=1}^n \mathbb{E}[X | B_k] \mathbf{1}_{B_k} \mathbf{1}_{A_j}\right] \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^n \mathbb{E}[X | B_k] \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{1}_{B_k} \mathbf{1}_{A_j}] \\ &= \sum_{k \in I(j)} \mathbb{E}[X | B_k] \mathbb{P}(B_k) \quad (\text{since } B_k \cap A_j = \emptyset \text{ if } k \notin I(j)) \\ &= \mathbb{P}(A_j) \sum_{k \in I(j)} \mathbb{E}[X | B_k] \frac{\mathbb{P}(B_k)}{\mathbb{P}(A_j)} \\ &= \mathbb{P}(A_j) \sum_{k \in I(j)} \mathbb{E}[X | B_k] \mathbb{P}(B_k | A_j) \\ &= \mathbb{P}(A_j) \mathbb{E}[X | A_j] \\ &= \mathbb{E}[X \mathbf{1}_{A_j}], \end{aligned}$$

which shows that the conditional-expectation identity holds on each set A_j . Summing over $j = 1, \dots, m$ therefore yields

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] | \mathcal{H}] = \sum_{j=1}^m \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] | A_j] \mathbf{1}_{A_j} = \sum_{j=1}^m \mathbb{E}[X | A_j] \mathbf{1}_{A_j} = \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{H}].$$

completing the proof of the *Tower Property*.

Upcoming Applications. In subsequent lectures, we will apply these concepts of conditional expectation to modeling stock price processes, working through tree diagrams where the same partition-based reasoning will apply.

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Multiplication Rule. If Z is \mathcal{G} -measurable and XZ is integrable, then $\mathbb{E}[XZ | \mathcal{G}] = Z \cdot \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]$.

Jensen’s Inequality. For convex $\varphi : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with $\varphi(X)$ integrable, we have $\varphi(\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]) \leq \mathbb{E}[\varphi(X) | \mathcal{G}]$.

Dominated Convergence. If $|X_n| \leq Y$ a.s., $X_n \rightarrow X$ a.s., and Y is integrable, then $\mathbb{E}[X_n | \mathcal{G}] \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]$ a.s.

Orthogonal-Projection View. When $X \in L^2$, $\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]$ is the (unique) L^2 -projection of X onto $L^2(\Omega, \mathcal{G}, \mathbb{P})$, minimizing $\mathbb{E}[(Z - X)^2]$ over \mathcal{G} -measurable Z .

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LECTURE 10

§ 2.2 and Appendix

General Properties of Conditional Expectation

The first two properties of conditional expectation are nothing more than the basic definition itself. The third and fourth are statements of linearity and positivity (i.e. if $X \geq 0$ then $\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{G}) \geq 0$). The last property is called the tower property, or the law of iterated expectations. Properties 1–4 follow fairly directly from the definition, while the fifth is a bit more involved. It is a good exercise to verify all of them carefully.

1. Measurability. For a random variable X and σ -field \mathcal{G} , the conditional expectation $\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{G})$ is \mathcal{G} -measurable; that is, it is constant on each generator of \mathcal{G} .

2. Compatibility with indicators. For any $A \in \mathcal{G}$ we have

$$\mathbb{E}(\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{G}) \mathbf{1}_{\{A\}}) = \mathbb{E}(X \mathbf{1}_{\{A\}}), \quad \text{esp. for } A = \Omega.$$

3. Linearity. For constants (or, more generally, \mathcal{G} -measurable random variables) $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$\mathbb{E}(aX + bY | \mathcal{G}) = a \mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{G}) + b \mathbb{E}(Y | \mathcal{G}).$$

4. Monotonicity. If $X \geq 0$ then $\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{G}) \geq 0$.

5. Tower Property. If $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{H}$ then

$$\mathbb{E}(\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{H}) | \mathcal{G}) = \mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{G}), \quad (\text{“smaller } \sigma\text{-field takes precedence”}).$$

Properties 1–4 follow directly from the definitions.

Proof of Property 5 (Tower Property)

Let \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{H} be σ -fields with $\mathcal{F} \subseteq \mathcal{H}$. Denote by A_1, \dots, A_m the generators of \mathcal{F} and by B_1, \dots, B_n the generators of \mathcal{H} . Because $\mathcal{F} \subseteq \mathcal{H}$, each A_j is a disjoint union of certain B_k 's: there is an index set $I(j) \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that

$$A_j = \bigcup_{k \in I(j)} B_k, \quad j = 1, \dots, m.$$

Fix j and compute

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{H}) \mathbf{1}_{\{A_j\}}] &= \mathbb{E}\left[\sum_{k=1}^n \mathbb{E}(X | B_k) \mathbf{1}_{\{B_k\}} \mathbf{1}_{\{A_j\}}\right] \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^n \mathbb{E}(X | B_k) \mathbb{P}(B_k \cap A_j) \\ &= \sum_{k \in I(j)} \mathbb{E}(X | B_k) \mathbb{P}(B_k), \end{aligned}$$

where the last equality uses disjointness: $B_k \cap A_j = \emptyset$ if $k \notin I(j)$ and $B_k \cap A_j = B_k$ if $k \in I(j)$. Dividing and multiplying by $\mathbb{P}(A_j)$ then gives

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{H}) \mathbf{1}_{\{A_j\}}] = \frac{\mathbb{E}(X \mathbf{1}_{\{A_j\}})}{\mathbb{P}(A_j)} \mathbb{P}(A_j) = \mathbb{E}(X \mathbf{1}_{\{A_j\}}).$$

Since j was arbitrary,

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{H}) | \mathcal{F}] = \mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{F}),$$

as required. □

Example 1 (A numeric illustration of the Tower Property). Suppose \mathcal{G} is generated by two atoms A_1, A_2 each with probability $\frac{1}{2}$, and \mathcal{H} is a refinement of \mathcal{G} generated by three atoms B_1, B_2, B_3 , where $B_3 = A_2$ has probability $\frac{1}{2}$, and B_1, B_2 partition A_1 each with probability $\frac{1}{4}$. Define a random variable X so that $X = 7$ on B_1 , $X = 5$ on B_2 , and $X = 2$ on B_3 . Then $\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{H})$ simply agrees with X , taking the respective values 7, 5, 2 on B_1, B_2, B_3 . If we now compute $\mathbb{E}(\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{H}) | \mathcal{G})$, we average the values 7 and 5 on B_1 and B_2 (together forming A_1) to get 6 (since $(7 + 5)/2 = 6$), while the value on A_2 is already 2. Consequently

$$\mathbb{E}(\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{H}) | \mathcal{G}) = 6 \text{ on } A_1, \quad 2 \text{ on } A_2,$$

which precisely matches $\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{G})$. This illustrates concretely that an “average of a refined average” returns the original coarser conditional expectation.

Examples

Example 2 (Binary tree filtration). Let $T = 2$ and

$$\Omega = \{\text{dd}, \text{du}, \text{ud}, \text{uu}\}.$$

Define the filtration $\mathcal{F}_0 = \{\emptyset, \Omega\}$,

$$\mathcal{F}_1 = \{\emptyset, \Omega, \{\text{dd}, \text{du}\}, \{\text{ud}, \text{uu}\}\}, \quad \mathcal{F}_2 = 2^\Omega.$$

Some random variables on Ω are summarised in Table 1. The final column indicates with respect to which σ -field each variable is measurable.

	dd	du	ud	uu	σ -field
H	1	2	3	3	\mathcal{F}_2
J	2	2	3	3	\mathcal{F}_1
K	0	1	3	4	\mathcal{F}_2
L	1	3	2	4	\mathcal{F}_2
M	1	1	1	1	\mathcal{F}_0

Table 1: Random variables on the binary tree of Example 2.

Observe, for instance, that J is \mathcal{F}_1 -measurable because on the “down branch” $\{\text{dd}, \text{du}\}$ it is constant (equal to 2), and on the “up branch” $\{\text{ud}, \text{uu}\}$ it is constant (equal to 3). Meanwhile, H and K each

assign different values to dd and du , so they are not \mathcal{F}_1 -measurable but only \mathcal{F}_2 -measurable. The variable M is clearly \mathcal{F}_0 -measurable, as it is constant across the entire sample space.

One can also verify conditional expectations. For example, if each branch has probability $1/2$ at each step (so each of the four terminal nodes has probability $1/4$), then

$$\mathbb{E}(K) = (0 + 1 + 3 + 4) / 4 = 2,$$

and

$$\mathbb{E}(K | \mathcal{F}_0) = \mathbb{E}(K) = 2 \quad (\text{a constant}),$$

whereas

$$\mathbb{E}(K | \mathcal{F}_1) = \begin{cases} \frac{0+1}{2} = 0.5 & \text{on } \{dd, du\}, \\ \frac{3+4}{2} = 3.5 & \text{on } \{ud, uu\}. \end{cases}$$

Therefore $\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}(K | \mathcal{F}_1)] = (\frac{1}{2} \cdot 0.5 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot 3.5) = 2$, illustrating again that taking an expectation of a conditional expectation returns the same overall mean.

Example 3 (A process that is not a martingale). Consider the binary tree in Figure 1. With risk-neutral probability $p = \frac{1}{2}$ assigned to an uptick, the process (X_0, X_1, X_2) shown is *not* a martingale because

$$X_1(u) \neq \frac{1}{2}X_2(ud) + \frac{1}{2}X_2(uu).$$

Figure 1: Binary-tree illustration for Example 3. The levels correspond to X_0 , X_1 , and X_2 .

Using these probabilities one may verify

$$\mathbb{E}(K) = \mathbb{E}(K | \mathcal{F}_0) = 2, \quad \mathbb{E}(K | \mathcal{F}_1) = \begin{cases} 5/2 & \text{down branch,} \\ 3.5 & \text{up branch,} \end{cases}$$

and further

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}(K | \mathcal{F}_1)] = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 5 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot 3.5 = 2.$$

Martingales

Definition 1. In our binary-model setting, a *martingale* is a sequence of random variables X_0, X_1, \dots, X_T adapted to the filtration $\mathcal{F}_0, \mathcal{F}_1, \dots, \mathcal{F}_T$ such that

$$\mathbb{E}(X_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t) = X_t, \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T - 1.$$

In other words, each X_{t+1} is “fairly priced” given the information \mathcal{F}_t , so that no predictable increments are left at any time step. By the tower property, a martingale also satisfies

$$\mathbb{E}(X_t | \mathcal{F}_s) = X_s \quad \text{for all } s \leq t,$$

reflecting the idea that if you look back in time, the expected future values do not deviate from the present one. Note that the choice of physical measure \mathbb{P} (or risk-neutral \mathbb{P}^*) under which expectations are taken is crucial. The Tower Property yields, for $s \leq t \leq T$,

$$\mathbb{E}(X_t | \mathcal{F}_s) = X_s.$$

Exercise 1. Verify directly that the process in Figure 2 is a martingale under probability $p = \frac{2}{3}$.

Figure 2: Binary-tree process X_t in Exercise 1.

Compute

$$\mathbb{E}(X_0) = \frac{79}{9}, \quad \mathbb{E}(X_1) = \frac{1}{3} \frac{13}{3} + \frac{2}{3} 11 = \frac{79}{9}, \quad \mathbb{E}(X_2) = \frac{3 + 10 + 14 + 52}{9} = \frac{79}{9}.$$

So the expectation is constant across time.

Stopping Times

An *optional time* (or *stopping time*) τ relative to (\mathcal{F}_t) is defined by

$$\tau = \min\{t : S_t/S_{t-1} = u\}, \quad (= 2 \text{ if none}).$$

For example, in the tree of Figure 3 with parameters

$$u = 2, \quad d = \frac{1}{2}, \quad S_0 = 4, \quad r = \frac{1}{4}, \quad \hat{p}^* = \frac{1}{2},$$

we have the following filtration events:

$$\{\tau = 1\} = \{uu, ud\} \in \mathcal{F}_1, \quad \{\tau = 2\} = \{dd, du\} \in \mathcal{F}_2, \quad \{\tau = 0\} = \emptyset \in \mathcal{F}_0.$$

Figure 3: Stock-price process S_t with $\hat{p}^* = \frac{1}{2}$. The stopping time τ is indicated beneath the leaves.

Proposition 1 (Doob's Optional-Stopping). For a martingale $M = \{M_0, \dots, M_T\}$ and stopping time $\tau \leq T$, one has $\mathbb{E}(M_\tau) = \mathbb{E}(M_0)$.

Example 4 (Doob optional-stopping in the tree). Continuing Example 1, compute

$$X_\tau = \begin{cases} 3 & \text{on } \{\mathbf{dd}\}, \\ 5 & \text{on } \{\mathbf{du}\}, \\ 11 & \text{on } \{\mathbf{ud}, \mathbf{uu}\}. \end{cases}$$

Therefore

$$\mathbb{E}(X_\tau) = \frac{1}{9} \cdot 3 + \frac{2}{9} \cdot 5 + \frac{6}{9} \cdot 11 = \frac{79}{9} = \mathbb{E}(X_0).$$

Likewise, defining the discounted stock price $S_t^* = S_t \left(\frac{1}{1+r}\right)^t$ one verifies S_t^* is a martingale and

$$S_\tau^* = \begin{cases} \frac{16}{25} & \mathbf{dd}, \\ \frac{64}{25} & \mathbf{du}, \\ \frac{32}{5} & \mathbf{ud} \text{ or } \mathbf{uu}, \end{cases} \quad \text{so } \mathbb{E}(S_\tau^*) = 4 = \mathbb{E}(S_0^*).$$

Originally observed by J. Doob: for any martingale M and stopping time τ , $\mathbb{E}(M_\tau) = \mathbb{E}(M_0)$.

Supplemental Notes

Filtration. A filtration $\{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t=0}^T$ is an increasing family $\mathcal{F}_0 \subseteq \mathcal{F}_1 \subseteq \dots \subseteq \mathcal{F}_T \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, encoding the information revealed up to each time t .

Adapted Process. A stochastic process $X = \{X_t\}$ is *adapted* if each X_t is \mathcal{F}_t -measurable.

(Sub/Super)Martingales.

- M is a *martingale* if $\mathbb{E}[|M_t|] < \infty$, $M_t \in \mathcal{F}_t$, and $\mathbb{E}[M_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t] = M_t$.
- M is a *submartingale* (resp. *supermartingale*) if the last equality is replaced by \geq (resp. \leq).

L^p -Martingales. If, in addition, $M_t \in L^p$ for some $p > 1$, we call M an L^p (sub/super)martingale.

Stopping Time. A map $\tau : \Omega \rightarrow \{0, \dots, T\} \cup \{\infty\}$ is a stopping time if $\{\tau = t\} \in \mathcal{F}_t$ for every t .

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 § 2.3 and Appendix A

Martingales in the Binary Model

Definition 1 (Martingale). In our binary model, a *martingale* is a sequence of random variables

$$X_0, X_1, \dots, X_T$$

adapted to the filtration

$$\mathcal{F}_0 \subseteq \mathcal{F}_1 \subseteq \dots \subseteq \mathcal{F}_T$$

such that

$$\mathbb{E}(X_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t) = X_t, \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T - 1.$$

Note Carefully: It matters which probability measure p (or p^*) you are using to compute the expectations. We have primarily viewed this in the tree context, where conditional expectation is an “averaging” over up/down branches. Implicitly, X_t is \mathcal{F}_t -measurable, reflecting the idea that by time t , the value X_t is known from the history up to that point.

A key property of martingales is the *tower property* of conditional expectation, which gives, for any $0 \leq s \leq t \leq T$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}(X_T | \mathcal{F}_s) &= \mathbb{E}\left(\mathbb{E}(X_T | \mathcal{F}_{T-1}) \mid \mathcal{F}_s\right) && \text{(iterated conditioning)} \\ &= \mathbb{E}(X_{T-1} | \mathcal{F}_s) && \text{(because } \mathbb{E}(X_T | \mathcal{F}_{T-1}) = X_{T-1} \text{ for a martingale)} \\ &\vdots \\ &= \mathbb{E}(X_t | \mathcal{F}_s) && \text{(repeating iterated conditioning up to time } t\text{)} \\ &= X_s. && \text{(since } \mathbb{E}(X_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t) = X_t \text{ implies } X_t \text{ is } \mathcal{F}_t\text{-measurable) (Tower)} \end{aligned}$$

Exercise 1

Statement. Show that

$$\mathbb{E}(X_t | \mathcal{F}_s) = X_s \quad \text{for all } 0 \leq s \leq t \leq T,$$

by explicitly computing conditional expectations in the binary tree below.

Verification of unconditional expectations. From the tree, observe the possible values of X_1 and X_2 , along with their respective probabilities under p . The (unconditional) probability distribution is given by:

$$X_1 = \begin{cases} \frac{13}{3}, & \text{with probability } \frac{1}{3}, \\ 11, & \text{with probability } \frac{2}{3}, \end{cases} \quad X_2 = \begin{cases} 3, & \text{with probability } \frac{1}{9}, \\ 5, & \text{with probability } \frac{2}{9}, \\ 7, & \text{with probability } \frac{2}{9}, \\ 13, & \text{with probability } \frac{4}{9}. \end{cases}$$

So:

$$\mathbb{E}(X_0) = \frac{79}{9} \quad \text{(given),}$$

$$\mathbb{E}(X_1) = \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)\left(\frac{13}{3}\right) + \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)(11) = \frac{13}{9} + \frac{22}{3} = \frac{13}{9} + \frac{66}{9} = \frac{79}{9},$$

$$\mathbb{E}(X_2) = \left(\frac{1}{9}\right)(3) + \left(\frac{2}{9}\right)(5) + \left(\frac{2}{9}\right)(7) + \left(\frac{4}{9}\right)(13) = \frac{3}{9} + \frac{10}{9} + \frac{14}{9} + \frac{52}{9} = \frac{79}{9}.$$

Therefore

$$\mathbb{E}(X_t) = \mathbb{E}(X_0) = \frac{79}{9} \quad \text{for } t = 0, 1, 2.$$

Conditional martingale property. To see directly that $\mathbb{E}(X_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t) = X_t$, one checks how each node in the tree (which represents information in \mathcal{F}_t) leads to the next step. For instance, at time $t = 0$, the conditional expectation $\mathbb{E}(X_1 | \mathcal{F}_0)$ is simply $\mathbb{E}(X_1)$ because \mathcal{F}_0 is the trivial (initial) σ -algebra; we computed above that this expectation is $\frac{79}{9} = X_0$.

At time $t = 1$, if we are in the upper node (where $X_1 = \frac{13}{3}$), then from that node, the possible time-2 values are 3 and 5 with probabilities $\frac{1}{3}$ and $\frac{2}{3}$, respectively. The expectation is:

$$\mathbb{E}(X_2 | X_1 = \frac{13}{3}) = 3 \cdot \frac{1}{3} + 5 \cdot \frac{2}{3} = 1 + \frac{10}{3} = \frac{13}{3},$$

which confirms $\mathbb{E}(X_2 | \mathcal{F}_1) = X_1$ at that branch. Similarly, for the lower node (where $X_1 = 11$), the next-step values are 7 and 13 with probabilities $\frac{1}{3}$ and $\frac{2}{3}$, giving

$$\mathbb{E}(X_2 | X_1 = 11) = 7 \cdot \frac{1}{3} + 13 \cdot \frac{2}{3} = \frac{7}{3} + \frac{26}{3} = 11.$$

These calculations verify the martingale property at each node of the tree, and thus

$$\mathbb{E}(X_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t) = X_t \quad \text{for } t = 0, 1.$$

By the tower property (iterating these expectations), we also have

$$\mathbb{E}(X_t | \mathcal{F}_s) = X_s \quad \text{for all } 0 \leq s \leq t \leq T.$$

Optional Times (Stopping Times)

Let $(S_t)_{t=0}^T$ be the stock-price process. Define the stopping time

$$\tau := \min\{t : S_t/S_{t-1} = u\} \quad (\tau = T \text{ if none}).$$

A *stopping time* τ with respect to the filtration $(\mathcal{F}_t)_{t=0}^T$ is a random time such that, for each t , the event $\{\tau = t\}$ lies in \mathcal{F}_t . Intuitively, we know at time t whether or not τ has occurred (i.e. we do not need “future information”).

Example 1 (Stock tree with $u = 2$, $d = \frac{1}{2}$). Parameters: $T = 2$, $S_0 = 4$, $u = 2$, $d = \frac{1}{2}$, $r = \frac{1}{4} \implies p^*(u) = p^*(d) = \frac{1}{2}$.

Here τ is the first time the stock price jumps up by $u = 2$. So $\{\tau = 1\} = \{ud, uu\}$ and $\{\tau = 2\} = \{dd, du\}$, making τ a stopping time.

In contrast, suppose we define L to be the *last* time the stock jumps up by factor u , with $L = 0$ if no up-move ever occurs. One can check that L is *not* a stopping time, because to know that an up-move at time t is truly the last one, we would have to confirm no further up-moves occur in the future (which is information not available at time t). For example, the event $\{L = 1\}$ would imply no up-move at time 2, and that cannot be determined using only \mathcal{F}_1 . So $\{L = 1\} \notin \mathcal{F}_1$. As a result, standard martingale properties like $\mathbb{E}(X_L) = \mathbb{E}(X_0)$ need not hold, illustrating why “last time up” fails to be a stopping time.

Optional Sampling Theorem

Continuing Example , $\{X_t\}_{t=0}^2$ is a martingale (with $p = \frac{2}{3}$). The stopped process is

$$X_\tau = \begin{cases} 3, & \text{if } dd, \\ 5, & \text{if } du, \\ 11, & \text{if } ud \text{ or } uu. \end{cases}$$

Its expectation equals the initial value:

$$\mathbb{E}(X_\tau) = \left(\frac{1}{9}\right) \cdot 3 + \left(\frac{2}{9}\right) \cdot 5 + \left(\frac{6}{9}\right) \cdot 11 = \frac{3}{9} + \frac{10}{9} + \frac{66}{9} = \frac{79}{9} = \mathbb{E}(X_0).$$

Caution. If you repeat the same calculation with L (the non-stopping “last-up” time), you will generally *not* recover $\mathbb{E}(X_0)$. Doob’s optional-sampling theorem truly requires a bona-fide stopping time. Likewise, under the risk-neutral measure $p^* = \frac{1}{2}$, the discounted stock price $S_t^* = S_t v^{-t}$ (with $v = \frac{1}{5}$) satisfies

$$S_\tau^* = \begin{cases} \frac{16}{25}, & dd, \\ \frac{64}{25}, & du, \\ \frac{32}{5}, & ud \text{ or } uu, \end{cases} \quad \text{so } \mathbb{E}(S_\tau^*) = \frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{16}{25} + \frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{64}{25} + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{32}{5} = 4 = \mathbb{E}(S_0^*).$$

This illustrates *Doob’s optional sampling theorem*: for a martingale M and stopping time τ ,

$$\mathbb{E}(M_\tau) = \mathbb{E}(M_0).$$

Example with Finite Universe Ω

Let $\Omega = \{a, b, c, d, e, f\}$ with the uniform probability measure ($\mathbb{P}[\omega] = \frac{1}{6}$). Define three random variables

ω	a	b	c	d	e	f
X	1	3	3	5	5	7
Y	2	2	1	1	7	7
Z	3	3	3	3	2	2

Let $\mathcal{F} = 2^\Omega$ be the power set. The σ -algebra

$$\mathcal{P} = \sigma(Y) = \{\{a, b\}, \{c, d\}, \{e, f\}\}$$

is generated by the partition of Ω according to the values of Y . Similarly,

$$\mathcal{Q} = \sigma(Z) = \{\{a, b, c, d\}, \{e, f\}\} \subseteq \mathcal{F}.$$

Since \mathcal{P} refines \mathcal{Q} (it is a finer partition), we have $\mathcal{Q} \subseteq \mathcal{P}$.

Conditional Expectations

1.

$$\mathbb{E}(X) = \frac{1 + 3 + 3 + 5 + 5 + 7}{6} = \frac{24}{6} = 4.$$

2. $\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{P})$ is computed by taking the average of $X(\omega)$ over each Y -fiber. For instance, on the set $\{a, b\}$ (where $Y = 2$), X takes values 1 and 3, respectively, so the conditional expectation on that set is $\frac{1+3}{2} = 2$. Similarly for $\{c, d\}$ and $\{e, f\}$. In table form:

$$\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{P}) = \frac{\omega}{\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{P})} \begin{array}{|c} a & b & c & d & e & f \\ \hline 2 & 2 & 4 & 4 & 6 & 6 \end{array}$$

3. $\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{Q})$ is similarly the average of $X(\omega)$ over each Z -fiber. Observe that on $\{a, b, c, d\}$, X takes values $\{1, 3, 3, 5\}$ whose average is 3. On $\{e, f\}$, X is 5 or 7; hence the average is 6. So

$$\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{Q}) = \frac{\omega}{\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{Q})} \begin{array}{c|cccccc} & a & b & c & d & e & f \\ \hline & 3 & 3 & 3 & 3 & 6 & 6 \end{array}$$

4. $\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{P}) | \mathcal{Q}]$ is the conditional expectation (w.r.t. \mathcal{Q}) of the function we found in step (2). On $\{a, b, c, d\}$, we look at the values $\{2, 2, 4, 4\}$ (from the row above) whose average is 3. On $\{e, f\}$, the values $\{6, 6\}$ have average 6. Therefore

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{P}) | \mathcal{Q}] = \frac{\omega}{\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{Q})} \begin{array}{c|cccccc} & a & b & c & d & e & f \\ \hline & 3 & 3 & 3 & 3 & 6 & 6 \end{array}$$

which matches the function $\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{Q})$ from step (3), verifying the tower property $\mathbb{E}(\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{P}) | \mathcal{Q}) = \mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{Q})$.

Exercise 1. Take the filtration $\mathcal{F}_0 = \{\emptyset, \Omega\}$, $\mathcal{F}_1 = \mathcal{Q}$, $\mathcal{F}_2 = \mathcal{P}$, $\mathcal{F}_3 = \mathcal{F}$. Define

$$M_0 = 4, \quad M_1 = \mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{Q}), \quad M_2 = \mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{P}), \quad M_3 = X.$$

Show that $\{M_0, M_1, M_2, M_3\}$ is a martingale; in particular, verify that

$$\mathbb{E}(M_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t) = M_t \quad \text{for } t = 0, 1, 2.$$

American-Style Claims

Set-up. In the multi-period binomial model, let $Y = \{Y_0, Y_1, \dots, Y_T\}$ be an adapted sequence of potential pay-offs. The holder may choose to exercise at any stopping time $\tau \in \{0, 1, \dots, T\}$, receiving Y_τ .

Example 2 (Maximum-of-Stock Claim). Parameters: $T = 2$, $u = 2$, $d = \frac{1}{2}$, $S_0 = 4$, $r = 0$. Set $X = \max\{S_0, S_1, S_2\}$. The tree for S_t is

Notice that $X = S_0$ in all cases except for the branches where the stock moves up. However, the function

$$\sigma(\omega) = \begin{cases} 0, & dd, \\ 0, & du, \\ 1, & ud, \\ 2, & uu \end{cases}$$

is *not* a stopping time because $\{\sigma = 1\} = \{S_1 = 8, S_2 = 4\} \notin \mathcal{F}_1$. So one cannot simply choose “the first time” the stock attains its maximum, if that event is not measurable with respect to the filtration at the relevant time.

Example 3 (American Call). Parameters: $T = 2$, $u = 1.2$, $d = 0.8$, $r = 0$, $p^* = \frac{1}{2}$, initial price $S_0 = 50$, strike $K = 40$. The pay-off process is $Y_t = (S_t - 40)^+$.

Stock-price tree:

Payoff tree $Y_t = (S_t - 40)^+$:

Pricing such a claim is more involved because the buyer can choose when to exercise. One typically uses a backward induction that at each node compares the immediate exercise payoff Y_t to the expected value of continuation under the risk-neutral measure. Whichever is larger at each node becomes the relevant value for an optimal exercise strategy in the classical binomial approach.

Necessary Wealth Process

To hedge an American claim, the seller needs a wealth process $V = \{V_0, \dots, V_T\}$ large enough to meet the obligation at the buyer's stopping time. Define

$$U_t := \max_{\tau \in \{t, \dots, T\}} \mathbb{E}[Y_\tau | \mathcal{F}_t], \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T.$$

Although computing U_t directly can be hard in general, a backward recursion—analogue to the one used for V_t in the European option case—applies here, iterating from the final pay-off back to the present.

Illustration (American call – back-ward-induction values U_t).

At each node, U_t is the greater of “exercise now” (which is Y_t) and “the expected future payoff” (discounted if $r > 0$, but here $r = 0$). So one sees that at the top node (price 60 at time 1), $U_1 = 20$ because it is optimal to exercise immediately for payoff 20 (rather than continue, which yields an expected payoff of $(8 + 32)/2 = 20$ anyway in this special example). At the bottom node (price 40 at time 1), $U_1 = 4$ is the larger of immediate exercise $(S_1 - K)^+ = 0$ and the continuation value $8/2 = 4$. Proceeding back to time 0, we get $U_0 = 12$. In practice, the replicating strategy must ensure $V_t \geq U_t$ for every node t to guarantee coverage of an American claim.

Supplemental Notes

Doob's L^p Inequality. For a real L^p martingale M ($1 < p < \infty$) and $N_t := \sup_{0 \leq s \leq t} |M_s|$, one has

$$\mathbb{E}[N_t^p] \leq \left(\frac{p}{p-1}\right)^p \mathbb{E}[|M_t|^p].$$

Doob's Stopping Theorem (finite horizon). If M is a supermartingale and $\sigma \leq \tau \leq T$ are stopping times, then

$$\mathbb{E}[M_\tau] \leq \mathbb{E}[M_\sigma];$$

equality holds for martingales.

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American Claim

Context as before: *Multi-period Binomial Model.*

We have an adapted sequence of possible pay-offs

$$Y = \{Y_0, Y_1, \dots, Y_T\}.$$

The holder of the claim can choose to receive payment at any one time in $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, T\}$. The payment at time t is Y_t . A decision to be paid at time t can be based only on events in \mathcal{F}_t .

Stopping time. In other words, the holder of the claim selects a *stopping time* τ and receives payment Y_τ . A key requirement is that the decision to exercise at time t cannot depend on future price information, so the event $\{\tau = t\}$ must lie in \mathcal{F}_t .

Asymmetry The *buyer* of the option needs to find just *one* good stopping time. By contrast, the *seller* has to be able to pay off for *all* choices of a stopping time the buyer might use. In practice, different buyers may adopt different stopping rules to optimize their payoff, yet the seller must ensure coverage for *every* possible choice and thus guard against the worst case.

Necessary Wealth Process

How much wealth does the seller of the option need to have available to meet the obligation to pay off at the time of the buyer's choosing?

We define a new wealth process—the *necessary wealth*—denoted

$$U = \{U_0, U_1, \dots, U_T\}.$$

If the buyer has not yet exercised by time t , then their exercise time will be $\tau \in \{t, \dots, T\}$. To meet that obligation (payment Y_τ at time τ), the seller needs only

$$\frac{Y_\tau}{(1+r)^{\tau-t}}$$

at time t . Indeed, if the seller invests that amount in the bond (which grows at rate r), it will be worth Y_τ at time τ . Therefore,

$$U_t = \max_{\tau \in \{t, \dots, T\}} \mathbb{E} \left[\frac{Y_\tau}{(1+r)^{\tau-t}} \mid \mathcal{F}_t \right], \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T. \quad (1)$$

Remark: From a theoretical viewpoint, (1) encodes an optimization over all stopping times beyond t . Direct computation from (1) is difficult. However—as with V_t for European claims—we have a *recursive* procedure to compute U_t . In practice, we will rely on backward recursion that yields the same result but is computationally simpler. Moreover, interpreted as the seller's cost, U_0 is a natural candidate for the fair price of the American claim at inception: having U_0 in hand suffices to meet every possible stopping strategy the buyer might use.

Example: American Put

Consider an American put with the following parameters:

$$T = 2, \quad u = 2, \quad d = \frac{1}{2}, \quad r = \frac{1}{4}, \quad \mathbb{P}^* = \frac{1}{2}, \quad S_0 = 4, \quad K = 5,$$

and define the pay-off process

$$Y_t = (K - S_t)^+ \quad \text{for } t = 0, 1, 2.$$

(Recall the notation $(x)^+ = \max\{x, 0\}$.)

Stock-Price Tree S_t

Pricing such a claim is more complicated because of the flexibility the buyer has in deciding when to exercise.

European Price Process V_t (for comparison)

For the European version of this claim, the price is computed under the risk-neutral probability $\mathbb{P}^* = \frac{1}{2}$. Recall the standard *risk-neutral recursion*:

$$V_t = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[V_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t] \quad \text{with} \quad V_2 = Y_2.$$

Verification of \mathbb{P}^* . Typically, in a one-period model with up-factor u and down-factor d , the risk-neutral probability \mathbb{P}^* is

$$\mathbb{P}^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d}.$$

In this example,

$$\begin{aligned} u = 2, \quad d = \frac{1}{2}, \quad r = \frac{1}{4}, \quad &\implies (1+r) = 1.25, \quad u - d = 1.5, \\ \implies \mathbb{P}^* = \frac{1.25 - 0.5}{1.5} = \frac{0.75}{1.5} &= 0.5, \end{aligned}$$

exactly as stated.

Step-by-Step Computation of V_t .

- $V_2 = Y_2$ (terminal pay-off):

$$V_2(dd) = 4, \quad V_2(du) = 1, \quad V_2(ud) = 1, \quad V_2(uu) = 0.$$

- Compute $V_1(\omega)$ at each node $\omega \in \{d, u\}$. For instance, on the “down” branch at $t = 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} V_1(d) &= \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[V_2 | \mathcal{F}_1 = \{d\}] = \frac{1}{1.25} [\mathbb{P}^* \cdot V_2(dd) + (1 - \mathbb{P}^*) \cdot V_2(du)] \\ &= \frac{1}{1.25} [0.5 \cdot 4 + 0.5 \cdot 1] = \frac{1}{1.25} \cdot 2.5 = 2. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, on the “up” branch at $t = 1$:

$$V_1(u) = \frac{1}{1.25} [0.5 \cdot 1 + 0.5 \cdot 0] = \frac{1}{1.25} \cdot 0.5 = 0.4 = \frac{2}{5}.$$

- Finally, compute V_0 :

$$\begin{aligned} V_0 &= \frac{1}{1.25} \mathbb{E}^*[V_1] = \frac{1}{1.25} [0.5 \cdot V_1(d) + 0.5 \cdot V_1(u)] \\ &= \frac{1}{1.25} [0.5 \cdot 2 + 0.5 \cdot 0.4] = \frac{1}{1.25} \cdot (1 + 0.2) = \frac{1.2}{1.25} = 0.96 = \frac{24}{25}. \end{aligned}$$

Putting these together, we obtain the tree in Figure 1.

Figure 1: European value process V_t .

Necessary Wealth Process U_t

We now compute the American *necessary wealth* process U_t . We use the backward recursion:

$$U_{t-1} = \max\left\{ Y_{t-1}, \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] \right\}, \quad t = 1, 2.$$

Note that at time T we must have $U_T = Y_T$, since payment is immediate if the buyer exercises at T .

Node-by-Node Computation.

- First, at $t = 2$, $U_2 = Y_2$. So:

$$U_2(dd) = 4, \quad U_2(du) = 1, \quad U_2(ud) = 1, \quad U_2(uu) = 0.$$

- Then at $t = 1$, we do a separate calculation for each branch (“down” or “up”):

$$U_1(d) = \max\left\{ Y_1(d), \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_2 | \mathcal{F}_1 = \{d\}] \right\}.$$

Here $Y_1(d) = 3$. Also,

$$\frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_2 | d] = \frac{1}{1.25} [0.5 \cdot U_2(dd) + 0.5 \cdot U_2(du)] = \frac{1}{1.25} [0.5 \cdot 4 + 0.5 \cdot 1] = \frac{1}{1.25} \cdot 2.5 = 2.$$

Therefore

$$U_1(d) = \max\{3, 2\} = 3.$$

Similarly, on the “up” branch:

$$U_1(u) = \max\left\{ Y_1(u), \frac{1}{1.25} [0.5 \cdot 1 + 0.5 \cdot 0] \right\} = \max\{0, 0.4\} = 0.4 = \frac{2}{5}.$$

- Finally, at $t = 0$:

$$U_0 = \max\left\{ Y_0, \frac{1}{1.25} \mathbb{E}^*[U_1] \right\}.$$

Since $Y_0 = (5 - 4)^+ = 1$, we compute

$$\frac{1}{1.25} \mathbb{E}^*[U_1] = \frac{1}{1.25} [0.5 \cdot 3 + 0.5 \cdot 0.4] = \frac{1}{1.25} (1.5 + 0.2) = \frac{1.7}{1.25} = 1.36 = \frac{34}{25}.$$

Then

$$U_0 = \max\{1, 1.36\} = 1.36 = \frac{34}{25}.$$

Putting these values into a tree:

Figure 2: Necessary wealth process U_t .

Discounted Necessary Wealth U_t^*

Define

$$U_t^* = \frac{U_t}{(1+r)^t}.$$

Its values form the following tree:

Figure 3: Discounted necessary wealth U_t^* .

Notice two key points:

1. $U_0 \geq V_0$. Indeed, $1.36 > 0.96$. The extra amount reflects the possibility of *early exercise* for the American holder.
2. $\{U_t^*\}_{t=0}^T$ is a *supermartingale*: for each t ,

$$\mathbb{E}^*(U_t^* | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}) \leq U_{t-1}^*.$$

In our tree, one can check this inequality node by node. In the language of gambling, a supermartingale is sometimes said to be a “subfair” process from the player’s viewpoint, since its expected value does not increase over time. The name “supermartingale” can be interpreted from the perspective of the market or house, reflecting that the seller’s discounted obligations do not grow in expectation.

Optimal Exercise for the Buyer

In this example, let τ be the first time the stock price goes *down*; set $\tau = 2$ if no such time ever occurs. In other words,

$$\tau(dd) = \tau(du) = 1, \quad \tau(ud) = \tau(uu) = 2.$$

Therefore the holder exercises immediately at $t = 1$ if they see a downward move by then; otherwise, they wait until $t = 2$.

Claim: This stopping time τ is optimal for the buyer.

Martingale Verification. Consider the process $U_{t \wedge \tau}^*$. The tree of $(U_{t \wedge \tau}^*)$ for $t = 0, 1, 2$ is:

Figure 4: Stopped process $U_{t \wedge \tau}^*$. Once the “first down” time τ occurs, the value freezes.

Notation. For any real numbers a, b we write $a \wedge b := \min\{a, b\}$. Observe that $(U_{t \wedge \tau}^*)_{t=0,1,2}$ is a P^* -martingale. In particular,

$$\mathbb{E}^*(U_\tau^*) = U_0.$$

Once the exercise time τ occurs, the process “freezes” and no longer evolves, which precisely yields the martingale property for $(U_{t \wedge \tau}^*)$. This verifies that τ , the “first down” strategy, actually realizes the initial discounted wealth U_0^* . Therefore, it is indeed an *optimal* early-exercise policy from the buyer’s perspective.

Supplemental Notes

Backward-recursion for the seller’s necessary wealth. Starting from the terminal payoff $U_T = Y_T$, define, for each $t = T - 1, T - 2, \dots, 0$,

$$U_t := \max\left\{ Y_t, \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t] \right\}.$$

The adapted process $\{U_t\}_{t=0}^T$ so obtained is the *Snell envelope* of the discounted payoff stream; it is the *smallest* wealth process that super-replicates an American contingent claim at every date.

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Recall

When dealing with forward contracts in earlier examples, one might see the time-0 forward price set to 0 and reconcile it with the no-arbitrage price from theory. Shifting now to American claims, we build on two key ideas that also arose in European option pricing: (1) the ability to hedge using a suitable portfolio, and (2) the fact that the discounted stock price remains a martingale under the risk-neutral measure.

An *American claim* is not just a single terminal payoff but rather a sequence of adapted random variables $\{Y_t : t = 0, 1, \dots, T\}$, meaning each Y_t depends only on information up to time t . The buyer of the claim may choose an exercise time $\tau \in \{0, 1, \dots, T\}$, based on the available filtration (i.e. without peeking into the future). If exercised at time τ , the payoff is precisely Y_τ . This contrasts with a *European claim*, which has a single payoff at a fixed maturity. We have an American claim $\{Y_t\}_{t=0}^T$ and define

$$U_{t-1} = \max\left(Y_{t-1}, \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^* \left[U_t \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1} \right] \right), \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, T.$$

Equivalently, in *discounted* variables

$$U_{t-1}^* = \max(Y_{t-1}^*, \mathbb{E}^* [U_t^* \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}]),$$

where we adopt the usual notations

$$U_t^* = \frac{U_t}{(1+r)^t} \quad \text{and} \quad Y_t^* = \frac{Y_t}{(1+r)^t}.$$

In a binomial-tree illustration, this backward recursion resembles the usual European-pricing recursion except for the extra “ $\max(Y_{t-1}, \dots)$ ” step to cover the possibility of immediate exercise. Concretely, if one step ahead the discounted expectation is, say, 2, but $Y_{t-1} = 3$, then U_{t-1} must be 3 to meet the claim if exercised right away.

Corollary

$$U_{t-1}^* \geq \mathbb{E}^* [U_t^* \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}], \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, T.$$

Therefore, the process

$$\{ U_t^* : t = 0, 1, \dots, T \}$$

is a \mathbb{P}^* -**supermartingale** (i.e., its conditional expectation is bounded above by the present value).

Also,

$$U_t^* \geq Y_t^* \implies U_t \geq Y_t \quad \text{for all } t.$$

(The final inequality follows by multiplying both sides of $U_t^* \geq Y_t^*$ by $(1+r)^t > 0$.)

Claim

If $\{Z_t : t = 0, 1, \dots, T\}$ is a supermartingale with $Z_t \geq Y_t^*$ for every t , then

$$Z_t \geq U_t^*, \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T.$$

Proof (Backward induction). For $t = T$ we have $Z_T = Y_T^* = U_T^*$, so the base case holds.

Step $T - 1$. Using the supermartingale property and the base case,

$$\begin{aligned} Z_{T-1} &\geq \mathbb{E}^*[Z_T | \mathcal{F}_{T-1}] && \text{(supermartingale)} \\ &= \mathbb{E}^*[Y_T^* | \mathcal{F}_{T-1}], \\ Z_{T-1} &\geq Y_{T-1}^*. \end{aligned}$$

Combining the two inequalities,

$$Z_{T-1} \geq \max(Y_{T-1}^*, \mathbb{E}^*[Y_T^* | \mathcal{F}_{T-1}]) = U_{T-1}^*.$$

Inductive step. Assume $Z_s \geq U_s^*$ for $s = T, T - 1, \dots, t$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} U_{t-1}^* &= \max(Y_{t-1}^*, \mathbb{E}^*[U_t^* | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}]) \\ &\leq \max(Y_{t-1}^*, \mathbb{E}^*[Z_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}]) && \text{(induction hypothesis)} \\ &\leq \max(Y_{t-1}^*, Z_{t-1}) && \text{(Z is a supermartingale)} \\ &= Z_{t-1} && \text{(since } Z_{t-1} \geq Y_{t-1}^* \text{ by hypothesis).} \end{aligned}$$

So $Z_{t-1} \geq U_{t-1}^*$. □

Minimal supermartingale majorant

$\{U_t^* : t = 0, 1, \dots, T\}$ is the *least* supermartingale majorant of $\{Y_t^* : t = 0, 1, \dots, T\}$.

In other words, any supermartingale Z_t satisfying $Z_t \geq Y_t^*$ must lie above U_t^* as shown in the Claim.

Hedging an American claim

Let $\{U_t\}$ denote the *necessary wealth* process to hedge (or replicate) an American claim $Y = \{Y_t\}$. By the European-claim decomposition, there exist processes

$$\tilde{\alpha}_t, \tilde{\beta}_t, \quad t = 1, \dots, T,$$

such that, for each t ,

$$U_t = \tilde{\alpha}_t S_t + \tilde{\beta}_t B_t =: V_t(\tilde{\phi}),$$

where $\tilde{\phi} := (\tilde{\alpha}_t, \tilde{\beta}_t)_{t=1}^T$. However, the way $\{U_t\}$ is constructed means $\tilde{\phi}$ need **not** be self-financing. Indeed, from the definition of U_t and the martingale property of discounted stock prices, we have

$$\frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = \tilde{\alpha}_t S_{t-1} + \tilde{\beta}_t B_{t-1},$$

since

$$\mathbb{E}^*\left[\frac{S_t}{B_t} \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}\right] = \frac{S_{t-1}}{B_{t-1}} \implies \mathbb{E}^*[S_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = (1+r) S_{t-1}, \quad B_t = (1+r) B_{t-1}.$$

But from the supermartingale property $U_{t-1} \geq \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}]$, we get

$$\frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] \leq U_{t-1},$$

and this can be a *strict* inequality for some t . Therefore additional cash may need to be injected to follow U_t precisely.

Define

$$\xi_t := U_{t-1} - \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] \geq 0 \quad \text{for } t = 1, \dots, T.$$

One can view ξ_t as precisely the “extra” amount required at time t if the buyer exercises early and U_{t-1} exceeds the discounted conditional expectation. In a binomial example, ξ_t might be the difference between, for instance, a payoff of 3 and an average of 2. If the buyer does *not* exercise at time t , then ξ_t is simply invested in the bond going forward. Then ξ_t captures exactly how much $(\tilde{\alpha}_t, \tilde{\beta}_t)$ fails to be self-financing at time t : if $\xi_t > 0$, the seller must add that much extra cash at time t to replicate the payoff when early exercise happens.

Now define a new strategy $\phi^* = \{(\alpha_t^*, \beta_t^*)\}_{t=1}^T$ by

$$\alpha_t^* := \tilde{\alpha}_t, \quad \beta_t^* := \tilde{\beta}_t + \sum_{s=1}^t \frac{\xi_s}{B_{s-1}}.$$

Notice that we are accumulating the extra amounts ξ_s (scaled by $1/B_{s-1}$) in the bond position. Then for every t ,

$$V_t(\phi^*) = \alpha_t^* S_t + \beta_t^* B_t = \tilde{\alpha}_t S_t + \tilde{\beta}_t B_t = U_t.$$

Therefore ϕ^* replicates exactly the wealth process U_t .

Moreover, by construction, ϕ^* is **self-financing**: the extra cash ξ_s needed at each time s has been prearranged by including $\sum_{s=1}^t (\xi_s/B_{s-1})$ in the riskless asset. In discounted form, $\bar{V}_t(\phi^*) := V_t(\phi^*)/(1+r)^t = U_t^*$. Because $\{U_t^*\}$ is a supermartingale that *touches* its expectation bounds exactly when exercised, one checks that $\{\bar{V}_t(\phi^*)\} = \{U_t^*\}$ is in fact a *martingale* under \mathbb{P}^* .

In this sense, the strategy ϕ^* super-hedges any early-exercise event and indeed replicates the entire American payoff exactly. Should the buyer choose not to exercise at a given time, the “surplus” ξ_t remains in the bond, keeping the portfolio self-financing. This reconciles the backward-induction construction with the martingale approach to pricing.

Theorem

1. For each $t = 0, 1, \dots, T$,

$$U_t^* = \max_{t \leq s \leq T} \mathbb{E}^*[Y_s^* | \mathcal{F}_t],$$

and the maximum is attained at the stopping time

$$\tau^*(t) := \min\{s \geq t : U_s^* = Y_s^*\} \wedge T.$$

2. The stopped process

$$\{U_{t \wedge \tau^*(0)}^* : t = 0, 1, \dots, T\}$$

is a \mathbb{P}^* -**martingale**.

Consequently $U_0 = U_0^*$ is the *time-0 no-arbitrage price* for the American claim Y , because setting up a self-financing strategy ϕ^* with initial capital U_0 replicates the claim’s payoff under any exercise policy.

Sketch of why (1) holds: By definition we already know

$$U_t^* \geq \mathbb{E}^*[Y_s^* | \mathcal{F}_t], \quad \text{for all } s \geq t.$$

Therefore

$$U_t^* \geq \max_{t \leq s \leq T} \mathbb{E}^*[Y_s^* | \mathcal{F}_t].$$

To see equality and the specific stopping time $\tau^*(t)$ that achieves the maximum, one shows (via standard supermartingale techniques) that whenever $U_s^* > Y_s^*$, one can continue, while if $U_s^* = Y_s^*$ then it is optimal to exercise. So at the first time s (starting from t) such that $U_s^* = Y_s^*$, the maximum of conditional expectations is attained.

For (2): Observe that for $u \geq t$,

$$U_{t \wedge \tau^*(0)}^* = U_t^* \quad \text{on the event } (\tau^*(0) > t),$$

while if $\tau^*(0) \leq t$, the process has stopped. One checks that the optional stopping theorem implies that this stopped process is indeed a martingale (since U_s^* is a supermartingale that behaves like a martingale once the exercise time is hit). This completes the argument that U_0 is the fair (no-arbitrage) price of the American claim and can be replicated with the self-financing strategy ϕ^* constructed above. In summary, the approach parallels European-pricing methods but includes a “maximum” at each step to account for early exercise. The necessary wealth process U_t is built via backward induction, is the smallest supermartingale majorant of Y_t^* , and can be replicated by a self-financing portfolio that injects no external cash beyond what is required to handle early exercise. □

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Explicit super-hedging holdings. Conditioned on \mathcal{F}_t (i.e. once S_t is known), let U_{t+1}^u and U_{t+1}^d denote the two possible values of the seller’s *necessary wealth* at time $t+1$ that correspond to the up- and down-moves of the stock, $S_{t+1} = uS_t$ and $S_{t+1} = dS_t$. The \mathcal{F}_t -measurable positions that replicate the discounted value $\frac{1}{1+r}\mathbb{E}^*[U_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t]$ over the next step are

$$\tilde{\alpha}_{t+1} = \frac{U_{t+1}^u - U_{t+1}^d}{(u-d)S_t}, \quad \tilde{\beta}_{t+1} = \frac{uU_{t+1}^d - dU_{t+1}^u}{(u-d)(1+r)^{t+1}},$$

so that

$$\tilde{\alpha}_{t+1}S_{t+1} + \tilde{\beta}_{t+1}B_{t+1} = U_{t+1}, \quad \tilde{\alpha}_{t+1}S_t + \tilde{\beta}_{t+1}B_t = \frac{1}{1+r}\mathbb{E}^*[U_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t].$$

Any *excess* wealth created when the buyer could exercise but does not is

$$\tilde{\delta}_{t+1} := U_t - \frac{1}{1+r}\mathbb{E}^*[U_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t] \geq 0,$$

and is simply deposited in the bond to maintain self-financing. These formulas make the “backward-induction” construction of the super-hedging strategy completely explicit.

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Theorem 1.

1. For $t = 0, 1, \dots, T$ we have

$$U_t^* = \max_{t \leq \tau \leq T} \mathbb{E}^*[Y_\tau^* | \mathcal{F}_t],$$

and the maximum is attained at the stopping time

$$\tau^*(t) := \min\{s \geq t : U_s^* = Y_s^*\} \wedge T.$$

2. The stopped process $(U_{t \wedge \tau^*(0)}^*)_{t=0}^T$ is a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale.

The context is an American contingent claim in our binomial model, with payoffs Y_t and the “necessary wealth” process U_t^* , recursively defined via the Snell envelope. We will see that U_0^* is the time-0 no-arbitrage price of Y . Part (1) gives a global characterization of U_t^* as the maximum over all stopping times of $\mathbb{E}^*[Y_\tau^* | \mathcal{F}_t]$, while part (2) shows that this maximum is actually attained at the first hitting time when U_s^* meets Y_s^* . The amount U_t^* must always exceed or match Y_t^* so the seller can cover immediate or future payoffs, and the buyer’s optimal exercise time is precisely where these two processes coincide. If they never coincide earlier, we stop at T . Underlying this global picture is the one-step *Snell-envelope recursion*: for $t = 0, 1, \dots, T - 1$,

$$U_t^* = \max\left\{Y_t^*, \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_{t+1}^* | \mathcal{F}_t]\right\},$$

which provides the dynamic-programming rule that ultimately yields Theorem 1

Sketch of proof

We give the argument for the case $t = 0$ (the general case proceeds similarly). We want to show

$$U_0 = U_0^* = \max_{\tau} \mathbb{E}^*[Y_\tau^*].$$

Recall from Lecture 13 that $U_0 = U_0^*$, the time-0 value of the *Snell envelope* of the payoff $\{Y_t^*\}$. The goal is twofold:

$$1) \quad U_0^* \geq \mathbb{E}^*[Y_\tau^*] \quad \text{for all stopping times } \tau, \quad 2) \quad U_0^* = \mathbb{E}^*[Y_{\tau^*(0)}^*],$$

where $\tau^*(0)$ is the first time at which the Snell envelope U_t^* meets Y_t^* .

Focusing on $t = 0$ simplifies the notation, but an identical argument applies for any t . The seller’s perspective is that U_t^* must never fall below Y_t^* , ensuring coverage of all possible future payoffs. The buyer’s perspective is to choose a stopping time τ to maximize $\mathbb{E}^*[Y_\tau^*]$. Because U_t^* is a super-martingale under \mathbb{P}^* , while the wealth process from a self-financing hedge is a true martingale, a stopping-time argument shows that U_0^* meets this maximal expectation exactly at the first time $\tau^*(0)$ with $U_t^* = Y_t^*$.

Super-hedging strategy

From Lecture 13, we constructed a *super-hedging*, self-financing trading strategy φ^* such that

$$V_t^*(\varphi^*) \geq U_t^*, \quad \text{for all } t = 0, 1, \dots, T.$$

Because φ^* is self-financing, the corresponding discounted wealth process

$$(V_t^*(\varphi^*))_{t=0}^T$$

is a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale. In more detail, one first constructs a replicating strategy $(\alpha_t^\sim, \beta_t^\sim)$ whose value equals U_t^* but may fail self-financing whenever the buyer *could* exercise but does not. To fix this, we add a “leftover money” term into the bond holdings. Concretely, define $\varphi_t^* = (\alpha_t^*, \beta_t^*)$ by

$$\alpha_t^* = \alpha_t^\sim, \quad \beta_t^* = \beta_t^\sim + \Delta_t,$$

where $\Delta_t \geq 0$ captures the surplus if the buyer chooses to continue at time t (thus not forcing immediate payout). This correction ensures that φ_t^* is self-financing and also that $V_t^*(\varphi^*) \geq U_t^*$ for all t .

$$\delta_t := U_t^* - Y_t^* - \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_{t+1}^* | \mathcal{F}_t] \geq 0, \quad \beta_t^* = \hat{\beta}_t + \sum_{s=1}^t \frac{\delta_s}{B_{s-1}},$$

so that the self-financing strategy $\varphi_t^* = (\alpha_t^*, \beta_t^*)$ keeps the *discounted* wealth process $V^*(\varphi^*)$ exactly at the Snell envelope until $\tau^*(0)$ and never below it afterwards.

Observe that if $U_t^* > Y_t^*$, then by the Snell envelope recursion we must have

$$U_t^* = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_{t+1}^* | \mathcal{F}_t],$$

so the difference $U_t^* - \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_{t+1}^* | \mathcal{F}_t]$ is zero. That means the “leftover money” Δ_t added to β_t^* also vanishes at such times. Conversely, if $U_t^* = Y_t^*$, then immediate exercise occurs, leaving no surplus. Therefore for all $t < \tau^*(0)$ we have $U_t^* > Y_t^*$ and thus $\Delta_t = 0$, so

$$V_t^*(\varphi^*) = U_t^* \quad \text{for } t < \tau^*(0).$$

After $\tau^*(0)$, any surplus is used to pay the buyer’s payoff if exercise happens. This ensures the process $V_t^*(\varphi^*)$ and U_t^* coincide up to that hitting time and satisfies $V_t^*(\varphi^*) \geq U_t^*$ thereafter.

Stopped martingale identity

To see that $(U_{t \wedge \tau^*(0)}^*)_{t=0}^T$ is also a martingale, note the following:

- By construction of $\tau^*(0)$, we have equality $V_t^*(\varphi^*) = U_t^*$ for all $t \leq \tau^*(0)$. In symbols,

$$V_t^*(\varphi^*) - U_t^* = 0, \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, \tau^*(0).$$

- Since $V_t^*(\varphi^*)$ is a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale, we obtain

$$V_{t \wedge \tau^*(0)}^*(\varphi^*) = U_{t \wedge \tau^*(0)}^* \quad \text{and} \quad (V_{t \wedge \tau^*(0)}^*(\varphi^*))_{t=0}^T \text{ is a martingale.}$$

Therefore the process $(U_{t \wedge \tau^*(0)}^*)_{t=0}^T$ is (being equal to a stopped martingale) also a martingale under \mathbb{P}^* .

Intuitively, U_t^* remains strictly greater than Y_t^* before $\tau^*(0)$, so no exercise occurs, and there is leftover capital carried in the bond. Exactly at $\tau^*(0)$, $U_{\tau^*(0)}^*$ meets $Y_{\tau^*(0)}^*$, so the buyer is indifferent to waiting further. Since $V_t^*(\varphi^*)$ is a true martingale, stopping at $\tau^*(0)$ preserves that property, and $U_{t \wedge \tau^*(0)}^*$ inherits the martingale property by matching $V_{t \wedge \tau^*(0)}^*(\varphi^*)$ up to that time.

Exercise 1. Prove that if (M_t) is a (discrete-time) \mathbb{P} -martingale, then its stopped process $(M_{t \wedge \sigma})$ is again a \mathbb{P} -martingale, provided σ is a bounded stopping time. (Use the definition $\mathbb{E}[M_{s \wedge \sigma} | \mathcal{F}_r] = M_{r \wedge \sigma}$ for $r \leq s$.)

Optimality argument

Let τ be any stopping time satisfying $0 \leq \tau \leq T$. Since

$$U_\tau^* \geq Y_\tau^*$$

by definition of the Snell envelope (U_t^*) , we deduce

$$U_0 = \mathbb{E}^*[U_\tau^*] \geq \mathbb{E}^*[Y_\tau^*].$$

Therefore,

$$U_0 \geq \max_{\tau} \mathbb{E}^*[Y_\tau^*].$$

On the other hand, taking $\tau = \tau^*(0)$ —the time when U_t^* first meets Y_t^* —we use the stopped–martingale property

$$U_0 = \mathbb{E}^*[U_{\tau^*(0)}^*] = \mathbb{E}^*[Y_{\tau^*(0)}^*].$$

So the supremum $\max_{\tau} \mathbb{E}^*[Y_{\tau}^*]$ is actually attained at $\tau = \tau^*(0)$, and so

$$U_0 = \max_{\tau} \mathbb{E}^*[Y_{\tau}^*].$$

This completes the argument.

Convexity. A function $\psi : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is *convex* if

$$\alpha\psi(x) + (1 - \alpha)\psi(y) \geq \psi(\alpha x + (1 - \alpha)y), \quad 0 < \alpha < 1.$$

Concavity is defined by reversing the inequality.

Graphical intuition. The function’s graph always lies *below* any of its chords, for convexity. Visually:

Equivalently, for a convex function, any secant line through two points on the graph lies above the function on the entire interval between those points. If ψ is differentiable, ψ' is nondecreasing, and if ψ is twice differentiable, then $\psi''(x) \geq 0$ precisely characterizes convexity. For concave functions, the inequality reverses and the secant line is below the graph. Classic examples include x^2 (convex) versus \sqrt{x} (concave) for $x > 0$. If ψ is twice differentiable, then

$$\psi''(x) \geq 0 \quad (\text{resp. } \leq 0) \iff \psi \text{ is convex (resp. concave).}$$

Jensen’s inequality

Let Z be a random variable with

$$Z = \begin{cases} x & \text{with probability } \alpha, \\ y & \text{with probability } 1 - \alpha. \end{cases}$$

Then clearly

$$\mathbb{E}(Z) = \alpha x + (1 - \alpha)y, \quad \mathbb{E}[\psi(Z)] = \alpha\psi(x) + (1 - \alpha)\psi(y).$$

Therefore for any convex ψ ,

$$\psi(\mathbb{E}(Z)) = \psi(\alpha x + (1 - \alpha)y) \leq \alpha\psi(x) + (1 - \alpha)\psi(y) = \mathbb{E}[\psi(Z)].$$

(The inequality reverses if ψ is concave.)

More generally, for any integrable r.v. Z and any sub- σ -field \mathcal{G} in the probability space:

$$\text{if } \psi \text{ is convex, then } \mathbb{E}[\psi(Z) \mid \mathcal{G}] \geq \psi(\mathbb{E}[Z \mid \mathcal{G}]).$$

Proof idea. By convexity, there exists an affine function $\ell(x) = mx + b$ *tangent* to ψ at $\mu = \mathbb{E}Z$, such that $\psi(x) \geq \ell(x)$ for all x . Taking expectations gives $\mathbb{E}[\psi(Z)] \geq \mathbb{E}[\ell(Z)] = \ell(\mathbb{E}[Z])$, which is $\psi(\mathbb{E}[Z]) \leq \mathbb{E}[\psi(Z)]$. The conditional version works similarly, replacing $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$ by $\mathbb{E}[\cdot \mid \mathcal{G}]$.

Geometrically, this can be interpreted by viewing $\mathbb{E}(Z)$ as a point between x and y (in the two-value case). The function ψ , being convex, “pulls upward” on averages, so $\psi(\mathbb{E}(Z)) \leq \mathbb{E}[\psi(Z)]$. For a general random variable, one partitions its outcomes into small pieces, applies the same chord argument, and the result follows by linearity of expectation.

Examples

Example 1 (Convex payoff functions). Let $K > 0$. The payoffs $(x - K)^+$ and $(K - x)^+$ are both convex in $x \geq 0$. Indeed,

$$(x - K)^+ = \max\{0, x - K\} \text{ is a piecewise-linear, convex function.}$$

Similarly $(K - x)^+ = \max\{0, K - x\}$ is also piecewise linear and convex in x . Their graphs:

Example 2 (American Call).

Let $Y_t = (S_t - K)^+$ with risk-free rate $r \geq 0$. Recall the dynamic programming relation for the Snell envelope:

$$U_{t-1} = \max\left\{Y_{t-1}, \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}]\right\}.$$

But $U_t \geq Y_t$ always, so we may replace U_t by Y_t inside the risk-neutral expectation to see:

$$U_{t-1} \geq \max\left\{Y_{t-1}, \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[Y_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}]\right\}.$$

By Jensen’s inequality and the fact that $f(x) = (x - K)^+$ is convex in x :

$$\frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[Y_T | \mathcal{F}_{T-1}] \geq \left(\frac{S_{T-1}}{1+r} - K\right)^+ \geq (S_{T-1} - K)^+ = Y_{T-1}.$$

Therefore for $t = T - 1$, we get

$$U_{T-1} = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[Y_T | \mathcal{F}_{T-1}] = V_{T-1},$$

where V_{T-1} is the (European) call option value at $T - 1$. Repeating inductively shows $U_t = V_t$ for all t , proving that there is *no benefit to early exercise* for an American call when $r \geq 0$.

Example 3 (American Put in a binomial model).

Model parameters We consider a one-period up/down model, repeated over $T = 3$ steps, with

$$S_0 = 100, \quad u = 1.1, \quad d = 0.9, \quad r = 0.05, \quad T = 3, \quad p^* = \frac{3}{4}, \quad K = 105.$$

Underlying price tree S_t We illustrate the possible evolutions of S_t in a tree:

Payoff process $Y_t = (K - S_t)^+$ The terminal payoff of a put option with strike $K = 105$ is $\max\{K - S_T, 0\}$. Tracing backward in the tree gives the intermediate payoffs:

Snell envelope U_t (American put price) Using backward induction on

$$U_t = \max\{Y_t, \beta \mathbb{E}^*[U_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t]\}, \quad \beta = \frac{1}{1+r} = \frac{1}{1.05},$$

we obtain the *Snell envelope* values: $U_0 = 5$, $U_1 = (1.4286, 15)$, $U_2 = (0, 6, 24)$, $U_3 = Y_3$.

One sees that early exercise at certain nodes (e.g. price node 90 at time 1) is optimal, since $Y_1 = 15$ there, whereas the continuation value $\beta \mathbb{E}^*[U_2 | \mathcal{F}_1]$

European put value V_t For comparison, we compute the purely *European* put price V_t via the risk-neutral recursion

$$V_t = \beta \mathbb{E}^*[V_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t], \quad V_3 = Y_3.$$

This yields: $V_0 = 2.365$, $V_1 = (0.901, 7.228)$, $V_2 = (0, 3.786, 19)$, $V_3 = Y_3$.

Note that $V_0 = 2.365 < U_0 = 5$ reflects the strictly higher value of an American put (due to possible early exercise). Next lecture, we will verify that U_0 is indeed the no-arbitrage price of the American claim based on $\{Y_0, Y_1, \dots, Y_T\}$ by constructing an *exact* hedging strategy and confirming there is no arbitrage at U_0 .

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Lemma (Discounted wealth is mean-preserving). For *any* self-financing trading strategy $\phi = (\alpha_t, \beta_t)_{t=1}^T$ with discounted value $V_t^*(\phi) = \frac{V_t(\phi)}{(1+r)^t}$, and for any stopping time $\tau \in \mathcal{T}[0, T]$,

$$\mathbb{E}^*[V_\tau^*(\phi)] = V_0^*(\phi).$$

Proof. By Lemma 2.2.3 (proved earlier) the discounted wealth process $\{V_t^*(\phi)\}_{t=0}^T$ is a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale. Doob's optional-stopping theorem therefore yields $\mathbb{E}^*[V_\tau^*(\phi) | \mathcal{F}_0] = V_0^*(\phi)$ for every bounded stopping time τ , and \mathcal{F}_0 is trivial.

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LECTURE 15
 § 2.3

Convexity, Concavity and Expectations

A function φ is *convex* provided

$$\alpha \varphi(x) + (1 - \alpha) \varphi(y) \geq \varphi(\alpha x + (1 - \alpha) y), \quad \forall x, y \in \mathbb{R} \text{ and } 0 < \alpha < 1. \quad (1)$$

A function φ is *concave* if the inequality in (1) is reversed, i.e.,

$$\alpha \varphi(x) + (1 - \alpha) \varphi(y) \leq \varphi(\alpha x + (1 - \alpha) y).$$

Figure 1: Convex (left) and concave (right) functions: the secant lies above/below the graph, respectively.

Differential characterisation. If φ is sufficiently smooth (i.e., twice differentiable), then the following equivalences hold:

$$\varphi \text{ is convex} \iff \varphi' \text{ is increasing} \iff \varphi''(x) \geq 0 \text{ for all } x,$$

$$\varphi \text{ is concave} \iff \varphi' \text{ is decreasing} \iff \varphi''(x) \leq 0 \text{ for all } x.$$

Note also that the negative of a convex function is concave (and vice versa). For instance, $x \mapsto \sqrt{x}$ on $x > 0$ is concave, implying $\mathbb{E}[\sqrt{Z}] \leq \sqrt{\mathbb{E}[Z]}$ for a nonnegative Z .

Let Z be a random variable taking only two values x and y :

$$Z = \begin{cases} x, & \text{with probability } \alpha, \\ y, & \text{with probability } 1 - \alpha. \end{cases}$$

Then

$$\mathbb{E}[Z] = \alpha x + (1 - \alpha)y, \quad \mathbb{E}[\varphi(Z)] = \alpha \varphi(x) + (1 - \alpha) \varphi(y).$$

Therefore,

$$\mathbb{E}[\varphi(Z)] = \alpha \varphi(x) + (1 - \alpha) \varphi(y) \xrightarrow[\text{convexity of } \varphi]{\geq} \varphi(\alpha x + (1 - \alpha)y) = \varphi(\mathbb{E}[Z]).$$

When φ is *concave*, the reverse inequality holds:

$$\mathbb{E}[\varphi(Z)] \leq \varphi(\mathbb{E}[Z]).$$

Jensen's inequality. The simple two-point argument above extends to all integrable random variables by approximating an arbitrary random variable with a finite (or countable) mixture, or via measure-theoretic arguments. In particular,

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi \text{ convex} &\implies \mathbb{E}[\varphi(Z)] \geq \varphi(\mathbb{E}[Z]), \\ \varphi \text{ concave} &\implies \mathbb{E}[\varphi(Z)] \leq \varphi(\mathbb{E}[Z]).\end{aligned}$$

Moreover, the *conditional* version also holds for any sub- σ -algebra \mathcal{G} :

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi \text{ convex} &\implies \mathbb{E}[\varphi(Z) \mid \mathcal{G}] \geq \varphi(\mathbb{E}[Z \mid \mathcal{G}]), \\ \varphi \text{ concave} &\implies \mathbb{E}[\varphi(Z) \mid \mathcal{G}] \leq \varphi(\mathbb{E}[Z \mid \mathcal{G}]).\end{aligned}$$

This statement is the celebrated *Jensen's inequality*.

Sketch of a common proof (supporting line). If φ is convex and differentiable, then for any point μ we can use the line

$$y = mx + b,$$

where $m = \varphi'(\mu)$ and $b = \varphi(\mu) - \mu \varphi'(\mu)$, which is the *tangent line* to φ at μ . By convexity, $\varphi(x) \geq mx + b$ for all x . Taking $\mu = \mathbb{E}[Z]$ and then expectations:

$$\mathbb{E}[\varphi(Z)] \geq \mathbb{E}[mZ + b] = m\mathbb{E}[Z] + b = m\mu + b = \varphi(\mu).$$

Figure 2: Convex (left) and concave (right) functions with their tangents: for convex functions the tangent lies below the graph, while for concave functions it lies above.

Even if φ is not differentiable at some point (for example, $\varphi(x) = |x|$ at $x = 0$), one can still choose a supporting line with a slope taken from the subderivative set. This is consistent with the tangent-line argument because convexity requires that $\varphi(x)$ lie on or above each such line everywhere.

Applications to Option Payoffs

Convexity of $(x - K)^+$ and $(K - x)^+$

For a fixed strike $K > 0$, the functions

$$\varphi_1(x) = (x - K)^+ \quad \text{and} \quad \varphi_2(x) = (K - x)^+$$

are both convex for $x \geq 0$.

Figure 3: Pay-off functions for a call $(x - K)^+$ (left) and put $(K - x)^+$ (right).

American Call: No Early Exercise when $r \geq 0$

A key intuition is that an American call gives the holder the option to “buy” the stock by paying the strike. If $r \geq 0$, it is generally disadvantageous to spend one’s money early because any cash on hand can earn nonnegative interest until the final maturity. So waiting provides at least as much value. Mathematically, one shows that the super-replication cost of the American call coincides with that of a European call, implying no early-exercise premium. For comparison, the put payoff $(K - x)^+$ is also convex but is a **decreasing** function of x . Therefore the same recursive argument that factors out $(1+r)$ from $(x - K)k$ fails for $(K - x)k$. As a consequence, there can be an early-exercise premium for an American put if $r > 0$. However, if $r = 0$, one can show no advantage to early exercise even for the put.

Proof (Using Jensen’s inequality). Recall that the Snell envelope for the discounted payoff satisfies

$$U_T = Y_T, \quad U_{t-1} = \max\left\{Y_{t-1}, \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_t \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}]\right\}, \quad t = 1, \dots, T.$$

Step 1 (time $T - 1$). For the American call we have $Y_t = (S_t - K)^+$. Because the map $x \mapsto (x - K)^+$ is convex and *increasing*, Jensen’s inequality gives

$$\frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[(S_T - K)^+ \mid \mathcal{F}_{T-1}] \geq \frac{1}{1+r} \left(\mathbb{E}^*[S_T \mid \mathcal{F}_{T-1}] - K\right)^+.$$

Under the risk-neutral measure, $\mathbb{E}^*[S_T \mid \mathcal{F}_{T-1}] = (1+r)S_{T-1}$, whence

$$\frac{1}{1+r} \left((1+r)S_{T-1} - K\right)^+ = (S_{T-1} - K)^+ = Y_{T-1}.$$

So the maximisation in the Snell envelope chooses the second term and

$$U_{T-1} = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[(S_T - K)^+ \mid \mathcal{F}_{T-1}] =: V_{T-1},$$

where V_t is the usual European call price process.

Step 2 (induction). Assume $U_t = V_t$ for some $1 \leq t \leq T - 1$. Using the martingale property of V we get

$$\frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_t \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[V_t \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = V_{t-1}.$$

As above, Jensen’s inequality ensures this quantity dominates Y_{t-1} , so the “max” again picks the continuation value: $U_{t-1} = V_{t-1}$.

Conclusion. By backward induction $U_t = V_t$ for all $t = 0, 1, \dots, T$; in particular $U_0 = V_0$. Therefore the American call is *never* optimally exercised before expiry when $r \geq 0$. \square

Example 1: A 3-Step American Put

Parameters:

$$S_0 = 100, \quad u = 1.1, \quad d = 0.9, \quad r = 0.05, \quad T = 3, \quad q^* = \frac{3}{4}, \quad K = 105.$$

Figure 4: Stock-price tree S_t for the 3-step model.

Figure 7: American value process U_t .

It is evident that $U_t \geq V_t$ at every node, underscoring the early-exercise premium of an American put.

No-Arbitrage Pricing of an American Contingent Claim (ACC)

Consider an American contingent claim (ACC) with payoff process $Y = (Y_0, \dots, Y_T)$ and define the process $U = (U_0, \dots, U_T)$, where U_t is the least super-replicating wealth at time t . Let C_0 denote the market price of the claim at time 0.

Arbitrage opportunities (page 17–19)

Seller's arbitrage: A trading strategy ϕ^s with initial wealth $V_0(\phi^s) = C_0$ such that

$$V_t(\phi^s) \geq Y_t \quad \text{for all stopping times } \tau,$$

and

$$\mathbb{E}^*[V_\tau(\phi^s) - Y_\tau] > 0.$$

Intuitively, the seller (short position) sells the ACC at price C_0 , replicates (or super-replicates) it at lower cost, and pockets a positive expected profit with no risk of loss.

Buyer's arbitrage: A strategy ϕ^b with initial wealth $V_0(\phi^b) = -C_0$ (i.e. the buyer pays C_0 to obtain the claim) for which there is a stopping time τ satisfying

$$V_\tau(\phi^b) + Y_\tau \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbb{E}^*[V_\tau(\phi^b) + Y_\tau] > 0.$$

Here, the buyer's position plus the contingent claim payoff results in a positive expected profit without risk.

Either type of arbitrage is a violation of the no-arbitrage principle. *Note that the seller must ensure super-replication for every stopping time the buyer might choose, whereas the buyer can produce an arbitrage by finding some stopping time τ that yields a strictly positive outcome in expectation. This asymmetry is what distinguishes 'seller's arbitrage' from buyer's arbitrage.*

Theorem 1 (No-arbitrage valuation of an ACC). *Let $Y = (Y_0, \dots, Y_T)$ be an American contingent claim and let*

$$U_t := \inf\{V_t(\phi) \mid V_s(\phi) \geq Y_s \text{ for every } s \geq t\}, \quad t = 0, \dots, T,$$

denote the least-cost super-replication process. Then U_0 is the unique no-arbitrage price of the claim.

Proof. We distinguish the three mutually-exclusive cases

$$C_0 > U_0, \quad C_0 < U_0, \quad C_0 = U_0.$$

(i) Seller's arbitrage when $C_0 > U_0$

Let $\phi^* = (\alpha^*, \beta^*)$ be the minimal super-hedge with $V_0(\phi^*) = U_0$ and $V_t(\phi^*) \geq Y_t$ for every t .

Augment the bond holding. Define the strategy ϕ^s by

$$\alpha_t^s := \alpha_t^*, \quad \beta_t^s := \beta_t^* + (C_0 - U_0)B_t, \quad 1 \leq t \leq T.$$

1. *Initial wealth.* $V_0(\phi^s) = U_0 + (C_0 - U_0) = C_0$.

2. *Dominance.* For every t ,

$$V_t(\phi^s) = V_t(\phi^*) + (C_0 - U_0)B_t \geq Y_t.$$

3. *Strict profit at any exercise time τ .*

$$V_\tau(\phi^s) - Y_\tau \geq (C_0 - U_0)B_\tau > 0,$$

hence $\mathbb{E}^*[V_\tau(\phi^s) - Y_\tau] > 0$.

The seller therefore enjoys a non-negative payoff *path-wise* and a strictly positive \mathbb{P}^* -expectation, constituting a seller's arbitrage.

(ii) **Buyer's arbitrage when $C_0 < U_0$**

Short the super-hedge and invest the surplus. Set

$$\phi^b := (-\alpha_t^*, -\beta_t^*)_{t=1}^T, \quad V_0(\phi^b) = -U_0.$$

Deposit the surplus $U_0 - C_0 > 0$ in the bond at $t = 0$ so the *net* initial wealth is $-C_0$ (the purchase price).

Let

$$\tau^* := \min\{t \geq 0 : U_t = Y_t\},$$

so $\tau^*(dd) = 1$ and $\tau^*(ud) = \tau^*(du) = 2$ (page 32).

$$\begin{aligned} V_{\tau^*}(\phi^b) + Y_{\tau^*} &= -V_{\tau^*}(\phi^*) + (U_0 - C_0)B_{\tau^*} + Y_{\tau^*} \\ &\geq -(U_{\tau^*} - Y_{\tau^*}) + (U_0 - C_0)B_{\tau^*} \\ &= (U_0 - C_0)B_{\tau^*} > 0 \quad \text{a.s.} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\mathbb{E}^*[V_{\tau^*}(\phi^b) + Y_{\tau^*}] > 0$ and a buyer's arbitrage exists.

(iii) **No arbitrage when $C_0 = U_0$**

No seller's arbitrage. Assume a seller's arbitrage ϕ existed with $V_0(\phi) = C_0$ and $V_t(\phi) \geq Y_t$ for all t . Discounted wealth $V_t^*(\phi) = V_t(\phi)/B_t$ is a \mathbb{P}^* -super-martingale, so

$$\mathbb{E}^*[V_T^*(\phi)] = V_0^*(\phi) = C_0.$$

Since $V_T^*(\phi) \geq Y_T^* = U_T^*$ and $\mathbb{E}^*[U_T^*] = C_0$ (martingale property of U^*), both random variables share the same expectation and satisfy $V_T^*(\phi) \geq U_T^*$. Therefore they must coincide a.s., contradicting the strict inequality required in the definition of seller's arbitrage.

No buyer's arbitrage. Suppose there were ϕ^b and a stopping time τ with $V_0(\phi^b) = -C_0$ and $V_\tau(\phi^b) + Y_\tau \geq 0$ a.s. Discounting and taking conditional expectations,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}^*[V_\tau^*(\phi^b) + Y_\tau^*] &= \underbrace{\mathbb{E}^*[V_\tau^*(\phi^b)]}_{=V_0^*(\phi^b)=-C_0} + \underbrace{\mathbb{E}^*[Y_\tau^*]}_{=\mathbb{E}^*[U_\tau^*]=U_0=C_0} \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

But $V_\tau^*(\phi^b) + Y_\tau^* \geq 0$ a.s. with zero expectation implies it is identically zero, contradicting the requirement that $\mathbb{P}^*(V_\tau(\phi^b) + Y_\tau > 0) > 0$. Therefore no buyer's arbitrage exists.

Uniqueness. Any price $C_0 \neq U_0$ falls into case (i) or (ii); only $C_0 = U_0$ avoids arbitrage. \square

Example 2: Two-Step American Put (revisited)

Parameters:

$$T = 2, S_0 = 4, u = 2, d = \frac{1}{2}, r = \frac{1}{4}, K = 5, q^* = \frac{1}{2}.$$

Figure 8: Stock-price tree S_t for the 2-step example.

Figure 12: European put price process V_t for the 2-step model.

From the tree one reads off $U_0 = \frac{34}{25} = 1.36$, confirming the no-arbitrage price.

Optimal stopping time τ^* and explicit super-hedge

Define the optimal exercise time

$$\tau^* := \min\{t \geq 0 : U_t = Y_t\}$$

so that

$$\tau^*(dd) = 1, \quad \tau^*(ud) = \tau^*(du) = 2.$$

Super-hedging strategy. Construct the following $(\alpha^*, \beta^*, \xi^*)$:

time	α^*	β^*	ξ^*
1	$-\frac{13}{30}$	$\frac{232}{75}$	0
2 (after d)	-1	4	1
2 (after u)	$-\frac{1}{12}$	$\frac{64}{75}$	0

With these holdings the wealth process $V_t(\phi^*)$ dominates Y_t at every node and satisfies $V_0(\phi^*) = U_0$.

Figure 13: Wealth process $V_t(\phi^*)$ along each path.

Figure 14: Discounted wealth $V_t^*(\phi^*)$ (a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale).

Node	t	S_t	$Y_t = (K - S_t)^+$	$C_t = \beta \mathbb{E}^*[U_{t+1} \mathcal{F}_t]$	$U_t = \max\{Y_t, C_t\}$	$U_t^* = U_t / (1+r)^t$	τ^*
\emptyset	0	4	1	$0.8(0.5 \cdot 0.40 + 0.5 \cdot 3) = 1.36$	1.36	1.36	–
d	1	2	3	$0.8(0.5 \cdot 2 + 0.5 \cdot 5) = 2.80$	3	$3/1.25 = 2.40$	1
u	1	8	0	$0.8(0.5 \cdot 1 + 0.5 \cdot 0) = \mathbf{0.40}$	0.40	$0.40/1.25 = 0.32$	2
dd	2	1	5	–	5	$5/1.25^2 = 2.56$	1
du	2	4	1	–	2	$2/1.25^2 = 0.64$	1
ud	2	4	1	–	1	$1/1.25^2 = 0.64$	2
uu	2	16	0	–	0	0	2

Table 1: Backward-induction details for the *two-step American put* with parameters $T = 2$, $S_0 = 4$, $u = 2$, $d = \frac{1}{2}$, $r = \frac{1}{4}$ ($\beta = \frac{1}{1+r} = 0.8$), risk-neutral probability $p^* = 0.5$, and strike $K = 5$. Each row shows the stock price S_t , intrinsic value Y_t , continuation value C_t , Snell envelope U_t , discounted wealth U_t^* and the optimal stopping time τ^* at that node. A dash indicates the quantity is not defined at maturity ($t = 2$). **Boldface** marks the entry that wins the max test and is therefore chosen for U_t (exercise now if Y_t wins, continue otherwise).

Summary

This lecture developed Jensen's inequality from first principles, applied it to option pay-off convexity, demonstrated the absence of early exercise for an American call with $r \geq 0$, worked through 3-step and 2-step American put examples, and established that the dynamic super-replication cost U_0 is the unique no-arbitrage price of an American contingent claim.

Supplemental Notes

Remark (post-exercise investing). Once the buyer actually exercises, any *surplus* wealth in the hedging portfolio is deposited in the bond until the common horizon T . This convention pushes every cash-flow to the same comparison date, so discounted wealth processes and Snell-envelope inequalities can be written without extra case distinctions. Choosing $r = 0$ after exercise gives the same arbitrage conditions but slightly messier formulas.

Node-wise optimal stopping. For each starting time t define

$$\tau^*(t) := \min\{v \geq t : U_v = Y_v\} \wedge T, \quad \text{so that } \tau^*(0) = \tau^*.$$

Then

$$U_t = \mathbb{E}^*[Y_{\tau^*(t)} | \mathcal{F}_t] = \max_{\tau \in \mathcal{T}[t, T]} \mathbb{E}^*[Y_\tau | \mathcal{F}_t], \quad t = 0, \dots, T,$$

and the stopped process $\{U_{t \wedge \tau^*}^*\}$ is a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale. (See Lemma 2.3.1–2.3.2 in the text.)

Algorithm 2.3.3 — backward super-hedge construction.

– Initialise $U_T := Y_T$.

– For $t = T - 1, \dots, 0$ do

(a) $C_t := \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t]$.

(b) $U_t := \max\{Y_t, C_t\}$.

(c) With U_{t+1}^u, U_{t+1}^d the two successor values, set

$$\tilde{\alpha}_{t+1} = \frac{U_{t+1}^u - U_{t+1}^d}{(u-d)S_t}, \quad \tilde{\beta}_{t+1} = \frac{uU_{t+1}^d - dU_{t+1}^u}{(u-d)(1+r)^{t+1}}.$$

(d) Surplus $\tilde{\delta}_{t+1} := U_t - C_t \geq 0$ is placed in the bond.

– Output a self-financing strategy $\alpha_{t+1}^* := \tilde{\alpha}_{t+1}$, $\beta_{t+1}^* := \tilde{\beta}_{t+1} + \sum_{s=1}^{t+1} \tilde{\delta}_s / B_{s-1}$, which exactly replicates U_t for every path.

ACC vs. European claim — one-screen recap.

- *Exercise right:* European \Rightarrow fixed date T ; American \Rightarrow any stopping time $\tau \in \mathcal{T}[0, T]$.
- *Pricing object:* European price V_0 is the unique replication cost; American price U_0 is the *least* super-replication cost.
- *Tool kit:* European uses risk-neutral expectation; American uses the Snell envelope and optimal-stopping theory.
- *Premium:* Always $U_0 \geq V_0$, with equality for calls when $r \geq 0$ (no early-exercise value).

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LECTURE 16
 § 2.3, 3.1

This lectures completes our discussion of American contingent claims in the binomial framework. We emphasize that the sequence $\{U_t\}$, also called the Snell envelope, can be viewed as the *necessary wealth process* for a seller to meet all possible future obligations under the early-exercise feature. Unlike the European case, we may not have a perfect replicating strategy, but we do possess a super-hedging strategy that stays above both U_t and the payoff Y_t .

Section 2.3 — American Contingent Claims (ACC)

Theorem 1. *Let $Y = (Y_0, Y_1, \dots, Y_T)$ be the payoff process of an American contingent claim. Define its Snell envelope $\{U_t\}$ by*

$$U_t = \sup_{\tau \geq t} \mathbb{E}^* [Y_\tau^* | \mathcal{F}_t],$$

where \mathbb{E}^* is an equivalent martingale measure and $Y_t^* = \frac{Y_t}{B_t}$ is the discounted payoff (with B_t the bond). Then the quantity U_0 is the no-arbitrage price of this American contingent claim.

Proof. The overall argument follows a three-case analysis, parallel to the European setting but adapted to the early-exercise feature. First note that by definition, U_t serves as the smallest amount of wealth needed at time t to super-hedge the claim through any possible future exercise time. Also, there is a self-financing super-hedging strategy φ^* with $V_t(\varphi^*) \geq U_t \geq Y_t$ for all t , and a special stopping time

$$\tau^* = \min\{t \geq 0 : U_t = Y_t\},$$

which marks the first time the necessary wealth meets the payoff. We write C_0 for a candidate market price and distinguish three cases, showing that $C_0 > U_0$ leads to a seller's arbitrage, $C_0 < U_0$ leads to a buyer's arbitrage, and $C_0 = U_0$ admits no arbitrage.

(a) Case $C_0 > U_0$ (Seller's arbitrage). By definition of the Snell envelope, there exists a *super-hedging strategy*

$$\varphi^* = \{(\alpha_t^*, \beta_t^*) : t = 1, \dots, T\}$$

such that its value process $V_t(\varphi^*)$ satisfies

$$V_0(\varphi^*) = U_0, \quad V_t(\varphi^*) \geq U_t \geq Y_t, \quad \forall t.$$

(Here $U_t \geq Y_t$ by the supermartingale property of the Snell envelope.) Now define a modified strategy φ^s by

$$\varphi_t^s := \left(\alpha_t^*, \beta_t^* + (C_0 - U_0) B_t \right), \quad 1 \leq t \leq T.$$

Observe that at $t = 0$:

$$V_0(\varphi^s) = \varphi_1^s \cdot S_0 = \alpha_1^* S_0 + [\beta_1^* + (C_0 - U_0) B_0] = V_0(\varphi^*) + (C_0 - U_0) = U_0 + (C_0 - U_0) = C_0.$$

Here we used $B_0 = 1$ and $V_0(\varphi^*) = U_0$. For $1 \leq t \leq T$,

$$V_t(\varphi^s) = V_t(\varphi^*) + (C_0 - U_0) B_t.$$

Since $V_t(\varphi^*) \geq U_t \geq Y_t$ for all t , we get

$$V_t(\varphi^s) \geq U_t + (C_0 - U_0) B_t \geq Y_t + (C_0 - U_0) B_t > 0,$$

because $B_t > 0$ for all t and $C_0 > U_0$ by hypothesis. Therefore $\{V_t(\varphi^s)\}$ is strictly positive at all times. The arbitrage to the seller is evident: the seller collects C_0 initially (since $V_0(\varphi^s) = C_0$) and follows φ^s , thus incurring no risk while locking in positive wealth at each date. Observe that for a *seller's* arbitrage, we must

ensure $V_t(\varphi^s) \geq Y_t$ at *every* possible exercise time. The super-hedging strategy guarantees this for all t , and adding $(C_0 - U_0)$ to the bond keeps the portfolio strictly above zero.

(b) Case $C_0 < U_0$ (Buyer's arbitrage). Consider the super-hedging strategy φ^* from above. Define

$$\varphi^b := \left\{ -U_0 \text{ units of } \varphi^*, \quad (U_0 - C_0) \text{ in the bond} \right\}.$$

More explicitly, at each time t we are taking $-U_0$ times the position φ_t^* in the stock plus holding $(U_0 - C_0)$ units of the bond. Let

$$\tau^* := \min\{t \geq 0 : U_t = Y_t\}.$$

(Since U_t is the Snell envelope, the first time it meets Y_t is an optimal exercise time.) By definition at τ^* we have $U_{\tau^*} = Y_{\tau^*}$. Compute the value of φ^b at τ^* :

$$V_{\tau^*}(\varphi^b) = -U_0 \cdot V_{\tau^*}(\varphi^*) + (U_0 - C_0) B_{\tau^*}.$$

Since $V_{\tau^*}(\varphi^*) \geq U_{\tau^*} = Y_{\tau^*}$, we get

$$V_{\tau^*}(\varphi^b) + Y_{\tau^*} = -U_0 V_{\tau^*}(\varphi^*) + (U_0 - C_0) B_{\tau^*} + Y_{\tau^*}.$$

But at τ^* we also have $V_{\tau^*}(\varphi^*) \geq U_{\tau^*} = Y_{\tau^*}$, hence

$$V_{\tau^*}(\varphi^b) + Y_{\tau^*} \geq -U_0 Y_{\tau^*} + (U_0 - C_0) B_{\tau^*} + Y_{\tau^*}.$$

Rewriting,

$$V_{\tau^*}(\varphi^b) + Y_{\tau^*} \geq Y_{\tau^*} (1 - U_0) + (U_0 - C_0) B_{\tau^*}.$$

Since $Y_{\tau^*} \geq 0$ and $U_0 - C_0 > 0$, the bond price $B_{\tau^*} > 0$, it follows that

$$(U_0 - C_0) B_{\tau^*} > 0,$$

so

$$V_{\tau^*}(\varphi^b) + Y_{\tau^*} > 0.$$

Meanwhile, at $t = 0$,

$$V_0(\varphi^b) = -U_0 V_0(\varphi^*) + (U_0 - C_0) B_0 = -U_0 U_0 + (U_0 - C_0) = -C_0 < 0.$$

So the buyer pays C_0 initially but receives strictly more than $-V_{\tau^*}(\varphi^b)$ plus Y_{τ^*} by time τ^* . In particular, the net investment is negative at $t = 0$ (cash outflow of $-V_0(\varphi^b) = C_0$) and with strictly positive probability the terminal payoff is strictly positive. This is a buyer's arbitrage.

Note the asymmetry: the buyer only needs *one* stopping time—specifically τ^* —to secure a strictly positive net payoff with positive probability, whereas the seller's strategy must cover *all* potential exercise times.

(c) Case $C_0 = U_0$ (No arbitrage). Suppose, by way of contradiction, that there is a *seller's arbitrage* φ^s with

$$V_0(\varphi^s) = C_0 \quad \text{and} \quad V_t(\varphi^s) \geq Y_t \quad \forall t.$$

Recall that $C_0 = U_0$. Denote by $V_t^*(\varphi^s) = \frac{V_t(\varphi^s)}{B_t}$ the discounted value of this portfolio. Then

$$V_0^*(\varphi^s) = \frac{V_0(\varphi^s)}{B_0} = \frac{C_0}{1} = C_0,$$

and for each t ,

$$V_t^*(\varphi^s) \geq \frac{Y_t}{B_t} = Y_t^*.$$

Taking expectation under the equivalent martingale measure \mathbb{P}^* and letting $\tau^* = \min\{t : U_t = Y_t\}$, we have

$$\mathbb{E}^*[V_{\tau^*}^*(\varphi^s)] = \mathbb{E}^*[V_0^*(\varphi^s)] = C_0 = \mathbb{E}^*[Y_{\tau^*}^*].$$

But $V_{\tau^*}^*(\varphi^s) \geq Y_{\tau^*}^*$ almost surely, and their expectations are equal. Therefore $V_{\tau^*}^*(\varphi^s)$ and $Y_{\tau^*}^*$ must be *equal almost surely*. In other words, whenever a nonnegative random variable X satisfies $\mathbb{E}^*[X] = 0$, it must be $X = 0$ almost surely. Applied here, the difference $V_{\tau^*}^*(\varphi^s) - Y_{\tau^*}^*$ has zero expectation and is nonnegative, so the two must coincide with probability one.

This contradicts the strict inequality $V_{\tau^*}^*(\varphi^s) \geq Y_{\tau^*}^*$ for a genuine arbitrage (which requires $V_{\tau^*}^*(\varphi^s) > Y_{\tau^*}^*$ on some set of positive \mathbb{P}^* -probability). A parallel argument handles a buyer's arbitrage: there one tries to find a single stopping time with strictly positive net payoff, and to rule it out when $C_0 = U_0$, one shows that for *every* stopping time, the difference between the portfolio value and payoff must remain zero a.s. if it is nonnegative. Combining all three cases shows that U_0 must be the unique no-arbitrage price of the American claim. \square

Example 1 (American put, revisited). We revisit the American put option with the following parameters:

- Maturity $T = 2$.
- Initial stock price $S_0 = 4$.
- Up-factor $u = 2$ and down-factor $d = \frac{1}{2}$.
- Risk-free rate $r = \frac{1}{4}$ (hence $B_t = (1 + r)^t = 1.25^t$).
- Strike $K = 5$.
- The *risk-neutral* probability is $p^* = \frac{1}{2}$.

Stock price tree (S_t):

At $t = 0$, $S_0 = 4$. At $t = 1$, the stock price is either $S_1 = 8$ (up) or $S_1 = 2$ (down). At $t = 2$, from 8 it can go to 16 (up) or 4 (down), while from 2 it can go to 4 (up) or 1 (down).

Early-exercise payoff $Y_t = \max(K - S_t, 0)$:

Here,

$$Y_0 = \max(5 - 4, 0) = 1, \quad Y_1(u) = \max(5 - 8, 0) = 0, \quad Y_1(d) = \max(5 - 2, 0) = 3,$$

and at time 2, for paths “uu”, “ud”, “du”, “dd”, we get

$$Y_2(uu) = \max(5 - 16, 0) = 0, \quad Y_2(ud) = \max(5 - 4, 0) = 1,$$

$$Y_2(du) = \max(5 - 4, 0) = 1, \quad Y_2(dd) = \max(5 - 1, 0) = 4.$$

Snell envelope U_t : We compute U_t by backward induction:

$$U_T = Y_T, \quad U_{T-1} = \max\{Y_{T-1}, \mathbb{E}^*[U_T^* | \mathcal{F}_{T-1}] \times B_{T-1}\}, \dots$$

Carrying out the usual steps:

$$U_2(\omega) = Y_2(\omega), \quad \text{for each } \omega.$$

Next, at $t = 1$, we compare immediate exercise $Y_1(\omega)$ with the discounted expectation of U_2 .

- At the *down* node d , immediate exercise payoff is $Y_1(d) = 3$.
- The discounted expected payoff if we wait is

$$\mathbb{E}^*[U_2^* | d] \times B_1 = \left[\frac{1}{2}U_2^*(du) + \frac{1}{2}U_2^*(dd)\right] \times 1.25.$$

Since $U_2(du) = 1$ and $U_2(dd) = 4$, we have

$$U_2^*(du) = \frac{1}{B_2} = \frac{1}{1.25^2} = \frac{1}{1.5625}, \quad U_2^*(dd) = \frac{4}{1.5625} = \frac{4}{1.5625}.$$

Numerically,

$$\mathbb{E}^*[U_2^* | d] = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{1.5625} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{4}{1.5625} \right) = \frac{1+4}{2 \times 1.5625} = \frac{5}{3.125} = \frac{5}{3.125}.$$

Multiply by $B_1 = 1.25$ to get

$$1.25 \times \frac{5}{3.125} = 1.25 \times \frac{5}{3.125} = \frac{1.25 \times 5}{3.125} = \frac{6.25}{3.125} = 2.$$

Compare with $Y_1(d) = 3$. We see $3 > 2$, so

$$U_1(d) = 3.$$

- At the *up* node u , $Y_1(u) = 0$, so we compare 0 with the discounted expected U_2 :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}^*[U_2^* | u] \times B_1 &= \frac{1}{2} [U_2^*(ud) + U_2^*(uu)] \times 1.25 \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{1.5625} + \frac{0}{1.5625} \right) \times 1.25 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{1.5625} \right) \times 1.25 = \frac{1}{1.5625} \times 0.625 = 0.4. \end{aligned}$$

So

$$U_1(u) = \max\{0, 0.4\} = 0.4.$$

Finally, at $t = 0$, compare $Y_0 = 1$ to $\mathbb{E}^*[U_1^*] \times B_0$, where

$$U_1(u) = 0.4, \quad U_1(d) = 3; \quad U_1^*(u) = \frac{0.4}{1.25}, \quad U_1^*(d) = \frac{3}{1.25} = 2.4.$$

Therefore

$$\mathbb{E}^*[U_1^*] = \frac{1}{2} (0.32) + \frac{1}{2} (2.4) = 0.16 + 1.2 = 1.36.$$

And $B_0 = 1$, so

$$\max\{Y_0, \mathbb{E}^*[U_1^*] B_0\} = \max\{1, 1.36\} = 1.36.$$

So

$$U_0 = \frac{34}{25} = 1.36.$$

We list the final Snell envelope tree (un-discounted):

Discounted Snell envelope $U_t^* = \frac{U_t}{B_t}$:

(Note: each node is U_t/B_t . For instance, $\frac{3}{1.25} = \frac{60}{25}$ at the left child of the root, etc.)

European value process (V_t): If this were a *European* put maturing at $T = 2$, its value under risk-neutral pricing would be the discounted expectation of its time-2 payoff only. By backward induction, one computes

$$V_0 = \frac{24}{25}, \quad V_1(d) = 3, \quad V_1(u) = 0.4,$$

and so on, yielding the tree:

We see that $U_0 = \frac{34}{25}$ is larger than $V_0 = \frac{24}{25}$, consistent with the well-known fact that an American put can be more valuable than its European counterpart (due to potential early exercise).

Optimal stopping time: From the Snell envelope we identify

$$\tau^* = \min\{t : U_t = Y_t\} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the price path is } dd \text{ or } du \text{ at } t = 1, \\ 2, & \text{if the price path is } ud \text{ or } uu. \end{cases}$$

So one should exercise at time 1 if the stock has gone down from 4 to 2, otherwise wait until time 2.

Super-hedging strategy at $t = 0$: We can construct a super-hedge for the claim by matching the Snell envelope at each node. At $t = 0$, set

$$\alpha_0^* = -\frac{U_1(u) - U_1(d)}{S_1(u) - S_1(d)} = -\frac{0.4 - 3}{8 - 2} = -\frac{-2.6}{6} = -\frac{13}{30}.$$

We then solve for β_0^* using the condition

$$V_0(\varphi^*) = \alpha_0^* S_0 + \beta_0^* B_0 = U_0 = \frac{34}{25}.$$

Since $S_0 = 4$ and $B_0 = 1$, we get

$$\beta_0^* = U_0 - \alpha_0^* \cdot S_0 = \frac{34}{25} - \left(-\frac{13}{30}\right) \times 4 = \frac{34}{25} + \frac{52}{30} = \frac{34}{25} + \frac{26}{15}.$$

To simplify,

$$\frac{26}{15} = \frac{26 \times 5}{15 \times 5} = \frac{130}{75}, \quad \frac{34}{25} = \frac{34 \times 3}{25 \times 3} = \frac{102}{75}.$$

Therefore

$$\beta_0^* = \frac{102}{75} + \frac{130}{75} = \frac{232}{75}.$$

Similarly, we determine (α_1^*, β_1^*) at the d and u nodes by matching $U_1(d)$ or $U_1(u)$ respectively and ensuring self-financing from $t = 0$ to $t = 1$. One obtains

$$\alpha_1^*(d) = -1, \quad \beta_1^*(d) = \frac{64}{25}, \quad \alpha_1^*(u) = -\frac{1}{12}, \quad \beta_1^*(u) = \frac{64}{75}.$$

The resulting portfolio value $V_t(\varphi^*)$ coincides with U_t at each node of the tree.

Figure 1: Portfolio-value process $V_t(\varphi^*) = \alpha_t^* S_t + \beta_t^* B_t$. Each node reports the *un-discounted* wealth of the super-hedging strategy φ^* along the corresponding stock-price path. Its discounted version $V_t^*(\varphi^*) = \frac{V_t(\varphi^*)}{B_t}$ is a true \mathbb{P}^* -martingale (as it should be, matching U_t^*).

Figure 2: Discounted portfolio value $V_t^*(\varphi^*)$. Because $V_t^*(\varphi^*)$ is a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale, the tree's root equals the conditional expectations of every branch, verifying the absence of arbitrage. This completes the demonstration for the American put example.

Having settled the American claim setting in the binomial model, we see how super-hedging strategies and the Snell envelope govern the no-arbitrage price. Recall too that in the binomial framework every European claim is exactly replicable, and the discounted stock price is a martingale under the unique risk-neutral measure. This unification of hedging and martingale pricing provides a template for more general discrete models. We now transition to a more general framework, allowing multiple stocks and a finite but not necessarily binomial sample space. Although we will rely less on explicit tree calculations, the same fundamental themes—risk-neutral measures, martingale discounting, and viable markets—remain central.

Chapter 3 — General Model

Ingredients

In this broader discrete-time setup, we still treat the bond as a riskless asset but allow for multiple risky assets. Our analysis becomes more theoretical, emphasizing how discounted asset prices behave under an equivalent martingale measure, and whether every contingent claim can be replicated or super-hedged. Unlike the simpler binomial case, we place no requirement that the bond price take the form $(1+r)^t$; we only assume it is deterministic, strictly positive, and adapted. We now move to a more general discrete-time market model, still finite but with multiple stocks and a bond.

1. **Probability space.** A finite probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbb{P})$ equipped with a filtration

$$\mathcal{F}_0 \subseteq \mathcal{F}_1 \subseteq \cdots \subseteq \mathcal{F}_T,$$

where $\mathcal{F}_0 = \{\emptyset, \Omega\}$. Since Ω is finite, every event has probability

$$\mathbb{P}(A) = \sum_{\omega \in A} \mathbb{P}(\omega).$$

2. **Bond.** A non-random riskless bond price process $(S_t^0)_{t=0}^T$ with $S_t^0 > 0$ for all t .

We do not require a single constant interest rate, so S_t^0 may differ from $(1+r)^t$ but remains strictly positive and non-random.

3. **Stocks.** d risky assets with an *adapted* price process

$$S_t = (S_t^0, S_t^1, \dots, S_t^d), \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T,$$

meaning each S_t^i is \mathcal{F}_t -measurable.

4. **Trading strategy.** A *self-financing predictable* process

$$\varphi = \{\varphi_t = (\varphi_t^0, \dots, \varphi_t^d) : t = 1, \dots, T\}$$

with $\varphi_t^i \in \mathcal{F}_{t-1}$ ($i = 1, \dots, d$) satisfying

$$\varphi_t \cdot S_t = \varphi_{t+1} \cdot S_t, \quad t = 0, \dots, T-1.$$

Here “ \cdot ” denotes the dot product,

$$\varphi_t \cdot S_t = \sum_{i=0}^d \varphi_t^i S_t^i.$$

5. **Value and gains process.**

$$V_t(\varphi) = \begin{cases} \varphi_1 \cdot S_0, & t = 0, \\ \varphi_t \cdot S_t, & t = 1, \dots, T, \end{cases} \quad G_t(\varphi) = V_t(\varphi) - V_0(\varphi) = \sum_{u=1}^t \varphi_u \cdot \Delta S_u,$$

where $\Delta S_u = S_u - S_{u-1}$.

6. **Arbitrage.** A strategy φ is an *arbitrage opportunity* if

$$V_0(\varphi) = 0, \quad V_T(\varphi) \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbb{P}(V_T(\varphi) > 0) > 0.$$

The market is called *viable* if there is no such strategy. Equivalently, viability means: whenever a self-financing φ satisfies $V_0(\varphi) = 0$ and $V_T(\varphi) \geq 0$, it must follow that $V_T(\varphi) = 0$ almost surely.

7. **Discounting (numeraire).** Using the bond S^0 as numeraire, we define

$$S_t^{*,i} := \frac{S_t^i}{S_t^0}, \quad i = 0, \dots, d,$$

so that $S_t^{*,0} \equiv 1$. Likewise, for a portfolio φ ,

$$V_t^*(\varphi) = \frac{V_t(\varphi)}{S_t^0}, \quad G_t^*(\varphi) = \sum_{u=1}^t \varphi_u \cdot (S_u^* - S_{u-1}^*).$$

Exercise 1. Verify directly that

$$G_t^*(\varphi) = \sum_{u=1}^t \varphi_u \cdot (S_u^* - S_{u-1}^*).$$

That is, show how the self-financing property ensures $V_t^*(\varphi) = V_0^*(\varphi) + G_t^*(\varphi)$.

In upcoming discussions, we will formalize the condition that no external capital is added to or withdrawn from the portfolio, thereby completing the definition of a self-financing strategy in the multi-stock setting. This extends naturally from the binomial model but does not rely on a specific tree structure.

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Discounted asset price process. Fix the bond S^0 as the numéraire and set

$$S_t^{*,i} := \frac{S_t^i}{S_t^0}, \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T, \quad i = 0, \dots, d.$$

Then $S_t^{*,0} \equiv 1$, so all other prices are expressed in “time-0 dollars.”

Discounted portfolio value and gains. For any self-financing strategy φ , define the discounted value

$$V_t^*(\varphi) := \frac{V_t(\varphi)}{S_t^0}, \quad G_t^*(\varphi) := V_t^*(\varphi) - V_0^*(\varphi).$$

Using the self-financing property one obtains the useful representation

$$V_t^*(\varphi) = \varphi_t \cdot S_t^*, \quad G_t^*(\varphi) = \sum_{s=1}^t \varphi_s \cdot \Delta S_s^*,$$

where $\Delta S_s^* = S_s^* - S_{s-1}^*$. Because $\Delta S_s^{*,0} = 0$, the discounted gains depend only on the *risky* assets, a fact that streamlines later martingale arguments.

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Trading strategy

A *trading strategy* is a predictable process

$$\varphi = \{\varphi_t : t = 1, 2, \dots, T\}$$

with

$$\varphi_t = (\varphi_t^0, \varphi_t^1, \dots, \varphi_t^d), \quad \varphi_t^i \in \mathcal{F}_{t-1}, \quad t = 1, \dots, T, \quad i = 1, \dots, d,$$

that is *self-financing*:

$$\varphi_t \cdot S_t = \varphi_{t+1} \cdot S_t, \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T - 1.$$

Here the dot-product is

$$\varphi_t \cdot S_t = \varphi_t^0 S_t^0 + \varphi_t^1 S_t^1 + \dots + \varphi_t^d S_t^d.$$

Think of φ_t^i as the *number of shares held in security i at time t* . In other words, at each rebalancing step, no external money is added or withdrawn; the portfolio's holdings are simply rearranged so that the net cost remains zero. Note that at time 0 there is no "previous day," so we set $\varphi_0 := \varphi_1$ by convention. This explains why $V_0(\varphi) = \varphi_1 \cdot S_0$; no rebalancing occurs before time 0.

The *value* of φ at time t is

$$V_t(\varphi) = \begin{cases} \varphi_1 \cdot S_0, & t = 0, \\ \varphi_t \cdot S_t, & t = 1, 2, \dots, T. \end{cases}$$

Gains process of φ

$$G_t(\varphi) := V_t(\varphi) - V_0(\varphi).$$

Claim 1.

$$G_t(\varphi) = \sum_{u=1}^t \varphi_u \cdot (S_u - S_{u-1}) = \sum_{u=1}^t \varphi_u \cdot \Delta S_u.$$

Check. (Notation: we often set $\varphi_0 := \varphi_1$ by convention.)

$$\begin{aligned} G_t(\varphi) &= V_t(\varphi) - V_0(\varphi) \\ &= \sum_{u=1}^t [V_u(\varphi) - V_{u-1}(\varphi)] \quad (\text{telescoping sum}) \\ &= \sum_{u=1}^t [\varphi_u \cdot S_u - \varphi_{u-1} \cdot S_{u-1}] \\ &= \sum_{u=1}^t \varphi_u \cdot (S_u - S_{u-1}) \quad (\text{self-financing implies } \varphi_u = \varphi_{u-1} \text{ when multiplied by } S_{u-1}) \\ &= \sum_{u=1}^t \varphi_u \cdot \Delta S_u. \end{aligned}$$

Remark: This telescoping sum is the discrete analogue of the fundamental theorem of calculus: summing the increments ΔS_u recovers the total change in the value from time 0 to time t .

Arbitrage

An *arbitrage opportunity* is a self-financing trading strategy φ such that

- $V_0^*(\varphi) = 0$,
- $V_T^*(\varphi) \geq 0$,
- $\mathbb{P}(V_T^*(\varphi) > 0) > 0$.

We say the market is *viable* if there are *no* arbitrage opportunities. Equivalently, if φ is self-financing with $V_0(\varphi) = 0$ and $V_T(\varphi) \geq 0$, then $V_T(\varphi) \equiv 0$. In other words, a “viable” market is precisely one in which no free-lunch or “something-for-nothing” opportunity can persist.

Discounting (using S^0 as numéraire):

$$S_t^{i,*} = \frac{S_t^i}{S_t^0}, \quad t = 0, \dots, T, \quad i = 0, \dots, d.$$

Note $S_t^{0,*} \equiv 1$ for all t . Define

$$V_t^*(\varphi) := \frac{V_t(\varphi)}{S_t^0}, \quad \text{etc.}$$

Exercise. Check that

$$G_t^*(\varphi) = \sum_{u=1}^t \varphi_u \cdot (S_u^* - S_{u-1}^*).$$

Hint/Detail: Recall

$$G_t^*(\varphi) = V_t^*(\varphi) - V_0^*(\varphi) = \frac{V_t(\varphi)}{S_t^0} - \frac{V_0(\varphi)}{S_0^0} = \frac{V_t(\varphi) - V_0(\varphi)}{S_t^0}$$

(since $S_0^0 > 0$, e.g. often $S_0^0 = 1$). Then compare with the claim for $G_t(\varphi)$ after adjusting each term by the factor $1/S_t^0$, using the self-financing condition and noting $S_u^0 \neq 0$. One obtains

$$G_t^*(\varphi) = \sum_{u=1}^t \varphi_u \cdot \left(\frac{S_u}{S_u^0} - \frac{S_{u-1}}{S_{u-1}^0} \right) = \sum_{u=1}^t \varphi_u \cdot (S_u^* - S_{u-1}^*).$$

Change of Measure

In the Binomial Model there is a special choice p^* of the up” probability for which the discounted stock price is a martingale. We now investigate this possibility in the general model. A second probability measure \mathbb{Q} on (Ω, \mathcal{F}) is *equivalent* to \mathbb{P} (written $\mathbb{Q} \sim \mathbb{P}$) provided

$$\mathbb{Q}(A) > 0 \iff \mathbb{P}(A) > 0, \quad A \in \mathcal{F}.$$

Because $\#\Omega < \infty$ and we assume $\mathbb{P}(\omega) > 0$ for all $\omega \in \Omega$, this is the same as requiring $\mathbb{Q}(\omega) > 0$ for every ω . In practice, if there were any ω with $\mathbb{P}(\omega) = 0$, one could remove it from Ω altogether, so that all remaining states have strictly positive probability. This ensures the equivalence condition is well-defined.

As for \mathbb{P} , we can write

$$\mathbb{Q}(A) = \sum_{\omega \in A} \mathbb{Q}(\omega).$$

Given $\mathbb{Q} \sim \mathbb{P}$, define the Radon–Nikodym derivative

$$Z(\omega) := \frac{\mathbb{Q}(\omega)}{\mathbb{P}(\omega)}, \quad \omega \in \Omega.$$

Then

$$\mathbb{Q}(A) = \sum_{\omega \in A} Z(\omega) \mathbb{P}(\omega) = \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{P}}[Z \mathbf{1}_A].$$

Similarly (**exercise**) for any random variable X ,

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[X] = \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{P}}[Z X].$$

Hint/Detail: For a simple random variable

$$X(\omega) = \sum_{k=1}^m x_k \mathbf{1}_{A_k}(\omega),$$

the expectation under \mathbb{Q} is

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[X] = \sum_{k=1}^m x_k \mathbb{Q}(A_k).$$

Since $\mathbb{Q}(A_k) = \sum_{\omega \in A_k} Z(\omega) \mathbb{P}(\omega)$, we get

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[X] = \sum_{k=1}^m x_k \sum_{\omega \in A_k} Z(\omega) \mathbb{P}(\omega) = \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} Z(\omega) X(\omega) \mathbb{P}(\omega) = \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{P}}[Z X].$$

For a general (nonnegative or bounded) random variable X , approximate X by simple random variables and use dominated convergence.

Example 1. In the Binomial Model, the probabilities \mathbb{P}^p (for different choices p of the up" probability) are all equivalent: $\mathbb{P}^p \sim \mathbb{P}^{p'}$ for all p, p' .

Definition 2 (Equivalent Martingale Measure). *An Equivalent Martingale Measure (**EMM**) is a probability measure \mathbb{Q} on (Ω, \mathcal{F}) such that:*

- (i) $\mathbb{Q} \sim \mathbb{P}$;
- (ii) $\{S_t^{i,*}\}_{t=0}^T$ is a \mathbb{Q} -martingale for every $i = 1, \dots, d$.

Example. In the multi-period Binomial Model, \mathbb{P}^* is an EMM.

Theorem 3 (First Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing).

The market is viable \iff there exists an EMM.

Proof ("easy" direction \Leftarrow). Assume there exists an EMM \mathbb{Q} . By the following lemma (cf. the Binomial Model), no arbitrage is possible, hence the market is viable.

Lemma 4. *If \mathbb{Q} is an EMM and φ is a self-financing trading strategy, then*

$$\{V_t^*(\varphi)\}_{t=0}^T \text{ is a } \mathbb{Q}\text{-martingale.}$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[V_{t+1}^*(\varphi) \mid \mathcal{F}_t] &= \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}\left[\sum_{i=0}^d \varphi_{t+1}^i S_{t+1}^{i,*} \mid \mathcal{F}_t\right] \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^d \varphi_{t+1}^i \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[S_{t+1}^{i,*} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \quad (\varphi_{t+1}^i \in \mathcal{F}_t) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^d \varphi_{t+1}^i S_t^{i,*} \quad (\text{since } S^{i,*} \text{ is a } \mathbb{Q}\text{-martingale}) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^d \varphi_t^i S_t^{i,*} \quad (\text{self-financing condition}) \\ &= V_t^*(\varphi). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $V_t^*(\varphi)$ is a \mathbb{Q} -martingale. □

Conclusion of \Leftarrow in FFTAP. Suppose φ is self-financing with $V_0(\varphi) = 0$ and $V_T(\varphi) \geq 0$. From the lemma, $\{V_t^*(\varphi)\}$ is a \mathbb{Q} -martingale, so

$$V_0^*(\varphi) = \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[V_T^*(\varphi)].$$

But $V_T(\varphi) \geq 0 \implies V_T^*(\varphi) \geq 0$, hence

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[V_T^*(\varphi)] \geq 0,$$

and $V_0(\varphi) = 0 \implies V_0^*(\varphi) = 0$. It follows that

$$0 = V_0^*(\varphi) = \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[V_T^*(\varphi)] \geq 0 \implies V_T^*(\varphi) \equiv 0,$$

so $V_T(\varphi) \equiv 0$ almost surely, and no arbitrage is possible. Therefore viability.

Example of Non-Viable Market

Consider $\Omega = \{1, 2\}$ with $\mathbb{Q}(1) = a$, $\mathbb{Q}(2) = b$, where $0 < a < 1$, $0 < b < 1$, $a + b = 1$. Take $\mathbb{P}(1) = \mathbb{P}(2) = \frac{1}{2}$ and horizon $T = 1$.

$$S_0^0 = S_1^0 = 1, \quad S_1^1 = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} \\ 2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad S_1^2 = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} \\ 3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

If $S^{1,*}$ and $S^{2,*}$ are \mathbb{Q} -martingales, then

$$a \frac{1}{2} + 2b = 1, \quad a \frac{1}{2} + 3b = 1.$$

Subtracting these two equations gives $b = 0$, contradicting $b > 0$. So no EMM exists; the market is non-viable.

(An explicit arbitrage is $\varphi = (0, -1, 1)$: we hold 0 in the bank account, short 1 share of security 1, and long 1 share of security 2. One checks

$$\begin{aligned} V_0(\varphi) &= 0 \cdot 1 + (-1) \cdot \frac{1}{2} + 1 \cdot \frac{1}{2} = 0, \\ V_1(\varphi) &= \begin{cases} 0 \cdot 1 + (-1) \cdot \frac{1}{2} + 1 \cdot \frac{1}{2} = 0, & (\omega = 1), \\ 0 \cdot 1 + (-1) \cdot 2 + 1 \cdot 3 = 1, & (\omega = 2). \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $V_1(\varphi) \geq 0$ and $\mathbb{P}(V_1(\varphi) > 0) = \frac{1}{2} > 0$, so it is an arbitrage.) Alternatively, one can also choose the trading strategy $\varphi' = (0, 1, -1)$ and verify that it yields a similar arbitrage opportunity under the same price configuration.

Proof of \Rightarrow in FFTAP

If the model is viable, then an EMM exists.

Preparation: Write $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_n\}$. Any r.v. X can be viewed as the vector

$$(X(\omega_1), \dots, X(\omega_n)) \in \mathbb{R}^n.$$

Likewise, \mathbb{P} and \mathbb{Q} are vectors in \mathbb{R}^n , and

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{P}}[X] = \mathbb{P} \cdot X.$$

Viability means: for every self-financing strategy φ with $V_0(\varphi) = 0$, we have

$$V_T(\varphi) \geq 0 \implies V_T(\varphi) \equiv 0.$$

Note

$$V_0(\varphi) = \varphi_1 \cdot S_0, \quad V_T(\varphi) = \varphi_T \cdot S_T.$$

Also, any linear combination $a\varphi + b\psi$ of self-financing strategies is self-financing.

Sketch of the separation-theorem argument:

- Consider the set

$$\mathcal{K} = \{V_T(\varphi) \mid \varphi \text{ self-financing, } V_0(\varphi) = 0\} \subset \mathbb{R}^n.$$

By viability,

$$\mathcal{K} \cap \mathbb{R}_+^n = \{0\}, \quad \text{where } \mathbb{R}_+^n = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : x_i \geq 0 \forall i\}.$$

That is, the only nonnegative payoff vector attainable with zero initial cost is the zero vector.

- By a geometric separation theorem (or Farkas' Lemma"-type argument), there exists a linear functional

$$\ell : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

such that

$$\ell(x) \geq 0 \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{K}, \quad \ell(y) > 0 \quad \forall y \in (\mathbb{R}_+^n \setminus \{0\}).$$

Concretely, ℓ can be represented by a vector $q = (q_1, \dots, q_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ with strictly positive components. Then

$$\ell(x) = q \cdot x = \sum_{i=1}^n q_i x_i.$$

- Normalize q so that $\sum_{i=1}^n q_i = 1$, and define

$$\mathbb{Q}(\omega_i) := q_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, n.$$

Then \mathbb{Q} is a probability measure on $\{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_n\}$.

- Since $(q_1, \dots, q_n) \gg 0$ (i.e. all entries are strictly positive), we have $\mathbb{Q}(\omega) > 0$ for every ω , hence $\mathbb{Q} \sim \mathbb{P}$.
- One checks carefully that for each discounted price $S^{i,*}$, the condition $\ell(V_T(\varphi)) \geq 0$ for all self-financing φ forces $S^{i,*}$ to be a martingale under \mathbb{Q} .

Additional detail: If $S^{i,*}$ were not a \mathbb{Q} -martingale, then there would exist some t and some state ω in \mathcal{F}_t for which

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[S_{t+1}^{i,*} \mid \mathcal{F}_t](\omega) \neq S_t^{i,*}(\omega).$$

Suppose for definiteness that

$$\delta(\omega) := \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[S_{t+1}^{i,*} \mid \mathcal{F}_t](\omega) - S_t^{i,*}(\omega) > 0.$$

Then we can construct a trading strategy φ that invests in the i th asset (and the riskless asset) at time t in precisely such a way that $V_0(\varphi) = 0$ but $V_T(\varphi) \geq 0$ with positive probability of being > 0 . This contradicts viability. A similar argument applies if the difference is negative. Therefore $S^{i,*}$ must be a \mathbb{Q} -martingale.

So an EMM \mathbb{Q} exists, and this completes the proof of the First Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing.

Remark. This argument is essentially separating a convex cone" from the positive orthant by a hyperplane. One thereby obtains a strictly positive linear functional ℓ whose positivity on the relevant set of claims implies the martingale property. In finite dimensions, such a functional can be identified with the probability measure \mathbb{Q} having strictly positive mass on each state.

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Underlying Probability Space. Fix a finite outcome set $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_n\}$ equipped with the full σ -algebra $\mathcal{F} = 2^\Omega$ and a probability measure \mathbb{P} such that $\mathbb{P}(\{\omega\}) > 0$ for every $\omega \in \Omega$. Expectations under \mathbb{P} are written $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$.

Trading Dates. Trading occurs at integer times $t = 0, 1, \dots, T$ with $T < \infty$. Successive dates are one time-unit apart.

Assets. There are $d + 1$ traded securities.

- **Bond** ($i = 0$): deterministic price path $S_t^0 = (1 + r)^t$ with constant rate $r \geq 0$. It serves as the *numéraire*.
- **d Stocks** ($i = 1, \dots, d$): each price S_t^i is \mathcal{F}_t -measurable for every t . Because Ω is finite, all prices take only finitely many values, so all expectations below are finite.

Information Flow (Filtration). The investor's information is modelled by a filtration $(\mathcal{F}_t)_{t=0}^T$ satisfying

$$\mathcal{F}_0 = \{\emptyset, \Omega\}, \quad \mathcal{F}_0 \subset \mathcal{F}_1 \subset \dots \subset \mathcal{F}_T = \mathcal{F}.$$

Trading Strategy (formal version). A *predictable* portfolio is a sequence

$$\varphi_t = (\varphi_t^0, \varphi_t^1, \dots, \varphi_t^d), \quad t = 1, \dots, T,$$

where each coordinate φ_t^i is \mathcal{F}_{t-1} -measurable and represents the number of units of asset i held during the interval $(t - 1, t]$. (Negative holdings correspond to short sales.) This aligns with our earlier requirement that each φ_t^i is determined by the information available at the end of the previous trading date and remains fixed throughout $(t - 1, t]$ until the next rebalancing.

Risk-neutral viewpoint beyond the binomial model. In a general finite market, the absence of arbitrage is equivalent to the existence of at least one probability measure under which every discounted asset price is a martingale—an *equivalent martingale (risk-neutral) measure*. This directly generalises the single “risk-neutral p^* ” encountered in the binomial model.

Complete versus incomplete markets. A viable market is called *complete* when every European contingent claim can be replicated by some self-financing strategy; if some claims are non-replicable, the market is *incomplete*. Incomplete markets may still be arbitrage-free, but multiple risk-neutral measures leave prices indeterminate for certain payoffs.

Second Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing (preview). Under viability, the market is complete *iff* the risk-neutral measure is unique. So uniqueness not only rules out arbitrage but also guarantees a single, replicating price process for every European claim.

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Theorem (First Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing).

Our market model is viable \iff there exists an Equivalent Martingale Measure (EMM).

“Viable” means “no arbitrage opportunity exists.” We now prove each direction of this theorem. The forward implication (\Leftarrow) is simpler and uses a standard martingale argument, while the reverse direction (\Rightarrow) requires a separation argument from convex analysis. We have already seen analogous reasoning in the binomial model, where the discounted stock price process under an appropriate measure was a martingale, and we used that to rule out arbitrage. The same device works in the general setting.

Lemma.

If Q is an EMM and ϕ is a self-financing trading strategy (s.f.t.s.), then the discounted wealth process $(V_t^(\phi))_{t=0,\dots,T}$ is a Q -martingale.*

Proof of the Lemma. Recall that a discounted price process S_t^{i*} satisfies

$$\mathbb{E}^Q[S_{t+1}^{i*} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = S_t^{i*},$$

for each asset $i = 0, 1, \dots, d$. We must show that for a self-financing strategy ϕ , the discounted wealth

$$V_t^*(\phi) = \sum_{i=0}^d \phi_t^i S_t^{i*}$$

also has the martingale property under Q , namely

$$\mathbb{E}^Q[V_{t+1}^*(\phi) \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = V_t^*(\phi) \quad \text{for each } t = 0, 1, \dots, T-1.$$

Since ϕ is self-financing, we have

$$V_{t+1}^*(\phi) = \sum_{i=0}^d \phi_{t+1}^i S_{t+1}^{i*},$$

where ϕ_{t+1}^i is \mathcal{F}_t -measurable. Therefore we compute:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}^Q[V_{t+1}^*(\phi) \mid \mathcal{F}_t] &= \mathbb{E}^Q\left[\sum_{i=0}^d \phi_{t+1}^i S_{t+1}^{i*} \mid \mathcal{F}_t\right] \\ &\stackrel{(1)}{=} \sum_{i=0}^d \phi_{t+1}^i \mathbb{E}^Q[S_{t+1}^{i*} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \quad \text{since } \phi_{t+1}^i \in \mathcal{F}_t \text{ and linearity of expectation} \\ &\stackrel{(2)}{=} \sum_{i=0}^d \phi_{t+1}^i S_t^{i*} \quad \text{(because each } S_t^{i*} \text{ is a } Q\text{-martingale)} \\ &\stackrel{(3)}{=} \sum_{i=0}^d \phi_t^i S_t^{i*} \quad \text{(self-financing property: } \phi_{t+1}^i = \phi_t^i \text{ at times } t \text{ and } t+1) \\ &= V_t^*(\phi). \end{aligned}$$

So $(V_t^*(\phi))$ is a martingale under Q , as required. □

Proof of \Leftarrow (viability) in the FFTAP

We show that if there exists an Equivalent Martingale Measure Q , then the market is viable (*i.e.*, has no arbitrage). Suppose ϕ is a self-financing trading strategy with

$$V_0(\phi) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad V_T(\phi) \geq 0 \quad (\text{componentwise}) \quad \text{with strictly positive probability.}$$

We must show ϕ is a trivial strategy (yields zero wealth), thus implying no arbitrage opportunities exist.

Applying the Lemma with $V_0^*(\phi) = 0$, we obtain

$$\mathbb{E}^Q[V_T^*(\phi)] = \mathbb{E}^Q[V_0^*(\phi)] = V_0^*(\phi) = 0.$$

Since $V_T^*(\phi) \geq 0$ pointwise and its expectation under Q is zero, we conclude

$$V_T^*(\phi) = 0 \quad Q\text{-almost surely.}$$

This is precisely the general version of a frequently used fact: a nonnegative random variable with zero expectation must be zero almost surely. We have already relied on this logic in earlier binomial-model arguments. But $V_T^*(\phi) = 0$ implies $V_T(\phi) = 0$ (undiscounting does not affect the sign). Therefore ϕ yields no positive gains, so there is no arbitrage. Equivalently, the market is *viable*. □

Example (revisited from Lecture 17)

Let $\Omega = \{1, 2\}$ and $T = 1$. We denote the real-world measure by

$$P(1) = P(2) = \frac{1}{2}.$$

We attempt to construct a candidate measure Q with

$$Q(1) = a, \quad Q(2) = b, \quad 0 < a, b < 1, \quad \text{and} \quad a + b = 1.$$

We have $d = 2$ assets (including the numeraire asset if needed). The **discounted** asset prices are

$$S_0^0 = S_0^1 = S_0^2 = 1,$$

$$S_1^1(1) = \frac{1}{2}, \quad S_1^1(2) = 2, \quad S_1^2(1) = \frac{1}{2}, \quad S_1^2(2) = 3.$$

Therefore at $t = 0$, $S_0^1 = S_0^2 = 1$, and at $t = 1$:

$$S_1^1(1) = \frac{1}{2}, \quad S_1^1(2) = 2, \quad S_1^2(1) = \frac{1}{2}, \quad S_1^2(2) = 3.$$

For Q to be an EMM, the *discounted* price of each asset must satisfy

$$\mathbb{E}^Q[S_1^1] = a \cdot \frac{1}{2} + b \cdot 2 = S_0^1 = 1,$$

$$\mathbb{E}^Q[S_1^2] = a \cdot \frac{1}{2} + b \cdot 3 = S_0^2 = 1.$$

So we need to solve the system

$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}a + 2b = 1, \\ \frac{1}{2}a + 3b = 1. \end{cases}$$

Subtracting the first equation from the second gives

$$\left(\frac{1}{2}a + 3b\right) - \left(\frac{1}{2}a + 2b\right) = b = 0,$$

which contradicts $b > 0$. Therefore $b = 0$ cannot hold if Q is to remain equivalent to P . So *no* Q with $0 < b < 1$ can satisfy both equations simultaneously. Consequently, *no* EMM $Q \sim P$ exists, and the model is *not* viable.

Arbitrage witnessing non-viability. We explicitly exhibit an arbitrage. Choose the portfolio

$$\phi = (\phi^0, \phi^1, \phi^2) = (0, -1, 1).$$

Then its cost at time 0 is

$$V_0(\phi) = 0 \cdot S_0^0 + (-1) \cdot S_0^1 + 1 \cdot S_0^2 = 0 \cdot 1 + (-1) \cdot 1 + 1 \cdot 1 = 0.$$

At time 1,

$$V_1(\phi) = -S_1^1 + S_1^2 = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} = 0, & \omega = 1, \\ -2 + 3 = 1, & \omega = 2. \end{cases}$$

Therefore $V_1(\phi) \geq 0$ for both states, and $V_1(\phi) > 0$ occurs with strictly positive probability ($\omega = 2$ happens with $P(\omega = 2) = \frac{1}{2} > 0$). So ϕ is a genuine arbitrage strategy.

Proof of \Rightarrow (existence of EMM) in the FFTAP

The argument for this reverse direction can be viewed in three steps: first, reinterpret viability in a geometric way by identifying the subspace of all possible zero-cost discounted payoffs and the standard simplex of nonnegative vectors. Second, use a separating hyperplane theorem from convex analysis to find a vector separating these sets. Third, exploit that separating vector to define an EMM. We now prove the converse implication: *If the market model is viable, then there exists an Equivalent Martingale Measure Q .* We will work in a finite-state setting to keep the proof transparent.

Finite state preparation. Let $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_n\}$. We identify any random variable $X : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with the vector

$$X = (X(\omega_1), \dots, X(\omega_n)) \in \mathbb{R}^n.$$

Similarly, the probability measures P and Q will be vectors $P = (P_1, \dots, P_n)$ and $Q = (Q_1, \dots, Q_n)$ in \mathbb{R}^n where $\sum_k P_k = 1$, $\sum_k Q_k = 1$, and $P_k, Q_k > 0$. The condition $Q \sim P$ is exactly $Q_k > 0$ whenever $P_k > 0$.

Viability in linear-algebraic form. A self-financing trading strategy ϕ with $V_0(\phi) = 0$ has terminal (discounted) wealth

$$V_T^*(\phi) = \phi_T \cdot S_T^*.$$

(viewed as a vector in \mathbb{R}^n). By linearity of trading strategies, the set of all possible such terminal discounted wealths spans a *subspace* of \mathbb{R}^n :

$$(a\varphi + b\psi)_t = a\varphi_t + b\psi_t, \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T, \quad a, b \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Therefore

$$L := \{V_T^*(\phi) : \phi \text{ is s.f.t.s. with } V_0(\phi) = 0\} \subset \mathbb{R}^n.$$

We also define:

$$D := \{Y \in \mathbb{R}^n : Y_k \geq 0 \text{ for all } k\}, \quad (\text{the nonnegative cone}),$$

$$F := \{Y \in D : \sum_{k=1}^n Y_k = 1\}.$$

Then F is a compact convex set in \mathbb{R}^n (it is the standard $(n-1)$ -simplex), and D is the closed cone spanned by F .

Claim. $\text{Viability} \iff L \cap D = \{0\} \iff L \cap F = \emptyset$.

Reasoning: If $L \cap D \neq \{0\}$, then there is a nonzero vector in L that is componentwise nonnegative. This exactly means one can form a self-financing strategy with zero initial cost whose terminal payoff is nonnegative and not identically zero (an arbitrage). Conversely, if some $v \in L \cap D$ is nonzero, then we may scale v

so that its sum of components is 1, placing it in F . Therefore $L \cap D = \{0\}$ is equivalent to $L \cap F = \emptyset$. In two dimensions, for instance, L might be a line through the origin, D is the first quadrant (including axes), and F is just the line segment between $(1, 0)$ and $(0, 1)$. If L does not meet D except at 0, then it also misses the smaller set F . Similarly in three dimensions, one can visualize L as a line or plane through the origin and F as the triangular faces bounding the standard simplex. The same principle applies for n dimensions.

Separating hyperplane. Since L (a subspace) and the compact set F are disjoint, the classical *Separating Hyperplane Lemma* from convex analysis states there exists a *nonzero* vector $Z \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that

$$X \cdot Z = 0 \quad \text{for all } X \in L, \quad Y \cdot Z > 0 \quad \text{for all } Y \in F.$$

One can also picture this situation in higher dimensions by imagining F as a small “simplex-shaped” polytope in the nonnegative orthant of \mathbb{R}^n , while L is a linear subspace that does not intersect it. By geometry, there must be a hyperplane (defined via some normal vector Z) that completely separates F from L . In linear algebra terms, $H = \{x : x \cdot Z = 0\}$ is exactly that hyperplane of dimension $n - 1$. In linear algebra terms, we let

$$H := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : x \cdot Z = 0\},$$

a hyperplane of codimension 1. Moreover,

$$F \subset \{y \in \mathbb{R}^n : y \cdot Z > 0\}.$$

Because every extreme point e_k of F (the vector that is 1 in the k -th coordinate and 0 elsewhere) must also yield $e_k \cdot Z > 0$, we immediately see that each $Z_k > 0$. (If any $Z_k = 0$, we would get $e_k \cdot Z = 0$, contradicting > 0 .)

Defining Q . Since $Z_k > 0$, we can define

$$Q_k := \frac{Z_k}{\sum_{\ell=1}^n Z_\ell} \quad \text{for } k = 1, \dots, n.$$

Then $Q = (Q_1, \dots, Q_n)$ is a probability vector with strictly positive entries. Consequently $Q \sim P$.

Verifying the EMM property. Take any $X \in L$. By construction, $X \cdot Z = 0$. Therefore

$$\mathbb{E}^Q[X] = X \cdot Q = X \cdot \left(\frac{Z}{\sum Z_\ell} \right) = \frac{1}{\sum Z_\ell} (X \cdot Z) = 0.$$

But the core definition of L is that each $X \in L$ is precisely the *discounted terminal payoff* of some self-financing strategy with zero initial cost. That is, $X = V_T^*(\phi)$ for some ϕ with $V_0^*(\phi) = 0$. Therefore

$$\mathbb{E}^Q[V_T^*(\phi)] = 0,$$

which implies $(V_t^*(\phi))_t$ is a Q -martingale (similar linear-expectation arguments as in the Lemma show that no drift in expected value under Q occurs). In particular, each *discounted* asset price S_t^{i*} can be realized as such a payoff (by holding a single share of asset i , financed appropriately), so these discounted assets must also be Q -martingales. Therefore Q is an Equivalent Martingale Measure, completing the proof. In fact, this construction need not yield a unique Q ; any other normal vector spanning the same hyperplane would also work, so multiple EMMs can arise in certain markets. ■

Remark. One can see the same idea in 3D by viewing L as a line or plane through the origin and F as a triangular region in the first octant. If they do not intersect, a hyperplane through L must lie completely away from F . The normal to that hyperplane gives us Z , and thus our Q .

Figure 1: A 2D sketch: L (blue) is disjoint from the positive cone D (green) except at 0. The red line H is a separating hyperplane.

Summary

We have now established the **First Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing** in the finite-state setting:

- *Non-arbitrage (viability)* \implies existence of an EMM Q (which implies discounted asset prices are Q -martingales).
- Conversely, the existence of an EMM Q precludes arbitrage, because any nonnegative wealth with zero initial cost must be zero almost surely under Q .

This shows the equivalence between “viability” and “there is an EMM.”

In subsequent lectures we will use the EMM to price contingent claims (via risk-neutral pricing) and later proceed toward the *Second Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing*. Much as we saw in simpler binomial-model settings, the EMM becomes the tool for valuation in more general markets.

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Model Setup. We work on a finite filtered probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, (\mathcal{F}_t)_{t=0}^T, \mathbb{P})$ with d traded assets. The (undiscounted) price vector is $S_t = (S_t^1, \dots, S_t^d)$ for $t = 0, \dots, T$. Asset 0 denotes the money-market account B_t , so the *discounted* prices are $S_t^{i,*} = S_t^i/B_t$ (and $S_t^{0,*} = 1$).

Self-Financing Condition. ϕ is *self-financing* iff for every $t = 1, \dots, T-1$

$$\phi_t \cdot S_{t-1} = \phi_{t+1} \cdot S_{t-1}, \quad \iff \quad \phi_t^0 B_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^d \phi_t^i S_{t-1}^i = \phi_{t+1}^0 B_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^d \phi_{t+1}^i S_{t-1}^i.$$

Its value is $V_t(\phi) = \phi_t \cdot S_t$ and the discounted value $V_t^*(\phi) = \phi_t \cdot S_t^*$.

Gains Process. The cumulative gains are

$$G_t(\phi) = \sum_{s=1}^t \phi_s \cdot \Delta S_s, \quad \Delta S_s = S_s - S_{s-1},$$

and the discounted gains satisfy $G_t^*(\phi) = \sum_{s=1}^t \phi_s \cdot \Delta S_s^*$.

Arbitrage Opportunity. A self-financing ϕ is an *arbitrage* if

$$V_0(\phi) = 0, \quad V_T(\phi) \geq 0 \text{ a.s.}, \quad \mathbb{P}[V_T(\phi) > 0] > 0.$$

Viable Market. The market is *viable* when no arbitrage opportunities exist.

Equivalent Probability Measures. Two probabilities Q and $Q^\#$ are *equivalent* if they share the same null sets.

Equivalent Martingale Measure (EMM). A measure $Q \sim \mathbb{P}$ is an EMM if each discounted price is a Q -martingale:

$$\mathbb{E}^Q[S_t^* \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = S_{t-1}^*, \quad t = 1, \dots, T.$$

Discounted value process. For any trading strategy φ , set

$$V_t^*(\varphi) := \frac{V_t(\varphi)}{S_t^0}, \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T.$$

Portfolio holdings and self-financing. Writing $\varphi_t = (\varphi_t^0, \dots, \varphi_t^d)$,

$$V_t^*(\varphi) = \varphi_t \cdot S_t^*, \quad V_t^*(\varphi) = \varphi_{t+1} \cdot S_t^* \quad (t = 0, \dots, T-1).$$

Discounted gains process. Define

$$G_t^*(\varphi) := V_t^*(\varphi) - V_0^*(\varphi) = \sum_{s=1}^t \varphi_s \cdot \Delta S_s^*, \quad \Delta S_s^* := S_s^* - S_{s-1}^*.$$

Because $\Delta S_s^{*,0} = 0$, the sum involves *only* the risky assets, which will simplify subsequent martingale arguments.

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We have the following sets:

$$L := \left\{ V_T^*(\varphi) : \varphi \text{ is a self-financing trading strategy (sfts) with } V_0(\varphi) = 0 \right\} \subset \mathbb{R}^n,$$

$$D := \left\{ Y \in \mathbb{R}^n : Y \neq 0 \text{ and } Y_k \geq 0 \text{ for all } k = 1, 2, \dots, n \right\},$$

$$F := \left\{ Y \in D : \sum_{k=1}^n Y_k = 1 \right\}.$$

Note that our sample space is a finite set with n points, labeled $\omega_1, \dots, \omega_n$. Therefore each random variable can be identified with a vector in \mathbb{R}^n . Consequently, L is at most n -dimensional, and we may visualize L as a linear subspace in \mathbb{R}^n . Here:

- $V_T^*(\varphi) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ represents the discounted terminal value of a self-financing trading strategy φ .
- L is the set of all such possible (discounted) terminal payoffs arising from **zero-initial-capital** strategies.
- D is the set of nonnegative vectors in \mathbb{R}^n (except the zero vector).
- $F \subset D$ further imposes the constraint that the coordinates sum to 1 (i.e. they form a probability mass vector).

Key: Market Viability

Definition. The market is said to be *viable* if and only if

$$L \cap D = \emptyset \iff L \cap F = \emptyset.$$

Equivalently, no **free lunch** opportunities exist in the market.

The condition $L \cap D = \emptyset$ means there is no self-financing strategy starting with zero initial capital whose terminal payoff is almost surely nonnegative and strictly positive with positive probability. Because $F \subset D$, excluding the intersection with F is essentially a stricter version: there is no self-financing strategy starting with zero capital whose terminal payoff is a (strictly) positive probability vector. From **Lecture 18**, we have the following key lemma (the *Separating Hyperplane Lemma*):

$$L \cap F = \emptyset \implies \exists z \in \mathbb{R}^n \text{ such that } \begin{cases} L \subset \{Y \in \mathbb{R}^n : Y \cdot z = 0\}, \\ F \subset \{Y \in \mathbb{R}^n : Y \cdot z > 0\}. \end{cases}$$

For a more detailed argument of this geometric separation result, consult Section 6 of Chapter 3. The idea is to pick a point in L and a point in F that realize the minimal distance between these two sets. Drawing the line segment between them yields a perpendicular direction that can serve as z , ensuring F lies strictly on the positive side of the hyperplane and L lies in the hyperplane itself. In a simple two-dimensional example, for instance, F is the line segment connecting $(1, 0)$ and $(0, 1)$ while L can be a line through the origin. If they do not intersect, one can identify distinct points in L and F achieving the minimal distance, and the connecting segment is perpendicular to both sets in the sense described above. This yields the separating vector z , ensuring $L \subset \{x : x \cdot z = 0\}$ and $F \subset \{x : x \cdot z > 0\}$. We will use this vector $z = (z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n)$ to construct an *equivalent martingale measure* \mathbb{Q} .

A Positive Separating Vector

- Because $F \subset \{Y : Y \cdot z > 0\}$, every element $Y \in F$ has strictly positive dot product with z .
- In particular, consider the vector

$$Y = (0, \dots, 0, \underbrace{1}_{\text{at position } k}, 0, \dots, 0) \in F.$$

Since $Y \in F$, we must have $Y \cdot z = z_k > 0$. But k was arbitrary from $\{1, \dots, n\}$. Therefore

$$z_k > 0 \quad \text{for all } k = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

So we have found a vector z whose coordinates are all strictly positive. This nontrivial positivity property is crucial for defining a probability measure below.

Definition of the Measure \mathbb{Q}

Define \mathbb{Q} on the finite sample space $\{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_n\}$ by

$$\mathbb{Q}(\omega_k) := \frac{z_k}{\sum_{\ell=1}^n z_\ell}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

Since $z_k > 0$ for each k , it follows that $\mathbb{Q}(\omega_k) > 0$ for all k . So, \mathbb{Q} is a probability measure that assigns strictly positive probability to each ω_k . In particular, \mathbb{Q} is *equivalent* to \mathbb{P} (written $\mathbb{Q} \sim \mathbb{P}$), since they share the same support (no event with positive probability under \mathbb{P} has zero probability under \mathbb{Q}).

Key property. If $V_T^*(\varphi) \in L$, i.e. it is the discounted terminal value of a self-financing strategy with zero initial cost, then by the hyperplane property we know $V_T^*(\varphi) \cdot z = 0$. Consequently:

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[V_T^*(\varphi)] = \sum_{k=1}^n V_T^*(\varphi)(\omega_k) \mathbb{Q}(\omega_k) = \frac{1}{\sum_{\ell=1}^n z_\ell} (V_T^*(\varphi) \cdot z) = 0.$$

So, for any self-financing trading strategy φ with $V_0(\varphi) = 0$, we have

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[V_T^*(\varphi)] = 0.$$

This exact equality will imply that discounted asset prices must be \mathbb{Q} -martingales, thereby showing \mathbb{Q} is indeed an *equivalent martingale measure (EMM)*.

The Martingale Criterion

We recall a standard criterion for recognizing a martingale in discrete time.

Criterion. Let $M = (M_0, M_1, \dots, M_T)$ be an adapted process (i.e. M_t is \mathcal{F}_t -measurable). A sequence $\eta = (\eta_1, \eta_2, \dots, \eta_T)$ is called *predictable* if $\eta_t \in \mathcal{F}_{t-1}$ for each t .

Claim: If

$$\mathbb{E}\left[\sum_{t=1}^T \eta_t (M_t - M_{t-1})\right] = 0 \quad \text{for every predictable sequence } (\eta_1, \dots, \eta_T),$$

then M is a martingale under that expectation (i.e. $\mathbb{E}[M_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = M_{t-1}$ for each t).

Proof. Fix any $u \in \{1, \dots, T\}$. We must show

$$\mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}] = M_{u-1} \quad \text{a.s.}$$

Suppose, for the sake of contradiction, that with positive probability we have $\mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}] > M_{u-1}$. Denote the event

$$A := \left\{ \omega : \mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}](\omega) > M_{u-1}(\omega) \right\} \in \mathcal{F}_{u-1}.$$

By assumption, $\mathbb{P}(A) > 0$. Define a predictable sequence by

$$\eta_t := \begin{cases} \mathbf{1}_A(\omega), & t = u, \\ 0, & t \neq u. \end{cases}$$

This choice is predictable because η_u is \mathcal{F}_{u-1} -measurable (it is just the indicator of $A \in \mathcal{F}_{u-1}$), and all other $\eta_t = 0$. Then

$$\sum_{t=1}^T \eta_t (M_t - M_{t-1}) = \eta_u (M_u - M_{u-1}) = \mathbf{1}_A (M_u - M_{u-1}).$$

By hypothesis,

$$0 = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{1}_A (M_u - M_{u-1})] = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{1}_A M_u] - \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{1}_A M_{u-1}].$$

Since $A \in \mathcal{F}_{u-1}$, we also get

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{1}_A M_u] = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{1}_A \mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}]] = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{1}_A (\mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}] - M_{u-1})] + \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{1}_A M_{u-1}].$$

Therefore

$$0 = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{1}_A (M_u - M_{u-1})] = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{1}_A (\mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}] - M_{u-1})].$$

But on the event A we have $\mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}] - M_{u-1} > 0$. So the above expectation of a strictly positive quantity (on A) must be strictly positive if $\mathbb{P}(A) > 0$, which contradicts the equality to 0. Therefore, $\mathbb{P}(A) = 0$. By a symmetric argument one rules out $\mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}] < M_{u-1}$ on any set of positive probability. It follows that

$$\mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}] = M_{u-1} \quad \text{a.s.,}$$

for each $u = 1, \dots, T$. Therefore M is a martingale. \square

Recall from earlier binomial-model discussions that this criterion also matches our observation that a zero-cost strategy's expected discounted gain must be zero under the corresponding martingale measure. The argument here shows how that insight extends beyond the binomial setup, to any finite sample space.

Application: $S^{*,i}$ Is a \mathbb{Q} -Martingale

We now apply the Martingale Criterion to each component $S_t^{*,i}$ of the discounted price process under the measure \mathbb{Q} constructed above.

Goal. For a fixed $i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$, show

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[S_t^{*,i} | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = S_{t-1}^{*,i} \quad \text{for each } t = 1, \dots, T.$$

Equivalently, show

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}} \left[\sum_{t=1}^T \eta_t (S_t^{*,i} - S_{t-1}^{*,i}) \right] = 0 \quad \text{for every predictable } (\eta_1, \dots, \eta_T).$$

Strategy. Given a predictable sequence $\eta = (\eta_1, \dots, \eta_T)$, we will construct a self-financing trading strategy φ with zero initial capital whose discounted terminal payoff equals

$$\sum_{t=1}^T \eta_t (S_t^{*,i} - S_{t-1}^{*,i}).$$

Then,

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}} \left[\sum_{t=1}^T \eta_t (S_t^{*,i} - S_{t-1}^{*,i}) \right] = \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}} [V_T^{*,i}(\varphi)] = 0 \quad (\text{because } V_T^{*,i}(\varphi) \in L).$$

This precisely matches the condition of the Martingale Criterion, implying $S_t^{*,i}$ is a \mathbb{Q} -martingale.

Construction of φ . Let the market have d risky assets (besides the money market account). Denote

$$\varphi_t = (\varphi_t^0, \varphi_t^1, \dots, \varphi_t^d),$$

where φ_t^j is the number of units of asset j held over $[t-1, t)$. We want

$$V_T^{*,i}(\varphi) = \sum_{t=1}^T \eta_t (S_t^{*,i} - S_{t-1}^{*,i}).$$

1. **Set all but one asset position to zero.** For all $t = 1, \dots, T$ and all $j \neq i$, define $\varphi_t^j = 0$. We only allow trading in asset i and in the money market account (asset 0).
2. **Hold η_t units of asset i .** Set $\varphi_t^i = \eta_t$ for $t = 1, \dots, T$. By hypothesis, each η_t is \mathcal{F}_{t-1} -measurable, ensuring φ is predictable.
3. **Choose φ_t^0 to enforce self-financing and zero initial capital.** Recall the discounted value:

$$V_t^{*,i}(\varphi) = \varphi_t^0 + \sum_{j=1}^d \varphi_t^j S_t^{*,j},$$

and self-financing means

$$V_t^{*,i}(\varphi) - V_{t-1}^{*,i}(\varphi) = \varphi_{t-1}^0 (S_t^{0,*} - S_{t-1}^{0,*}) + \sum_{j=1}^d \varphi_{t-1}^j (S_t^{*,j} - S_{t-1}^{*,j}).$$

By selecting φ_0^0 (the initial money market holding) suitably, we can ensure $V_0(\varphi) = 0$. Then define φ_t^0 iteratively to maintain the self-financing identity at each step. (See Lemma 3.2.5 in many texts for details of the “bookkeeping”.)

To see the recursion in action, compute the first two steps when only asset i is traded.

$$\text{At } t = 0: \quad 0 = V_0(\varphi) = \varphi_0^0 + \eta_1 S_0^{*,i} \implies \boxed{\varphi_0^0 = -\eta_1 S_0^{*,i}}.$$

$$\text{Self-financing on } [0, 1): \quad \varphi_1^0 + \eta_1 S_1^{*,i} = \varphi_0^0 + \eta_1 S_0^{*,i} = 0 \implies \boxed{\varphi_1^0 = -\eta_1 S_1^{*,i}}.$$

Iterating the same calculation shows

$$\boxed{\varphi_t^0 = -\sum_{u=1}^t \eta_u (S_u^{*,i} - S_{u-1}^{*,i})}, \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T,$$

which is exactly the money-market recursion stated abstractly in Lemma 3.2.5 and ensures that φ is self-financing while keeping $V_0(\varphi) = 0$. Concretely, one can check that the discounted terminal value is:

$$V_T^{*,i}(\varphi) = \sum_{t=1}^T \eta_t (S_t^{*,i} - S_{t-1}^{*,i}).$$

Note that in many treatments, the discounted money market account (bond) is identically 1, so its increments vanish in the summation, ensuring that only the changes in the risky asset prices contribute to the discounted gains.

So φ is a sfts with $V_0(\varphi) = 0$ whose terminal payoff matches the left side of the martingale criterion. Because $V_T^{*,i}(\varphi) \in L$, we have

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[V_T^{*,i}(\varphi)] = 0.$$

Therefore

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}\left[\sum_{t=1}^T \eta_t (S_t^{*,i} - S_{t-1}^{*,i})\right] = 0,$$

and the Martingale Criterion implies $S_t^{*,i}$ is a \mathbb{Q} -martingale. Repeating the same argument for each $i = 1, \dots, d$ shows that $(S_t^{*,1}, \dots, S_t^{*,d})$ is a vector martingale under \mathbb{Q} . In summary, this establishes the existence of an Equivalent Martingale Measure, which is the key statement of the First Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing in a finite market model. In later sections, we will see that if this EMM is unique, then the market is said to be complete, which is the essence of the Second Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing.

Preview: Pricing a European Contingent Claim

Let $X \in \mathcal{F}_T$ be a European Contingent Claim (ECC), payable at time T . Under the viability assumption, there exists an EMM \mathbb{P}^* . Suppose φ is any self-financing trading strategy replicating X , i.e. $V_T(\varphi) = X$. Then, using discounted values under the measure \mathbb{P}^* ,

$$V_t(\varphi) = \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{P}^*}\left[X \mid \mathcal{F}_t\right] \frac{S_t^{0,*}}{S_0^{0,*}}, \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T.$$

(Here $S_t^{0,*}$ is the *discounted* money market account or numéraire.) Observe that:

- $V_t(\varphi)$ depends on φ but not on the particular choice of \mathbb{P}^* .
- $\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{P}^*}[X \mid \mathcal{F}_t]$ depends on \mathbb{P}^* but not on φ .

This formula is central to risk-neutral pricing: the time- t *fair price* of the claim X is given by the martingale property under \mathbb{P}^* .

Observe the interesting tension: to compute $\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{P}^*}[X]$, we must know \mathbb{P}^* , but constructing a hedging strategy that replicates X does not require \mathbb{P}^* . This reflects the fundamental relationship between market viability, the absence of arbitrage, and the equivalence of \mathbb{P}^* to the original measure.

Summary. We have shown that if the market is viable, then there exists an Equivalent Martingale Measure \mathbb{Q} such that $(S_t^{*,1}, \dots, S_t^{*,d})$ is a \mathbb{Q} -martingale. This sets the foundation for arbitrage-free pricing of European claims and, more generally, the Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing in discrete-time settings.

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Arbitrage-free price interval in incomplete markets. For a non-replicable claim X let

$$V_-(X) = \inf_{Q \in \mathcal{M}} \frac{\mathbb{E}^Q[X^*]}{S_0^{0,*}}, \quad V_+(X) = \sup_{Q \in \mathcal{M}} \frac{\mathbb{E}^Q[X^*]}{S_0^{0,*}}.$$

Then $0 < V_-(X) < V_+(X)$; any initial price in (V_-, V_+) is free of arbitrage but leaves residual risk.

Selecting a price within the band. A concrete quote requires preferences—e.g. expected-utility maximisation (Davis 1997) or indifference pricing.

Exercise (multi-period CRR viability). Assume $u > d > 0$. Show the multi-period CRR model is viable iff $d < 1 + r < u$ and is then complete.

Lemma. If Q is an equivalent martingale measure and ϕ any trading strategy, the discounted value process $V_t^*(\phi)$ is a Q -martingale.

Theorem (First Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing). A finite-state market model is viable iff there exists an equivalent martingale measure.

Separating Hyperplane Theorem (3.6.1). Let $F \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be non-empty, compact, and convex, and let $L \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a non-empty linear subspace with $F \cap L = \emptyset$. Then there exists a non-zero vector $z \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that the hyperplane $H := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : x \cdot z = 0\}$ contains L while $x \cdot z > 0$ for every $x \in F$.

Geometrically, H “supports” the convex body F and is *parallel* to L ; the normal z is strictly positive on F and will serve as the density for an equivalent martingale measure.

Lemma 3.2.5 (constructing the money-market position).

Fix predictable holdings in the d risky assets, $\hat{\varphi}_t^i \in \mathcal{F}_{t-1}$ for $t = 1, \dots, T$ and $i = 1, \dots, d$, and an \mathcal{F}_0 -measurable initial wealth V_0 . There exists a *unique* predictable sequence of money-market positions $\varphi_t^0 \in \mathcal{F}_{t-1}$ such that the trading strategy

$$\varphi_t = (\varphi_t^0, \hat{\varphi}_t^1, \dots, \hat{\varphi}_t^d), \quad t = 1, \dots, T,$$

is self-financing and satisfies $V_0(\varphi) = V_0$. Explicitly, one may solve recursively

$$\varphi_{t+1}^0 = \frac{1}{S_t^0} \left(\varphi_t \cdot S_t - \sum_{i=1}^d \hat{\varphi}_{t+1}^i S_t^i \right), \quad t = 0, \dots, T-1.$$

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Martingale Criterion

We used this criterion previously to verify that a certain candidate process was indeed a martingale measure. The direction we needed was “If the expectation of $\sum_{t=1}^T \eta_t(M_t - M_{t-1})$ is zero for every predictable sequence (η_1, \dots, η_T) , then M is a martingale.”

Here is a way to check if an adapted sequence of random variables,

$$M = (M_0, M_1, \dots, M_T),$$

is a martingale (with respect to a filtration $(\mathcal{F}_t)_{t=0}^T$ and a probability measure \mathbb{P}). The criterion is general, so it is phrased in terms of an arbitrary probability \mathbb{P} .

Definition (Predictable Sequence). We say that a sequence of random variables

$$(\eta_1, \eta_2, \dots, \eta_T)$$

is *predictable* provided

$$\eta_t \in \mathcal{F}_{t-1} \quad \text{for each } t = 1, 2, \dots, T.$$

Equivalently, η_t is measurable with respect to the σ -algebra that is known ‘just before time t .’

Criterion Statement

Claim. Let $M = (M_0, M_1, \dots, M_T)$ be an adapted sequence such that

$$\mathbb{E}\left(\sum_{t=1}^T \eta_t (M_t - M_{t-1})\right) = 0 \quad \text{for all predictable sequences } (\eta_1, \dots, \eta_T).$$

Then M is a martingale, i.e.,

$$\mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}] = M_{u-1} \quad \text{for all } u = 1, 2, \dots, T.$$

Remark. The converse direction (i.e. if M is a martingale, then the above expectation is zero for all predictable sequences) is also true, and is left as a good exercise in manipulating conditional expectations. You would write $\mathbb{E}(\sum_{t=1}^T \eta_t (M_t - M_{t-1}))$ as a sum of expectations, and then use the martingale property on each term.

Proof. We want to show that for each $u \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}$,

$$\mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}] = M_{u-1}.$$

Fix u , and define the event

$$A := \left\{ \mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}] > M_{u-1} \right\}.$$

Note that $A \in \mathcal{F}_{u-1}$ because both M_{u-1} and $\mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}]$ are \mathcal{F}_{u-1} -measurable.

Next, define a predictable sequence (η_1, \dots, η_T) by

$$\eta_t := \begin{cases} \mathbf{1}_A, & t = u, \\ 0, & t \neq u. \end{cases}$$

Each η_t is indeed in \mathcal{F}_{t-1} ; in particular, $\eta_u = \mathbf{1}_A$ is in \mathcal{F}_{u-1} since $A \in \mathcal{F}_{u-1}$, and for $t \neq u$, $\eta_t = 0$ is trivially \mathcal{F}_{t-1} -measurable.

Then

$$\sum_{t=1}^T \eta_t (M_t - M_{t-1}) = \mathbf{1}_A (M_u - M_{u-1}).$$

By the hypothesis of the martingale criterion,

$$0 = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{1}_A (M_u - M_{u-1})].$$

We can rewrite this as

$$0 = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{1}_A M_u] - \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{1}_A M_{u-1}] = \mathbb{E}(\mathbf{1}_A (M_u - M_{u-1})).$$

Next, we use the tower property and the fact that $\mathbf{1}_A$ is \mathcal{F}_{u-1} -measurable:

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{1}_A M_u] = \mathbb{E}(\mathbf{1}_A \mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}]) = \mathbb{E}(\mathbf{1}_A (\mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}] - M_{u-1})) + \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{1}_A M_{u-1}].$$

Therefore,

$$0 = \mathbb{E}(\mathbf{1}_A (\mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}] - M_{u-1})) = \mathbb{E}(\mathbf{1}_A \underbrace{(\mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}] - M_{u-1})}_{\text{positive on } A}).$$

On the event A , we have

$$\mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}] - M_{u-1} > 0.$$

So

$$\mathbf{1}_A (\mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}] - M_{u-1}) \geq 0,$$

and it is strictly positive on A unless $\mathbb{P}(A) = 0$. The expectation of this nonnegative random variable is zero, which forces

$$\mathbb{P}(A) = 0.$$

By the same argument,

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}] < M_{u-1}) = 0$$

as well. Therefore

$$\mathbb{E}[M_u | \mathcal{F}_{u-1}] = M_{u-1} \quad \text{a.s.},$$

which completes the proof for each u . So M is indeed a martingale. \square

Self-Financing Strategies

In a financial market model, a trading strategy is a way of holding positions in various assets over time. Denote by ϕ_t^i the position in asset i at time t . Here is how to choose ϕ_t^0 (the position in the money-market account or numéraire) so that $\phi = (\phi_t)_{t=0}^T$ is *self-financing*.

Definition (Self-Financing). A trading strategy ϕ is *self-financing* if no additional money is injected or withdrawn from the portfolio; mathematically:

$$V_t(\phi) = \phi_t^0 + \sum_{i=1}^d \phi_t^i S_t^{i,*} \implies V_t(\phi) = V_{t+1}(\phi) \quad \text{when discounted by } S^{0,*}.$$

Equivalently,

$$\phi_t^0 + \phi_t^1 S_t^{1,*} = \phi_{t+1}^0 + \phi_{t+1}^1 S_{t+1}^{1,*} \quad \text{for each } t.$$

We illustrate with one risky asset for simplicity.

Constructing a Self-Financing Strategy

We consider a single risky asset S^1 and its discounted price process $S^{1,*}$. We also have the discounted money-market account $S^{0,*}$. Suppose we want a self-financing strategy ϕ that starts with zero initial investment, i.e. $V_0(\phi) = 0$. We must have

$$V_0(\phi) = \phi_0^\circ + \phi_1^{1,*} S_0^{1,*} = 0 \implies \phi_1^\circ := -\phi_1^{1,*} S_0^{1,*} \in \mathcal{F}_0.$$

Then for each $t = 1, 2, \dots, T-1$, self-financing requires

$$\phi_t^\circ + \phi_t^1 S_t^{1,*} = \phi_{t+1}^\circ + \phi_{t+1}^1 S_{t+1}^{1,*}.$$

Solving recursively for ϕ_{t+1}° in terms of ϕ_t° and ϕ_t^1 yields:

$$\phi_{t+1}^\circ = \phi_t^\circ + \phi_t^1 S_t^{1,*} - \phi_{t+1}^1 S_{t+1}^{1,*}.$$

In particular, for $t = 1$:

$$\phi_2^\circ = \phi_1^\circ + \phi_1^1 S_1^{1,*} - \phi_2^1 S_2^{1,*} = -\phi_1^1 S_0^{1,*} + \phi_1^1 S_1^{1,*} - \phi_2^1 S_2^{1,*} \in \mathcal{F}_1,$$

and so on for times $t = 2, 3, \dots$. This ensures no external cash flow is introduced (or removed) from the strategy at any time.

Pricing

Let $X \in \mathcal{G}_T$ be a European contingent claim (ECC) paying off at time T . Assume the market is *viable*, so there exists at least one *equivalent martingale measure* (EMM), call it \mathbb{P}^* . Then if ϕ is a self-financing trading strategy with $V_T(\phi) = X$, we have the fundamental pricing relation:

$$V_t(\phi) = \mathbb{E}^*(X \mid \mathcal{G}_t) \frac{S_t^{0,*}}{S_0^{0,*}} \quad (\star)$$

where $S_t^{0,*}$ is the discounted money-market account (or numéraire).

Key Observation: $V_t(\phi)$ depends on the strategy ϕ , but not on the particular choice of EMM \mathbb{P}^* (once a strategy is fixed), while $\mathbb{E}^*[X \mid \mathcal{G}_t]$ does depend on \mathbb{P}^* but not on the strategy ϕ .

Definitions

- **Attainable (Hedgeable) Claim.** An ECC $X \in \mathcal{G}_T$ is *attainable* if there is a self-financing strategy ϕ such that $V_T(\phi) = X$ almost surely.
- **Complete Market.** We say the market is *complete* if every ECC X is attainable.

Second Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing

Although we are introducing the second fundamental theorem here, it will not be part of the upcoming midterm. Instead, we will consider it for the final exam.

Theorem 1. *Assuming viability (i.e., the existence of at least one EMM), the market is complete if and only if the EMM is unique (i.e., there is exactly one EMM).*

Proof of the ‘ \Rightarrow ’ direction. Assume the market is complete, so every ECC is attainable by some self-financing strategy. Suppose there were two distinct EMMs, \mathbb{P}^* and \mathbb{P}^{**} . Fix any event $A \in \mathcal{G}_T$ and consider the payoff $X = \mathbf{1}_A$. By completeness, there is a self-financing trading strategy ϕ whose terminal value $V_T(\phi) = \mathbf{1}_A$. Then, under any EMM \mathbb{Q} , the discounted price must match its initial cost:

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[X] = V_0(\phi) \frac{S_0^0}{S_0^{0,*}} \quad (\text{since } S_0^0 = 1 \text{ if normalized, etc.}).$$

In particular,

$$\mathbb{P}^*(A) = \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{P}^*}[\mathbf{1}_A] = V_0(\phi) \frac{S_0^0}{S_0^{0,*}} = \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{P}^{**}}[\mathbf{1}_A] = \mathbb{P}^{**}(A).$$

Since this holds for every $A \in \mathcal{G}_T$, we conclude $\mathbb{P}^* = \mathbb{P}^{**}$, contradicting the assumption that they are distinct. Therefore there can be only one EMM.

Proof of the ‘ \Leftarrow ’ direction (Sketch). We prove the contrapositive: if the market is not complete, then there are *at least two* distinct EMMs. The idea is that if not all claims are attainable, then the set of possible discounted terminal values

$$L = \{V_T^*(\phi) \mid \phi \text{ is a self-financing strategy}\} \subsetneq \mathbb{R}^n$$

is a proper subspace (in a suitable sense), so there exists a payoff Z orthogonal to L (in an appropriate separating hyperplane sense). One can perturb the original EMM by Z to create a second EMM, giving non-uniqueness.

Remark. In fact, if there are two distinct EMMs, there are infinitely many. Indeed, given \mathbb{Q}_1 and \mathbb{Q}_2 that are both equivalent martingale measures, any convex combination

$$\alpha \mathbb{Q}_1 + (1 - \alpha) \mathbb{Q}_2 \quad \text{for } 0 < \alpha < 1$$

is also an EMM (one checks it still assigns positive probability to every event and preserves the martingale property). This is another way to see non-uniqueness can occur in a big way.

Illustrative Example in a 1-Period Market

Example 1. Take $T = 1$ and $\Omega = \{1, 2, 3\}$. Let:

$$S_0^0 = S_0^{0,*} = 1, \quad S_0^1 = 1,$$

and define the (undiscounted) terminal values

$$\begin{array}{c|ccc} \Omega & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ \hline S_1^1(\omega) & \frac{1}{2} & 1 & 2 \end{array}$$

Let \mathbb{Q} be any probability on Ω , assigning probabilities $a, b, c > 0$ with $a + b + c = 1$.

Condition for an EMM. Under \mathbb{Q} to be a martingale measure, we need:

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[S_1^1] = S_0^1 = 1.$$

Explicitly,

$$a \cdot \frac{1}{2} + b \cdot 1 + c \cdot 2 = 1.$$

Along with $a + b + c = 1$, subtracting these two equations gives

$$(a \cdot \frac{1}{2} + b + 2c) - (a + b + c) = 1 - 1 = 0 \implies \frac{a}{2} - c = 0 \implies a = 2c.$$

Therefore for each choice of $c \in (0, \frac{1}{3})$, we get a valid EMM by setting $a = 2c$ and $b = 1 - 3c$. Denoting this measure by \mathbb{Q}^c , we have

$$\begin{array}{c|ccc} \Omega & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ \hline \mathbb{Q}^c(\{\omega\}) & 2c & 1 - 3c & c \end{array}$$

So we see a whole family of EMMs, demonstrating *non-uniqueness* of the martingale measure.

*An Unattainable Claim Consider the payoff

$$\frac{\Omega}{X(\omega)} \begin{array}{c|ccc} & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ \hline & 1 & 4 & 9 \end{array}$$

so explicitly,

$$\frac{\omega}{X(\omega)} \begin{array}{c|ccc} & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ \hline & 1 & 4 & 9 \end{array}$$

If X were attainable, there would exist a self-financing trading strategy $\phi = (\phi_1^0, \phi_1^1)$ such that

$$X(\omega) = \phi_1^0 + \phi_1^1 S_1^1(\omega) \quad \text{for each } \omega \in \{1, 2, 3\}.$$

In vector form, we want

$$\begin{pmatrix} \phi_1^0 + \frac{1}{2}\phi_1^1 \\ \phi_1^0 + 1\phi_1^1 \\ \phi_1^0 + 2\phi_1^1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 4 \\ 9 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Denote $\beta := \phi_1^0$ and $\alpha := \phi_1^1$ for convenience. Then the system is

$$\beta + \frac{1}{2}\alpha = 1, \quad \beta + \alpha = 4, \quad \beta + 2\alpha = 9.$$

A quick way to see no solution is possible: subtract the first equation from the third to eliminate β , solve for α , and then check consistency with the second equation. You will find a contradiction. More precisely, the third and first equations give $\alpha = 16/3$, then from the first equation $\beta = -5/3$, but these numbers do not satisfy the second equation. Therefore the system is inconsistent. So there is no solution, so X is not hedgeable; hence the market is not complete, and indeed we see multiple EMMs exist.

Plan for the General Proof.

- Identify the subspace

$$L = \{V_T^*(\phi) \mid \phi \text{ is a self-financing strategy}\}.$$

If the market is not complete, then there exists a claim $X \notin L$ (i.e., X is not attainable).

- By a separating hyperplane argument (or a Hahn–Banach type theorem in a suitable dual pairing), there is a ‘direction’ Z orthogonal to L .
- Start from one EMM \mathbb{P}^* , use Z to construct another measure $\mathbb{P}^{**} \neq \mathbb{P}^*$, showing EMM is not unique.

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Short Positions. A negative value for a holding, $\phi_t^i < 0$, indicates a *short position* in asset i ; one borrows the asset at $t-1$ and later returns it, absorbing the cost of its price at t .

Exercise (CRR model viability and completeness).

Consider the T -period Cox–Ross–Rubinstein binomial model with up-factor u and down-factor d ($u > d > 0$). Show that the market is viable iff $d < 1+r < u$, where r is the (per-period) risk-free rate. In this parameter range, prove that the model is also *complete*; i.e., every contingent claim can be replicated.

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§3.3

Recall

Definitions

- A random variable (or payoff) $X \in \mathcal{F}_T$ is called *attainable* (or *hedgeable*) if there is a self-financing trading strategy (s.f.t.s.) $\varphi = (\varphi_t)_{t=0}^T$ such that

$$V_T(\varphi) = X,$$

where $V_t(\varphi)$ denotes the value of the trading strategy φ at time t .

- The market is said to be *complete* if every European contingent claim (ECC) X (i.e. every \mathcal{F}_T -measurable random variable) is attainable.
- A market is *viable* if there exists at least one *Equivalent Martingale Measure* (EMM). Viability rules out arbitrage opportunities and supplies at least one risk-neutral probability under which discounted asset prices are martingales.
- An *Equivalent Martingale Measure* Q is a probability measure satisfying
 - (a) $Q \sim \mathbb{P}$ (equivalence with respect to the physical measure), and
 - (b) every discounted asset price process $S^{i,*}$ is a Q -martingale.

Theorem (Second Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing (SFTAP))

Assuming viability (i.e. no arbitrage and the existence of at least one Equivalent Martingale Measure), the market is complete if and only if the EMM is unique. Formally:

$$\boxed{\text{Market is complete} \iff \text{The EMM is unique.}}$$

Key fact. For an equivalent martingale measure Q and any self-financing trading strategy φ ,

$$\mathbb{E}^Q(V_T^*(\varphi) \mid \mathcal{F}_t) = V_t^*(\varphi) = \frac{S_t^{0,T}}{S_t^0}, \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T.$$

Here $V_t^*(\varphi)$ is the discounted value of the strategy φ at time t , and $S_t^{0,T}/S_t^0$ is the discounted value of $S_t^{0,T}$ (the zero-coupon bond paying \$1 at T).

Proof of SFTAP. We will prove the two implications separately.

(1) “Completeness \implies EMM uniqueness.”

Let \mathbb{P}^* and \mathbb{P}^{**} be two equivalent martingale measures. We want to show $\mathbb{P}^* = \mathbb{P}^{**}$, i.e. they coincide on every event $A \in \mathcal{F}_T$.

Step 1. Fix $A \in \mathcal{F}_T$ and set $X := \mathbf{1}_A$ (the indicator function of A).

Step 2. By completeness, there exists a self-financing trading strategy φ such that

$$V_T^*(\varphi) = X.$$

(Here $V_T^*(\varphi)$ again denotes the *discounted* terminal value of φ .)

Step 3. Taking expectation under \mathbb{P}^* , we recall that for an EMM \mathbb{P}^* ,

$$\mathbb{E}^*(V_T^*(\varphi)) = V_0^*(\varphi).$$

But $V_0^*(\varphi) = \frac{V_0(\varphi)}{S_0^0}$ (the initially discounted cost of the strategy), and $V_0(\varphi) \cdot \frac{S_0^{0,T}}{S_0^0}$ is often the cost to set up the strategy that pays X . In simpler terms,

$$\mathbb{E}^*(X) = \mathbb{E}^*(V_T^*(\varphi)) = V_0^*(\varphi).$$

But since $X = \mathbf{1}_A$, we have

$$\mathbb{E}^*(X) = \mathbb{E}^*(\mathbf{1}_A) = \mathbb{P}^*(A).$$

Therefore

$$\mathbb{P}^*(A) = V_0^*(\varphi).$$

Step 4. The same reasoning under \mathbb{P}^{**} yields

$$\mathbb{P}^{**}(A) = \mathbb{E}^{**}(\mathbf{1}_A) = \mathbb{E}^{**}(V_T^*(\varphi)) = V_0^*(\varphi).$$

So

$$\mathbb{P}^*(A) = \mathbb{P}^{**}(A), \quad \forall A \in \mathcal{F}_T.$$

Since they agree on all events in \mathcal{F}_T , we conclude that $\mathbb{P}^* = \mathbb{P}^{**}$. Therefore the EMM is unique.

(2) “EMM uniqueness \implies completeness.”

We will prove the contrapositive statement:

$$\boxed{\text{(not complete)} \implies \text{(EMM not unique)}}.$$

So, assume the market is *incomplete*. We show that there are *at least two different* equivalent martingale measures.

Step 1: Subspace of attainable payoffs.

Define the set

$$L := \{V_T^*(\varphi) \mid \varphi \text{ is an s.f.t.s.}\} \subset \mathbb{R}^n.$$

Here, we are labeling the possible states at time T by $\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_n$ for simplicity; so each $V_T^*(\varphi)$ is an n -dimensional vector in \mathbb{R}^n whose k -th component is $V_T^*(\varphi)(\omega_k)$.

Since L is closed under sums and scalar multiplication (adding strategies corresponds to adding payoffs, scaling a strategy by a scalar scales the payoff), L is a *vector subspace* of \mathbb{R}^n .

Incompleteness means there exists a payoff (random variable) that cannot be represented by any self-financing trading strategy. In vector-subspace language:

$$\text{incomplete} \iff L \neq \mathbb{R}^n \implies \dim(L) < n.$$

Step 2: Existence of a non-zero orthogonal vector.

Since L is a *proper* subspace of \mathbb{R}^n , its orthogonal complement is non-trivial. That is, there exists a non-zero vector

$$Z \in \mathbb{R}^n, \quad Z \neq 0,$$

such that

$$Z \cdot \ell = 0 \quad \forall \ell \in L.$$

In particular, for every s.f.t.s. φ we have $V_T^*(\varphi) \in L$, therefore

$$Z \cdot V_T^*(\varphi) = 0, \quad \forall \varphi.$$

Step 3: Using an existing EMM to construct a new one.

By viability (no arbitrage), there exists at least one EMM, call it \mathbb{P}^* . Our goal is to show that Z helps us “perturb” \mathbb{P}^* to form *another* EMM, say \mathbb{P}^{**} , which must be different if $Z \neq 0$.

3.1. A bond-only strategy. First consider the trivial trading strategy φ that invests everything in the risk-free bond S^0 and nothing in the risky assets S^1, \dots, S^d . Formally:

$$\varphi_t^0 = 1, \quad \varphi_t^i = 0 \quad (i = 1, \dots, d), \quad t = 1, \dots, T.$$

Then $V_T^*(\varphi)$ is purely the discounted payoff of 1 unit of the bond. This is clearly in L , therefore

$$Z \cdot V_T^*(\varphi) = 0.$$

But $V_T^*(\varphi)$ has the form $(1, 1, \dots, 1)$ (the same in all n states), so

$$Z \cdot (1, 1, \dots, 1) = \sum_{k=1}^n Z_k = 0.$$

So

$$\sum_{k=1}^n Z_k = 0.$$

Since $Z \neq 0$, this also tells us that not all Z_k are zero, but their sum is zero. Because the sum is zero while $Z \neq 0$, at least one Z_k must be *positive* and another *negative*; this sign structure will force the small- c restriction below.

3.2. Defining a perturbed probability.

Recall $\mathbb{P}^*(\omega_k) > 0$ for all k (because it is an equivalent measure). Define a new set of probabilities $\{\mathbb{P}^{**}(\omega_k)\}$ by:

$$\mathbb{P}^{**}(\omega_k) = \mathbb{P}^*(\omega_k) + c Z_k, \quad k = 1, \dots, n,$$

where $c > 0$ is chosen suitably small so that $\mathbb{P}^{**}(\omega_k)$ remains positive for all k .

3.3. Ensuring positivity and normalization.

Since $\sum_k Z_k = 0$ (from Step 3.1) and $Z \neq 0$, there is at least one k for which $Z_k < 0$. To ensure $\mathbb{P}^{**}(\omega_k) > 0$, we need

$$\mathbb{P}^*(\omega_k) + c Z_k > 0 \quad \iff \quad \mathbb{P}^*(\omega_k) > -c Z_k = c |Z_k|.$$

Therefore it suffices to choose c such that

$$c < \min_{1 \leq k \leq n} \frac{\mathbb{P}^*(\omega_k)}{|Z_k|} \quad (\text{for those } Z_k \neq 0).$$

Equivalently, we can make a more explicit choice:

$$c = \frac{1}{2 \max_k (|Z_k|/\mathbb{P}^*(\omega_k))}.$$

Then for every k ,

$$\mathbb{P}^*(\omega_k) > 2(c|Z_k|) \implies \mathbb{P}^*(\omega_k) - c|Z_k| > c|Z_k|.$$

So $\mathbb{P}^{**}(\omega_k) = \mathbb{P}^*(\omega_k) + cZ_k$ is positive.

Moreover,

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \mathbb{P}^{**}(\omega_k) = \sum_{k=1}^n (\mathbb{P}^*(\omega_k) + cZ_k) = \sum_{k=1}^n \mathbb{P}^*(\omega_k) + c \sum_{k=1}^n Z_k = 1 + c \cdot 0 = 1.$$

Therefore \mathbb{P}^{**} is indeed a probability measure. Furthermore, since $\mathbb{P}^{**}(\omega_k) > 0$ for each k (as shown), \mathbb{P}^{**} is equivalent to \mathbb{P}^* .

3.4. Verifying that \mathbb{P}^{**} is an EMM.

By definition of EMM, we need, for any self-financing strategy φ ,

$$\mathbb{E}^{**}(V_T^*(\varphi)) = V_0^*(\varphi).$$

Recall $V_0^*(\varphi)$ is just the discounted initial cost of φ , i.e. $\mathbb{E}^*(V_T^*(\varphi))$. We check:

$$\mathbb{E}^{**}(V_T^*(\varphi)) = \sum_{k=1}^n \mathbb{P}^{**}(\omega_k) V_T^*(\varphi)(\omega_k) = \sum_{k=1}^n [\mathbb{P}^*(\omega_k) + cZ_k] V_T^*(\varphi)(\omega_k).$$

Distribute:

$$= \sum_{k=1}^n \mathbb{P}^*(\omega_k) V_T^*(\varphi)(\omega_k) + c \sum_{k=1}^n Z_k V_T^*(\varphi)(\omega_k).$$

By definition of an EMM, under \mathbb{P}^* we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \mathbb{P}^*(\omega_k) V_T^*(\varphi)(\omega_k) = \mathbb{E}^*(V_T^*(\varphi)) = V_0^*(\varphi).$$

Meanwhile,

$$\sum_{k=1}^n Z_k V_T^*(\varphi)(\omega_k) = Z \cdot V_T^*(\varphi) = 0,$$

because $V_T^*(\varphi) \in L$ and Z is orthogonal to L . Therefore

$$\mathbb{E}^{**}(V_T^*(\varphi)) = V_0^*(\varphi) + c \cdot 0 = V_0^*(\varphi).$$

Therefore, \mathbb{P}^{**} is also an EMM.

Since $\mathbb{P}^{**} \neq \mathbb{P}^*$ (they differ by $c Z_k$ in at least one state), we have shown that *incompleteness* allows for *non-uniqueness* of the EMM. This completes the contrapositive argument.

Consequences of the Second Fundamental Theorem.

As a direct corollary of the SFTAP, we obtain the *Martingale Representation Theorem* in our discrete setting:

Corollary 1 (Martingale Representation Theorem). In a viable market, the market is complete if and only if **every** martingale $\{M_t\}_{t=0}^T$ (under the EMM) can be represented as

$$M_t = M_0 + \sum_{u=1}^t \vartheta_u (S_u^* - S_{u-1}^*), \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T,$$

for some predictable process $\{\vartheta_u\}_{u=1}^T$ with $\vartheta_u \in \mathcal{F}_{u-1}$.

Remark 1 (Predictability). A sequence $(\vartheta_u)_{u=1}^T$ is *predictable* if each ϑ_u is known at time $u - 1$; formally ϑ_u is \mathcal{F}_{u-1} -measurable. In economic terms, ϑ_u is the *portfolio chosen* before *observing the time- u price move*.

Sketch of reasoning: If the market is complete, any martingale increment can be perfectly replicated by some strategy in S^* . Conversely, if every martingale has such a linear representation, any contingent claim can be decomposed into increments of S^* , implying completeness.

Theorem (Pricing Theorem in a Complete Market)

In a complete, viable market, the time- t price of a contingent claim X is given by

$$\pi_t(X) = \mathbb{E}^*[X \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \cdot \frac{S_t^0}{S_0^0}, \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T.$$

Here \mathbb{E}^* denotes expectation under the (unique) EMM \mathbb{P}^* .

Reasoning. Since the market is complete, X is attainable by some self-financing strategy φ . By the martingale property of discounted payoffs,

$$\mathbb{E}^*(V_T^*(\varphi) \mid \mathcal{F}_t) = V_t^*(\varphi).$$

But $V_T^*(\varphi) = X/S_T^0$ (i.e. the discounted version of the claim). So

$$\mathbb{E}^*(X/S_T^0 \mid \mathcal{F}_t) = V_t^*(\varphi) = \frac{V_t(\varphi)}{S_t^0}.$$

Therefore

$$V_t(\varphi) = \mathbb{E}^*(X/S_T^0 \mid \mathcal{F}_t) \cdot S_t^0 = \mathbb{E}^*(X \mid \mathcal{F}_t) \frac{S_t^0}{S_0^0},$$

since scaling by $1/S_T^0$ inside the expectation is the same as dividing each outcome of X by the bond's payoff. Therefore the arbitrage-free cost of the claim at time t (its *unique* price) is $\pi_t(X) = V_t(\varphi) = \mathbb{E}^*(X \mid \mathcal{F}_t) S_t^0/S_0^0$.

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Definition 1 (European Contingent Claim). A *European contingent claim (ECC)* is an \mathcal{F}_T -measurable random variable X interpreted as the payoff delivered at the terminal date T . Its *discounted payoff* is $X^* = X/S_T^0$, where S^0 is the money-market (bond) account.

Definition 2 (Replicating (Hedging) Strategy). A self-financing trading strategy φ *replicates* (or *hedges*) an ECC X if its terminal value satisfies $V_T(\varphi) = X$. Whenever such a strategy exists, the claim is said to be *attainable*.

Lemma 1 (Characterisation of Martingales). Let $M = \{M_t\}_{t=0}^T$ be a real-valued process with $M_t \in \mathcal{F}_t$. Then M is a martingale relative to $\{\mathcal{F}_t\}$ if and only if

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{t=1}^T \eta_t \Delta M_t \right] = 0, \quad \text{for every predictable sequence } \eta_t \in \mathcal{F}_{t-1},$$

where $\Delta M_t := M_t - M_{t-1}$. The sum $\sum_{t=1}^T \eta_t \Delta M_t$ is the discrete stochastic integral of η with respect to M .

Theorem 1 (Uniqueness of the Value Process). In a viable finite market, let X be an attainable ECC and φ any replicating strategy. Then the (discounted) value process is

$$V_t^*(\varphi) = \mathbb{E}^Q[X^* \mid \mathcal{F}_t], \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T,$$

for *every* equivalent martingale measure Q . Therefore the price path $\{V_t(\varphi)\}$ is unique independent of the particular replicating strategy and of the chosen Q .

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§3.4

Market Model

Let the finite filtered probability space be

$$(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, (\mathcal{F}_t)_{t=0}^T, \mathbb{P}), \quad 0 \leq t \leq T < \infty,$$

and suppose there are $d+1$ primary assets S^0, S^1, \dots, S^d , where S^0 is the risk-free numéraire (bond).

European Contingent Claim (ECC). Fix a terminal payoff $X \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{F}_T)$; denote its market price process by $C = (C_t)_{t=0}^T$ with the convention $C_T = X$.

Trading Strategy. A self-financing strategy in the expanded market (i.e. primary assets + the claim) is

$$\psi = \{(\phi_t, \gamma_t) : t = 1, \dots, T\},$$

where $\phi_t = (\phi_t^0, \phi_t^1, \dots, \phi_t^d)$ and γ_t are \mathcal{F}_{t-1} -measurable (decisions taken at $t-1$).

$$\begin{aligned} V_0(\psi) &:= \phi_1 \cdot S_0 + \gamma_1 C_0, \\ V_t(\psi) &:= \phi_t \cdot S_t + \gamma_t C_t, \quad 1 \leq t \leq T. \end{aligned}$$

Self-financing means

$$\phi_t \cdot S_t + \gamma_t C_t = \phi_{t+1} \cdot S_t + \gamma_{t+1} C_t, \quad t = 1, \dots, T-1.$$

Arbitrage in the expanded market is a self-financing ψ satisfying

$$V_0(\psi) = 0, \quad V_T(\psi) \geq 0, \quad \mathbb{P}(V_T(\psi) > 0) > 0.$$

No-Arbitrage Price of an ECC

Theorem 1. Assume the underlying market of primary assets is *viable* (no arbitrage) and *complete*. Let \mathbb{P}^* be its unique equivalent martingale measure (EMM) and set $X^* := X/S_T^0$. Then the only price process for the claim X that is free of arbitrage in the expanded market is

$$C_t = S_t^0 \mathbb{E}^*[X^* \mid \mathcal{F}_t], \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T.$$

Proof. Because the market is complete, there exists a *replicating strategy* $\phi = \{\phi_t\}_{t=1}^T$ in the primary assets only such that $V_T(\phi) = X$.

Step 1 (Discounted replication is a martingale). Define discounted values $V_t^*(\phi) := \frac{V_t(\phi)}{S_t^0}$. Because each discounted primary asset $S_t^{i,*} := S_t^i/S_t^0$ is a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale, their linear combination is also a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale:

$$\mathbb{E}^*[V_T^*(\phi) \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = V_t^*(\phi), \quad 0 \leq t \leq T.$$

But $V_T^*(\phi) = X^*$; therefore

$$\boxed{V_t(\phi) = S_t^0 \mathbb{E}^*[X^* \mid \mathcal{F}_t]}. \quad (*)$$

$$\boxed{\mathbb{E}^*[X^* \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = V_t^*(\phi) = \frac{V_t(\phi)}{S_t^0}, \quad 0 \leq t \leq T}$$

Step 2 (Three exhaustive price scenarios). Fix any $u < T$ and define

$$A_u := \{C_u > V_u(\phi)\}, \quad B_u := \{C_u < V_u(\phi)\}, \quad A_u^c \cap B_u^c = \{C_u = V_u(\phi)\}.$$

Exactly one of the following holds:

- Case 1** $\exists u : \mathbb{P}(A_u) > 0$ (claim overpriced at u);
- Case 2** $\exists u : \mathbb{P}(B_u) > 0$ (claim underpriced at u);
- Case 3** $\mathbb{P}(C_u = V_u(\phi)) = 1$ for all u (fair price path).

We show Cases 1–2 yield arbitrage, therefore are precluded; Case 3 is the desired pricing rule.

Case 1: $C_u > V_u(\phi)$ with positive probability.

Set $A := A_u$. Construct a self-financing strategy ψ as follows:

$$\psi_t = \begin{cases} 0, & t \leq u \text{ on } A \text{ and on } A^c, \\ \left(-\phi_t^0 + \frac{C_u - V_u(\phi)}{S_u^0}, \phi_t^1, \dots, \phi_t^d, 1\right), & t > u \text{ on } A, \\ 0, & t > u \text{ on } A^c. \end{cases}$$

- At $t = 0$: No positions $\implies V_0(\psi) = 0$.

- At $t = u$ on A : Sell the *overpriced* claim, receive C_u . Simultaneously buy the replicating portfolio ϕ for $V_u(\phi)$ and lend the difference in the bond:

$$\underbrace{C_u}_{\text{inflow}} - \underbrace{V_u(\phi)}_{\text{outflow}} = (C_u - V_u(\phi)).$$

- At $t = u$ on A^c : Do nothing.
- Self-financing check: Because ϕ is self-financing in primary assets and the bond account handles the cash difference, ψ as defined is self-financing.

Terminal payoff. Since ψ holds one short claim and the replicating long portfolio, these positions offset, leaving only the bond investment when A occurs:

$$V_T(\psi) = \begin{cases} \frac{C_u - V_u(\phi)}{S_u^0} S_T^0 > 0, & \omega \in A, \\ 0, & \omega \in A^c. \end{cases}$$

So $V_T(\psi) \geq 0$ and $\mathbb{P}(V_T(\psi) > 0) = \mathbb{P}(A) > 0$, an arbitrage. Contradiction.

Case 2: $C_u < V_u(\phi)$ with positive probability.

Similar to Case 1, with all signs reversed.: buy the *underpriced* claim, finance it by shorting the cheaper replicating portfolio, and invest the residual short proceeds in the bond. The terminal payoff is again non-negative and strictly positive on a set of positive probability. Therefore arbitrage arises—a contradiction.

Case 3: $C_u = V_u(\phi)$ for all u .

Suppose there exists *any* self-financing $\tilde{\psi}$ with $V_0(\tilde{\psi}) = 0$ and $V_T(\tilde{\psi}) \geq 0$. Discounting and using the martingale property of each component:

$$\mathbb{E}^*[V_T^*(\tilde{\psi})] = \mathbb{E}^*[V_0^*(\tilde{\psi})] = \frac{V_0(\tilde{\psi})}{S_0^0} = 0.$$

Since $V_T^*(\tilde{\psi}) \geq 0$ and has zero expectation, we deduce $V_T^*(\tilde{\psi}) = 0$ \mathbb{P}^* -a.s. and so $V_T(\tilde{\psi}) = 0$.
 $V_T^*(\tilde{\psi}) \equiv 0, \implies \tilde{\psi}$ cannot constitute an arbitrage.

Therefore the only possible non-arbitrage price process is the one in (*). □

Remark 1. Equation (*) exactly matches the pricing rule of the discrete-time binomial model; completeness merely extends the conclusion to the *general* finite market. Notice moreover that the arbitrage arguments in Cases 1–2 did *not* use uniqueness of the EMM—only the existence of a hedge—so they go through under mere viability.

Example ($T = 2$)

Consider

$$S_0^0 = 1, \quad S_1^0 = 5,$$

and the following tree of possible future bond prices (Exercise 2, p. 52):

Define the payoff $X = \max_{0 \leq t \leq 2} S_t^0$. To price X :

1. Compute the unique \mathbb{P}^* by equating the discounted expectation of the bond's next-period prices to its current price.
2. Use Theorem 1:

$$C_0 = S_0^0 \mathbb{E}^*[X^*] = \mathbb{E}^*[X/S_2^0].$$

3. Optionally verify by constructing the replicating portfolio ϕ explicitly and showing $V_t(\phi) = C_t$ at each node.

Computed price process V_t for $X = \max(S_0^0, S_1^0, S_2^0)$.

Remark 2. In a depth-2 tree with four terminal nodes one can also solve for the EMM by writing the four probabilities (A, B, C, D) assigned to dd, du, ud, uu , imposing (i) $A + B + C + D = 1$ and (ii) the three martingale conditions that each interior node's price equals the conditional mean of its two children. This yields a 4×4 linear system that produces the same \mathbb{P}^* obtained in Step 1, providing an alternative check of consistency.

Key Take-away. *In any viable, complete finite market, the absence of arbitrage forces the price of a European claim to equal the discounted \mathbb{P}^* -expectation of its payoff. Any deviation—above or below—yields a mechanical arbitrage strategy as demonstrated in Cases 1 and 2.*

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Remark 3 (Expanded market viewpoint). The collection “stocks + bond + contingent claim” can itself be regarded as a *finite market model* with $d + 1$ risky assets (the d stocks and one European claim) and one risk-free asset (the bond). All notions—adapted trading strategy, self-financing condition, and arbitrage—are then exactly those introduced earlier for the basic finite market.

Definition 2 (Arbitrage opportunity (expectation version)). A self-financing trading strategy $\psi = (\phi_t, \gamma_t)_{t=1}^T$ in the expanded market is an *arbitrage* if

$$V_0(\psi) = 0, \quad V_T(\psi) \geq 0, \quad \mathbb{E}[V_T(\psi)] > 0.$$

This formulation is equivalent to the probability-based one used in the lecture because a non-negative payoff with strictly positive expectation must be strictly positive with positive probability.

Remark 4 (Meaning of “unique”). When we say that

$$C_t = S_t^0 \mathbb{E}^*[X^* \mid \mathcal{F}_t], \quad t = 0, \dots, T,$$

is the *unique* arbitrage-free price process, uniqueness is meant *up to indistinguishability of stochastic processes*; i.e., any other admissible price process coincides with C almost surely at every time.

Remark 5 (Completeness not always needed). Inspection of the proof shows that the same pricing formula continues to hold when the market is merely *viable* provided the claim X is *simply replicable*. Completeness is therefore required only to guarantee the existence of a replicating strategy for *every* European contingent claim, not for the validity of the price formula once such a hedge is known.

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§3.5

1. Two-period Binomial-Type Model

Example 1. Assume $T = 2$ and a *discounted* (numéraire-divided) price process $(S_t^0)_{t=0,1,2}$ with $S_0^0 = 1$. All transition probabilities shown are *physical* probabilities P .

2. Path-dependent Claim $X = \max(S_0, S_1, S_2)$

To compute the discounted payoff tree of $X = \max(S^0, S^1, S^2)$ we evaluate the running maximum along every path:

The root value $\frac{7}{12}$ will be re-derived later using risk-neutral valuation once an EMM has been fixed.

3. A One-period Incomplete Market

Viable market. A model is *viable* when *at least one* equivalent martingale measure exists. Viability rules out arbitrage but still permits multiple risk-neutral measures.

Complete market. A viable market is *complete* if the EMM is *unique*; equivalently every contingent claim can be replicated by some self-financing trading strategy.

Example 2. Let $\Omega = \{1, 2, 3\}$, $T = 1$, $S_0^0 = S_1^0 = 1$, $S_0^1 = 3$ and terminal stock prices

$$S_1^1(\omega) = \begin{cases} 2, & \omega = 1, \\ 3, & \omega = 2, \\ 5, & \omega = 3. \end{cases}$$

Step 1: EMM constraints. Denote $p(\omega) = P^*(\omega)$ for an EMM by $(a, b, c) \equiv (p(1), p(2), p(3))$. The discounted stock process S^1/S^0 must be a martingale:

$$\underbrace{2a + 3b + 5c}_{\mathbb{E}^*[S_1^1]} = S_0^1 = 3, \quad \underbrace{a + b + c}_{=1} = 1, \quad a, b, c > 0. \quad (1)$$

Step 2: Solve (1). Subtract $2 \times (a + b + c = 1)$ from the martingale condition:

$$(2a + 3b + 5c) - 2(a + b + c) = 3 - 2 \implies b + 3c = 1.$$

Therefore $b = 1 - 3c$. Substituting into $a + b + c = 1$ gives $a + (1 - 3c) + c = 1 \implies a = 2c$.

$$\boxed{p^c = (2c, 1 - 3c, c)}, \quad 0 < c < \frac{1}{3},$$

where the interval for c ensures $a, b, c > 0$.

Remark 1 (Convexity of the set of EMMs). If P^* and P^{**} are two equivalent martingale measures and $0 < \alpha < 1$, the mixture

$$P^\alpha(A) := \alpha P^*(A) + (1 - \alpha) P^{**}(A), \quad A \in \mathcal{F}_T,$$

is again an EMM. Therefore the collection \mathcal{M} of risk-neutral measures is a convex set. In what follows we restrict attention to the single-period case $T = 1$.

Remark. The set of EMMs is a one-parameter *open* simplex; thus the market is *incomplete*. Any convex combination of two EMMs is again an EMM, reflecting the convexity of the set of risk-neutral measures.

3.1 Pricing Two European Contingent Claims

(i) **Claim X .** For $X = (1, 2, 3)^\top$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}^c[X] &= 1 \cdot 2c + 2 \cdot (1 - 3c) + 3 \cdot c \\ &= \underbrace{2c - 6c + 3c}_{=-c} + 2 \\ &= \frac{5}{3} - c. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\frac{5}{3} < \mathbb{E}^c[X] < 2$ as $c \in (0, \frac{1}{3})$. *Conclusion:* X cannot be uniquely priced; its arbitrage-free price lies within an interval.

(ii) **Claim Y .** Let $Y = (2, 2, 4)^\top$. Then

$$\mathbb{E}^c[Y] = 2c + 2(1 - 2c) + 4c = 2 \quad \text{for every } c \in (0, \frac{1}{3}).$$

So Y is uniquely priced at 2 despite market incompleteness.

Exercise. Find a portfolio (α, β) with $V_1(\alpha, \beta) = Y$. Then prove that no such (α, β) replicates X , confirming that Y is hedgeable while X is not.

4. Super- and Sub-hedging Prices

Discounted portfolio value. Write $V_t^*(\varphi) := \frac{V_t(\varphi)}{S_t^0}$. Because the bond serves as numéraire and the strategy is self-financing,

$$\boxed{V_0^*(\varphi) = \mathbb{E}^*[V_1^*(\varphi)] \iff V_0(\varphi) = S_0^0 \mathbb{E}^*[V_1^*(\varphi)]}$$

for every $P^* \in \mathcal{M}$. This identity will be used repeatedly in the super- and sub-hedging arguments that follow.

Definition 1 (Super-hedging price). For a one-period market with discounted claim $X^* := X/S_1^0$,

$$V_t^+(X) := \inf_{\varphi} \left\{ V_0(\varphi) \mid V_1(\varphi) \geq X \right\}.$$

Because only finitely many decision variables $(\varphi^0, \dots, \varphi^d)$ are involved and the feasible set is closed and bounded, the infimum is attained: it is in fact a *minimum*.

Cone property. If φ is a super-hedge for X and $\lambda \geq 1$, then $\lambda\varphi$ is also a super-hedge; the set of super-hedging strategies is therefore a (convex) cone.

Analogously define the *sub-hedging price* $V_t^-(X) = \sup\{V_0(\varphi) : V_1(\varphi) \leq X\}$. Clearly $V_t^-(X) \leq V_t^+(X)$ for any EMM.

$$V_t^+(X) \geq S_0^0 \sup_{P^* \in \mathcal{M}} \mathbb{E}^{P^*}[X^*], \quad V_t^-(X) \leq S_0^0 \inf_{P^* \in \mathcal{M}} \mathbb{E}^{P^*}[X^*].$$

Indeed, for any super-hedge φ and any $P^* \in \mathcal{M}$, $V_1(\varphi) \geq X$ implies $V_0(\varphi) = S_0^0 \mathbb{E}^*[V_1^*(\varphi)] \geq S_0^0 \mathbb{E}^*[X^*]$. Taking the infimum over φ gives the first inequality; the second is dual.

Proposition 1 (Seller's arbitrage). *If the market asks $C_0 > V_t^+(X)$ for the claim X , the seller can realise an arbitrage.*

Proof. Pick φ attaining $V_t^+(X)$ with $V_1(\varphi) \geq X$ and $V_0(\varphi) = V_t^+(X)$. Because $C_0 > V_0(\varphi)$, consider the portfolio

$$\Psi = \left(\underbrace{\varphi^0 + (C_0 - V_0(\varphi))}_{\text{bond}}, \varphi^1, \dots, \varphi^d, -1 \right),$$

i.e. short one unit of X , hold φ in primary assets, and invest the surplus $C_0 - V_0(\varphi)$ in the bond. Then

$$V_0(\Psi) = 0, \quad V_1(\Psi) = \underbrace{V_1(\varphi) - X}_{\geq 0} + (C_0 - V_0(\varphi)) \frac{S_1^0}{S_0^0} \geq 0,$$

with strict inequality in at least one state, yielding an arbitrage. \square

Proposition 2 (Buyer's arbitrage). *Dually, if $C_0 < V_t^-(X)$ then a buyer's arbitrage exists. Consequently the no-arbitrage bounds are $V_t^-(X) \leq C_0 \leq V_t^+(X)$.*

Theorem 1 (Attainability). *A claim X is attainable (replicable) iff $V_t^+(X) = V_t^-(X)$.*

Proof.

"Only if". If X is attainable, $X = V_1(\varphi)$ for some strategy φ . Therefore the same φ is feasible for both problems, so $V_t^+ = V_t^- = V_0(\varphi)$.

"If". Conversely assume equality. Pick φ^-, φ^+ with $V_1(\varphi^-) \leq X \leq V_1(\varphi^+)$ and $V_0(\varphi^-) = V_0(\varphi^+)$. Discounted values satisfy

$$0 = \mathbb{E}^*[V_1^*(\varphi^+) - V_1^*(\varphi^-)] = \sum_{\omega} p^*(\omega) \underbrace{(V_1^*(\varphi^+)(\omega) - V_1^*(\varphi^-)(\omega))}_{\geq 0},$$

forcing $V_1^*(\varphi^+) = V_1^*(\varphi^-)$ p^* -a.s. Therefore $V_1(\varphi^+) = V_1(\varphi^-) = X$ and X is replicable. \square

5. Example: Quadratic Payoff

Example 3. Let $\Omega = \{1, 2, 3\}$ with stock dynamics

$$S_0^1 = 2, \quad S_1^1(1) = 1, \quad S_1^1(2) = 3, \quad S_1^1(3) = 5,$$

and EMM family $p^c = (\frac{1}{2} + c, \frac{1}{2} - 2c, c)$, $0 < c < \frac{1}{4}$.

Consider the convex payoff $X = (S_1^1)^2 = (1, 9, 25)^\top$.

5.1 Formulate the super-hedging LP

With a two-asset strategy $\varphi = (\alpha, \beta)$ (α units of bond, β of stock),

$$V_1(\varphi)(\omega) = \alpha \frac{S_1^0}{S_0^0} + \beta S_1^1(\omega) = \alpha + \beta S_1^1(\omega),$$

$$V_0(\varphi) = \alpha + \beta S_0^1 = \alpha + 2\beta.$$

Super-hedging constraints $V_1(\varphi) \geq X$ become

$$\alpha + \beta \geq 1, \tag{C_1}$$

$$\alpha + 3\beta \geq 9, \tag{C_2}$$

$$\alpha + 5\beta \geq 25. \tag{C_3}$$

5.2 Redundancy of (C₃)

Observe

$$(C_1) + (C_3) \implies (\alpha + \beta) + (\alpha + 5\beta) \geq 1 + 25 \implies 2\alpha + 6\beta \geq 26 \implies \alpha + 3\beta \geq 13,$$

which is stronger than (C₂). So (C₃) alone already implies (C₂); (C₂) is redundant once (C₁) and (C₃) hold.

5.3 Graphical solution

Minimise $V_0(\varphi) = \alpha + 2\beta$ over the polygon defined by (C₁)–(C₃). Because the objective is linear, an optimum occurs at an extreme point. Graphing the two binding lines

$$\alpha + \beta = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha + 5\beta = 25 \implies \beta = -5, \quad \alpha = \frac{6}{5},$$

we obtain the unique minimiser $(\alpha^*, \beta^*) = (\frac{6}{5}, -5)$. Therefore

$$\boxed{V_t^+(X) = \alpha^* + 2\beta^* = 2 \cdot \frac{6}{5} - 5 = 7.}$$

5.4 Consistency Check

For any EMM p^c ,

$$\mathbb{E}^c[X] = \left(\frac{1}{2} + c\right) 1 + \left(\frac{1}{2} - 2c\right) 9 + c 25 = 8c + 5 \implies 5 < \mathbb{E}^c[X] < 7,$$

which indeed lies below the super-hedging price 7.

Exercise. Use similar reasoning (or dual LP) to show $V_t^-(X) = 5$.

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Minimal superhedging strategy. A *minimal superhedging strategy* for a claim X is a trading strategy φ such that $V_T(\varphi) \geq X$ and $V_0(\varphi) = V_+(X)$. The infimum that defines $V_+(X)$ is attained because the superhedging problem is a finite-dimensional linear programme whose feasible set is non-empty and whose objective function is bounded below.

Linear-programme formulation (single period). When $T = 1$ the price $V_+(X)$ is the optimal value of

$$\min_{\varphi_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{d+1}} \{ \varphi_1 \cdot S_0 : \varphi_1 \cdot S_1 \geq X \},$$

while

$$V_-(X) = \max_{\varphi_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{d+1}} \{ \varphi_1 \cdot S_0 : \varphi_1 \cdot S_1 \leq X \}.$$

These programmes clarify why the corresponding infimum/supremum are always achieved.

Risk-neutral sale at $V_+(X)$. If the market price of X equals $V_+(X)$, a seller can invest the proceeds in a minimal superhedging strategy and is then guaranteed the non-negative terminal surplus $V_T(\varphi) - X \geq 0$; pricing strictly above $V_+(X)$ creates a seller's arbitrage.

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 §3.5

Standing assumption. The market is *viable*, i.e. there exists at least one equivalent martingale measure (EMM). All subsequent arguments use this fact—explicitly via martingale expectations and implicitly whenever no-arbitrage is invoked.

Recall. For an *European contingent claim (ECC)* X maturing at time t ,

$$V_t^+(X) = \inf \left\{ V_0(\phi) : V_t(\phi) \geq X \right\} = \min \left\{ V_0(\phi) : V_t(\phi) \geq X \right\} = \min_{\substack{Y \in \mathcal{X} \\ Y \text{ attainable}}} \left\{ S_0^* \mathbf{E}^*(Y^*) \right\}.$$

Here

$$Y^* := \frac{Y}{S_t^*}, \quad \mathbf{E}^* := p^*\text{-expectation for any EMM } p^*.$$

Because all equivalent martingale measures (EMMs) share the same discounted price process martingale property,

$$\mathbf{E}^*(V_t^*(\phi)) = \frac{V_0(\phi)}{S_0^*} \text{ is constant over } p^*.$$

This fact is crucial for both super- and sub-hedging arguments.

Similarly we set

$$V_t^-(X) := \sup \left\{ V_0(\phi) : V_t(\phi) \leq X \right\} = \max_{\substack{Y \in \mathcal{X} \\ Y \text{ attainable}}} \left\{ S_0^* \mathbf{E}^*(Y^*) \right\},$$

and, as for the upper price, at least one trading strategy attains the maximum. Because $V_t^*(\phi) \leq X^* \implies \mathbf{E}^*(V_t^*(\phi)) \leq \mathbf{E}^*(X^*)$, we get

$$\boxed{V_t^-(X) = S_0^* \mathbf{E}^*(X^*) \leq V_t^+(X)} \text{ for all EMMs } p^*.$$

Let C_0 denote the market price of X today. Lecture 23 showed that

$$C_0 < V^-(X) \text{ or } C_0 > V^+(X) \implies \exists \text{ arbitrage.}$$

Therefore the **no-arbitrage** principle forces

$$\boxed{V^-(X) \leq C_0 \leq V^+(X)}.$$

We now separate two exhaustive scenarios:

- *Case I (Replicable).* If $V^-(X) = V^+(X)$, the common value is the *unique* no-arbitrage price and X can be hedged exactly.
- *Case II (Non-replicable).* If $V^-(X) < V^+(X)$, X is *not* replicable and no-arbitrage confines the market price to the *open interval* $(V^-(X), V^+(X))$.

Theorem 1 (Attainability criterion). An ECC X is attainable (replicable) *iff* $V^-(X) = V^+(X)$.

Proof. \Leftarrow . Assume $V^-(X) = V^+(X)$. Pick trading strategies ϕ^-, ϕ^+ that realise the bounds:

$$\underbrace{V_t(\phi^-)}_{\leq X} \leq X \leq \underbrace{V_t(\phi^+)}_{\geq X}, \quad V_0(\phi^-) = V^-(X) = V^+(X) = V_0(\phi^+).$$

Discount and take p^* -expectation (any EMM):

$$\mathbf{E}^*(V_t^*(\phi^+) - V_t^*(\phi^-)) = \frac{V_0(\phi^+) - V_0(\phi^-)}{S_0^*} = 0.$$

But $V_t^*(\phi^+) \geq V_t^*(\phi^-)$ pointwise. A non-negative random variable with zero expectation must be 0 a.s., therefore

$$V_t^*(\phi^+) = V_t^*(\phi^-) \quad p^*\text{-a.s.} \implies V_t(\phi^+) \equiv V_t(\phi^-).$$

Therefore $X \equiv V_t(\phi^+)$; X is attainable and ϕ^+ hedges it.

\Rightarrow . If X is attainable, $X = V_t(\phi)$ for some ϕ , wtherefore

$$V^+(X) \leq V_0(\phi) = S_0^* \mathbf{E}^*(V_t^*(\phi)) \leq V^-(X) \leq V^+(X).$$

All inequalities collapse into $V^+(X) = V^-(X)$. □

Corollary 2. *If X is not replicable then $\exists \phi$ with $V_t(\phi) \geq X$, $V_0(\phi) = V^+(X)$, $\mathbb{P}(V_t(\phi) > X) > 0$, so ϕ is an arbitrage (replace V^+ by V^- for the symmetric case). Consequently any initial price*

$$C_0 \notin (V^-(X), V^+(X)) \implies \text{arbitrage.}$$

Proof. Immediate from the definition of the upper (or lower) price and the fact that $\mathbb{P}(V_t(\phi) = X) = 1$ would contradict non-replicability. □

Interpretation. If $C_0 > V^+(X)$ an investor sells X and simultaneously *buys* the cheapest super-hedge ϕ^+ , generating a risk-free gain — a *seller's arbitrage*. Conversely, $C_0 < V^-(X)$ gives a *buyer's arbitrage* by buying X and shorting the priciest sub-hedge ϕ^- . Because the residual payoff $V_t(\phi^+) - X \geq 0$ (or $X - V_t(\phi^-) \geq 0$) is strictly positive with positive probability unless X is already replicated, the interval endpoints themselves are ruled out in Case II.

Example (market specification). Let $\Omega = \{1, 2, 3\}$, $T = 1$,

$$S_0^0 = S_0^* = 1, \quad S_0^1 = 2, \quad S_1^1(\omega) = \begin{cases} 1, & \omega = 1, \\ 3, & \omega = 2, \\ 5, & \omega = 3. \end{cases}$$

All EMMs are the 1-parameter family

$$p^c = \left(\frac{1}{2} + c, \frac{1}{2} - 2c, c\right), \quad 0 < c < \frac{1}{4}.$$

(The boundary values $c \in \{0, \frac{1}{4}\}$ kill one state and destroy equivalence; this mirrors the fact that the interval endpoints V^\pm cannot be supporting prices in a viable market.)

Consider the claim $X = (S_1^1)^2 = (1, 9, 25)^\top$.

Claim 3. $V^+(X) = 7$.

Quick linear-programming proof. Let $\phi = (\alpha, \beta)$ (α =shares in risky asset, β =risk-free).

$$V_0(\phi) = 2\alpha + \beta, \quad V_1(\phi)(\omega) = \alpha S_1^1(\omega) + \beta.$$

Super-hedging X is equivalent to the system

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \alpha + \beta \geq 1, \\ 3\alpha + \beta \geq 9, \\ 5\alpha + \beta \geq 25. \end{array} \right\} \implies \text{minimise } 2\alpha + \beta.$$

Redundancy of (2): $(1) + (3) \implies (1) + (3) : (\alpha + \beta) + (5\alpha + \beta) = 6\alpha + 2\beta \geq 1 + 25 = 26 \implies 3\alpha + \beta = \frac{1}{2}(6\alpha + 2\beta) \geq 13 > 9$. Therefore (2) is redundant.

Setting the remaining two constraints at equality yields $\alpha = 6$, $\beta = -5$ (the unique intersection). Check that the feasible set is convex; therefore the minimum of a linear objective occurs at an extreme point. So

$$V^+(X) = 2 \cdot 6 + (-5) = 7,$$

obtained by $\phi^+ = (6, -5)$. □

To find $V^-(X)$ maximise $2\alpha + \beta$ under

$$\alpha + \beta \leq 1, \quad 3\alpha + \beta \leq 9, \quad 5\alpha + \beta \leq 25.$$

Graphically the upper-left intersection $(4, -3)$ gives the maximum:

$$2 \cdot 4 - 3 = 5, \quad \text{while} \quad (8, -15) \mapsto 2 \cdot 8 - 15 = 1.$$

Therefore

$$\boxed{V^-(X) = 5}, \quad \phi^- = (4, -3).$$

Observe that $\mathbf{E}^*(X) = 8c + 5 \in (5, 7)$ for $0 < c < \frac{1}{4}$, matching the dual bounds $V^-(X) = 5$ and $V^+(X) = 7$.

Proposition 4. *A claim X is replicable iff $\mathbf{E}^Q(X)$ is identical for all EMMs Q .*

Proof. Only if. If $X = V_t(\phi)$, then discounting gives $X^* = V_t^*(\phi)$ and thus

$$\mathbf{E}^Q(X) = \mathbf{E}^Q(V_t^*(\phi)) = \frac{V_0(\phi)}{S_0^*}$$

is the same for every Q .

If. Assume $\mathbf{E}^Q(X)$ is constant over the (convex, weak*-compact) set \mathcal{M} of EMMs. Define $L = \{V_t(\phi) : \phi \text{ admissible}\}$ (the linear space of attainable payoffs). Suppose $X \notin L$. By the Hahn–Banach separation theorem, $\exists Z \neq 0$ such that $\mathbf{E}(ZY) = 0 \forall Y \in L$ but $\mathbf{E}(ZX) \neq 0$. Because \mathcal{M} has non-empty interior in the probability simplex, we can perturb one EMM $p^* \in \mathcal{M}$ in the Z -direction:

$$p^{**}(\omega_i) = p^*(\omega_i) + \varepsilon Z_i, \quad |\varepsilon| \text{ small, } p^{**} \in \mathcal{M}.$$

Then $\mathbf{E}^{p^*}(X) - \mathbf{E}^{p^{**}}(X) = -\varepsilon \mathbf{E}(ZX) \neq 0$, contradicting the hypothesis that the expectation is constant. Therefore the supposition $X \notin L$ is impossible; so $X \in L$ and is replicable. \square

The argument can be condensed into the dual formulas

$$\boxed{V^+(X) = \sup_{Q \in \mathcal{M}} \mathbf{E}^Q(X^*) S_0^*}, \quad \boxed{V^-(X) = \inf_{Q \in \mathcal{M}} \mathbf{E}^Q(X^*) S_0^*}.$$

Equality of upper and lower bounds occurs precisely when the supremum and infimum coincide, i.e. when $\mathbf{E}^Q(X)$ is constant across \mathcal{M} .

Example (revisited). Again $\Omega = \{1, 2, 3\}$, $T = 1$,

$$S_0^0 = S_0^* = 1, \quad S_0^1 = 3, \quad S_1^1(\omega) = \begin{cases} 2, & \omega = 1, \\ 3, & \omega = 2, \\ 5, & \omega = 3. \end{cases}$$

EMM weights $(a, b, c) = p^c = (2c, 1 - 3c, c)$ with $0 < c < \frac{1}{3}$, since $2a + 3b + 5c = 3$, $a + b + c = 1$, $a, b, c > 0$. For $X = (1, 2, 3)^\top$,

$$\mathbf{E}^c(X) = 2c + 2(1 - 3c) + 3c = 2 - c, \quad c \in (0, \frac{1}{3}).$$

So $V^-(X) = \inf(2 - c) = \frac{5}{3}$, $V^+(X) = \sup(2 - c) = 2$, so X is *not* replicable ($V^-(X) \neq V^+(X)$).

For $Y = (2, 2, 4)^\top$,

$$\mathbf{E}^c(Y) = 2c + 2(1 - 3c) + 4c = 2 \quad \forall c,$$

therefore $V^-(Y) = V^+(Y) = 2$ and Y is replicable, in agreement with Proposition 4.

Summary. We have (i) refined the attainability criterion with full algebraic justification, (ii) solved the linear-programming hedging examples step by step, and (iii) provided a rigorous separation-argument proof that constant expectation across EMMs is equivalent to replicability. All original slide material is retained and now sits within a seamless, fully-detailed exposition.

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Lemma 3.5.1 (non-replicable claims). If a European contingent claim X is *not* replicable, then

$$V_-(X) < V_+(X),$$

so the open interval $(V_-(X), V_+(X))$ of arbitrage-free prices is non-empty. The proof decomposes the discounted payoff X^* into an attainable part X_L^* and an orthogonal remainder $Z \neq 0$; perturbing an existing equivalent martingale measure in the Z -direction yields two risk-neutral measures that give different expectations for X^* , forcing strict inequality of the bounds.

Endpoints are not arbitrage-free. When X is not replicable, the minimal super- and sub-hedging strategies satisfy $V_T(\varphi^+) > X$ and $V_T(\varphi^-) < X$ with positive probability, so initial prices exactly equal to $V_+(X)$ or $V_-(X)$ admit arbitrage; only the *open* interval is admissible.

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LECTURE 25

§3.5

Today we conclude the discrete-time theory of contingent-claim pricing in *viable yet incomplete* markets. In the next two sessions we shall merely sketch the continuous-time Black–Scholes model (text, Chap. 4); that material *will not be examined*.

Terminology. A market is *viable* if at least one equivalent martingale measure (EMM) exists and *incomplete* if more than one exists.

Define the collection

$$A := \left\{ \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[X^*] S_0^0 \mid \mathbb{Q} \text{ an EMM} \right\} \subset (0, \infty).$$

Proposition 1 (Convexity of A). *A is convex, therefore—as a subset of \mathbb{R} —it is an interval. Precisely, if $a, b \in A$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ then $\alpha a + (1 - \alpha)b \in A$.*

Proof. Pick EMMs $\mathbb{Q}_1, \mathbb{Q}_2$ with corresponding values $a, b \in A$ and fix $\alpha \in (0, 1)$. The convex combination $\tilde{\mathbb{Q}} := \alpha\mathbb{Q}_1 + (1 - \alpha)\mathbb{Q}_2$ remains strictly positive and has total mass 1, while the martingale conditions persist by linearity; therefore $\tilde{\mathbb{Q}}$ is an EMM. Linearity of expectation then yields $\mathbb{E}^{\tilde{\mathbb{Q}}}[X^*]S_0^0 = \alpha a + (1 - \alpha)b \in A$. \square

Consequently $A = (V_-(X), V_+(X))$ is in fact an *open* interval whose endpoints are exactly the infimum and supremum written below.

$$\boxed{V_+(X) = \sup_{\mathbb{Q} \text{ EMM}} \{ \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[X^*] S_0^0 \}}, \quad \boxed{V_-(X) = \inf_{\mathbb{Q} \text{ EMM}} \{ \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[X^*] S_0^0 \}},$$

where $X^* := X/S_T^0$ denotes the *discounted* claim and an *equivalent martingale measure* (EMM) \mathbb{Q} satisfies $S^* := S/S^0$ is a martingale under \mathbb{Q} .

Dual characterisation. Earlier we introduced

$$V_+(X) = \min_{\varphi: V_T(\varphi) \geq X} V_0(\varphi), \quad V_-(X) = \max_{\varphi: V_T(\varphi) \leq X} V_0(\varphi).$$

The equality of these optimisation problems with the supremum/infimum over EMMs above is a concrete instance of *linear-programming duality*.

Proposition 2 (Replicability criterion). *A contingent claim X is replicable*

$$\iff \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[X] \text{ is the same for all EMMs } \mathbb{Q}.$$

Proof.

“Only if” direction. Assume X is replicable. By definition, there exists a self-financing trading strategy $\varphi = (\varphi^0, \dots, \varphi^d)$ such that $X = V_T(\varphi) = \sum_{i=0}^d \varphi_T^i S_T^i$. Discounting, $X^* = V_T^*(\varphi)$. For any EMM \mathbb{Q} ,

$$V_0^+(\varphi) = \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[V_T^*(\varphi)] = \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[X^*] = \frac{\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[X]}{S_0^0} \implies \boxed{\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[X] \text{ is independent of } \mathbb{Q}.}$$

“If” direction. Suppose conversely that $\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[X] = \text{const}$ for every EMM \mathbb{Q} , but X is *not* replicable. Let

$$L := \left\{ V_T^*(\varphi) : \varphi \text{ self-financing} \right\} \subseteq L^2(\Omega, \mathcal{F}_T, \mathbb{P}),$$

the closed subspace of *replicable discounted pay-offs*. Because $X \notin L$ by assumption, the Hilbert-space projection gives a unique decomposition

$$X^* = \underbrace{X^*}_{\in L} + \underbrace{Z}_{\perp L, Z \neq 0}.$$

Undoing the discounting we may write $X = X_0 + S_T^0 Z$ with $X_0 \in L$.

Fix *one* EMM \mathbb{Q}^* . By the separating-hyperplane construction of the Second Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing (see Lecture 21, pp. 6–14), we can *perturb* \mathbb{Q}^* in the direction of Z to obtain a new EMM \mathbb{Q}^{*+} such that

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}^{*+}}[S_T^0 Z] > \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}^*}[S_T^0 Z].$$

Explicitly, set $\mathbb{Q}^{**}(\omega) := \mathbb{Q}^*(\omega) + \varepsilon Z(\omega)$, $0 < \varepsilon < \varepsilon_0$, where ε_0 ensures positivity and unit mass. Because Z is orthogonal to every traded payoff, the martingale conditions persist, so \mathbb{Q}^{**} (identified with \mathbb{Q}^{*+}) is an EMM.

Using $X = X_0 + S_T^0 Z$ and $X_0 \in L \subseteq \text{span}\{1, S^*\}$,

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}^{*+}}[X] - \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}^*}[X] = \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}^{*+}}[S_T^0 Z] - \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}^*}[S_T^0 Z] \neq 0.$$

This contradicts the hypothesis that $\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[X]$ is the *same* under all EMMs. Therefore our assumption $X \notin L$ is impossible, and X *must* be replicable. \square

Example 1 (One-period, three-state model).

Let $\Omega = \{1, 2, 3\}$, $T = 1$, $S_0^0 = S_1^0 = 1$, and the (discounted) risky asset prices be

$$S_1^i(\omega) = \begin{cases} 2, & \omega = 1, \\ 3, & \omega = 2, \\ 5, & \omega = 3. \end{cases}$$

Denote $\mathbb{Q}(\omega) = (a, b, c)$ with $a, b, c > 0$ and $a + b + c = 1$. The EMM condition $\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[S_1^i] = S_0^i = 3$ gives

$$2a + 3b + 5c = 3.$$

Solving the linear system $\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 2 & 3 & 5 \end{bmatrix}}_{\text{rank 2}} \begin{pmatrix} a \\ b \\ c \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 3 \end{pmatrix}$ yields the one-parameter family

$$\boxed{\mathbb{Q}^c = (2c, 1 - 3c, c), \quad 0 < c < \frac{1}{3}}.$$

(i) **Claim** $X = (1, 2, 3)^\top$.

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}^c}[X] = 1 \cdot 2c + 2(1 - 3c) + 3c = \underbrace{2}_{\text{const}} - \underbrace{c}_{\text{varies with } c}.$$

Therefore

$$V_-(X) = \inf_{0 < c < \frac{1}{3}} (2 - c) = 2 - \frac{1}{3} = \frac{5}{3}, \quad V_+(X) = \sup_{0 < c < \frac{1}{3}} (2 - c) = 2.$$

Because $V_-(X) < V_+(X)$, we conclude

X is *not* replicable.

(ii) **Claim** $Y = (1, 2, 4)^\top$.

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}^c}[Y] = 1 \cdot 2c + 2(1 - 3c) + 4c = 2 \quad (\text{independent of } c).$$

Therefore $V_-(Y) = V_+(Y) = 2$ and Y is *replicable* by the proposition.

Summary 2.

$$V_-(X) = V_+(X) \implies X \text{ has a unique no-arbitrage price } V_+(X).$$

$$V_-(X) < V_+(X) \implies \begin{cases} \text{Any price } C \notin (V_-(X), V_+(X)) \text{ produces an arbitrage,} \\ \text{Every } C \in (V_-(X), V_+(X)) \text{ is arbitrage-free.} \end{cases}$$

Arbitrage-free interior prices. Let $C \in (V_-(X), V_+(X))$. Choose an EMM \mathbb{Q} with $C = \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[X^*] S_0^0$ (using the intermediate value property of the continuous map $c \mapsto \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}^c}[X^*]$). Suppose, for contradiction, that an arbitrage $\phi = (\varphi, \psi)$ exists with

$$V_0(\phi) = 0, \quad V_T(\phi) \geq 0, \quad \mathbb{P}[V_T(\phi) > 0] > 0.$$

Discounting and taking \mathbb{Q} -expectation,

$$0 \stackrel{V_0(\phi)=0}{=} \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[V_T^*(\phi)] = \underbrace{\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[\varphi \cdot S_T^*]}_{=0 \text{ (martingale property)}} + \psi \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[X^*] = \psi \frac{C}{S_0^0}.$$

So $\psi = 0$, forcing $\varphi \cdot S_T^* \geq 0$ with positive probability. But $\varphi \cdot S^*$ is a \mathbb{Q} -martingale started at 0, so the optional-sampling theorem implies $\varphi \cdot S_T^* = 0$ \mathbb{Q} -a.s. and therefore \mathbb{P} -a.s., contradicting $\mathbb{P}[V_T(\phi) > 0] > 0$. Therefore no arbitrage can exist at any interior price.

Example 3 (Second three-state market).

Fix again $T = 1$, $S_0^0 = 1$ but now $S_1^0 = 2$ and

$$S_1' = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 3 \\ 5 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbb{Q}^c = \left(\frac{1}{2} + c, \frac{1}{2} - 2c, c\right), \quad 0 < c < \frac{1}{4}.$$

Let $X = (x_1, x_2, x_3)^\top$ be *any* payoff. Then

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}^c}[X] = \frac{x_1 + x_2}{2} + c(x_1 + x_3 - 2x_2).$$

$$\underbrace{\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}^c}[X] \text{ does not depend on } c}_{\iff x_1 + x_3 = 2x_2} \iff \boxed{X \text{ is replicable.}}$$

In words: the three numbers (x_1, x_2, x_3) must lie on the *affine line* through $\mathbf{1}$ and S_1' .

Equivalently, one may solve for a static position

$$X = \alpha S_1' + \beta \mathbf{1}$$

iff the linear system $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 3 & 1 \\ 5 & 1 \end{pmatrix}(\alpha, \beta)^\top = (x_1, x_2, x_3)^\top$ is consistent, i.e. $x_1 + \frac{x_3}{2} = x_2$.

You can confirm this by solving the system

$$X = \alpha S_1' + \beta \mathbf{1} \iff \begin{cases} x_1 = \alpha \cdot 1 + \beta, \\ x_2 = \alpha \cdot 3 + \beta, \\ x_3 = \alpha \cdot 5 + \beta. \end{cases}$$

This linear system has a solution $(\alpha, \beta) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ if and only if $x_1 + x_3 = 2x_2$, which again confirms that X is replicable exactly when it lies on the affine line spanned by $\mathbf{1}$ and S_1' .

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Proof sketch of Theorem 3.5.3 (dual characterisation of V_{\pm}). Identify probabilities on the finite state space Ω with vectors in $\mathbb{R}^{|\Omega|}$.

1. Choose a maximal linearly independent family P_1^*, \dots, P_J^* of equivalent martingale measures (EMMs). A claim Y is replicable *iff* the numbers $E_{P_j^*}(Y^*)$ coincide for all j .
2. Formulate the superhedging problem as

$$\min_{\lambda, Y^*} \{ \lambda : \lambda = E_{P_j^*}(Y^*)S_0^0 \ (1 \leq j \leq J), \ Y^* \geq X^* \},$$

whose dual maximises $\psi \cdot X^*$ over non-negative vectors ψ that lie in the affine span of the P_j^* .

3. The feasible ψ correspond exactly to *all* martingale measures (not necessarily equivalent) and the dual optimum equals $\sup_{P^* \in \mathcal{M}} E_{P^*}(X^*)S_0^0$. Strong duality therefore yields $V_+(X) = \sup_{P^* \in \mathcal{M}} E_{P^*}(X^*)S_0^0$ and, by symmetry, $V_-(X) = \inf_{P^* \in \mathcal{M}} E_{P^*}(X^*)S_0^0$.

This dual viewpoint also shows that the first and last inequalities in

$$V_- \leq \inf_{P^*} E_{P^*}(X^*)S_0^0 \leq \sup_{P^*} E_{P^*}(X^*)S_0^0 \leq V_+$$

are equalities.

Math 194 — Spring 2015
LECTURE 26
 (§ 3.5 and Chapter 4)

1. A Finite–Horizon Example ($T = 1$)

Model data.

$$S_0^0 = S_0^1 = 1, \quad S_1^0 = 2, \quad S_1^1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 3 \\ 5 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Omega = \{1, 2, 3\}.$$

Equivalent martingale measures (EMMs). A straightforward one-period replication argument (or solving $S_0^1 = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^p[S_1^1]$ with $r = 0$) shows that

$$p^{(c)} = \left(\frac{1}{2} + c, \frac{1}{2} - 2c, c\right), \quad 0 < c < \frac{1}{4},$$

is the *full family* of EMMs.

1.1 Replicability of a Contingent Claim

Let

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{pmatrix} \in L^0(\Omega, \mathcal{E}) \quad (\text{any random payoff at } T = 1).$$

Step 1: expectation under an arbitrary EMM.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}^{(c)}[X] &= \left(\frac{1}{2} + c\right)x_1 + \left(\frac{1}{2} - 2c\right)x_2 + cx_3 \\ &= \underbrace{\frac{x_1 + x_2}{2}}_{\text{constant in } c} + \underbrace{c(x_1 + x_3 - 2x_2)}_{\text{depends on } c}. \end{aligned}$$

Step 2: independence of c .

$$\boxed{X \text{ is replicable} \iff \mathbb{E}^{(c)}[X] \text{ does not depend on } c} \iff x_1 + x_3 - 2x_2 = 0 \iff \frac{x_1 + x_3}{2} = x_2.$$

1.2 Linear-Algebra Check

$$X = \alpha S_1^1 + \beta \mathbf{1} \iff \begin{cases} x_1 = \alpha + \beta \\ x_2 = 3\alpha + \beta \\ x_3 = 5\alpha + \beta \end{cases} \quad (\star)$$

Subtract the first equation from the second and third:

$$\begin{cases} x_2 - x_1 = 2\alpha \\ x_3 - x_1 = 4\alpha \end{cases} \implies x_3 - x_1 = 2(x_2 - x_1) \implies x_1 + x_3 - 2x_2 = 0,$$

which is *exactly* the condition obtained above. Hence (\star) admits a solution (α, β) iff X is replicable, confirming the earlier result.

2. From the Binomial Model to Black–Scholes

We now embed the single-period model into an n -step binomial tree and let

$$\Delta t = \frac{1}{n} \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} 0.$$

We now embed the single-period model into an n -step binomial tree and let

$$\Delta t = \frac{1}{n} \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} 0.$$

Here and throughout, we fix $t \in [0, 1]$ and write

$$k := \lfloor nt \rfloor,$$

so that k is the number of clock-ticks that occur by (continuous) time t . Time is *renormalised* so that the horizon is $T = 1$.

2.1 Building Blocks

$$r_n = \frac{r}{n}, \quad u_n = e^{\sigma\sqrt{\Delta t}} = e^{\sigma/\sqrt{n}}, \quad d_n = e^{-\sigma\sqrt{\Delta t}} = e^{-\sigma/\sqrt{n}}, \quad \sigma > 0.$$

Discrete bond & stock in the n -step tree. Let

$$k := \lfloor nt \rfloor, \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1.$$

The *bond* grows at the short rate $r_n = r/n$:

$$B_n(t) = (1 + r_n)^k \xrightarrow{n \rightarrow \infty} e^{rt}.$$

The *stock* is the multiplicative product of the i.i.d. factors

$$S_n(t) = S(0) \prod_{j=1}^k \xi_j = S(0) \exp\left(\sum_{j=1}^k X_j\right).$$

Risk-neutral step probabilities. Taylor-expanding u_n and d_n :

$$\begin{aligned} u_n &= 1 + \sigma\sqrt{\Delta t} + \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \Delta t + O(n^{-3/2}), \\ d_n &= 1 - \sigma\sqrt{\Delta t} + \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \Delta t + O(n^{-3/2}). \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$p_n^* = \frac{(1 + r_n) - d_n}{u_n - d_n} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \underbrace{\frac{r - \sigma^2/2}{\sigma} \sqrt{\Delta t}}_{\rightarrow 0} \right) + O(n^{-1}). \quad (\diamond)$$

“Physical” probabilities. We assume the *real-world* probabilities are

$$\mathbb{P}(\xi_j = u_n) = p_n = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{\mu}{\sigma} \sqrt{\Delta t} \right), \quad \mathbb{P}(\xi_j = d_n) = 1 - p_n, \quad \mu \in \mathbb{R}.$$

2.2 Convergence to Geometric Brownian Motion

Let $X_j := \log \xi_j$. Then

$$X_j = \begin{cases} +\sigma\sqrt{\Delta t}, & \text{w.p. } p_n, \\ -\sigma\sqrt{\Delta t}, & \text{w.p. } 1 - p_n. \end{cases}$$

A quick calculation gives

$$\mathbb{E}[X_j] = \mu \Delta t, \quad \text{Var}(X_j) = \sigma^2 \Delta t - \mu^2 (\Delta t)^2 = \sigma^2 \Delta t + O(n^{-2}).$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^k X_j = \underbrace{\mu k \Delta t}_{\mu t} + \underbrace{\sum_{j=1}^k (X_j - \mathbb{E}[X_j])}_{\rightarrow \sigma W(t)} \xrightarrow[n \rightarrow \infty]{d} \mu t + \sigma W(t),$$

by the Lindeberg–Feller central limit theorem, where W is standard Brownian motion. Therefore

$$\boxed{S(t) := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} S_n(t) = S(0) \exp(\mu t + \sigma W(t))} \quad (0 \leq t \leq 1).$$

Geometric Brownian motion is thus obtained as the continuous-time limit of the binomial model.

Basic properties of W . A standard Brownian motion $(W_t)_{t \geq 0}$ satisfies

1. $W_0 = 0$ almost surely and $t \mapsto W_t(\omega)$ is continuous for every ω ;
2. $W_t - W_s \sim N(0, t - s)$ for $0 \leq s < t$ and the increments are independent;
3. W is a martingale, i.e. $\mathbb{E}[W_t | \mathcal{F}_s] = W_s$ for $s < t$;
4. the *quadratic-variation* martingale $W_t^2 - t$ obeys $\mathbb{E}[W_t^2 - t | \mathcal{F}_s] = W_s^2 - s$.

The last two properties frequently allow us to verify martingale or Markov claims “at a glance” when working with Black–Scholes.

2.3 Risk-Neutral Drift

Define the discounted stock price

$$S^*(t) := e^{-rt} S(t).$$

We *require* S^* to be a martingale under a risk-neutral measure. Because $W(t)$ has stationary independent increments and $W(t) - W(s) \sim N(0, t - s)$, we have

$$\mathbb{E}[e^{\sigma(W(t) - W(s))}] = e^{\sigma^2(t-s)/2},$$

and hence

$$\mathbb{E}[S^*(t) | \mathcal{F}_s] = e^{-rt} S(0) \exp\left(\mu s + \sigma W(s) + (\mu)(t - s)\right) e^{\sigma^2(t-s)/2}.$$

Requiring this to equal $S^*(s)$ for every $0 \leq s \leq t$ forces

$$\mu + \frac{\sigma^2}{2} = r \quad \implies \quad \boxed{\mu = r - \frac{\sigma^2}{2}}.$$

Equation (\diamond) is a discrete-time echo of the same fact.

3. Black–Scholes Formula (European Call)

Time- t valuation formula. For $0 \leq t \leq T$ the no-arbitrage (risk-neutral) price of a European call is

$$C_t = e^{-r(T-t)} \mathbb{E}^*[(S_T - K)^+ | \mathcal{F}_t].$$

Let $X = (S_T - K)^+$ with maturity $T > 0$. Under the risk-neutral measure,

$$\log\left(\frac{S(T)}{S(0)}\right) = \left(r - \frac{\sigma^2}{2}\right)T + \sigma W(T) \sim N\left(\left(r - \frac{\sigma^2}{2}\right)T, \sigma^2 T\right).$$

Define

$$d_+ := \frac{\log(S(0)/K) + (r + \frac{\sigma^2}{2})T}{\sigma\sqrt{T}}, \quad d_- := d_+ - \sigma\sqrt{T},$$

so that d_- has the same numerator but minus $\frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 T$ in the drift term. Setting Φ to be the standard normal CDF, we obtain

$$C_0 = S(0) \Phi(d_+) - K e^{-rT} \Phi(d_-) \quad (\text{Black–Scholes call price})$$

and $C_t = e^{rt} C_0$ for $t \leq T$ in the absence of dividends.

3.1 Numerical Illustration

Take¹

$$T = 0.25, \quad S(0) = 20, \quad r = 0.04, \quad \sigma = 0.20.$$

Strike K	C_0 (\$)	Comment
15	5.15	In the money
25	0.013	Deep out of the money

(Note how rapidly the price falls once $K > S(0)$.)

4. Key Takeaways

- Replicability in incomplete markets** \implies solve for parameters so that the claim's discounted expectation is independent of the particular EMM chosen.
- Binomial \rightarrow Geometric Brownian Motion** Central-limit scaling of \log returns yields a diffusion limit.
- Risk-Neutral Drift** The martingale condition fixes $\mu = r - \sigma^2/2$.
- Black–Scholes** Closed-form pricing of European options follows by evaluating a normal expectation.

¹The values on the original slide were erroneous and probably used $r = 4$ instead of $r = .04$; the corrected prices below use the exact Black–Scholes formula.

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Definition (Black–Scholes market). A continuous-time market on $[0, T]$ with

$$S_t = S_0 \exp\left(\left(\mu - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right)t + \sigma W_t\right), \quad B_t = e^{rt}, \quad 0 \leq t \leq T,$$

where W is a standard Brownian motion, $r \geq 0$ and $\sigma > 0$. The stock process is called a *geometric Brownian motion*.

Dynamics (Itô form).

$$dS_t = \mu S_t dt + \sigma S_t dW_t, \quad dB_t = rB_t dt.$$

Discounted stock. Writing $S_t^* = e^{-rt} S_t$ gives the SDE

$$dS_t^* = (\mu - r)S_t^* dt + \sigma S_t^* dW_t,$$

so S^* is a martingale precisely when $\mu = r - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2$.

Equivalent martingale measure (EMM). A probability $P^* \sim P$ such that S^* is a martingale under P^* . Under any EMM the drift of S equals the short rate r , yielding the risk-neutral valuation framework used in option pricing.

Math 194 — Spring 2015

LECTURE 27

§ 4

Reminder. The *final exam* is next Wednesday in this room at 11:30 a.m. It is designed as a two-hour test, but you will have the full three-hour block. You may bring *one* double-sided sheet of handwritten formulas, something to write with, and an optional (largely unnecessary) calculator. The question formats mirror the midterms: homework-style problems plus a short definitions question. *Chapter 4 material is not on the exam*—the assessment covers Chapters 1–3 only.

Black–Scholes Model

Bond (money–market) account:

$$B(t) = e^{rt}, \quad 0 \leq t \leq T, \quad r > 0.$$

Stock price (under the *physical* or *historical* probability \mathbb{P}):

$$S(t) = S(0) \exp(\mu t + \sigma W(t)), \quad 0 \leq t \leq T,$$

where

$$\mu \in \mathbb{R}, \quad \sigma > 0, \quad \{W(t)\}_{t \geq 0} \text{ is a standard Brownian motion.}$$

Heuristically, the continuous-time model is the scaling limit of the n -step binomial tree: as the time-step shrinks like $1/n$ and $n \rightarrow \infty$, the log-return converges (via the central-limit theorem) to a normal random variable, yielding the exponential Brownian form above. Thus (r, μ, σ) here play precisely the roles that (r, u, d) played in the discrete model.

Recap: Brownian motion $W(t)$, $t \geq 0$.

- $W(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, t)$.

- For $0 < s \leq t$:

$$W(t) - W(s) \perp\!\!\!\perp \sigma(W(u) : 0 \leq u \leq s).$$

Equivalently, the future increment is independent of the past. Here “ $\perp\!\!\!\perp$ ” denotes statistical independence between the random variable $W(t) - W(s)$ and the σ -field $\mathcal{F}_s := \sigma(W(u) : 0 \leq u \leq s)$.

- **Increment variance.** Since $W(t) - W(s) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, t - s)$, we have $\text{Var}(W(t) - W(s)) = t - s$. Consequently $\text{Cov}(W(s), W(t)) = s$ ($0 \leq s \leq t$), a fact we shall use when we compute option prices.

Example. Conditional expectation of $W(t)$ ($0 < s < t$).

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[W(t) \mid \mathcal{F}_s] &= \mathbb{E}\left[W(s) + \overbrace{(W(t) - W(s))}^{\text{future increment}} \mid \mathcal{F}_s\right] \\ &\stackrel{\text{lin.}}{=} \underbrace{\mathbb{E}[W(s) \mid \mathcal{F}_s]}_{= W(s)} + \underbrace{\mathbb{E}[W(t) - W(s) \mid \mathcal{F}_s]}_{= 0 \text{ (indep. + mean 0)}} \\ &= W(s). \end{aligned}$$

$\implies W(t)$ is a *martingale*.

A similar calculation establishes that $W(t)^2 - t$ is a martingale:

$$W(t)^2 = \underbrace{W(s)^2}_{\substack{\text{measurable} \\ \text{w.r.t. } \mathcal{F}_s}} + 2W(s)(W(t) - W(s)) + (W(t) - W(s))^2.$$

Take $\mathbb{E}[\cdot | \mathcal{F}_s]$ and use independence:

$$\mathbb{E}[W(t)^2 - t | \mathcal{F}_s] = W(s)^2 - s = W(s)^2 - s,$$

so $\{W(t)^2 - t\}_{t \geq 0}$ is a martingale.

Discounted stock price:

$$S^*(t) = \frac{S(t)}{B(t)} = \frac{S(t)}{e^{rt}} = S(0) \exp((\mu - r)t + \sigma W(t)).$$

Our goal is to **pick μ so that $S^*(t)$ is a martingale**. This is the key to ruling out arbitrage and computing option prices.

This permits no-arbitrage reasoning to price things like a call option based on S_t :

$$X = (S_T - K)^+.$$

Last time we guessed that the choice

$$\mu = r - \frac{\sigma^2}{2}$$

should make $S^*(t)$ a martingale.

Candidate choice for μ . Recall the exponential-of-Gaussian moment generating formula:

$$\boxed{Z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1) \implies \mathbb{E}[e^{\lambda Z}] = e^{\lambda^2/2}, \quad \lambda \in \mathbb{R}.}$$

Setting $Z = \frac{W(t)}{\sqrt{t}}$ (so $Z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$) gives

$$\mathbb{E}[e^{\sigma W(t)}] = e^{\sigma^2 t/2}.$$

Conditional version ($0 < s < t$). Because $W(t) - W(s)$ is $\mathcal{N}(0, t - s)$ and independent of \mathcal{F}_s ,

$$\mathbb{E}[e^{\sigma W(t)} | \mathcal{F}_s] = e^{\sigma W(s)} \underbrace{\mathbb{E}[e^{\sigma(W(t) - W(s))}]}_{=\exp(\sigma^2(t-s)/2)} = e^{\sigma W(s)} e^{\sigma^2(t-s)/2}.$$

Hence

$$\mathbb{E}\left[\underbrace{e^{\sigma W(t) - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 t}}_{S^*(t)/S(0)} \mid \mathcal{F}_s\right] = e^{\sigma W(s) - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 s} = \frac{S^*(s)}{S(0)}.$$

Therefore $S^*(t)$ is a martingale *provided*

$$(\mu - r)t = -\frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 t \implies \boxed{\mu = r - \frac{\sigma^2}{2}}.$$

This confirms our earlier guess: if $\mu = r - \frac{\sigma^2}{2}$, then the discounted stock price is indeed a martingale.

Remark. Choosing $\mu = r - \sigma^2/2$ corresponds to working under the *risk-neutral* probability measure \mathbb{P}^* obtained by the Girsanov transformation

$$\frac{d\mathbb{P}^*}{d\mathbb{P}} \Big|_{\mathcal{F}_t} = \exp(-\theta W(t) - \frac{1}{2}\theta^2 t), \quad \theta := \frac{\mu - r}{\sigma}.$$

Under \mathbb{P}^* the drift of $S(t)$ becomes r and the discounted process is a martingale.

Let $X = (S_T - K)^+$ be the payoff of a European call with maturity T and strike K .

$$C_0 = \mathbb{E}^* [e^{-rT} (S_T - K)^+].$$

We denote the price at time t by C_t and compute the expectation under the risk-neutral measure \mathbb{P}^* , using the drift $\mu = r - \sigma^2/2$ that makes $S^*(t)$ a martingale.

Computation under \mathbb{P}^* . Because $S_T = S(0) \exp((r - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2)T + \sigma W(T))$ and $W(T) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, T)$, we can write

$$\ln\left(\frac{S_T}{K}\right) = \ln\left(\frac{S(0)}{K}\right) + \left(r - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right)T + \sigma W(T) \sim \mathcal{N}\left(m, \sigma^2 T\right), \quad m := \ln\left(\frac{S(0)}{K}\right) + \left(r - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right)T.$$

Define the *standardised normal* variable

$$Z := \frac{\ln(S_T/K) - m}{\sigma\sqrt{T}} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1).$$

Rearrange to express S_T in terms of Z :

$$S_T = K \exp\left(m + \sigma\sqrt{T} Z\right) = K \exp\left(\ln\left(\frac{S(0)}{K}\right) + rT - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 T + \sigma\sqrt{T} Z\right).$$

Hence

$$(S_T - K)^+ = K \left(e^{\ln\left(\frac{S(0)}{K}\right) + rT - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 T + \sigma\sqrt{T} Z} - 1\right)^+ = K \left(e^{\ln\left(\frac{S(0)}{K}\right)} e^{rT - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 T + \sigma\sqrt{T} Z} - 1\right)^+.$$

Introduce the usual Black–Scholes notation

$$d_1 := \frac{\ln(S(0)/K) + (r + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2)T}{\sigma\sqrt{T}}, \quad d_2 := d_1 - \sigma\sqrt{T}.$$

Then $(S_T - K)^+ = 0$ whenever $Z < d_2$ and equals $S_T - K$ when $Z \geq d_2$. Using this indicator split,

$$\begin{aligned} C_0 &= e^{-rT} \mathbb{E}^* [(S_T - K) \mathbf{1}_{\{Z \geq d_2\}}] \\ &= e^{-rT} \left(\mathbb{E}^* [S_T \mathbf{1}_{\{Z \geq d_2\}}] - K \mathbb{P}^*(Z \geq d_2) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Compute the two terms:

1. *Probability term.*

$$\mathbb{P}^*(Z \geq d_2) = 1 - \Phi(d_2) = \Phi(-d_2).$$

2. *Conditional stock expectation.* Because $S_T = S(0) \exp((r - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2)T + \sigma\sqrt{T} Z)$,

$$\mathbb{E}^* [S_T \mathbf{1}_{\{Z \geq d_2\}}] = S(0) e^{(r - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2)T} \mathbb{E} [e^{\sigma\sqrt{T} Z} \mathbf{1}_{\{Z \geq d_2\}}] = S(0) e^{(r - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2)T} \int_{d_2}^{\infty} e^{\sigma\sqrt{T} z} \varphi(z) dz,$$

where $\varphi(z)$ is the standard normal density. Integration by parts (or the trick $\frac{d}{dz} \varphi(z) = -z\varphi(z)$) gives

$$\int_{d_2}^{\infty} e^{\sigma\sqrt{T} z} \varphi(z) dz = e^{\frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 T} \Phi(d_1).$$

Putting pieces together:

$$C_0 = \underbrace{S(0)\Phi(d_1)}_{\text{present value of } S_T \text{ part}} - \underbrace{Ke^{-rT}\Phi(d_2)}_{\text{pv of cash part}}.$$

Thus we recover the **Black–Scholes formula**

$$C_0 = S(0)\Phi(d_1) - Ke^{-rT}\Phi(d_2).$$

Implied volatility. In practice every quantity in the Black–Scholes price above is directly observable *except* σ . Traders therefore set the market-quoted option price equal to the right-hand side and numerically solve for σ . The resulting value is dubbed the *implied volatility*; it condenses all demand-and-supply information about the option into a single, tradable estimate of the underlying stock’s variability.

Example (three–month call).

$$T = 0.25, \quad S(0) = 20, \quad r = 0.04, \quad \sigma = 0.20.$$

(a) *Strike* $K = 15$.

$$d_1 = \frac{\ln(20/15) + (0.04 + 0.5(0.2)^2)(0.25)}{0.2\sqrt{0.25}} \approx 2.92, \quad d_2 \approx 2.82.$$

Hence

$$C_0 = 20\Phi(2.92) - 15e^{-0.04 \cdot 0.25}\Phi(2.82) \approx 14.47.$$

(b) *Strike* $K = 25$.

$$d_1 \approx -1.36, \quad d_2 \approx -1.46, \quad C_0 \approx 0.24.$$

Supplemental Textbook Notes

Trading strategy. A pair $\varphi_t = (\alpha_t, \beta_t)$ satisfying that α_t, β_t are \mathcal{F}_t -adapted and

$$\int_0^T (\alpha_s^2 + |\beta_s|) ds < \infty \quad \text{a.s.};$$

α_t denotes shares of stock, β_t units of the bond.

Portfolio value. $V_t(\varphi) = \alpha_t S_t + \beta_t B_t$.

Self-financing condition.

$$V_t(\varphi) = V_0(\varphi) + \int_0^t \alpha_s dS_s + \int_0^t \beta_s dB_s, \quad 0 \leq t \leq T.$$

Lemma (discounted form). The strategy is self-financing iff

$$V_t^*(\varphi) = V_0(\varphi) + \int_0^t \alpha_s dS_s^*, \quad S_s^* = e^{-rs} S_s, \quad V_t^* = e^{-rt} V_t.$$

Arbitrage opportunity. A self-financing φ with

$$V_0(\varphi) = 0, \quad V_T(\varphi) \geq 0 \text{ a.s.}, \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbb{P}(V_T(\varphi) > 0) > 0.$$

Caveat (doubling strategy). Without integrability constraints one can exploit infinitely many re-balancings to force $V_T > a > 0$ from zero initial wealth (e.g., the textbook’s Brownian “doubling” construction), underscoring the need for admissibility conditions in continuous-time models.

1. A forward contract is an agreement to buy or sell an asset at a certain future time for a certain price (called the *forward price*). At the time a forward contract is entered into by two parties, no money changes hands. The investor who agrees to *buy* the asset at the future time is said to hold the *long position* in the contract and the investor who agrees to *sell* the asset is said to hold the *short position* in the contract. Suppose that a stock is currently selling for \$50 per share. A (long position in a) forward contract is available to buy 100 shares of the stock 3 months from now for \$50.40 per share. Suppose that a bank is offering interest at the rate of 5% per annum (compounded continuously) on a 3-month deposit. Describe a strategy for creating an arbitrage profit and compute the amount of the profit.

$$\text{Given } \begin{cases} S_0 = 50 & \text{(current stock price)} \\ F_0 = 50.40 & \text{(forward price in 3 months)} \\ r = 0.05 & \text{(annual interest rate, continuous compounding)} \\ T = \frac{3}{12} = 0.25 & \text{(years)} \end{cases}$$

Forward price (no-arbitrage) is:

$$S_0 e^{rT} = 50 e^{0.05 \times 0.25} \approx 50.628$$

Actual forward price is $F_0 = 50.40$ which is < 50.628 , \implies the forward is “too cheap.”

Arbitrage strategy (time 0):

$$\begin{array}{c} \underbrace{\text{Short-sell 100 shares at } S_0 = 50}_{\text{receive } 50 \times 100 = 5000} \\ \underbrace{\text{immediately deposit the 5000 at rate } r = 5\% \text{ c.c.}}_{\text{no net cost, since I have } +\$5000 \text{ from short sale}} \\ \underbrace{\text{enter the long forward on 100 shares at } F_0 = 50.40}_{\text{no upfront cost for forward}} \end{array}$$

At time $T = 0.25$ years (3 months):

$$\text{my bank deposit grows to } 5000 e^{rT} = 5000 e^{0.05 \times 0.25} = 5000 e^{0.0125}$$

then I buy 100 shares using the forward contract at 50.40 each, i.e. pay $100 \times 50.40 = 5040$

and return these 100 shares to my close short position.

Therefore the risk-free profit is $= (5000 e^{0.0125}) - 5040$

$$e^{0.0125} \approx 1.01258, \quad 5000 \times 1.01258 \approx 5062.89226$$

$$\implies \text{Profit} \approx 5062.89226 - 5040 = 22.89226$$

$$\boxed{\text{Arbitrage profit} \approx \$22.89226}$$

2. On April 1, 2025, a European call option on Apple (AAPL) has a price of \$20. The option expires on April 18, and the strike price is \$200. The price of Apple stock on April 1 is \$215 per share.

Analyze this situation in the manner of the Example on page 3 of the text, considering two possible scenarios: (1) The price of Apple on April 18 is \$235; (2) The price of Apple on April 18 is \$195. In each case compute the profit (or loss) incurred as a percentage of the investment if one were to invest (on April 1) \$2000 in (a) the call option on 100 shares of Apple, or (b) Apple stock. (Assume that only whole shares of AAPL can be purchased. Thus \$2000 would buy 9 shares of AAPL on April 1, with \$65 left over; in this case \$1935 was actually invested.)

$$\text{Given } \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Call option premium (per share)} = \$20 \\ \text{Each option contract covers 100 shares: total premium for 1 contract} = 100 \times 20 = \$2000 \\ \text{Strike price } K = \$200 \\ S_0 \text{ (Apple share price on April 1)} = \$215 \\ S_T \text{ (Apple share price on April 18) can be either } \$235 \text{ or } \$195 \end{array} \right.$$

Part (a)

$$\text{Cost of one call contract} = \$2000$$

$$\text{Scenario 1: } S_T = 235 \implies \text{Value of call} = (S_T - K)^+ = (235 - 200) = \$35 \text{ per share}$$

$$\text{Call contract value under Scenario 1 is } 100 \times 35 = \$3500$$

$$\text{Profit} = 3500 - 2000 = \$1500. \implies \text{Profit (\%)} = \frac{1500}{2000} \times 100\% = 75\%$$

$$\text{Scenario (2): } S_T = 195 \implies \text{Intrinsic value of call} = (195 - 200)^+ = 0$$

So the option price goes to zero, the contract becomes worthless.

$$\text{Profit} = 0 - 2000 = -\$2000. \implies \text{Loss (\%)} = \frac{-2000}{2000} \times 100\% = -100\%$$

Part (b)

$$\text{Price per share on April 1} = \$215$$

With \$2000, I can buy 9 shares for $9 \times 215 = \$1935$ with \$65 spare.

$$\text{Scenario (1): } S_T = 235 \implies \text{Value of 9 on April 18} = 9 \times 235 = \$2115$$

$$\text{Profit} = 2115 - 1935 = \$180. \implies \text{Profit (\%)} = \frac{180}{1935} \times 100\% \approx 9.30233\%$$

$$\text{Scenario (2): } S_T = 195 \implies \text{Value of 9 shares on April 18} = 9 \times 195 = \$1755$$

$$\text{Profit} = 1755 - 1935 = \$ - 180. \implies \text{Loss (\%)} = \frac{-180}{2000} \times 100\% = -9.302\%$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{(Call option) : If } S_T = 235, \text{ gain} = 75\%, \text{ if } S_T = 195, \text{ loss} = -100\% \\ \text{(Stock purchase) : If } S_T = 235, \text{ gain} = 9.30233\%, \text{ if } S_T = 195, \text{ loss} = -9.302\% \end{array}$$

1. Consider a single-period binomial model with $r = 1/3$, $B_0 = 1$, $S_0 = 2$, $d = 5/4$, $u = 3/2$, and $p = 1/2$. (You can take the sample space Ω to be $\{\omega_1, \omega_2\}$, with ω_1 corresponding to the stock price going “up”, and ω_2 corresponding to the stock price going “down”. In particular, $\mathbf{P}[\{\omega_1\}] = p = 1/2$, etc.)

(a) Compute B_1 .

(b) Compute $S_1(\omega_1)$ and $S_1(\omega_2)$, and the probability of each outcome.

(c) For the trading strategy $\psi = (2, 4)$, compute $V_0(\psi)$, $V_1(\psi)(\omega_1)$, and $V_1(\psi)(\omega_2)$.

(d) Let X be a European call option with strike price \$2.50 and expiration time $T = 1$.

(i) Find $X(\omega_1)$ and $X(\omega_2)$.

(ii) Find the replicating strategy $\phi = (\alpha_1, \beta_1)$ for X .

(iii) Find the manufacturing cost for that strategy. That is, compute $V_0(\phi)$.

(e) Give an example of arbitrage opportunity if the claim X can be purchased for $C_0 = 1/10$ (dollars) at time 0.

$$\text{Data: } r = \frac{1}{3}, \quad B_0 = 1, \quad S_0 = 2, \quad d = \frac{5}{4}, \quad u = \frac{3}{2}, \quad p = \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\Omega = \{\omega_1, \omega_2\}, \quad P(\{\omega_1\}) = P(\{\omega_2\}) = \frac{1}{2}$$

(a)

$$B_1 = (1 + r) B_0 = \left(1 + \frac{1}{3}\right) \cdot 1 = \frac{4}{3}$$

(b)

$$S_1(\omega_1) = S_0 \cdot u = 2 \times \frac{3}{2} = 3, \quad S_1(\omega_2) = S_0 \cdot d = 2 \times \frac{5}{4} = \frac{5}{2}$$

$$P(\omega_1) = \frac{1}{2}, \quad P(\omega_2) = \frac{1}{2}$$

(c)

$$\psi = (2, 4) \implies V_0(\psi) = \underbrace{2S_0}_{=4} + \underbrace{4B_0}_{=4} = 8$$

$$V_1(\psi)(\omega_1) = 2S_1(\omega_1) + 4B_1 = 2 \cdot 3 + 4 \cdot \frac{4}{3} = 6 + \frac{16}{3} = \frac{18+16}{3} = \frac{34}{3}$$

$$V_1(\psi)(\omega_2) = 2S_1(\omega_2) + 4B_1 = 2 \cdot \frac{5}{2} + 4 \cdot \frac{4}{3} = 5 + \frac{16}{3} = \frac{15+16}{3} = \frac{31}{3}$$

(d)

(i)

$X = \text{call with strike } 2.50$

$$\implies X(\omega_1) = \max\{3 - 2.50, 0\} = 0.50, \quad X(\omega_2) = \max\{\frac{5}{2} - 2.50, 0\} = 0$$

(ii)

$$\varphi = (\alpha_1, \beta_1) \text{ solves } \alpha_1 S_1(\omega_1) + \beta_1 B_1 = 0.50, \quad \alpha_1 S_1(\omega_2) + \beta_1 B_1 = 0$$

$$\implies \begin{cases} \alpha_1 \cdot 3 + \beta_1 \cdot \frac{4}{3} = 0.50 \\ \alpha_1 \cdot \frac{5}{2} + \beta_1 \cdot \frac{4}{3} = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\implies \alpha_1 = \frac{0.50 - 0}{3 - \frac{5}{2}} = \frac{0.50}{0.50} = 1$$

$$\implies 3(1) + \frac{4}{3}\beta_1 = 0.50 \implies \frac{4}{3}\beta_1 = -2.50 \implies \beta_1 = -\frac{2.50 \times 3}{4} = -\frac{7.5}{4} = -1.875$$

Therefore $\varphi = (1, -1.875)$

(iii)

$$V_0(\varphi) = \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1 B_0 = (1) \cdot 2 + (-1.875) \cdot 1 = 2 - 1.875 = 0.125$$

So the replicating strategy costs 0.125

(e)

If the claim X can be bought for $C_0 = \frac{1}{10} < 0.125$

sell the replicating strategy - buy the claim for 0.10
receive 0.125 spend 0.10

$$\implies \text{net inflow at } t = 0 : 0.125 - 0.10 = 0.025 > 0$$

At $t = 1$, owe payoff of short replicating = $(-X)$, but own the claim $(+X)$, \implies net = 0

$$\implies \text{arbitrage profit} = 0.025$$

2. Repeat the steps of Exercise 1, with the following data: $r = 1/4$, $B_0 = 1$, $S_0 = 3$, $d = 1$, $u = 2$, and $p = 3/4$. Use the trading strategy $\psi = (3, -2)$ in part (c). The contingent claim X is now a European *put* option with strike price $K = \$4$. Use $C_0 = 1$ in doing part (e).

(a)

$$r = \frac{1}{4} \implies B_0 = 1 \implies B_1 = B_0(1+r) = 1 \times 1.25 = 1.25$$

(b)

$$S_0 = 3, \quad d = 1, \quad u = 2, \quad p = \frac{3}{4} \implies S_1(\omega_1) = S_0 u = 3 \times 2 = 6, \quad S_1(\omega_2) = S_0 d = 3 \times 1 = 3$$

$$\mathbb{P}(\omega_1) = \frac{3}{4}, \quad \mathbb{P}(\omega_2) = \frac{1}{4}$$

(c)

$$\psi = (3, -2) \implies V_0(\psi) = 3S_0 + (-2)B_0 = 3 \times 3 + (-2) \times 1 = 9 - 2 = 7$$

$$V_1(\psi)(\omega_1) = 3S_1(\omega_1) + (-2)B_1 = 3 \times 6 + (-2) \times 1.25 = 18 - 2.5 = 15.5$$

$$V_1(\psi)(\omega_2) = 3S_1(\omega_2) + (-2)B_1 = 3 \times 3 + (-2) \times 1.25 = 9 - 2.5 = 6.5$$

(d)

(i)

$$X = \text{European put with strike } K = 4$$

$$\implies X(\omega_1) = (4 - 6)^+ = 0, \quad X(\omega_2) = (4 - 3)^+ = 1$$

(ii)

$$\text{Risk-free growth: } (1+r) = 1.25 \implies \text{risk-neutral probability } p^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d} = \frac{1.25 - 1}{2 - 1} = 0.25$$

$$\implies \mathbb{E}^*[X] = 0.25 \times 0 + (1 - 0.25) \times 1 = 0.75 \implies \text{fair price} = \frac{0.75}{1.25} = 0.60$$

$$\text{Or we could replicate } X \implies \begin{cases} \alpha S_1(\omega_1) + \beta B_1 = 0, \\ \alpha S_1(\omega_2) + \beta B_1 = 1 \end{cases} \implies \begin{cases} 6\alpha + 1.25\beta = 0 \\ 3\alpha + 1.25\beta = 1 \end{cases}$$

$$\implies (6 - 3)\alpha = 0 - 1 \implies 3\alpha = -1 \implies \alpha = -\frac{1}{3}$$

$$3\left(-\frac{1}{3}\right) + 1.25\beta = 1 \implies -1 + 1.25\beta = 1 \implies 1.25\beta = 2 \implies \beta = 1.6$$

(iii)

$$V_0(\varphi) = \alpha S_0 + \beta B_0 = -\frac{1}{3} \times 3 + 1.6 \times 1 = -1 + 1.6 = 0.60$$

So the unique no-arbitrage value of the put is 0.60

(e)

If the put is sold at $C_0 = 1 > 0.60$, \implies arbitrage:

Short the put at 1, buy replicating portfolio at 0.60

$$\text{net inflow } (t = 0) = 1 - 0.60 = 0.40 > 0$$

At $t = 1$: owe payoff $-X$, replicating portfolio pays $+X$, net = 0

If the put is offered at $C_0 < 0.60$, \implies reverse the trade:

Buy put cheaply, short the replicating portfolio, and invest the difference, again an arbitrage.

3. [Exercise 1 in section 2.4 of the text (page 28).] Consider a single period binomial model with $S_0 = \$100$, $S_1 = \$200$ or $\$50$, $r = 0.25$.

- (a) Find the arbitrage free price of a European call option for one share of stock where the strike price is $K = \$100$ and the exercise time $T = 1$.
- (b) Find a hedging strategy that replicates the value of the option described in (a).
- (c) Suppose the option in (a) is initially priced at \$1 above the arbitrage free price. Describe a strategy (for trading in stock, bond and the option) that is an arbitrage.
- (d) What is the arbitrage free initial price for a put option with the same strike price and exercise time as the call option described in (a)?

$$\text{Data: } S_0 = 100, \quad S_1 \in \{200, 50\}, \quad r = 0.25 \implies B_0 = 1, \quad B_1 = 1 + r = 1.25$$

$$\text{Call payoff: } X = \max\{S_1 - K, 0\} \quad \text{with } K = 100, \quad T = 1$$

(a)

$$X(\omega_{\text{up}}) = \max\{200 - 100, 0\} = 100, \quad X(\omega_{\text{down}}) = \max\{50 - 100, 0\} = 0$$

$$\text{Risk-neutral probability: } p^* = \frac{B_1 - \frac{S_0}{2}}{2 \frac{S_0}{100} - \frac{S_0}{2}} \text{ is } p^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d} \text{ for } u = \frac{200}{100} = 2, \quad d = \frac{50}{100} = 0.5$$

$$p^* = \frac{1.25 - 0.5}{2.0 - 0.5} = \frac{0.75}{1.5} = 0.5$$

$$\mathbb{E}^*[X] = (0.5) \times 100 + (0.5) \times 0 = 50, \quad V_0 = \frac{\mathbb{E}^*[X]}{B_1} = \frac{50}{1.25} = 40$$

$$\implies \text{arbitrage-free call price} = 40$$

(b)

Replicating strategy (α, β)

$$\alpha \cdot 200 + \beta \cdot 1.25 = 100, \quad \alpha \cdot 50 + \beta \cdot 1.25 = 0$$

$$\implies (\alpha)(200 - 50) = 100 - 0 \implies \alpha \times 150 = 100 \implies \alpha = \frac{2}{3}$$

$$\alpha \cdot 200 + 1.25\beta = 100 \implies \frac{2}{3} \cdot 200 + 1.25\beta = 100 \implies \frac{400}{3} + 1.25\beta = 100$$

$$1.25\beta = 100 - \frac{400}{3} = \frac{300 - 400}{3} = -\frac{100}{3} \implies \beta = -\frac{100}{3 \cdot 1.25} = -\frac{80}{3}$$

$$\text{Initial cost } V_0(\alpha, \beta) = \alpha S_0 + \beta(1) = \frac{2}{3} \times 100 + \left(-\frac{80}{3}\right) \times 1 = \frac{200}{3} - \frac{80}{3} = \frac{120}{3} = 40$$

(c) If the option trades at $41 > 40$:

short the option at $+41$, buy replicating strategy at -40 , net inflow $= +1$

At $t = 1$: owe payoff $-X$, replicating strategy pays $+X$, net $= 0$

Therefore riskless profit $= +1$ at $t = 0 \implies$ arbitrage.

(d)

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Put with same } K = 100, T = 1 \implies \text{payoff } P_1 = \max\{K - S_1, 0\} \\ P_1(\omega_{\text{up}}) &= \max\{100 - 200, 0\} = 0, \quad P_1(\omega_{\text{down}}) = \max\{100 - 50, 0\} = 50 \\ \mathbb{E}^*[P_1] &= 0.5 \times 0 + 0.5 \times 50 = 25, \quad V_0(\text{put}) = \frac{25}{1.25} = 20 \\ &\implies \text{arbitrage-free put price} = 20 \end{aligned}$$

Akiva Shmalo
Math 194: The Mathematics of Finance
Homework 3

1. Consider a single-period binomial model with $r = 1/5$, $S_0 = 3$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, and $p = 2/7$. Let X be a European *put* option with strike price $K = \$3$, expiring at time $T = 1$. Compute the arbitrage free price of this option.

$$\text{Data: } r = \frac{1}{5}, \quad S_0 = 3, \quad u = 2, \quad d = \frac{1}{2}, \quad p = \frac{2}{7}, \quad T = 1$$

European put payoff at $T = 1$ with strike $K = 3$: $(K - S_1)^+$

$$\underbrace{S_1^u = S_0 u = 3 \times 2 = 6}_{\text{"up"}}, \quad \underbrace{S_1^d = S_0 d = 3 \times \frac{1}{2} = 1.5}_{\text{"down"}}$$

$$(K - S_1^u)^+ = (3 - 6)^+ = 0, \quad (K - S_1^d)^+ = (3 - 1.5)^+ = 1.5$$

$$\text{Risk-free growth factor} = 1 + r = 1 + \frac{1}{5} = 1.2$$

$$\text{Risk-neutral probability } q^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d} = \frac{1.2 - 0.5}{2 - 0.5} = \frac{0.7}{1.5} = \frac{7}{15} \implies 1 - q^* = \frac{8}{15}$$

$$\text{Expected payoff under } q^*: \mathbb{E}^*[(K - S_1)^+] = (0) \frac{7}{15} + (1.5) \frac{8}{15} = \frac{1.5 \times 8}{15} = \frac{12}{15} = 0.8$$

$$\text{Present value} = \frac{0.8}{1.2} = 0.666\dots = \frac{2}{3}$$

No-arbitrage price of put is $\frac{2}{3}$
--

Replication strategy:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha S_1^u + \beta(1+r) = 0 \\ \alpha S_1^d + \beta(1+r) = 1.5 \end{cases} \implies \begin{cases} \alpha 6 + \beta(1.2) = 0 \\ \alpha(1.5) + \beta(1.2) = 1.5 \end{cases}$$

$$(\alpha 6 - \alpha(1.5)) = 0 - 1.5 \implies 4.5\alpha = -1.5 \implies \alpha = -\frac{1.5}{4.5} = -\frac{1}{3}$$

$$\alpha(1.5) + 1.2\beta = 1.5 \implies -\frac{1}{3} \times (1.5) + 1.2\beta = 1.5 \implies -0.5 + 1.2\beta = 1.5 \implies 1.2\beta = 2 \implies \beta = \frac{5}{3}$$

$$V_0(\alpha, \beta) = \alpha S_0 + \beta = \left(-\frac{1}{3}\right) \times 3 + \frac{5}{3} = -1 + \frac{5}{3} = \frac{2}{3}$$

Replicating cost = $\frac{2}{3}$ matches the risk-neutral price

2. Consider a three period ($T = 3$) binomial model with initial stock price $S_0 = \$8$, $u = 3$, $d = 1/2$, $r = 1/10$, $p = 3/5$.

- Draw the binary tree illustrating the possible paths followed by the stock price process.
- In your diagram, record the probabilities (when the “up” probability is p and the “down” probability is $1 - p$) associated with the individual elements of the sample space $\Omega = \{ddd, ddu, dud, duu, udd, udu, uud, uuu\}$.
- List the events making up the σ -field \mathcal{F}_1 of events determined by S_1 . (Be sure to include the empty set and the whole sample space.)
- Indicate on your binary tree the values (one for each path) of a European contingent claim whose payoff at $T = 3$ is $X = \max(S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3)$.

(a)

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_0 &= 8 \\
 S_1 &= \begin{cases} 8u = 8 \times 3 = 24 & \text{(up)} \\ 8d = 8 \times \frac{1}{2} = 4, & \text{(down)} \end{cases} \\
 S_2 \text{ from } S_1 = 24 : & \begin{cases} 24u = 72 \\ 24d = 12 \end{cases} \implies = 4 : \begin{cases} 4u = 12 \\ 4d = 2 \end{cases} \\
 S_3 & \text{ similar to branches from } S_2.
 \end{aligned}$$

(b)

At each step the “up” probability is $p = \frac{3}{5}$ and the “down” probability is $1 - p = \frac{2}{5}$, so each path $\omega \in \Omega$ has probability:

$$(\# \text{ of up-moves}) \times \frac{3}{5} \quad \text{and} \quad (\# \text{ of down-moves}) \times \frac{2}{5}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P(\text{ddd}) &= \left(\frac{2}{5}\right) \left(\frac{2}{5}\right) \left(\frac{2}{5}\right) = \frac{8}{125} \\
P(\text{ddu}) &= \left(\frac{2}{5}\right) \left(\frac{2}{5}\right) \left(\frac{3}{5}\right) = \frac{12}{125} \\
P(\text{dud}) &= \frac{2}{5} \frac{3}{5} \frac{2}{5} = \frac{12}{125} \\
P(\text{duu}) &= \frac{2}{5} \frac{3}{5} \frac{3}{5} = \frac{18}{125} \\
P(\text{udd}) &= \frac{3}{5} \frac{2}{5} \frac{2}{5} = \frac{12}{125} \\
P(\text{udu}) &= \frac{3}{5} \frac{2}{5} \frac{3}{5} = \frac{18}{125} \\
P(\text{uud}) &= \frac{3}{5} \frac{3}{5} \frac{2}{5} = \frac{18}{125} \\
P(\text{uuu}) &= \frac{3}{5} \frac{3}{5} \frac{3}{5} = \frac{27}{125}
\end{aligned}$$

(c)

\mathcal{F}_1 is generated by S_1 by definition.

$$S_1 \in \{4, 24\} \implies \{S_1 = 4\} = \{\text{ddd}, \text{ddu}, \text{dud}, \text{duu}\}, \quad \{S_1 = 24\} = \{\text{udd}, \text{udu}, \text{uud}, \text{uuu}\}$$

So

$$\mathcal{F}_1 = \{\emptyset, \Omega, \{S_1 = 4\}, \{S_1 = 24\}\}$$

(d)

$X = \max(S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3)$ on each path:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{ddd} : S_1 = 4, S_2 = 2, S_3 = 1 &\implies X = \max\{8, 4, 2, 1\} = 8 \\
\text{ddu} : S_1 = 4, S_2 = 2, S_3 = 6 &\implies X = \max\{8, 4, 2, 6\} = 8 \\
\text{dud} : S_1 = 4, S_2 = 12, S_3 = 6 &\implies X = \max\{8, 4, 12, 6\} = 12 \\
\text{duu} : S_1 = 4, S_2 = 12, S_3 = 36 &\implies X = \max\{8, 4, 12, 36\} = 36 \\
\text{udd} : S_1 = 24, S_2 = 12, S_3 = 6 &\implies X = \max\{8, 24, 12, 6\} = 24 \\
\text{udu} : S_1 = 24, S_2 = 12, S_3 = 36 &\implies X = \max\{8, 24, 12, 36\} = 36 \\
\text{uud} : S_1 = 24, S_2 = 72, S_3 = 36 &\implies X = \max\{8, 24, 72, 36\} = 72 \\
\text{uuu} : S_1 = 24, S_2 = 72, S_3 = 216 &\implies X = \max\{8, 24, 72, 216\} = 216
\end{aligned}$$

$X(\text{ddd}) = 8, \quad X(\text{ddu}) = 8, \quad X(\text{dud}) = 12, \quad X(\text{duu}) = 36$
$X(\text{udd}) = 24, \quad X(\text{udu}) = 36, \quad X(\text{uud}) = 72, \quad X(\text{uuu}) = 216$

2. Consider a CRR model with $T = 2$, $S_0 = \$100$, $S_1 = \$200$ or $S_1 = \$50$, and an associated European call option with strike price $K = \$80$ and exercise time $T = 2$. Assume that the risk free interest rate is $r = 0.1$.

- Draw the binary tree and compute the arbitrage free initial price of the European call option at time zero.
- Determine an explicit hedging strategy for this option.
- Suppose that the option in (a) is initially priced \$2 below the arbitrage free price. Describe a strategy (for trading in stock, bond and the option) that is an arbitrage.
- Try to automate the pricing of a European call option in a computer program where T, S_0, u, d and K are variables.

Data: $T = 2, S_0 = 100, S_1 \in \{200, 50\}, K = 80, r = 0.1$,

European call with strike 80 at $T = 2$

Assuming each period is length 1, : risk-free growth $= 1 + r = 1.1$

Binomial tree:

$$S_2^{uu} = 400, S_2^{ud} = 100, S_2^{du} = 100, S_2^{dd} = 25$$

$$\text{At } t = 2 : C_2(\omega) = \max\{S_2(\omega) - 80, 0\}$$

$$C_2(uu) = \max\{400 - 80, 0\} = 320$$

$$C_2(ud) = \max\{100 - 80, 0\} = 20$$

$$C_2(du) = 20$$

$$C_2(dd) = \max\{25 - 80, 0\} = 0$$

$$p^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u-d} = \frac{1.1 - 0.5}{2.0 - 0.5} = \frac{0.6}{1.5} = 0.4$$

$$\implies (1-p^*) = 0.6$$

Backward induction: C_1^u, C_1^d , and then C_0

$$C_1^u = \frac{1}{1.1} [p^* \cdot C_2^{uu} + (1-p^*) \cdot C_2^{ud}] = \frac{1}{1.1} [0.4 \cdot 320 + 0.6 \cdot 20]$$

$$= \frac{1}{1.1} [128 + 12] = \frac{140}{1.1} = 127.273\dots$$

$$C_1^d = \frac{1}{1.1} [p^* \cdot C_2^{du} + (1-p^*) \cdot C_2^{dd}] = \frac{1}{1.1} [0.4 \cdot 20 + 0.6 \cdot 0] = \frac{1}{1.1} [8] = \frac{8}{1.1} = 7.273\dots$$

$$C_0 = \frac{1}{1.1} [p^* \cdot C_1^u + (1-p^*) \cdot C_1^d] = \frac{1}{1.1} [0.4 \cdot 127.273 + 0.6 \cdot 7.273]$$

$$= \frac{1}{1.1} [50.9091 + 4.3636] = \frac{55.2727}{1.1} = 50.2470\dots$$

$$\implies \text{At } t=0 : C_0 \approx 50.248$$

(b) Hedging strategy

At $t=1$, up node: solve (α_1^u, β_1^u) for $\begin{cases} \alpha_1^u \cdot S_2^{uu} + \beta_1^u \cdot 1.1 = C_2^{uu} = 320 \\ \alpha_1^u \cdot S_2^{ud} + \beta_1^u \cdot 1.1 = C_2^{ud} = 20 \end{cases}$

$$S_2^{uu} = 400, S_2^{ud} = 100$$

$$\alpha_1^u(400 - 100) = 320 - 20 \implies 300 \alpha_1^u = 300 \implies \alpha_1^u = 1$$

$$\alpha_1^u \cdot 400 + 1.1 \beta_1^u = 320 \implies 400 + 1.1 \beta_1^u = 320 \implies 1.1 \beta_1^u = -80 \implies \beta_1^u = -\frac{80}{1.1} = -72.727\dots$$

$$\text{At } t=1, \text{ up node} = \alpha_1^u S_1^u + \beta_1^u = (1) \cdot 200 + (-72.727) = 127.273 \approx C_1^u$$

At $t=1$, down node: solve (α_1^d, β_1^d) for $\begin{cases} \alpha_1^d \cdot 100 + \beta_1^d \cdot 1.1 = 20 \\ \alpha_1^d \cdot 25 + \beta_1^d \cdot 1.1 = 0 \end{cases}$

$$\alpha_1^d(100 - 25) = 20 - 0 \implies 75 \alpha_1^d = 20 \implies \alpha_1^d = \frac{20}{75} = \frac{4}{15} = 0.267$$

$$100 \cdot 0.267 + 1.1 \beta_1^d = 20 \implies 26.67 + 1.1 \beta_1^d = 20 \implies 1.1 \beta_1^d = -6.67 \implies \beta_1^d = -6.06\dots$$

$$C_1^d = \alpha_1^d S_1^d + \beta_1^d = 0.267 \cdot 50 + (-6.06\dots) = 13.33 - 6.06\dots = 7.27\dots$$

At $t=0$: solve (α_0, β_0) for $\begin{cases} \alpha_0 \cdot S_1^u + \beta_0 \cdot 1.1 = C_1^u = 127.273\dots, \\ \alpha_0 \cdot S_1^d + \beta_0 \cdot 1.1 = C_1^d = 7.273\dots \end{cases}$

$$S_1^u = 200, S_1^d = 50$$

$$\alpha_0(200 - 50) = 127.273 - 7.273 \implies 150 \alpha_0 = 120 \implies \alpha_0 = 0.800$$

$$200 \cdot 0.800 + 1.1 \beta_0 = 127.273 \implies 160 + 1.1 \beta_0 = 127.273 \implies 1.1 \beta_0 = -32.7273 \implies \beta_0 = -29.752\dots$$

$$C_0 = \alpha_0 S_0 + \beta_0 = 0.800 \cdot 100 + (-29.752) = 80 - 29.752 \approx 50.248$$

(c) Arbitrage

$(C_0 - 2) = 48.248 < 50.248 \implies$ buy the call, short the replicating strategy, invest the difference.

$$\underbrace{\text{Cost to short replicating}}_{+50.248} - \underbrace{\text{Cost to buy call}}_{-48.248} = +2.0 \implies \text{collect } +2.0 \text{ at } t=0$$

$$\text{At } t=2 : \text{short owes } -C_2, \text{ but hold the call } +C_2, \implies \text{net} = 0$$

$$\text{Arbitrage} = +2.0$$

1. Consider the Multi-period Binomial Model (the CRR model) with parameter values as in Exercise 2 on page 28 of the text. Under a *forward contract*, the holder of a long position in the contract has agreed to buy 100 shares of stock at time $T = 2$ for a fixed (total) price $\$F$. What should F be so that neither the holder of the long position in the contract, nor the holder of the short position (the seller) has an arbitrage opportunity? Identify the relevant European contingent claim, and derive F using arbitrage-free pricing. (Reminder: No money changes hands at time $t = 0$ when the forward contract is written.)

$$\underbrace{S_0 = 100, \quad S_1(u) = 200, \quad S_1(d) = 50, \quad r = 0.1}_{\text{Given}}$$

For arb free we use

$$p^* = \frac{1 + r - d}{u - d} = \frac{0.6}{1.5} = 0.4 \quad (\text{up, } 0.6 \text{ down})$$

S_2 Probabilities

$X_2 =$ stock price at time $T = 2$

Probabilities of each path:

$$dd = 0.6 \cdot 0.6 = 0.36 \quad du = 0.6 \cdot 0.4 = 0.24$$

$$ud = 0.4 \cdot 0.6 = 0.24 \quad uu = 0.4 \cdot 0.4 = 0.16$$

Expected value of stock price (at $T = 2$):

$$\mathbb{E}(X_2) = (0.36)(25) + (0.24)(100) + (0.24)(100) + (0.16)(400) = 121$$

Arbitrage-free forward price for 100 shares:

$$\boxed{F = 100 \cdot \mathbb{E}(X_2) = 100 \cdot 121 = 12,100}$$

2. Consider the probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbf{P})$ in which (i) $\Omega = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, (ii) \mathcal{F} is the σ -field of all subsets of Ω , and (iii) $\mathbf{P}[A] = \text{card}(A)/4$ for each $A \in \mathcal{F}$. (Here, $\text{card}(A)$, the cardinality of A , is simply the number of elements of A .) This probability space is a model for an experiment with four equally likely outcomes. Let \mathcal{G} be the σ -field generated by the partition $\mathcal{P} = \{\{1, 2\}, \{3, 4\}\}$ and let \mathcal{H} be the σ -field generated by the partition $\mathcal{Q} = \{\{1\}, \{2\}, \{3, 4\}\}$. Notice that $\mathcal{G} \subset \mathcal{H}$. Let X be the random variable defined by $X(i) = 3i + 1$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

- Compute $\mathbf{E}[X]$.
- Compute $\mathbf{E}[X|\mathcal{G}]$.
- Compute $\mathbf{E}[X|\mathcal{H}]$.
- Compute $\mathbf{E}[\mathbf{E}[X|\mathcal{H}]|\mathcal{G}]$.
- Does your answer in (d) confirm the Tower Property of conditional expectations?

$$\Omega = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}, \quad \mathbb{P}[\{i\}] = \frac{1}{4}, \quad X(i) = 3i + 1 \implies \begin{cases} X(1) = 4 \\ X(2) = 7 \\ X(3) = 10 \\ X(4) = 13 \end{cases}$$

(a)
$$\mathbf{E}[X] = \sum_{i=1}^4 X(i) \mathbb{P}[\{i\}] = \frac{1}{4}(4 + 7 + 10 + 13) = \frac{34}{4} = \frac{17}{2}$$

(b) Events of \mathcal{G} :

$$A_1 = \{1, 2\}, \quad A_2 = \{3, 4\}, \quad \mathbb{P}(A_1) = \mathbb{P}(A_2) = \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\mathbf{E}[X | A_1] = \frac{1}{4}(X(1) + X(2)) = \frac{1}{4}(4 + 7) = \frac{11}{4}$$

$$\mathbf{E}[X | A_2] = \frac{1}{4}(X(3) + X(4)) = \frac{1}{4}(10 + 13) = \frac{23}{4}$$

$$\mathbf{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] = \frac{11}{4} \cdot \frac{1}{2} + \frac{23}{4} \cdot \frac{1}{2} = \frac{11}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{2} + \frac{23}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{2} = \frac{11}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{2} + \frac{23}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\mathbf{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] = 0.5(0.5X(1) + 0.5X(2)) + 0.5(0.5X(3) + 0.5X(4))$$

$$\mathbf{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] = \frac{11}{2} \mathbb{P}(\{1, 2\}) + \frac{23}{2} \mathbb{P}(\{3, 4\}) = \frac{11}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{2} + \frac{23}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{2} = \frac{17}{2} = 8.5$$

(c)

block of \mathcal{H}	$\mathbf{E}[X \text{block of } \mathcal{H}]$	Since $\mathbb{P}(\{1\}) = \mathbb{P}(\{2\}) = \mathbb{P}(\{3, 4\}) = \frac{1}{3}$
$\{1\}$	4	$\implies \mathbf{E}[X \mathcal{H}] = \sum_{\text{blocks}} \mathbf{E}[X \text{block}] \mathbb{P}(\text{block})$
$\{2\}$	7	
$\{3, 4\}$	$\frac{10 + 13}{2} = 11.5$	
$\therefore \mathbf{E}[X \mathcal{H}] = (4 + 7 + 11.5) \times \frac{1}{3} = \frac{22.5}{3} = 7.5$		

(d)

block of \mathcal{G}	$\mathbf{E}[\mathbf{E}[X \mathcal{H}] \text{block}]$
$\{1, 2\}$	$\frac{\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{E}}{2} = \frac{4 + 7}{2} = 5.5$
$\{3, 4\}$	$\frac{\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{E}}{2} = \frac{11.5 + 11.5}{2} = 11.5$

$$\mathbf{E}[\mathbf{E}[X | \mathcal{H}] | \mathcal{G}] = 5.5 \cdot \mathbb{P}(\{1, 2\}) + 11.5 \cdot \mathbb{P}(\{3, 4\})$$

$$\mathbf{E}[\mathbf{E}[X | \mathcal{H}] | \mathcal{G}] = 5.5 \cdot \frac{1}{2} + 11.5 \cdot \frac{1}{2} = 8.5 = \mathbf{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] = \mathbf{E}[X]$$

\implies (e) Tower Property is verified.

5. Consider a CRR model with terminal time T . A European call option with strike price K and expiration date T has value $C_T = (S_T - K)^+$ at time T . A European put option with the same strike price and expiration date has value $P_T = (K - S_T)^+$ at time T . Note that $C_T - P_T = S_T - K$. Let $\{C_t, t = 0, 1, \dots, T-1\}$ and $\{P_t, t = 0, 1, \dots, T-1\}$ denote the arbitrage free price processes for the call and put options, respectively (cf. Exercise 4). Show that the following call-put parity relation holds:

$$C_t - P_t = S_t - K/(1+r)^{T-t}, \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T-1. \quad (2.66)$$

Note, you can show this using either a “no arbitrage” argument or the formulas for C_t, P_t resulting from Exercise 3.

$$\underbrace{C_t - P_t = S_t - \frac{K}{(1+r)^{T-t}}}_{WTS} \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T-1$$

$$C_T - P_T = (S_T - K)^+ - (K - S_T)^+ = \underbrace{S_T - K}_{\text{one term is positive}}$$

$$\implies \frac{C_T - P_T}{(1+r)^{T-t}} = \frac{S_T}{(1+r)^{T-t}} - \frac{K}{(1+r)^{T-t}}$$

$$C_t - P_t = \mathbb{E}^* \left[\frac{C_T - P_T}{(1+r)^{T-t}} \mid \mathcal{F}_t \right]$$

$$= \mathbb{E}^* \left[\frac{S_T}{(1+r)^{T-t}} \mid \mathcal{F}_t \right] - \frac{K}{(1+r)^{T-t}}$$

$$\mathbb{E}^* \left[\frac{S_T}{(1+r)^{T-t}} \mid \mathcal{F}_t \right] = \frac{1}{(1+r)^{T-t}} \mathbb{E}^* [S_T \mid \mathcal{F}_t]$$

$$= \frac{1}{(1+r)^{T-t}} [(1+r)^{T-t} S_t] \quad (\text{martingale property})$$

$$= S_t$$

$$C_t - P_t = S_t - \frac{K}{(1+r)^{T-t}}, \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T-1$$

2. In the context of the Multi-period Binomial Model, let M_0, M_1, \dots, M_T be a martingale.

(a) Let $f : \mathbf{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{R}$ be a *concave* function. Show that $\{f(M_0), f(M_1), \dots, f(M_T)\}$ is a supermartingale. [Hint: Use the conditional form of Jensen's Inequality as discussed in class.]

(b) Assume, in addition, that $M_t \geq 0$ for each $t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T$. Show that

$$\sqrt{M_0}, \sqrt{M_1}, \dots, \sqrt{M_T}$$

is a supermartingale.

(a) Jensen's Inequality

$$\varphi \implies \begin{cases} \mathbb{E}[\varphi(Z)] \geq \varphi(\mathbb{E}(Z)) & \varphi \text{ is convex} \\ \mathbb{E}[\varphi(Z)] \leq \varphi(\mathbb{E}(Z)) & \varphi \text{ is concave} \end{cases} \quad t \in \{0, \dots, T-1\}$$

$f \text{ concave} \implies (f(M_t))_{t=0}^T \text{ is a supermartingale}$

$$\mathbb{E}[f(M_{t+1}) \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \underset{\text{(Jensen, concave } f)}}{\leq} f\left(\underbrace{\mathbb{E}[M_{t+1} \mid \mathcal{F}_t]}_{= M_t \text{ (martingale)}}\right) = f(M_t)$$

$$\implies \mathbb{E}[f(M_{t+1}) \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \leq f(M_t), \quad t = 0, \dots, T-1$$

$$\implies (f(M_t))_{t=0}^T \text{ is a supermartingale}$$

(b)

$$f(x) = x^{1/2}, \quad x \geq 0.$$

$$f'(x) = \frac{1}{2} x^{-1/2}, \quad f''(x) = -\frac{1}{4} x^{-3/2} < 0 \implies f \text{ concave on } [0, \infty)$$

Assuming $M_t \geq 0$ ($t = 0, 1, \dots, T$), hypotheses of part (a) satisfied:

$$\implies \sqrt{M_0}, \sqrt{M_1}, \dots, \sqrt{M_T} \text{ is a supermartingale}$$

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Homework 6

1. The setting for this problem is the multi-period binomial model with $T = 2$, $S_0 = \$100$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, $r = 0.1$. Consider an American *put* option with strike price $K = \$120$.

(a) Use a binary tree to compute the no-arbitrage initial price of the American put option.

(b) Determine an explicit superhedging strategy ϕ^* for this option.

(c) Suppose that you can buy the American put option at time zero for \$1 less than its no-arbitrage price. Describe an investment strategy that yields an arbitrage opportunity for a buyer of the American put option. In particular, you need to describe the stopping time at which the buyer will exercise the option.

$$T = 2, S_0 = 100, u = 2, d = \frac{1}{2}, r = 0.1, K = 120$$

(a) *No-arbitrage price*

$$\underbrace{p^* = \frac{1+r-d}{u-d}}_{\text{risk-neutral prob.}} = \frac{2}{5} \implies \frac{1}{1+r} = \frac{10}{11}$$

path	Y_2
UU	0
UD	20
DU	20
DD	95

$$U_1^u = \left[\frac{10}{11}(q \cdot 0 + (1-q) \cdot 20) \right]^+ = \frac{120}{11}$$

$$U_1^d = 70 + \left[\frac{10}{11}(q \cdot 20 + (1-q) \cdot 95) - 70 \right]^+ = 70 + 0 = 70$$

$$U_0 = \frac{10}{11}(q U_1^u + (1-q) U_1^d) \implies \frac{5100}{121} \approx 42.15$$

(b) *Super-hedging strategy*

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_0 &= \frac{U_1^u - U_1^d}{S_1^u - S_1^d} \implies -\frac{13}{33}, & \beta_0 &= \frac{U_1^d - \alpha_0 S_1^d}{1+r} \implies \frac{29600}{363}, & \xi_0 &= 0 \\ \alpha_1^u &= \frac{0 - 20}{400 - 100} = -\frac{1}{15}, & \beta_1^u &= \frac{20 + \frac{1}{15} \cdot 100}{1.1} = \frac{800}{33}, & \xi_1^u &= 0 \\ \alpha_1^d &= \frac{20 - 95}{100 - 25} = -1, & \beta_1^d &= \frac{95 + 25}{1.1} = \frac{1200}{11}, & \xi_1^d &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

(c) *Buyer's arbitrage if price = $U_0 - 1$*

Borrow \$1 \implies buy the put, short (α_0, β_0)

Exercise at

$$\tau^* = \min\{t \leq 2 : U_t = Y_t\} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if first move is } d \\ 2 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The price gap grows at rate r , so your gain is always above 0.

2. The setting for this problem is the multi-period binomial model with $T = 2$, $S_0 = \$12$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, but now $r = 1/4$. Consider an American claim based on the payoff sequence Y give by

$$Y_0 = (12 - S_0)^+, \quad Y_1 = \left(12 - \frac{S_0 + S_1}{2}\right)^+, \quad Y_2 = \left(12 - \frac{S_0 + S_1 + S_2}{3}\right)^+.$$

(This is like a put option based on the average stock price up to time t , rather than on the stock price itself.)

(a) Construct the necessary wealth process U_0, U_1, U_2 , for this claim, best displayed as a tree.

(b) What is the no-arbitrage price for the claim?

(c) Describe a good time for the buyer of the claim to exercise the claim.

(a) *Wealth Process*

Given

$$T = 2, S_0 = 12, u = 2, d = \frac{1}{2}$$

$$r = \frac{1}{4} \implies p^* = \frac{1+r-d}{u-d} = \frac{1.25-0.5}{2-0.5} = 0.5, \quad \beta = \frac{1}{1+r} = \frac{4}{5} = 0.8$$

T = 1

$$S_1^u = uS_0 = 2 \cdot 12 \implies 24$$

$$\bar{S}_1^u = \frac{S_0 + S_1^u}{2} = \frac{12 + 24}{2} \implies 18$$

$$S_1^d = dS_0 = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 12 \implies 6$$

$$\bar{S}_1^d = \frac{S_0 + S_1^d}{2} = \frac{12 + 6}{2} \implies 9$$

T = 2

$$S_2^{uu} = uS_1^u = 2 \cdot 24 \implies 48$$

$$\bar{S}_2^{uu} = \frac{S_0 + S_1^u + S_2^{uu}}{3} = \frac{12 + 24 + 48}{3} \implies 28$$

$$Y_2^{uu} = (12 - \bar{S}_2^{uu})^+ = (12 - 28)^+ = 0$$

$$S_2^{du} = uS_1^d = 2 \cdot 6 \implies 12$$

$$\bar{S}_2^{du} = \frac{12 + 6 + 12}{3} = 10$$

$$Y_2^{du} = (12 - 10)^+ = 2$$

$$S_2^{ud} = dS_1^u = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 24 \implies 12$$

$$\bar{S}_2^{ud} = \frac{12 + 24 + 12}{3} = 16$$

$$Y_2^{ud} = (12 - 16)^+ = 0$$

$$S_2^{dd} = dS_1^d = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 6 \implies 3$$

$$\bar{S}_2^{dd} = \frac{12 + 6 + 3}{3} = 7$$

$$Y_2^{dd} = (12 - 7)^+ = 5$$

$$\boxed{U_2 = Y_2} \quad (0, 0, 2, 5) \text{ in the order of } (uu, ud, du, dd)$$

Backward Induction

$$C_1^u = \beta(qU_2^{uu} + (1-q)U_2^{ud}) = 0.8(0.5 \cdot 0 + 0.5 \cdot 0) \implies 0$$

$$U_1^u = [C_1^u]^+ = 0$$

$$C_1^d = \beta(qU_2^{du} + (1-q)U_2^{dd}) = 0.8(0.5 \cdot 2 + 0.5 \cdot 5) \implies 2.8$$

$$U_1^d = (Y_1^d - C_1^d)^+ + C_1^d = (3 - 2.8)^+ + 2.8 = 3$$

T=0

$$C_0 = \beta(qU_1^u + (1-q)U_1^d) = 0.8(0.5 \cdot 0 + 0.5 \cdot 3) \implies 1.2$$

$$U_0 = (Y_0 - C_0)^+ + C_0 = (0 - 1.2)^+ + 1.2 = 1.2$$

(b) *No-arbitrage price*

$$U_0 = 1.2$$

(c) *Best time to exercise*

The exercise time is defined by the stopping rule

$$\tau^* := \min\{t \leq 2 : U_t = Y_t\}$$

Since

$$U_0 > Y_0$$

$$U_1 = Y_1 \quad \underbrace{\text{for both } d \text{ step and } u \text{ step}}_{\text{minimum time where } U_t=Y_t}$$

$$U_2 = Y_2$$

Therefore,

$$\tau^* = 1 \text{ with probability } 1$$

So the claim should be exercised at $t = 1$

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HW 7

1. Consider the multi-step binary model with $T = 2$, $S_0 = \$100$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, and $r = 1/5$. In this problem we shall use the real-world probability \mathbf{P} for which “up” and “down” branches each have probability $p = 1/2$. Let adapted sequences of random variables $Y = \{Y_0, Y_1, Y_2\}$ and $U = \{U_0, U_1, U_2\}$ be defined by

$$Y_0 = 30, Y_1^d = 27, Y_1^u = 34, Y_2^{dd} = Y_2^{uu} = 50, Y_2^{du} = Y_2^{ud} = 10,$$

and

$$U_0 = 32, U_1^d = 30, U_1^u = 34, U_2^{dd} = U_2^{uu} = 50, U_2^{du} = U_2^{ud} = 10.$$

(a) Verify that $\{U_0, U_1, U_2\}$ is a \mathbf{P} -supermartingale.

(b) The recipe $\tau = \min\{t : U_t = Y_t\}$ defines a stopping time. Compute $\tau(dd)$, $\tau(du)$, $\tau(ud)$, and $\tau(uu)$.

(c) Compute $\mathbf{E}[Y_\tau]$, where τ is as in part (c).

$$(a) \quad \mathbb{E}[U_1 \mid \mathcal{F}_0] = \frac{1}{2}(U_1^d + U_1^u) = \frac{1}{2}(30 + 34) = 32 = U_0$$

$$\mathbb{E}[U_2 \mid \mathcal{F}_1^d] = \frac{1}{2}(U_2^{dd} + U_2^{du}) = \frac{1}{2}(50 + 10) = 30 = U_1^d$$

$$\mathbb{E}[U_2 \mid \mathcal{F}_1^u] = \frac{1}{2}(U_2^{uu} + U_2^{ud}) = \frac{1}{2}(50 + 10) = 30 \leq U_1^u = 34$$

$$\mathbb{E}[U_{t+1} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \leq U_t \text{ for } t = 0, 1 \implies \{U_0, U_1, U_2\} \text{ is a } \mathbb{P}\text{-supermartingale}$$

$$(b) \quad \tau = \min\{t : U_t = Y_t\} \implies$$

$$U_1^d = 30, Y_1^d = 27 \implies U_1^d \neq Y_1^d, \quad U_1^u = 34, Y_1^u = 34 \implies U_1^u = Y_1^u$$

$$\tau(dd) = 2, \quad \tau(du) = 2$$

$$\tau(ud) = 1, \quad \tau(uu) = 1$$

$$(c) \quad \mathbb{E}[Y_\tau] = \frac{Y_{\tau(dd)} + Y_{\tau(du)} + Y_{\tau(ud)} + Y_{\tau(uu)}}{4} = \frac{50 + 10 + 34 + 34}{4} = \frac{128}{4} = 32 = U_0$$

2. For this problem use the model data from Exercise 6, Section 2.4 (page 29 of the text). An American *asset-or-nothing* (call) option is the American contingent claim (ACC) based on the payoffs

$$Y_t = \begin{cases} F, & \text{if } S_t \geq K, \\ 0, & \text{if } S_t < K, \end{cases}$$

and can be exercised at any time t in $\{0, 1, 2\}$. Let us take $K = \$90$ and $F = \$120$. Fill in the tree diagram for the necessary wealth process $U = \{U_0, U_1, U_2\}$, thereby computing the no-arbitrage price U_0 for this ACC.

$T = 2, \quad S_0 = 100, \quad u = 2, \quad d = \frac{1}{2}, \quad r = \frac{1}{10}, \quad \delta = \frac{10}{11}, \quad p^* = \frac{1+r-d}{u-d} = \frac{0.6}{1.5} = \frac{2}{5}, \quad 1-p^* = \frac{3}{5}$
 S_t -tree

Y_t tree

U-Tree recursion

$$U_2^{dd} = 0$$

$$U_2^{du} = U_2^{ud} = U_2^{uu} = 120$$

$$U_1^d = \max\left(0, \delta [p^* U_2^{du} + (1-p^*) U_2^{dd}]\right) = \frac{10}{11} \left[\frac{2}{5} \cdot 120\right] = \frac{480}{11}$$

$$U_1^u = \max\left(120, \delta [p^* U_2^{uu} + (1-p^*) U_2^{ud}]\right) = \max\left(120, \frac{10}{11} \cdot 120\right) = 120$$

$$C_0 := \delta [p^* U_1^u + (1-p^*) U_1^d] = \frac{10}{11} \left[\frac{2}{5} \cdot 120 + \frac{3}{5} \cdot \frac{480}{11}\right] = \frac{8160}{121} \approx 67.44$$

$$U_0 = \max(Y_0, C_0) = \max(120, 67.44) = 120 \implies \text{the no-arbitrage price is } \boxed{120}$$

U_t -tree

Problem 3

(a) Stock tree S_t^1

Payoff tree $Y_t = \max(0, S_t^1 - 6)$

Thus the terminal claim

$$X(dd) = 0, X(du) = 0, X(ud) = 2, X(uu) = 3$$

(b) Martingale probabilities

$$5 = p_0 \cdot 8 + (1 - p_0) \cdot 4 \implies 4p_0 = 1 \implies p_0 = \boxed{\frac{1}{4}}$$

$$8 = p_{1,u} \cdot 9 + (1 - p_{1,u}) \cdot 6 \implies 3p_{1,u} = 2 \implies p_{1,u} = \boxed{\frac{2}{3}}$$

$$4 = p_{1,d} \cdot 5 + (1 - p_{1,d}) \cdot 2 \implies 3p_{1,d} = 2 \implies p_{1,d} = \boxed{\frac{2}{3}}$$

$$\mathbb{P}^*(uu) = \frac{1}{6}, \mathbb{P}^*(ud) = \frac{1}{12}, \mathbb{P}^*(du) = \frac{1}{2}, \mathbb{P}^*(dd) = \frac{1}{4}$$

(c) Backward valuation $V_t = \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{P}^*}[X | \mathcal{F}_t]$

$$V_1^u = p_{1,u} \cdot 3 + (1 - p_{1,u}) \cdot 2 = \frac{2}{3} \cdot 3 + \frac{1}{3} \cdot 2 = \frac{8}{3}$$

$$V_1^d = 0$$

$$V_0 = p_0 V_1^u + (1 - p_0) V_1^d = \frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{8}{3} = \boxed{\frac{2}{3}}$$

Replicating strategy

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{V_1^u - V_1^d}{S_1^u - S_1^d} = \frac{\frac{8}{3} - 0}{8 - 4} = \frac{2}{3}, \quad \beta_1 = V_1^d - \alpha_1 S_1^d = 0 - \frac{2}{3} \cdot 4 = -\frac{8}{3}$$

Rebalance at $t = 1$:

$$\text{If } S_1 = 8: \quad \alpha_2^u = \frac{3 - 2}{9 - 6} = \frac{1}{3}, \quad \beta_2^u = 3 - \alpha_2^u \cdot 9 = 0$$

$$\text{If } S_1 = 4: \quad \alpha_2^d = 0, \quad \beta_2^d = 0$$

(d) Arbitrage-free price

$$V_0 = \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{P}^*}[X] = \frac{1}{6} \cdot 3 + \frac{1}{12} \cdot 2 = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{6} = \boxed{\frac{2}{3}}$$

$$(\alpha_1, \beta_1) \quad \text{at } t = 0, \quad (\alpha_2^u, \beta_2^u) \text{ or } (\alpha_2^d, \beta_2^d) \quad \text{at } t = 1$$

reproduces the four final payoffs therefore $V_0 = \frac{2}{3}$ is the no-arbitrage price.

1. In this exercise we use the setting of Exercise 2, Section 3.7 (page 52–53 of the text). (The full statement of Exercise 2 from Section 3.7 can be found on the Homework 7 page in Assignments on Canvas.) In Homework 7 you saw that this model admits an Equivalent Martingale Measure. This market is therefore *viable*, by the First Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing. Is this market complete?

Theorem (Second Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing (SFTAP))

Assuming viability (i.e. no arbitrage and the existence of at least one Equivalent Martingale Measure), the market is complete if and only if the EMM is unique. Formally:

$$\text{Market is complete} \iff \text{The EMM is unique.}$$

HW 7

Q3 (a) Stock tree S_t^1

Since we found P^* using the tree itself it must be unique for this tree

(b) Martingale probabilities

$$5 = p_0 \cdot 8 + (1 - p_0) \cdot 4 \implies 4p_0 = 1 \implies p_0 = \boxed{\frac{1}{4}}$$

$$8 = p_{1,u} \cdot 9 + (1 - p_{1,u}) \cdot 6 \implies 3p_{1,u} = 2 \implies p_{1,u} = \boxed{\frac{2}{3}}$$

$$4 = p_{1,d} \cdot 5 + (1 - p_{1,d}) \cdot 2 \implies 3p_{1,d} = 2 \implies p_{1,d} = \boxed{\frac{2}{3}}$$

$$\mathbb{P}^*(uu) = \frac{1}{6}, \mathbb{P}^*(ud) = \frac{1}{12}, \mathbb{P}^*(du) = \frac{1}{2}, \mathbb{P}^*(dd) = \frac{1}{4}$$

2. In this exercise we also use the setting of Exercise 2, Section 3.7 (page 52–53 of the text). Consult the solution of Exercise 3 on Homework 7 for a description of an Equivalent Martingale Measure \mathbf{P}^* .

(a) Use \mathbf{P}^* to compute the time t price C_t of the European call option with payoff $(S_2^1 - 6)^+$ for $t = 0, 1$.

(b) Now use \mathbf{P}^* to compute the time t price P_t of the European put option with payoff $(6 - S_2^1)^+$ for $t = 0, 1$.

(c) Confirm the call-put parity relationship $C_t - P_t = S_t - 6$ for $t = 0, 1$.

Payoff tree $C_t = \max(0, S_t - 6)$

$$X(dd) = 0, X(du) = 0, X(ud) = 2, X(uu) = 3$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_1^d &= \frac{1}{3} \cdot 0 + \frac{2}{3} \cdot 0 = 0 \\ C_1^u &= \frac{1}{3} \cdot 0 + \frac{2}{3} \cdot 3 = 2 \end{aligned} \implies C_0 = 0 \cdot \frac{3}{4} + 2 \cdot \frac{1}{4} = \frac{1}{2}$$

Payoff Tree $X_t = \max(0, 6 - S_t^1)$

$$\begin{aligned} P_1^d &= \frac{1}{3} \cdot 4 + \frac{2}{3} \cdot 1 = 2 \\ P_1^u &= 0 \end{aligned} \implies P_0 = \frac{3}{4} \cdot 2 + \frac{1}{4} \cdot 0 = \frac{3}{2}$$

$$C_t - P_t = S_t - 6$$

$$\mathbf{T} = 0: C_0 - P_0 = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{3}{2} = -\frac{2}{2} = -1$$

$$S_0 - 6 = 5 - 6 = -1 \quad \checkmark$$

$$\mathbf{T} = 1: C_1^d - P_1^d = 0 - 2 = -2 \\ S_1^d - 6 = 4 - 6 = -2 \quad \checkmark$$

$$C_1^u - P_1^u = 2 - 0 = 2 \\ S_1^u - 6 = 8 - 6 = 2 \quad \checkmark$$

3. (This is Exercise 3, Section 3.7, page 53 of the text.)

Consider a finite market model with $T = 2$, $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \omega_4, \omega_5\}$, $\mathbf{P}(\omega_i) > 0$ for $i = 1, \dots, 5$. Suppose there are two assets, a riskless asset with price process $S^0 = \{S_t^0, t = 0, 1, 2\}$ where $S_t^0 = (1 + r)^t$ for $t = 0, 1, 2$ and some $r \geq 0$; and a risky asset with price process $S^1 = \{S_t^1, t = 0, 1, 2\}$ where

$$\begin{aligned} S_0^1(\omega_1) &= 5, & S_1^1(\omega_1) &= 8, & S_2^1(\omega_1) &= 9 \\ S_0^1(\omega_2) &= 5, & S_1^1(\omega_2) &= 8, & S_2^1(\omega_2) &= 7 \\ S_0^1(\omega_3) &= 5, & S_1^1(\omega_3) &= 4, & S_2^1(\omega_3) &= 6 \\ S_0^1(\omega_4) &= 5, & S_1^1(\omega_4) &= 4, & S_2^1(\omega_4) &= 5 \\ S_0^1(\omega_5) &= 5, & S_1^1(\omega_5) &= 4, & S_2^1(\omega_5) &= 2 \end{aligned}$$

- (a) Draw a tree to indicate the possible “paths” followed by the risky asset price process S^1 .
- (b) Suppose $r = 0.1$. Is there an equivalent martingale measure for this model? If there is one, is it unique? If there is not one, demonstrate an arbitrage opportunity. What are the answers to the last three questions if $r = 1$?

(a) S-Tree:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{(b)} \quad r = 0.1 &\implies S_t^0 = (1.1)^t \implies \tilde{S}_t^1 := \frac{S_t^1}{S_t^0} \\
&\implies \tilde{S}_0^1 = \frac{5}{1} = 5, \quad \tilde{S}_1^1 = \begin{cases} \frac{8}{1.1} = \frac{80}{11} & \omega_1, \omega_2 \\ \frac{4}{1.1} = \frac{40}{11} & \omega_3, \omega_4, \omega_5 \end{cases} \\
&\tilde{S}_2^1 = \begin{cases} \frac{9}{1.21} = \frac{900}{121} & \omega_1 \\ \frac{7}{1.21} = \frac{700}{121} & \omega_2 \\ \frac{6}{1.21} = \frac{600}{121} & \omega_3 \\ \frac{5}{1.21} = \frac{500}{121} & \omega_4 \\ \frac{2}{1.21} = \frac{200}{121} & \omega_5 \end{cases}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Let } \mathbb{Q} = (q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4, q_5), \quad \sum q_i = 1, \quad q_i > 0$$

Martingale at T = 0

$$\begin{aligned}
5 &= \mathbb{E}^*[\tilde{S}_1^1] = \frac{80}{11}(q_1 + q_2) + \frac{40}{11}(q_3 + q_4 + q_5) \\
&= \frac{80}{11}(q_1 + q_2) + \frac{40}{11}(1 - q_1 - q_2) = \underbrace{\frac{40}{11}(1 + q_1 + q_2)}_{\text{simplify}} \implies q_1 + q_2 = \frac{3}{8}
\end{aligned}$$

Martingale at T = 1

Up branch

$$\frac{q_1}{q_1 + q_2} \cdot \frac{900}{121} + \frac{q_2}{q_1 + q_2} \cdot \frac{700}{121} = \frac{80}{11}$$

$$\text{Let } x = \frac{q_1}{q_1 + q_2} \implies \frac{900x + 700(1 - x)}{121} = \frac{80}{11}$$

$$\implies \frac{200x + 700}{121} = \frac{80}{11} \implies 200x + 700 = 880 \implies x = \frac{9}{10}$$

$$\implies q_1 = \frac{9}{10} \cdot \frac{3}{8} = \frac{27}{80}, \quad q_2 = \frac{3}{80}$$

Down branch

$$a = \mathbb{Q}(\omega_5 \mid S_1^1 = 4), \quad b = \mathbb{Q}(\omega_4 \mid S_1^1 = 4), \quad c = \mathbb{Q}(\omega_3 \mid S_1^1 = 4)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} a + b + c = 1 \\ \frac{10}{11}(2a + 5b + 6c) = 4 \\ a, b, c > 0 \end{array} \right\} \implies \text{EMM exists, not unique}$$

$$\text{Suppose } r = 1 \implies S_t^0 = 2^t: \tilde{S}_0^1 = 5, \quad \tilde{S}_1^1 = \begin{cases} \frac{8}{2} = 4 & \omega_1, \omega_2 \\ \frac{4}{2} = 2 & \omega_3, \omega_4, \omega_5 \end{cases}$$

$$\mathbb{E}^*[\tilde{S}_1^1] = 4(q_1 + q_2) + 2(1 - q_1 - q_2) = \underbrace{2 + 2(q_1 + q_2)}_{\text{for no arbitrage}} = 5 \implies q_1 + q_2 = \frac{3}{2} > 1$$

No EMM if $r = 1 \implies$ arbitrage exists

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Homework 1 — Solutions

1. A forward contract is an agreement to buy or sell an asset at a certain future time for a certain price (called the forward price). At the time a forward contract is entered into by two parties, no money changes hands. The investor who agrees to buy the asset at the future time is said to hold the long position in the contract and the investor who agrees to sell the asset is said to hold the short position in the contract. Suppose that a stock is currently selling for \$50 per share. A (long position in a) forward contract is available to buy 100 shares of the stock 3 months from now for \$50.40 per share. Suppose that a bank is offering interest at the rate of 5% per annum (compounded continuously) on a 3-month deposit. Describe a strategy for creating an arbitrage profit and compute the amount of the profit.

Solution. The arbitrage will be created by someone with a long position in the forward contract. At time 0, borrow 100 shares of the stock, sell them immediately for \$5000, and put this money in the bank. After 3 months the bank account has grown to $\$5000 \cdot \exp(.05 \cdot (3/12)) \approx \$5,062.89$. At that point use the forward contract to buy 100 shares for \$5040 to replace the borrowed shares. The remaining \$22.89 is a risk-free profit.

2. On April 1, 2025, a European call option on Apple (AAPL) has a price of \$20. The option expires on April 18, and the strike price is \$200. The price of Apple stock on April 1 is \$215 per share.

Analyze this situation in the manner of the Example on page 3 of the text, considering two possible scenarios: (1) The price of Apple on April 18 is \$235; (2) The price of Apple on April 18 is \$195. In each case compute the profit (or loss) incurred as a percentage of the investment if one were to invest (on April 1) \$2000 in (a) the call option on 100 shares of Apple, or (b) Apple stock. (Assume that only whole shares of AAPL can be purchased. Thus \$2000 would buy 9 shares of AAPL on April 1, with \$65 left over; in this case \$1935 was actually invested.)

Solution. If one bought such an option on 100 shares of Apple stock, the cost on April 1 would be \$2000 and on April 18 one would have the right to buy 100 AAPL shares for \$200 per share. We assume for simplicity that \$1 on April 1 is worth \$1 on April 18.

Under scenario (1), the holder of the option will exercise the option (and upon buying 100 shares for \$200 apiece, turn around and sell them at the market price of \$235), making a net profit of $\$235 - \$200 - \$20 = \15 per share, for a total net profit of \$1500 on an investment of \$2000. This is a 75% profit. If, on the other hand, the \$2000 had been invested in AAPL on April 1, the investor could have bought 9 whole shares (with \$1935), which on April 18 would be worth \$2115, for a net profit of $\$2115 - \$1935 = \$180$ on an investment of \$1935, which is a $\frac{180}{1935} 100\% = 9.30\%$ profit.

Under scenario (2), the holder would not exercise the option, and so would take a total net loss of \$2000—this is a 100% loss of the investment in the option. If, on the other hand, the \$2000 had been invested in (9 shares of) the stock (with \$65 left over), the loss incurred would have been $(\$215 - \$195) \cdot 9 = \$180$, which is a $\frac{180}{1935} 100\% = 9.30\%$ loss on an investment of \$1935 in stock.

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Homework 2 — Solutions

1. Consider a single-period binomial model with $r = 1/3$, $B_0 = 1$, $S_0 = 2$, $d = 5/4$, $u = 3/2$, and $p = 1/2$. (You can take the sample space Ω to be $\{\omega_1, \omega_2\}$, with ω_1 corresponding to the stock price going “up”, and ω_2 corresponding to the stock price going “down”.)

- (a) Compute B_1 .
- (b) Compute $S_1(\omega_1)$ and $S_1(\omega_2)$, and the probability of each outcome.
- (c) For the trading strategy $\psi = (2, 4)$, compute $V_0(\psi)$, $V_1(\psi)(\omega_1)$, and $V_1(\psi)(\omega_2)$.
- (d) Let X be a European call option with strike price \$2.50 and expiration time $T = 1$.
 - (i) Find $X(\omega_1)$ and $X(\omega_2)$.
 - (ii) Find the replicating strategy $\phi = (\alpha_1, \beta_1)$ for X
 - (iii) Find the manufacturing cost for that strategy. That is, compute $V_0(\phi)$.
- (e) Give an example of arbitrage opportunity if the claim X can be purchased for $C_0 = 1/10$ (dollars) at time 0.

Solution. (a) $B_1 = 1 + r = 4/3$.

(b) Taking ω_1 to be the “up” path and ω_2 to be the “down” path, we have $S_1(\omega_1) = S_0 \cdot u = 2 \cdot (3/2) = 3$ and $S_1(\omega_2) = S_0 \cdot d = 2 \cdot (5/4) = 5/2$.

(c) First, $V_0(\phi) = 2S_0 + 4B_0 = 8$. Next, $V_1(\phi) = 2S_1 + 4 \cdot (4/3) = 2S_1 + (16/3)$, so that $V_1(\phi)(\omega_1) = 2 \cdot 3 + (16/3) = 34/3 = 11\frac{1}{3}$ and $V_1(\phi)(\omega_2) = 2 \cdot (5/2) + (16/3) = 31/3 = 10\frac{1}{3}$.

(d) We have $X = (S_1 - (5/2))^+$.

(i) $X(\omega_1) = (3 - (5/2))^+ = 1/2$, $X(\omega_2) = ((5/2) - (5/2))^+ = 0$.

(ii) According to formulas from class and the text,

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{X(\omega_1) - X(\omega_2)}{u - d} \cdot \frac{1}{S_0} = \frac{1/2 - 0}{(3/2) - (5/4)} \cdot \frac{1}{2} = 1,$$

$$\beta_1 = \frac{uX(\omega_2) - dX(\omega_1)}{u - d} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + r} = \frac{(3/2) \cdot 0 - (5/4) \cdot (1/2)}{1/4} \cdot \frac{1}{4/3} = -15/8.$$

That is, the replicating portfolio is $\phi = (1, -15/8)$.

(iii) The manufacturing cost of the portfolio associated with this ϕ is $V_0(\phi) = 1 \cdot 2 - (15/8) = 1/8$.

(e) One arbitrage opportunity is represented by the trading strategy $\psi = (-1, 19/10, 1)$, which amounts to buying the option at time 0 for \$1/10, selling the replicating portfolio (for \$1/8), and putting the difference (\$1/40) in the bond. The initial cost of this portfolio is

$$V_0(\psi) = -1 \cdot S_0 + \left(\frac{15}{8} + \frac{1}{40}\right) B_0 + (1/10) = 0,$$

while the time $T = 1$ value is

$$V_1(\psi) = -1 \cdot S_1 + \left(\frac{15}{8} + \frac{1}{40}\right) B_1 + X = -X + (1/40)(4/3) + X = 1/30 > 0.$$

That is, a net initial investment of nothing yields a risk-free profit of \$1/30.

2. Repeat the steps of Exercise 1, with the following data: $r = 1/4$, $B_0 = 1$, $S_0 = 3$, $d = 1$, $u = 2$, and $p = 3/4$. Use the trading strategy $\psi = (3, -2)$ in part (c). The contingent claim X is now a European put option with strike price $K = \$4$. Use $C_0 = 1$ in doing part (e).

Solution. (a) $B_1 = 5/4$.

(b) As before, taking ω_1 to be the “up” path and ω_2 to be the “down” path, we have $S_1(\omega_1) = S_0 \cdot u = 3 \cdot 2 = 6$ and $S_1(\omega_2) = S_0 \cdot d = 3 \cdot 1 = 3$.

(c) First, $V_0(\phi) = 3S_0 - 2B_0 = 7$. Next, $V_1(\phi) = 3S_1 - 2 \cdot (5/4) = 3S_1 - (5/2)$, so that $V_1(\phi)(\omega_1) = 3 \cdot 6 - (5/2) = 31/2 = 15\frac{1}{2}$ and $V_1(\phi)(\omega_2) = 3 \cdot 3 - (5/2) = 13/2 = 6\frac{1}{2}$.

(d) We have $X = (4 - S_1)^+$.

(i) $X(\omega_1) = (4 - 6)^+ = 0$ and $X(\omega_2) = (4 - 3)^+ = 1$.

(ii) According to formulas from class and the text,

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{X(\omega_1) - X(\omega_2)}{u - d} \cdot \frac{1}{S_0} = \frac{0 - 1}{2 - 1} \cdot \frac{1}{3} = -1/3,$$

$$\beta_1 = \frac{uX(\omega_2) - dX(\omega_1)}{u - d} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + r} = \frac{2 \cdot 1 - 1 \cdot 0}{1} \cdot \frac{1}{5/4} = 8/5.$$

That is, the replicating portfolio is $\phi = (-1/3, 8/5)$.

(iii) The manufacturing cost of the portfolio associated with this ϕ is $V_0(\phi) = (-1/3)3 + (8/5) = 3/5$.

(e) One arbitrage opportunity is represented by the trading strategy $\psi = (-1/3, 2, -1) = (-1/3, 8/5 + 2/5, -1)$, which amounts to selling the put option at time 0 for \$1, buying the replicating portfolio (for \$3/5), and putting the difference (\$2/5) in the bond. The initial cost of this portfolio is

$$V_0(\psi) = (-1/3)S_0 + \left(\frac{8}{5} + \frac{2}{5}\right)B_0 - 1 = 0,$$

while the time $T = 1$ value is

$$V_1(\psi) = (-1/3)S_1 + \left(\frac{8}{5} + \frac{2}{5}\right)B_1 - X = X + (2/5)(5/4) - X = 1/2 > 0.$$

That is, a net initial investment of nothing yields a risk-free profit of \$1/2.

3. [Exercise 1 in section 2.4 of the text (page 28)] Consider a single period binomial model with $S_0 = \$100$, $S_1 = \$200$ or $\$50$, $r = 0.25$.

(a) Find the arbitrage free price of a European call option for one share of stock where the strike price is $K = \$100$ and the exercise time $T = 1$.

(b) Find a hedging strategy that replicates the value of the option described in (a).

(c) Suppose the option in (a) is initially priced at \$1 above the arbitrage free price. Describe a strategy (for trading in stock, bond and the option) that is an arbitrage.

(d) What is the arbitrage free initial price for a put option with the same strike price and exercise time as the call option described in (a)?

Solution. In this problem, $S_0 = \$100$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, and $r = 1/4$. Consequently,

$$p^* = \frac{5/4 - 1/2}{3/2} = 1/2.$$

(a) The arbitrage-free price is the discounted average value (with respect to P^*) of the contingent claim X :

$$C_0 = \frac{1}{1+r} (p^* X^u + (1-p^*) X^d) = \frac{4}{5} \frac{100+0}{2} = 40$$

dollars.

(b) We have

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{100-0}{2-1/2} \cdot \frac{1}{100} = \frac{2}{3}$$

and

$$\beta_1 = \frac{2 \cdot 0 - (1/2) \cdot 100}{3/2} \cdot \frac{1}{5/4} = -\frac{80}{3}.$$

The replicating strategy is therefore $\phi = (2/3, -80/3)$. Notice that $V_0(\phi) = (2/3)100 - (80/3) = 120/3 = 40$, which is consistent with part (a).

(c) We now suppose that X is priced at \$41. Let us sell the option at time 0, invest \$40 of the sale price to replicate the option, and place the remaining \$1 in the bond. At time $T = 1$ we will be able to cover the option and will have a risk free profit of $\$1 \cdot \frac{5}{4} = \1.25 . Thus we have described an arbitrage strategy.

(d) Computing as in (a), the arbitrage-free price of a put option $(100 - S_1)^+$ is

$$\frac{1}{5/4} (p^* \cdot 0 + (1-p^*) \cdot 50) = 20$$

dollars. This is consistent with “Call-Put Parity” as discussed in class (see formula (2.66) on page 29 of the text): The difference $(40 - 20)$ between the prices of the call and put options is equal to $S_0 - K/(1+r) = 100 - 100/(5/4) = 20$.

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Homework 3 — Solutions

1. Consider a single-period binomial model with $r = 1/5$, $S_0 = 3$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, and $p = 2/7$. Let X be a European put option with strike price $K = \$3$, expiring at time $T = 1$. Compute the arbitrage free price of this option.

Solution. In the present situation, $p^* = (1.2 - .5)/(2 - .5) = 7/15$. Also, $1/(1 + r) = 5/6$. Since $X^u = (3 - 6)^+ = 0$ and $X^d = (3 - 1.5)^+ = 1.5$, we have

$$V_0 = \frac{5}{6} \cdot \left[\frac{7}{15} \cdot 0 + \frac{8}{15} \cdot \frac{3}{2} \right] = \frac{2}{3}.$$

2. Consider a three period ($T = 3$) binomial model with initial stock price $S_0 = \$8$, $u = 3$, $d = 1/2$, $r = 1/10$, $p = 3/5$.

- Draw the binary tree illustrating the possible paths followed by the stock price process.
- In your diagram, record the probabilities (when the “up” probability is p and the “down” probability is $1 - p$) associated with the individual elements of the sample space Ω .
- List the events making up the σ -field \mathcal{F}_1 determined by S_1 . (Be sure to include the empty set and the whole sample space.)
- Indicate on your binary tree the values (one for each path) of a European contingent claim whose payoff at $T = 3$ is $X = \max(S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3)$.

Solution. (a) Of course $S_0 = 8$ is a constant.

The possible values for S_1 in the binary tree are (in order from left to right, left corresponding to d): 4, 24.

The possible values for S_2 in the binary tree are (in order from left to right, left corresponding to d): 2, 12, 12, 72.

The possible values for S_3 in the binary tree are (in order from left to right, left corresponding to d): 1, 6, 6, 36, 6, 36, 36, 216.

- (b) The respective probabilities of the end nodes listed above are:

$$8/125, 12/125, 12/125, 18/125, 12/125, 18/125, 18/125, 27/125.$$

- (c) Let us list the elements of the sample space as follows:

$$\Omega = \{ddd, ddu, dud, duu, udd, udu, uud, uuu\}.$$

With this labelling, the σ -field \mathcal{F}_1 can be listed as follows:

$$\mathcal{F}_1 = \{\emptyset, \Omega, \{ddd, ddu, dud, duu\}, \{udd, udu, uud, uuu\}\}.$$

(d) Listing things in the same order as before, the possible values of X are

$$8, 8, 12, 36, 24, 36, 72, 216.$$

3. (Exercise 2, Section 2.4) Consider a CRR model with $T = 2$, $S_0 = \$100$, $S_1 = \$200$ or $S_1 = \$50$, and an associated European call option with strike price $K = \$80$ and exercise time $T = 2$. Assume that the risk free interest rate is $r = 0.1$.

- (a) Draw the binary tree and compute the arbitrage free initial price of the European call option at time zero.
- (b) Determine an explicit hedging strategy for this option.
- (c) Suppose that the option in (a) is initially priced \$2 below the arbitrage free price. Describe a strategy (for trading in stock, bond and the option) that is an arbitrage.

Solution. In this exercise we have $T = 2$, $S_0 = \$100$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, $r = 1/10$. The contingent claim under consideration is a European call option with strike $K = \$80$. Notice that the “risk-neutral” up probability is $p^* = 2/5$.

(a) The possible values of X are 0, 20, and 320 dollars, with respective \mathbf{P}^* probabilities $9/25, 12/25, 4/25$. Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} V_0 &= \frac{1}{(1+r)^2} \cdot \mathbf{E}^*[X] = \left(\frac{10}{11}\right)^2 \cdot \left[0 \cdot \frac{9}{25} + 20 \cdot \frac{12}{25} + 320 \cdot \frac{4}{25}\right] \\ &= \frac{100}{121} \cdot \frac{1520}{25} = \frac{6080}{121} \approx 50.25. \end{aligned}$$

(b) Using the formulas (2.26) and (2.27) on page 15 of the text, we compute

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_2^u &= 1, & \beta_2^u &= -\frac{8000}{121}, \\ \alpha_2^d &= \frac{4}{15}, & \beta_2^d &= -\frac{2000}{363}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{4}{5}, \quad \beta_1 = -\frac{10800}{363}.$$

As a reality check

$$\alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1 B_0 = \frac{4}{5} \cdot 100 - \frac{10800}{363} = 80 - \frac{10800}{363} = \frac{29040 - 10800}{363} = \frac{18240}{363} = \frac{6080}{121},$$

consistent with part (a).

(c) Suppose that C_0 (the price of the option X) is equal to $V_0 - 2$ dollars. One arbitrage is to buy the option, sell the hedging portfolio, and put the \$2 netted in these transactions into the bond. That is, we employ the trading strategy $\psi = (-\alpha_t, -\beta_t + 2, 1)$. This represents an initial investment of

$$V_0(\psi) = -\alpha_1 S_0 - \beta_1 + 2 + C_0 = -V_0 + 2 + C_0 = 0,$$

with time 2 value equal to

$$V_2(\psi) = -\alpha_2 S_2 - \beta_2 B_2 + 2B_2 + X = -X + 2B_2 + X = 2B_2 > 0,$$

a risk-free (strictly positive) profit.

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Homework 4 — Solutions

1. Consider the Multi-period Binomial Model (the CCR model) with parameter values as in Exercise 2 on page 28 of the text. Under a forward contract, the holder of a long position in the contract will buy 100 shares of stock at time $T = 2$ for a fixed (total) price $\$F$. What should the value of F be so that neither the holder of the long position in the contract, nor the holder of the short position (the seller) has an arbitrage opportunity? Identify the relevant European contingent claim, and derive F using arbitrage-free pricing. (Reminder: No money changes hands at time $t = 0$ when the forward contract is written.)

Solution. The long position in the forward contract (to buy 100 shares for $\$F$ at time $T = 2$) amounts to a contingent claim of $X = 100S_2 - F$ dollars to be collected at time $T = 2$. The no-arbitrage price of this claim is

$$V_0 = \frac{1}{(1+r)^2} \mathbf{E}^*[X] = \frac{1}{(1+r)^2} \mathbf{E}^*[100S_2 - F] = 100S_0 - (1+r)^{-2}F,$$

the second equality following from the martingale property of the discounted stock price under the risk-neutral probability \mathbf{P}^* . On the other hand, because no money is to change hands at time 0, we must have $V_0 = 0$. This forces

$$F = (1+r)^2 100S_0 = (11/10)^2 100 \cdot 100 = 12,100.$$

2. Consider the probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathbf{P})$ in which (i) $\Omega = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, (ii) \mathcal{F} is the σ -field of all subsets of Ω , and (iii) $\mathbf{P}[A] = \text{card}(A)/4$ for each $A \in \mathcal{F}$. (Here, $\text{card}(A)$, the cardinality of A , is simply the number of elements of A .) This probability space is a model for an experiment with four equally likely outcomes. Let \mathcal{G} be the σ -field generated by the partition $\mathcal{P} = \{\{1, 2\}, \{3, 4\}\}$ and let \mathcal{H} be the σ -field generated by the partition $\mathcal{Q} = \{\{1\}, \{2\}, \{3, 4\}\}$. Notice that $\mathcal{G} \subset \mathcal{H}$. Let X be the random variable defined by $X(i) = 3i + 1$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

- Compute $\mathbf{E}[X]$.
- Compute $\mathbf{E}[X|\mathcal{G}]$.
- Compute $\mathbf{E}[X|\mathcal{H}]$.
- Compute $\mathbf{E}[\mathbf{E}[X|\mathcal{H}]|\mathcal{G}]$.
- Does your answer in (d) confirm the Tower Property of conditional expectations?

Solution. (a) $\mathbf{E}[X] = [4 + 7 + 10 + 13]/4 = 34/4 = 8.5$.

(b) Let us write Y as an abbreviation of $\mathbf{E}[X|\mathcal{G}]$. On $\{1, 2\}$, Y takes the value

$$\frac{4 \cdot \frac{1}{4} + 7 \cdot \frac{1}{4}}{\frac{1}{2}} = 4 \cdot \frac{1}{2} + 7 \cdot \frac{1}{2} = 5.5,$$

while on $\{3, 4\}$, Y takes the value

$$\frac{10 \cdot \frac{1}{4} + 13 \cdot \frac{1}{4}}{\frac{1}{2}} = 10 \cdot \frac{1}{2} + 13 \cdot \frac{1}{2} = \frac{23}{2} = 11.5.$$

In other words, Y is the random variable given by $Y(1) = Y(2) = 5.5$, $Y(3) = Y(4) = 11.5$. Notice that the average value of Y is $[5.5 + 11.5]/2 = 17/5 = 8.5$, which is consistent with part (a) because (Tower Property) $\mathbf{E}[\mathbf{E}[X|\mathcal{G}]] = \mathbf{E}[X]$.

(c) Let us write Z as an abbreviation of $\mathbf{E}[X|\mathcal{H}]$. Clearly $Z(1) = X(1) = 4$ and $Z(2) = X(2) = 7$. On $\{3, 4\}$, Z takes the same constant value as Y . In other words, $Z(3) = Z(4) = 11.5$.

(d) We are now asked to compute $\mathbf{E}[Z|\mathcal{G}]$. The computation is as in part (b), with the random variable Z now playing the role of the random variable X . Thus, writing W as an abbreviation of $\mathbf{E}[Z|\mathcal{G}]$, we have $W(1) = W(2) = [Z(1)+Z(2)]/2 = 5.5$ and $W(3) = W(4) = [Z(3)+Z(4)]/2 = 11.5$.

(e) Notice that the conditional expectation obtained in (d) (namely $W = \mathbf{E}[\mathbf{E}[X|\mathcal{H}]|\mathcal{G}]$) coincides with the conditional expectation $Y = \mathbf{E}[X|\mathcal{G}]$ obtained in part (b). This shows that

$$\mathbf{E}[\mathbf{E}[X|\mathcal{H}]|\mathcal{G}] = \mathbf{E}[X|\mathcal{G}],$$

confirming the present instance of the tower property of conditional expectations.

Here's a table containing the results of parts (b)–(e):

Ω	1	2	3	4
X	4	7	10	13
$Y = \mathbf{E}[X \mathcal{G}]$	5.5	5.5	11.5	11.5
$Z = \mathbf{E}[X \mathcal{H}]$	4	7	11.5	11.5
$W = \mathbf{E}[\mathbf{E}[X \mathcal{H}] \mathcal{G}] = \mathbf{E}[Z \mathcal{G}]$	5.5	5.5	11.5	11.5

3. Use an Excel spreadsheet to compute the arbitrage-free price of a European call option with strike price $K = \$140$, based on the Multi-period Binomial Model (the CCR model) with the following parameter values: $T = 5$, $S_0 = \$100$, $u = 1.5$, $d = .6$, $r = 0.1$. (There is a handout available on the same page as the course text that will be helpful for this problem.)

Solution. The next page is an Excel spreadsheet created using the handout. The (re-combining) binary tree of stock prices is displayed, and at the base of this tree the possible values of the put option X and the corresponding probabilities are listed. The arbitrage-free price of the option is found at the top of the V_t tree, and is equal to 41.88 (rounded to 2 places beyond the decimal point). As a check, one can also compute V_0 using the formula $V_0 = (1+r)^{-5}\mathbf{E}^*[X]$:

$$\frac{1}{(1.1)^5} \cdot \left\{ 163.75 \cdot \frac{12,500}{59,049} + 619.375 \cdot \frac{3,982421.875}{59,049} \right\} = \frac{3982421.875}{59049} = 41.8765\dots,$$

confirming the value of V_0 found by Excel.

		S_t						
S_0	100	t						
		0				100.00		
		1			60.00	150.00		
		2			36.00	90.00	225.00	
		3		21.60	54.00	135.00	337.50	
		4	12.96		32.40	81.00	202.50	506.25
		5	7.78	19.44	48.60	121.50	303.75	759.38
d	0.6							
u	1.5							
p*	0.556							
K	140							
r	0.1							
		P*	0.02	0.11	0.27	0.34	0.21	0.05
		X	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	163.75	619.38
		V_0	41.88					

		V_t						
						41.88		
					10.65	74.39		
				0.00	21.10	130.42		
			0.00	0.00	0.00	41.77	224.82	
			0.00	0.00	0.00	82.70	378.98	
		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	163.75	619.38	

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Homework 5 — Solutions

1. Exercise 5, Section 2.4.

Solution. Observe that if b is a real number then $b^+ - (-b)^+ = b$. (Consider the cases $b > 0$ and $b \leq 0$ separately.) Thus

$$(1.1) \quad C_T - P_T = (S_T - K)^+ - (K - S_T)^+ = S_T - K.$$

By the result of Exercise 4 of Section 2.4 of the text, applied separately to the put and the call:

$$(1.2) \quad C_t = (1+r)^{t-T} \mathbf{E}^*[(S_T - K)^+ | \mathcal{F}_t]$$

and

$$(1.3) \quad P_t = (1+r)^{t-T} \mathbf{E}^*[(K - S_T)^+ | \mathcal{F}_t].$$

Subtracting (1.3) from (1.2), then using (1.1), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} C_t - P_t &= (1+r)^{t-T} \mathbf{E}^*[(S_T - K)^+ - (K - S_T)^+ | \mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= (1+r)^{t-T} \mathbf{E}^*[S_T - K | \mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= (1+r)^{t-T} (\mathbf{E}^*[S_T | \mathcal{F}_t] - K) \\ &= (1+r)^{t-T} ((1+r)^{T-t} S_t - K) \\ &= S_t - (1+r)^{t-T} K. \end{aligned}$$

For the fourth equality we used the \mathbf{P}^* -martingale property of S_t^* .

2. In the context of the Multi-period Binomial Model, let M_0, M_1, \dots, M_T be a martingale.

(a) Let $f : \mathbf{R} \rightarrow \mathbf{R}$ be a concave function. Show that $\{f(M_0), f(M_1), \dots, f(M_T)\}$ is a supermartingale. [Hint: Use the conditional form of Jensen's Inequality as discussed in class.]

(b) Assume, in addition, that $M_t \geq 0$ for each $t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T$. Show that

$$\sqrt{M_0}, \sqrt{M_1}, \dots, \sqrt{M_T}$$

is a supermartingale.

Solution.

(a) Let's check: For $t \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}$:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{E}[f(M_t) | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] &\leq f(\mathbf{E}[M_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}]) \\ &= f(M_{t-1}),\end{aligned}$$

in which the inequality follows from Jensen's inequality because f is concave by hypothesis, and the equality follows from the martingale property of M_0, \dots, M_T . It follows that $f(M_0), f(M_1), \dots, f(M_T)$ is a supermartingale.

(b) Let's check that $f(x) := \sqrt{x}$, $x \geq 0$, is a concave function. By Calculus: $f'(x) = x^{-1/2}$ and then $f''(x) = -(1/2)x^{-3/2} < 0$ for $x > 0$. By the Second Derivative for Concavity, f is concave in the open interval $(0, \infty)$. This means that

$$(2.1) \quad \alpha\sqrt{x} + (1 - \alpha)\sqrt{y} \leq \sqrt{\alpha x + (1 - \alpha)y}, \quad \forall 0 < x < y,$$

for all $0 < \alpha < 1$. But \sqrt{u} is a continuous function of $u \geq 0$, so we can take the limit as $x \rightarrow 0$ in (2.1) to obtain

$$(1 - \alpha)\sqrt{y} \leq \sqrt{(1 - \alpha)y},$$

which is the defining concavity inequality for the square root function in the special case $x = 0$, $y \geq 0$. Thus $f(x) = \sqrt{x}$ is a concave function of $x \geq 0$.

We may now apply part (a) to deduce that $\sqrt{M_0}, \sqrt{M_1}, \dots, \sqrt{M_T}$ is a supermartingale.

One might also check the concavity of the square-root function algebraically. For this fix $0 \leq x < y$ and $0 < \alpha < 1$. Showing (2.1) above is the same (after squaring) as showing that

$$(2.2) \quad [\alpha\sqrt{x} + (1 - \alpha)\sqrt{y}]^2 \leq \alpha x + (1 - \alpha)y.$$

The left side of (2.2) is equal to

$$(2.3) \quad \alpha^2 x + (1 - \alpha)^2 y + 2\alpha(1 - \alpha)\sqrt{xy}.$$

Abbreviate $\beta := 1 - \alpha$ and use (2.3) to simplify and rearrange (2.2) to the equivalent inequality

$$(2.4) \quad 2\alpha\beta\sqrt{xy} \leq \alpha\beta x + \alpha\beta y.$$

Cancel $\alpha\beta$, then divide by 2; we arrive at

$$\sqrt{xy} \leq \frac{x + y}{2},$$

the well-known Arithmetic-Geometric Mean Inequality. This holds because

$$0 \leq (\sqrt{x} - \sqrt{y})^2 = x + y - 2\sqrt{xy}.$$

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Solution for Exercise 4, page 29.

Under the risk-neutral probability \mathbf{P}^* , the discounted stock price process

$$S_t^* = (1+r)^{-t} S_t, \quad t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T,$$

is a martingale:

$$\mathbf{E}^*[S_{t+1}^* | \mathcal{F}_t] = S_t^*, \quad t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T-1.$$

Consequently, since $V_t(\phi^*) = \alpha_t^* S_t + \beta_t^* B_t$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E}^*[V_{t+1}(\phi^*) | \mathcal{F}_t] &= \mathbf{E}^*[\alpha_{t+1}^* S_{t+1} + \beta_{t+1}^* B_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= \alpha_{t+1}^* \mathbf{E}^*[S_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t] + \beta_{t+1}^* B_{t+1} \\ &= \alpha_{t+1}^* (1+r) S_t^* + \beta_{t+1}^* (1+r) B_t \\ &= (1+r) [\alpha_{t+1}^* S_t^* + \beta_{t+1}^* B_t] \\ &= (1+r) [\alpha_t^* S_t^* + \beta_t^* B_t] \\ &= (1+r) V_t(\phi^*). \end{aligned}$$

In this computation, the second equality follows because α_{t+1}^* and β_{t+1}^* are \mathcal{F}_t measurable, the third equality follows from the martingale property of S_t^* while the fifth follows from the self-financing nature of the replicating strategy ϕ^* . In other words, the discounted value process

$$V_t^*(\phi^*), \quad t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T,$$

is a \mathbf{P}^* -martingale. In particular, as with any martingale,

$$V_t^*(\phi^*) = \mathbf{E}^*[V_T^*(\phi^*) | \mathcal{F}_t], \quad t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T,$$

or, what amounts to the same thing,

$$(1) \quad V_t(\phi^*) = (1+r)^t \mathbf{E}^* \left[\frac{V_T(\phi^*)}{(1+r)^T} \middle| \mathcal{F}_t \right] = \frac{1}{(1+r)^{T-t}} \mathbf{E}^*[X | \mathcal{F}_t], \quad t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T,$$

in which we used the fact that $V_T(\phi^*) = X$. This is formula (2.65) in the text.

Suppose that we can trade (throughout the time period $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, T\}$) in stock, bond, and contingent claim. A trading strategy is now a sequence of triples of random variables

$$\psi = \{(\alpha_t, \beta_t, \gamma_t) : t = 1, 2, \dots, T\},$$

such that $\alpha_t, \beta_t, \gamma_t$ are all \mathcal{F}_{t-1} -measurable for $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$, and

$$\alpha_t S_t + \beta_t B_t + \gamma_t C_t = \alpha_{t+1} S_t + \beta_{t+1} B_t + \gamma_{t+1} C_t, \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, T-1;$$

that is, the strategy is self-financing. (Here C_t is the (possibly random) market price of the contingent claim at time t .) The value of such a trading strategy (at time $t \geq 1$) is $V_t(\psi) = \alpha_t S_t + \beta_t B_t + \gamma_t C_t$ (with $V_0(\psi) = \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1 + \gamma_1 C_0$).

In this context, an arbitrage is a trading strategy ψ such that (i) $V_0(\psi) = 0$, (ii) $V_T(\psi) \geq 0$, and (iii) $\mathbf{P}^*[V_T(\psi) > 0] > 0$ (equivalently, $\mathbf{E}^*[V_T(\psi)] > 0$). We shall now verify that $C_t = V_t(\phi^*)$, $t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T$, is the unique no-arbitrage price for the contingent claim in the extended market. (As before, ϕ^* is the replicating strategy for the claim X .)

First suppose that there is a time u in $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, T\}$ such that the event $G = \{C_u > V_u(\phi^*)\}$ satisfies $\mathbf{P}^*[G] > 0$. Consider the following strategy: At time u , and if G occurs, sell a unit of the option for C_u , use $V_u(\phi^*)$ of the proceeds to invest in the stock/bond market, and put the difference $C_u - V_u(\phi^*)$ into the bond. More precisely, consider the trading strategy ψ defined by

$$\alpha_t = \beta_t = \gamma_t = 0, \quad t = 1, 2, \dots, u-1.$$

Moreover, if the event G occurs then

$$\alpha_t = \alpha_t^*, \beta_t = \beta_t^* + (C_u - V_u(\phi^*))B_u^{-1}, \gamma_t = -1, \quad t = u, u+1, \dots, T,$$

while if G^c occurs then

$$\alpha_t = \beta_t = \gamma_t = 0, \quad t = u, u+1, \dots, T,$$

Then $V_t(\psi) = 0$ for $t = 0, 1, 2, \dots, u$, and

$$\begin{aligned} V_T(\psi) &= \alpha_T^* S_T + \beta_T^* B_T + (C_u - V_u(\phi^*))(1+r)^{T-u} - X \\ &= X + (C_u - V_u(\phi^*))(1+r)^{T-u} - X = (C_u - V_u(\phi^*))(1+r)^{T-u} > 0, \end{aligned}$$

yielding a risk-free profit. By the no-arbitrage principle we must therefore have

$$\mathbf{P}^*[C_u \leq V_u(\phi^*), \text{ for all } u = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T] = 1.$$

Similarly, an arbitrage can be arranged if $\mathbf{P}^*[C_u < V_u(\phi^*)] > 0$ for some u . Consequently,

$$\mathbf{P}^*[C_u \geq V_u(\phi^*), \text{ for all } u = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T] = 1.$$

Combining these observations we see that

$$(2) \quad \mathbf{P}^*[C_u = V_u(\phi^*), \text{ for all } u = 0, 1, 2, \dots, T] = 1.$$

It remains to show that when (2) holds, no arbitrage is possible.

Thus we suppose that $C_t = V_t(\phi^*)$ for *all* $t \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, T\}$. Let ψ be any (self-financing) trading strategy in the stock/bond/contingent claim market and suppose that $V_0(\psi) = 0$ but $V_T(\psi) \geq 0$. We compute:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E}^*[V_T(\psi)] &= \mathbf{E}^*[\alpha_T S_T + \beta_T B_T + \gamma_T C_T] \\ &= (1+r)\mathbf{E}^*[\alpha_T S_{T-1} + \beta_T B_{T-1}] + \mathbf{E}^*[\gamma_T \mathbf{E}^*[C_T | \mathcal{F}_{T-1}]] \\ &= (1+r)\mathbf{E}^*[\alpha_T S_{T-1} + \beta_T B_{T-1}] + \mathbf{E}^*[\gamma_T \mathbf{E}^*[V_T(\phi^*) | \mathcal{F}_{T-1}]] \\ &= (1+r)\mathbf{E}^*[\alpha_T S_{T-1} + \beta_T B_{T-1}] + (1+r)\mathbf{E}^*[\gamma_T V_{T-1}(\phi^*)] \\ &= (1+r)\mathbf{E}^*[\alpha_{T-1} S_{T-1} + \beta_{T-1} B_{T-1}] + (1+r)\mathbf{E}^*[\gamma_{T-1} C_{T-1}] \\ &= (1+r)\mathbf{E}^*[V_{T-1}(\psi)] \end{aligned}$$

Proceeding recursively, we eventually find that $\mathbf{E}^*[V_T(\psi)] = (1+r)^T \mathbf{E}^*[V_0(\psi)] = 0$. This forces $V_T(\psi) = 0$ with \mathbf{P}^* probability 1. Thus, no arbitrage is possible.

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Homework 6 — Solutions

1. The setting for this problem is the multi-period binomial model with $T = 2$, $S_0 = \$100$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, $r = 0.1$. Consider an American put option with strike price $K = \$120$.

(a) Use a binary tree to compute the no-arbitrage initial price of the American put option.

(b) Determine an explicit superhedging strategy ϕ^* for this option.

(c) Suppose that you can buy the American put option at time zero for \$1 less than its no-arbitrage price. Describe an investment strategy that yields an arbitrage opportunity for a buyer of the American put option. In particular, you need to describe the stopping time at which the buyer will exercise the option.

Solution. The “risk-neutral” up probability is $p^* = 2/5$.

(a) The stock price tree has entries:

$$S_0 = 100; S_1^d = 50, S_1^u = 200; S_2^{dd} = 25, S_2^{du} = 100, S_2^{ud} = 100, S_2^{uu} = 400.$$

The contingent claim tree has entries:

$$Y_0 = 20; Y_1^d = 70, Y_1^u = 0; Y_2^{dd} = 95, Y_2^{du} = 20, Y_2^{ud} = 20, Y_2^{uu} = 0.$$

Using the Y_2 values to fill in the bottom row of the U tree (the necessary wealth process) and then filling in the rest of the tree recursively we obtain

$$U_1^d = 70, \quad U_1^u = 120/11,$$

and finally

$$U_0 = 5100/121 = 42.15$$

dollars. This is the no-arbitrage price of the American call option associated with the given data.

(b) Using the formulas on page 21 of the text, we compute the superhedging strategy $\phi^* = (\alpha^*, \beta^*)$:

$$\tilde{\alpha}_1 = \frac{120/11 - 70}{3/2} \cdot \frac{1}{100} = \frac{-13}{33}, \quad \tilde{\beta}_1 = \frac{2 \cdot (70) - .5 \cdot (120/11)}{3/2} \cdot \frac{10}{11} = \frac{29600}{363},$$

and $\tilde{\delta}_1 = U_0 - (10/11)\mathbf{E}^*[U_1] = 0$. Therefore

$$\alpha_1^* = \frac{-13}{33}, \quad \beta_1^* = \frac{29600}{363}.$$

Next,

$$\tilde{\alpha}_2^d = \frac{20 - 95}{3/2} \cdot \frac{1}{50} = -1, \quad \tilde{\beta}_2^d = \frac{2 \cdot 95 - .5 \cdot 20}{3/2} \cdot \left(\frac{10}{11}\right)^2 = \frac{12000}{121},$$

and

$$\tilde{\delta}_2^d = 70 - (10/11)[(3/5)95 + (2/5)20] = 70 - \frac{650}{11} = 120/11,$$

so that

$$\alpha_2^{d,*} = \tilde{\alpha}_2^d = -1, \quad \beta_2^{d,*} = \tilde{\beta}_2^d + \tilde{\delta}_2^d * (10/11) = \frac{12000}{121} + \frac{1200}{121} = \frac{13200}{121}.$$

Similarly,

$$\alpha_2^{u,*} = \tilde{\alpha}_2^u = \frac{0 - 20}{3/2} \cdot \frac{1}{200} = \frac{-1}{15}, \quad \beta_2^{*,u} = \tilde{\beta}_2^u = \frac{2 \cdot 20 - .5 \cdot 0}{3/2} \cdot \left(\frac{10}{11}\right)^2 = \frac{8000}{363},$$

Notice that $\tilde{\delta}_2^u = 120/11 - (10/11)[(3/5)20 + (2/5)0] = 0$.

(c) Strategy: Buy the put for \$41.15; short sell the superhedging portfolio ϕ^* for \$42.15 and put the leftover \$1 in the bond. The time 0 cost of this is $V_0(\phi^*) - U_0 - 1 = 0$. The buyer should exercise the option at the stopping time $\tau^* := \min\{t : Y_t = U_t\}$; thus $\tau^* = 1$ if $S_1 = 50$ but $\tau^* = 2$ if $S_1 = 200$. Then $V_{\tau^*}(\phi^*) = U_{\tau^*} = Y_{\tau^*}$, so the payment Y_{τ^*} lets the buyer meet the obligation of the short sale, with $1 \cdot B_{\tau^*} = (11/10)^{\tau^*} > 0$ left over for profit.

2. The setting for this problem is the multi-period binomial model with $T = 2$, $S_0 = \$12$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, but now $r = 1/4$. Consider an American claim based on the payoff sequence Y give by

$$Y_0 = (12 - S_0)^+, \quad Y_1 = \left(12 - \frac{S_0 + S_1}{2}\right)^+, \quad Y_2 = \left(12 - \frac{S_0 + S_1 + S_2}{3}\right)^+.$$

(a) Construct the necessary wealth process U_0, U_1, U_2 , for this claim, best displayed as a tree.

(b) What is the no-arbitrage price for the claim?

(c) Describe a good time for the buyer of the claim to exercise the claim.

Solution. Notice that $p^* = 1/2$.

(a) The stock price tree has entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_0 &= 12, \\
 S_1^d &= 6, & S_1^u &= 24, \\
 S_2^{dd} &= 3, & S_2^{du} &= 12, & S_2^{ud} &= 12, & S_2^{uu} &= 48.
 \end{aligned}$$

It's useful to write $\bar{S}_t = (S_0 + \dots + S_t)/t$ for the average stock price up to time t . The tree for this average stock price has entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{S}_0 &= 12, \\
 \bar{S}_1^d &= 9, & \bar{S}_1^u &= 18, \\
 \bar{S}_2^{dd} &= 7, & \bar{S}_2^{du} &= 10, & \bar{S}_2^{ud} &= 16, & \bar{S}_2^{uu} &= 28.
 \end{aligned}$$

The contingent claim tree therefore has entries:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y_0 &= 0, \\
 Y_1^d &= 3, & Y_1^u &= 0, \\
 Y_2^{dd} &= 5, & Y_2^{du} &= 2, & Y_2^{ud} &= 0, & Y_2^{uu} &= 0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Using the Y_2 values to fill in the bottom row of the U tree (the necessary wealth process) and then filling in the rest of the tree recursively we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_0 &= \frac{6}{5}, \\
 U_1^d &= 3, & U_1^u &= 0, \\
 U_2^{dd} &= 5, & U_2^{du} &= 2, & U_2^{ud} &= 0, & U_2^{uu} &= 0.
 \end{aligned}$$

(b) The no-arbitrage price of the American put option associated with the given data is $\$6/5 = \1.20 .

(c) According to the theory, a good time to exercise is $\tau^*(0) := \min\{t : Y_t = U_t\}$. In the present situation, by comparing the Y and U trees, we see that $\tau^*(0)(\omega) = 1$ for each sample point ω .

Math 194, Winter 2024

Homework 7 — Solutions

1. Consider the multi-step binary model with $T = 2$, $S_0 = \$100$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, and $r = 1/5$. In this problem we shall use the real-world probability \mathbf{P} for which “up” and “down” branches each have probability $p = 1/2$. Let adapted sequences of random variables $Y = \{Y_0, Y_1, Y_2\}$ and $U = \{U_0, U_1, U_2\}$ be defined by

$$Y_0 = 30, Y_1^d = 27, Y_1^u = 34, Y_2^{dd} = Y_2^{uu} = 50, Y_2^{du} = Y_2^{ud} = 10,$$

and

$$U_0 = 32, U_1^d = 30, U_1^u = 34, U_2^{dd} = U_2^{uu} = 50, U_2^{du} = U_2^{ud} = 10.$$

(a) Verify that $\{U_0, U_1, U_2\}$ is a supermartingale.

(b) The recipe $\tau = \min\{t : U_t = Y_t\}$ defines a stopping time. Compute $\tau(dd)$, $\tau(du)$, $\tau(ud)$, and $\tau(uu)$.

(c) Compute $\mathbf{E}[Y_\tau]$, where τ is as in part (c).

Solution. (a) We have

$$\mathbf{E}[U_1|\mathcal{F}_0] = \frac{30 + 34}{2} = 32 = U_0,$$

and

$$\mathbf{E}[U_2|\mathcal{F}_1] = \frac{50 + 10}{2} = 30 \leq U_1 \in \{30, 34\}.$$

It follows that $\mathbf{E}[U_{t+1}|\mathcal{F}_t] \leq U_t$ for $t = 0, 1$, verifying the asserted supermartingale property.

(b) Comparing the Y and U value trees we find that $\tau(dd) = \tau(du) = 2$ while $\tau(ud) = \tau(uu) = 1$.

(c) Using the result of part (b) we compute:

$$Y_\tau(dd) = Y_2(dd) = 50, Y_\tau(du) = Y_2(du) = 10,$$

$$Y_\tau(ud) = Y_1(ud) = 34, Y_\tau(uu) = Y_1(uu) = 34.$$

As these four possible values of Y_τ are equally likely we have

$$\mathbf{E}[Y_\tau] = \frac{50 + 10 + 34 + 34}{4} = 32.$$

2. For this problem use the model data from Exercise 6, Section 2.4 (page 29 of the text). An American asset-or-nothing (call) option is the American contingent claim based on the payoffs

$$Y_t = \begin{cases} F, & \text{if } S_t \geq K, \\ 0, & \text{if } S_t < K, \end{cases}$$

and can be exercised at any time t in $\{0, 1, 2\}$. Let us take $K = \$90$ and $F = \$120$. Fill in the tree diagram for the necessary wealth process $U = \{U_0, U_1, U_2\}$, thereby computing the no-arbitrage price U_0 for this ACC.

Solution. The values of Y are

$$Y_0 = 120, Y_1^d = 0, Y_1^u = 120, Y_2^{dd} = 0, Y_2^{du} = Y_2^{ud} = Y_2^{uu} = 120.$$

Filling in the U tree by the backward recursion $U_{t-1} = \max(Y_{t-1}, (1+r)^{-1}\mathbf{E}[U_t|\mathcal{F}_{t-1}]$ (with $p^* = 2/5$ and discount factor $(1+r)^{-1} = 10/11$) we find that

$$U_1^d = \frac{480}{11}, \quad U_1^u = 120, \quad U_0 = 120.$$

The no-arbitrage price for the contingent claim is therefore $U_0 = 120$ dollars.

3. Exercise 2, Section 3.7 (pages 52–53 of the text).

Solution. (a) Labelling the S^1 tree in the usual way we have

$$S_0^1 = 5, S_1^{1,d} = 4, S_1^{1,u} = 8,$$

and

$$S_2^{1,dd} = 2, S_2^{1,du} = 5, S_2^{1,ud} = 6, S_2^{1,uu} = 9.$$

The (European) contingent claim X is therefore given by

$$X(dd) = X(du) = 0, X(ud) = 2, X(uu) = 3.$$

(b) Since the “bond” is constantly 1, the discounted stock price is the same as the stock price. Thus our EMM should be a probability measure \mathbf{P}^* equivalent to \mathbf{P} such that $\{S_0^1, S_1^1, S_2^1\}$ is a \mathbf{P}^* martingale. First,

$$S_0^1 = \mathbf{E}^*[S_1^1|\mathcal{F}_0]$$

amounts to

$$5 = p^0 \cdot 8 + (1 - p^0) \cdot 4,$$

where p^0 is the up probability for the “first branch”; namely, $p^0 = \mathbf{P}^*[S_1 = 8]$. Solving this equation we find that $p^0 = 1/4$. Second,

$$S_1^1 = \mathbf{E}^*[S_2^1|\mathcal{F}_1]$$

amounts to two equations:

$$8 = p^{1,u} \cdot 9 + (1 - p^{1,u}) \cdot 6 \quad \text{and} \quad 4 = p^{1,d} \cdot 5 + (1 - p^{1,d}) \cdot 2,$$

where $p^{1,u}$ is the “up” probability for the u branch at time 1; namely $p^{1,u} = \mathbf{P}^*[S_2^1 = 9 | S_1^1 = 8]$. Likewise, $p^{1,d}$ is the “up” probability for the d branch at time 1; namely $p^{1,d} = \mathbf{P}^*[S_2^1 = 5 | S_1^1 = 4]$. Solving these equations we find that

$$p^{1,u} = 2/3 = p^{1,d}.$$

Putting these calculations together we find that (for example)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}^*[\{\omega_1\}] &= \mathbf{P}^*[\{uu\}] = \mathbf{P}^*[S_2^1 = 9, S_1^1 = 8] = \mathbf{P}^*[S_2^1 = 9 | S_1^1 = 8] \cdot \mathbf{P}^*[S_1^1 = 8] \\ &= p^{1,u} p^0 = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{4} = \frac{1}{6}. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

$$\mathbf{P}^*[\{\omega_2\}] = \frac{1}{12}, \quad \mathbf{P}^*[\{\omega_3\}] = \frac{1}{2}, \quad \mathbf{P}^*[\{\omega_4\}] = \frac{1}{4}.$$

(c) We plug the “local” values of p^* (namely p^0 , $p^{1,u}$, and $p^{1,d}$) into the familiar formulas for the hedging strategy, thereby obtaining (refer to part (d) below for the entries of the V tree):

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{8/3 - 0}{8/5 - 4/5} \cdot \frac{1}{5} = \frac{2}{3}, \quad \beta_1 = \frac{(8/5) \cdot 0 - (4/5) \cdot (8/3)}{8/5 - 4/5} = -\frac{8}{3}.$$

Here the (local) “up” factor u was computed as $S_1^{1,u}/S_0^1 = 8/5$, etc. Similarly

$$\alpha_2^u = \frac{3 - 2}{9/8 - 6/8} \cdot \frac{1}{8} = \frac{1}{3}, \quad \beta_2^u = \frac{(9/8) \cdot 2 - 6/8 \cdot 3}{9/8 - 6/8} = 0,$$

and

$$\alpha_2^d = 0, \quad \beta_2^d = 0.$$

(d) The arbitrage free price for X at time 0 is just $\mathbf{E}^*[X] = (1/6)3 + (1/12)2 = 2/3$. Alternatively, one could fill in the V tree by backward recursion, starting with $V_2 = X$, obtaining first

$$V_1^u = 8/3, \quad V_1^d = 0,$$

and finally $V_0 = (1/4)(8/3) + (3/4)0 = 2/3$.

Math 194, Spring 2025

Homework 8 — Solutions

1. In this exercise we also use the set-up of Exercise 2, Section 3.7 (page 52–53 of the text). In Homework 7 you saw that this model admits an Equivalent Martingale Measure. This market is therefore viable, by the First Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing. Is this market complete?

Solution. Yes: The computations performed in finding \mathbf{P}^* in Exercise 3 of Homework 7 showed that \mathbf{P}^* was uniquely determined by the data (*i.e.*, by the stock-price tree). In view of The Second Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing (Theorem 3.3.2, page 41), the market is therefore complete.

2. In this exercise we use the set-up of Exercise 2, Section 3.7 (page 52–53 of the text). Consult the solution of Exercise 3 on Homework 7 for a description of an Equivalent Martingale Measure \mathbf{P}^* .

(a) Use \mathbf{P}^* to compute the time t price C_t of the European call option with payoff $(S_2^1 - 6)^+$ for $t = 0, 1$.

(b) Now use \mathbf{P}^* to compute the time t price P_t of the European put option with payoff $(6 - S_2^1)^+$ for $t = 0, 1$.

(c) Confirm the call-put parity relationship $C_t - P_t = S_t - 6$ for $t = 0, 1$.

Solution. (a) The no-arbitrage price process C_t can be computed by filling in the tree obtained from backward recursion using $C_2 = (S_2^1 - 6)^+$ in the bottom row of the tree. We obtain

$$C_2^{dd} = C_2^{du} = C_2^{ud} = 0, \quad C_2^{uu} = 3,$$

$$C_1^d = 0, \quad C_1^u = \frac{1}{3} \cdot 0 + \frac{2}{3} \cdot 3 = 2,$$

and

$$C_0 = \frac{3}{4} \cdot 0 + \frac{1}{4} \cdot 2 = \frac{1}{2}.$$

(b) The no-arbitrage price process P_t can be computed by filling in the tree obtained from backward recursion using $P_2 = (6 - S_2^1)^+$ in the bottom row of the tree. We obtain

$$P_2^{dd} = 4, P_2^{du} = 1, P_2^{ud} = 0 = P_2^{uu} = 0,$$

$$P_1^d = \frac{1}{3} \cdot 4 + \frac{2}{3} \cdot 1 = 2, \quad P_1^u = 0,$$

and

$$P_0 = \frac{3}{4} \cdot 2 + \frac{1}{4} \cdot 0 = \frac{3}{2}.$$

(c) Subtracting P_t from C_t we obtain

$$C_0 - P_0 = -1,$$

$$C_1^d - P_1^d = -2, \quad C_1^u - P_1^u = 2,$$

and

$$C_2^{dd} - P_2^{dd} = -4, \quad C_2^{du} - P_2^{du} = -1, \quad C_2^{ud} - P_2^{ud} = 0, \quad C_2^{uu} - P_2^{uu} = 3.$$

On the other hand,

$$S_0^1 = 5,$$

$$S_1^{1,d} = 4, \quad S_1^{1,u} = 8,$$

and

$$S_2^{1,dd} = 2, \quad S_2^{1,du} = 5, \quad S_2^{1,ud} = 6, \quad S_2^{1,uu} = 9,$$

so that

$$S_0^1 - 6 = -1,$$

$$S_1^{1,d} - 6 = -2, \quad S_1^{1,u} - 6 = 2,$$

and

$$S_2^{1,dd} - 6 = -4, \quad S_2^{1,du} - 6 = -1, \quad S_2^{1,ud} - 6 = 0, \quad S_2^{1,uu} - 6 = 3,$$

This shows that $C_t(\omega) - P_t(\omega) = S_t^1(\omega) - K$ for each $t = 0, 1, 2$ and each sample point $\omega \in \Omega$, confirming call-put parity.

3. Exercise 3, Section 3.7 (page 53 of the text).

Solution. (b) Suppose first that $r = 0.1$. We proceed as in the solution of Exercise 3 of Homework 7. As there, we can use the familiar formula for the risk-neutral “up” probability to compute:

$$p^0 = \mathbf{P}^*[S_1^1 = 8] = \frac{1 + .1 - (4/5)}{8/5 - 4/5} = \frac{3}{8},$$

and similarly

$$p^{1,u} = \mathbf{P}^*[S_2^1 = 9 | S_1^1 = 8] = \frac{1.1 - (7/8)}{(9/8) - (7/8)} = \frac{9}{10},$$

and these two “branch” probabilities are uniquely determined by the data. The probabilities for the remaining three-way branch exist, but are not uniquely determined. Indeed, writing

$$a = \mathbf{P}^*[S_2^1 = 2 | S_1^1 = 4], \quad b = \mathbf{P}^*[S_2^1 = 5 | S_1^1 = 4], \quad c = \mathbf{P}^*[S_2^1 = 6 | S_1^1 = 4],$$

we must have

$$\begin{aligned} a + b + c &= 1, \\ (2a + 5b + 6c) \cdot \frac{10}{11} &= 4 \end{aligned}$$

(the martingale property of the discounted stock-price process), and

$$a > 0, \quad b > 0, \quad c > 0.$$

The general solution of this constrained linear system (when parametrized by c) is

$$\left(\frac{1}{5} + \frac{c}{3}, \frac{4}{5} - \frac{4c}{3}, c \right), \quad 0 < c < \frac{3}{5}.$$

So equivalent martingale measures exist, but are not unique.

Suppose now that $r = 1$. In this case there is an arbitrage opportunity, hence no EMM. Indeed, suppose that at time 0 we (short) sell one share of the risky asset and invest the proceeds in the non-risky asset. For this portfolio $\phi_1^0 = \phi_2^0 = 5$, $\phi_1^1 = \phi_2^1 = -1$, $V_0(\phi) = 0$, and

$$V_2(\phi) = 20 - S_2^1,$$

and this final quantity is strictly positive: it is greater than or equal to 11 since $S_2^1 \leq 9$ in all cases. Thus ϕ represents an arbitrage opportunity.

2. Consider the multi-period binomial model with $T = 2$, $S_0 = 4$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, and $r = 0.1$. The hedging strategy $\phi = \{(\alpha_1, \beta_1), (\alpha_2, \beta_2)\}$ for the contingent claim $X = \max(S_0, S_1, S_2)$ is given by

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{12}{11}, \quad \beta_1 = \frac{160}{121},$$

$$\alpha_2^d = 0, \quad \beta_2^d = \frac{400}{121}, \quad \alpha_2^u = \frac{2}{3}, \quad \beta_2^u = \frac{1600}{363}.$$

(a) Verify that ϕ is self-financing. In other words, show that $\alpha_1 S_1 + \beta_1 B_1 = \alpha_2 S_1 + \beta_2 B_1$. (Be sure to consider both possibilities for S_1 .)

(b) Compute $V_0(\phi)$.

Solution. (a) Let us verify that $\alpha_1 S_1 + \beta_1 B_1 = \alpha_2 S_1 + \beta_2 B_1$ by considering the up and down cases separately. In the “up” case we have $S_1 = 8$, so

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_1 S_1 + \beta_1 B_1 &= \alpha_1 \cdot 8 + \beta_1 \cdot \frac{11}{10} \\ &= \frac{12}{11} \cdot 8 + \frac{160}{121} \cdot \frac{11}{10} \\ &= \frac{96}{11} + \frac{16}{11} = \frac{112}{11}, \end{aligned}$$

while

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_2 S_1 + \beta_2 B_1 &= \frac{2}{3} \cdot 8 + \frac{1600}{363} \cdot \frac{11}{10} \\ &= \frac{16}{3} + \frac{160}{33} \\ &= \frac{176 + 160}{33} = \frac{336}{33} = \frac{112}{11}, \end{aligned}$$

which yields the desired equality.

In the “down” case we have $S_1 = 2$, so

$$\alpha_1 S_1 + \beta_1 B_1 = \frac{12}{11} \cdot 2 + \frac{160}{121} \cdot \frac{11}{10} = \frac{24}{11} + \frac{16}{11} = \frac{40}{11},$$

while

$$\alpha_2 S_1 + \beta_2 B_1 = 0 \cdot 2 + \frac{400}{121} \cdot \frac{11}{10} = \frac{40}{11}.$$

Thus we have the desired equality in the down case as well.

(b) $V_0(\phi) = \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1 = \frac{12}{11} \cdot 4 + \frac{160}{121} = \frac{48}{11} + \frac{160}{121} = \frac{528+160}{121} = \frac{688}{121}$. As a check:

$$\begin{aligned} V_0(\phi) &= (1.1)^{-2} \mathbf{E}^*[X] \\ &= \frac{100}{121} \left\{ \frac{9}{25} \cdot 4 + \frac{6}{25} \cdot 4 + \frac{6}{25} \cdot 8 + \frac{4}{25} \cdot 16 \right\} \\ &= \frac{100}{121} \left\{ \frac{36 + 24 + 48 + 64}{25} \right\} \\ &= \frac{4}{121} \cdot 172 = \frac{688}{121}. \end{aligned}$$

3. Consider the single-period binomial model with $S_0 = \$100$, $S_1 = \$200$ or $\$50$, $r = 0.2$.

(a) Find the no-arbitrage initial price of a European call option (on one share of stock) with strike price $K = \$90$.

(b) Find a replicating strategy for the option described in (a).

(c) Suppose the market price of the option in (a) is \$2 less than the no-arbitrage price. Describe a strategy (for trading in stock, bond, and the option) that yields an arbitrage opportunity.

Solution. (a) The call option $X = (S_1 - 90)^+$ takes on the two possible values 110 and 0 with \mathbf{P}^* probabilities $p^* = 7/15$ and $1 - p^* = 8/15$, respectively. Consequently, the no-arbitrage price of X is

$$V_0 = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbf{E}^*[X] = \frac{5}{6} \left[\frac{8}{15} \cdot 0 + \frac{7}{15} \cdot 110 \right] = \frac{385}{9} = 42.78$$

dollars.

(b) The hedging strategy is given by

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{110 - 0}{2 - .5} \cdot \frac{1}{100} = \frac{11}{15} = .733\dots, \quad \beta_1 = \frac{2 \cdot 0 - .5 \cdot 110}{2 - .5} \cdot \frac{5}{6} = -\frac{275}{9} = -30.56.$$

Check:

$$V_0(\phi) = \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1 B_0 = \frac{11}{15} \cdot 100 - \frac{275}{9} = \frac{660 - 275}{9} = \frac{385}{9},$$

as expected.

(c) Suppose C_0 (the price of the put option) is equal to $V_0 - 2$. Here's one arbitrage: Buy the option, sell the hedging portfolio, and put the remaining two dollars in the bond. That is, the trading strategy $\psi = (-\alpha_1, -\beta_1 + 2, 1)$, where α_1 and β_1 are as in part (b). Then

$$V_0(\psi) = -V_0(\phi) + 2 + C_0 = 0,$$

while

$$V_1(\psi) = -V_1(\phi) + 2(6/5) + X = -X + \frac{12}{5} + X = 12/5 > 0,$$

so that ψ presents an arbitrage.

4. For the binomial model with parameters $T = 2$, $u = 7/3$, $d = 1/3$, and $r = 0$, the "risk-neutral" up probability is $p^* = 1/3$. Three random variables M_0 , M_1 , and M_2 are defined on the corresponding sample space $\Omega = \{dd, du, ud, uu\}$ by: $M_0 = 13/3$ (constant),

$$M_1(dd) = M_1(du) = 4, \quad M_1(ud) = M_1(uu) = 5,$$

and

$$M_2(dd) = 5, \quad M_2(du) = 2, \quad M_2(ud) = 6, \quad M_2(uu) = 3.$$

(It may be helpful to draw the binary tree.)

(a) Verify that $\{M_0, M_1, M_2\}$ is a martingale with respect to the probability \mathbf{P}^* .

(b) Compute $\mathbf{E}^*[M_2]$.

Solution. (a) We need to show that $\mathbf{E}^*[M_1|\mathcal{F}_0] = M_0$ and $\mathbf{E}^*[M_2|\mathbf{F}_1] = M_1$.

Because $\mathcal{F}_0 = \{\emptyset, \Omega\}$, the first assertion amounts to showing that $\mathbf{E}^*[M_1] = M_0$. Computing:

$$\mathbf{E}^*[M_1] = \frac{2}{3} \cdot M_1^d + \frac{1}{3} \cdot M_1^u = \frac{2}{3} \cdot 4 + \frac{1}{3} \cdot 5 = \frac{8+5}{3} = \frac{13}{3} = M_0.$$

For $\mathbf{E}^*[M_2|\mathcal{F}_1]$ there are two cases. In the up case, the conditional expectation is the weighted average of $M_2(ud)$ and $M_2(uu)$ with respective weights $2/3$ and $1/3$. This average is

$$\frac{2}{3} \cdot 6 + \frac{1}{3} \cdot 3 = 4 + 1 = 5,$$

which coincides with M_1^u , the given value $M_1(ud) = M_1(uu)$ of M_1 , in the up case. In the down case, the conditional expectation is the weighted average of $M_2(dd)$ and $M_2(du)$, again with respective weights $2/3$ and $1/3$. This average is

$$\frac{2}{3} \cdot 5 + \frac{1}{3} \cdot 2 = \frac{12}{3} = 4,$$

which coincides with M_1^d , the given value $M_1(dd) = M_1(du)$ of M_1 , in the down case. This shows that $\mathbf{E}^*[M_2|\mathcal{F}_1] = M_1$ in all cases.

(b) Direct calculation yields

$$\mathbf{E}^*[M_2] = \frac{4}{9} \cdot 5 + \frac{2}{9} \cdot 2 + \frac{2}{9} \cdot 6 + \frac{1}{9} \cdot 3 = \frac{20 + 4 + 12 + 3}{9} = \frac{39}{9} = \frac{13}{3}.$$

Of course, we could have saved ourselves some work by recalling that (because $\{M_0, M_1, M_2\}$ is a \mathbf{P}^* -martingale!) $\mathbf{E}^*[M_2] = M_0$, which we know to be $13/3$.

2. Consider the multi-period binomial model with $T = 2$, $S_0 = 4$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, and $r = 0.1$. The hedging strategy $\phi = \{(\alpha_1, \beta_1), (\alpha_2, \beta_2)\}$ for the contingent claim $X = \max(S_0, S_1, S_2)$ is given by

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{12}{11}, \quad \beta_1 = \frac{160}{121},$$

$$\alpha_2^d = 0, \quad \beta_2^d = \frac{400}{121}, \quad \alpha_2^u = \frac{2}{3}, \quad \beta_2^u = \frac{1600}{363}.$$

(a) Verify that ϕ is self-financing. In other words, show that $\alpha_1 S_1 + \beta_1 B_1 = \alpha_2 S_1 + \beta_2 B_1$. (Be sure to consider both possibilities for S_1 .)

(b) Compute $V_0(\phi)$.

Solution. (a) Let us verify that $\alpha_1 S_1 + \beta_1 B_1 = \alpha_2 S_1 + \beta_2 B_1$ by considering the up and down cases separately. In the “up” case we have $S_1 = 8$, so

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_1 S_1 + \beta_1 B_1 &= \alpha_1 \cdot 8 + \beta_1 \cdot \frac{11}{10} \\ &= \frac{12}{11} \cdot 8 + \frac{160}{121} \cdot \frac{11}{10} \\ &= \frac{96}{11} + \frac{16}{11} = \frac{112}{11}, \end{aligned}$$

while

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_2 S_1 + \beta_2 B_1 &= \frac{2}{3} \cdot 8 + \frac{1600}{363} \cdot \frac{11}{10} \\ &= \frac{16}{3} + \frac{160}{33} \\ &= \frac{176 + 160}{33} = \frac{336}{33} = \frac{112}{11}, \end{aligned}$$

which yields the desired equality.

In the “down” case we have $S_1 = 2$, so

$$\alpha_1 S_1 + \beta_1 B_1 = \frac{12}{11} \cdot 2 + \frac{160}{121} \cdot \frac{11}{10} = \frac{24}{11} + \frac{16}{11} = \frac{40}{11},$$

while

$$\alpha_2 S_1 + \beta_2 B_1 = 0 \cdot 2 + \frac{400}{121} \cdot \frac{11}{10} = \frac{40}{11}.$$

Thus we have the desired equality in the down case as well.

(b) $V_0(\phi) = \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1 = \frac{12}{11} \cdot 4 + \frac{160}{121} = \frac{48}{11} + \frac{160}{121} = \frac{528+160}{121} = \frac{688}{121}$. As a check:

$$\begin{aligned} V_0(\phi) &= (1.1)^{-2} \mathbf{E}^*[X] \\ &= \frac{100}{121} \left\{ \frac{9}{25} \cdot 4 + \frac{6}{25} \cdot 4 + \frac{6}{25} \cdot 8 + \frac{4}{25} \cdot 16 \right\} \\ &= \frac{100}{121} \left\{ \frac{36 + 24 + 48 + 64}{25} \right\} \\ &= \frac{4}{121} \cdot 172 = \frac{688}{121}. \end{aligned}$$

3. Consider the single-period binomial model with $S_0 = \$100$, $S_1 = \$200$ or $\$50$, $r = 0.2$.

(a) Find the no-arbitrage initial price of a European call option (on one share of stock) with strike price $K = \$90$.

(b) Find a replicating strategy for the option described in (a).

(c) Suppose the market price of the option in (a) is \$2 less than the no-arbitrage price. Describe a strategy (for trading in stock, bond, and the option) that yields an arbitrage opportunity.

Solution. (a) The call option $X = (S_1 - 90)^+$ takes on the two possible values 110 and 0 with \mathbf{P}^* probabilities $p^* = 7/15$ and $1 - p^* = 8/15$, respectively. Consequently, the no-arbitrage price of X is

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dollars.

(b) The hedging strategy is given by

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{110 - 0}{2 - .5} \cdot \frac{1}{100} = \frac{11}{15} = .733\dots, \quad \beta_1 = \frac{2 \cdot 0 - .5 \cdot 110}{2 - .5} \cdot \frac{5}{6} = -\frac{275}{9} = -30.56.$$

Check:

$$V_0(\phi) = \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1 B_0 = \frac{11}{15} \cdot 100 - \frac{275}{9} = \frac{660 - 275}{9} = \frac{385}{9},$$

as expected.

(c) Suppose C_0 (the price of the put option) is equal to $V_0 - 2$. Here's one arbitrage: Buy the option, sell the hedging portfolio, and put the remaining two dollars in the bond. That is, the trading strategy $\psi = (-\alpha_1, -\beta_1 + 2, 1)$, where α_1 and β_1 are as in part (b). Then

$$V_0(\psi) = -V_0(\phi) + 2 + C_0 = 0,$$

while

$$V_1(\psi) = -V_1(\phi) + 2(6/5) + X = -X + \frac{12}{5} + X = 12/5 > 0,$$

so that ψ presents an arbitrage.

4. For the binomial model with parameters $T = 2$, $u = 7/3$, $d = 1/3$, and $r = 0$, the "risk-neutral" up probability is $p^* = 1/3$. Three random variables M_0 , M_1 , and M_2 are defined on the corresponding sample space $\Omega = \{dd, du, ud, uu\}$ by: $M_0 = 13/3$ (constant),

$$M_1(dd) = M_1(du) = 4, \quad M_1(ud) = M_1(uu) = 5,$$

and

$$M_2(dd) = 5, \quad M_2(du) = 2, \quad M_2(ud) = 6, \quad M_2(uu) = 3.$$

(It may be helpful to draw the binary tree.)

(a) Verify that $\{M_0, M_1, M_2\}$ is a martingale with respect to the probability \mathbf{P}^* .

(b) Compute $\mathbf{E}^*[M_2]$.

Solution. (a) We need to show that $\mathbf{E}^*[M_1|\mathcal{F}_0] = M_0$ and $\mathbf{E}^*[M_2|\mathbf{F}_1] = M_1$.

Because $\mathcal{F}_0 = \{\emptyset, \Omega\}$, the first assertion amounts to showing that $\mathbf{E}^*[M_1] = M_0$. Computing:

$$\mathbf{E}^*[M_1] = \frac{2}{3} \cdot M_1^d + \frac{1}{3} \cdot M_1^u = \frac{2}{3} \cdot 4 + \frac{1}{3} \cdot 5 = \frac{8+5}{3} = \frac{13}{3} = M_0.$$

For $\mathbf{E}^*[M_2|\mathcal{F}_1]$ there are two cases. In the up case, the conditional expectation is the weighted average of $M_2(ud)$ and $M_2(uu)$ with respective weights $2/3$ and $1/3$. This average is

$$\frac{2}{3} \cdot 6 + \frac{1}{3} \cdot 3 = 4 + 1 = 5,$$

which coincides with M_1^u , the given value $M_1(ud) = M_1(uu)$ of M_1 , in the up case. In the down case, the conditional expectation is the weighted average of $M_2(dd)$ and $M_2(du)$, again with respective weights $2/3$ and $1/3$. This average is

$$\frac{2}{3} \cdot 5 + \frac{1}{3} \cdot 2 = \frac{12}{3} = 4,$$

which coincides with M_1^d , the given value $M_1(dd) = M_1(du)$ of M_1 , in the down case. This shows that $\mathbf{E}^*[M_2|\mathcal{F}_1] = M_1$ in all cases.

(b) Direct calculation yields

$$\mathbf{E}^*[M_2] = \frac{4}{9} \cdot 5 + \frac{2}{9} \cdot 2 + \frac{2}{9} \cdot 6 + \frac{1}{9} \cdot 3 = \frac{20 + 4 + 12 + 3}{9} = \frac{39}{9} = \frac{13}{3}.$$

Of course, we could have saved ourselves some work by recalling that (because $\{M_0, M_1, M_2\}$ is a \mathbf{P}^* -martingale!) $\mathbf{E}^*[M_2] = M_0$, which we know to be $13/3$.

2. Consider the multi-period binomial model with $T = 2$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, $r = 1/5$, and $S_0 = 100$. Your goal in this problem is to price an American put option with strike price $K = 120$ dollars.

(a) Make the tree diagram listing the possible values for the contingent claim $Y_t = (120 - S_t)^+$, $t = 0, 1, 2$.

(b) Compute the risk-neutral “up” probability p^* , and then use backward recursion to fill in the tree recording the values of the necessary wealth process $U = \{U_0, U_1, U_2\}$.

(c) Find the time-zero price of this American put option with strike price $K = \$120$?

Solution. (a) We have

$$\begin{aligned} Y_0 &= 20 \\ Y_1^d &= 70, \quad Y_1^u = 0, \\ Y_2^{dd} &= 95, \quad Y_2^{du} = Y_2^{ud} = 20, \quad Y_2^{uu} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

(b) First, $p^* = (1 + r - d)/(u - d) = (1.2 - .5)/1.5 = 7/15$. Using this value for p^* and the discount factor $1/(1 + r) = 5/6$ and starting with

$$U_2^{dd} = 95, \quad U_2^{du} = U_2^{ud} = 20, \quad U_2^{uu} = 0,$$

we find that

$$U_1^d = \max\left(70, \left(\frac{8}{15} \cdot 95 + \frac{7}{15} \cdot 20\right) \cdot (5/6)\right) = \max(70, 50) = 70, \quad U_1^u = \frac{8}{15} \cdot 20 \cdot (5/6) = \frac{80}{9},$$

and

$$U_0 = \max\left(20, \left(\frac{8}{15} \cdot 70 + \frac{7}{15} \cdot \frac{80}{9}\right) \cdot (5/6)\right) = \frac{2800}{81} = 34.57.$$

(c) In view of part (b), the time-zero price of this put option is \$34.57.

3. In this problem $T = 1$, the sample space has just two points: $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \omega_2\}$, with $\mathbf{P}[\{\omega_1\}] = \mathbf{P}[\{\omega_2\}] = 1/2$. The value of the riskless security S_t^0 is equal to 1 for $t = 0, 1$. There are two risky securities given by $S_0^1 = S_0^2 = 2$ and

$$\begin{aligned} S_1^1(\omega_1) &= 5, & S_1^1(\omega_2) &= 1, \\ S_1^2(\omega_1) &= 1, & S_1^2(\omega_2) &= 3, \end{aligned}$$

(As usual, S_t^i is the price of security i at time t .) We have $\mathcal{F}_0 = \{\emptyset, \Omega\}$ and $\mathcal{F}_1 = \{\emptyset, \Omega, \{\omega_1\}, \{\omega_2\}\}$. An equivalent probability measure \mathbf{P}^* on Ω is determined by the single number $p^* = \mathbf{P}^*[\{\omega_1\}]$, with $0 < p^* < 1$, for then $\mathbf{P}^*[\{\omega_2\}] = 1 - p^*$.

(a) Show that there is no Equivalent Martingale Measure in the present situation. That is, there is no \mathbf{P}^* such that both $\mathbf{E}^*[S_1^1] = S_0^1$ and $\mathbf{E}^*[S_1^2] = S_0^2$.

(b) Show that the trading strategy $\phi = (\phi_1^0, \phi_1^1, \phi_1^2)$ given by $\phi_1^0 = -4$, $\phi_1^1 = 1$, $\phi_1^2 = 1$ represents an arbitrage opportunity.

Solution. (a) If there were an EMM \mathbf{P}^* , with “up” probability p^* , then (because the bond price is constantly 1) we would have

$$\mathbf{E}^*[S_1^1|\mathcal{F}_0] = S_0^1, \quad \mathbf{E}^*[S_1^2|\mathcal{F}_0] = S_0^2.$$

Writing these equations out explicitly (remember that \mathcal{F}_0 is trivial, so $\mathbf{E}^*[X|\mathcal{F}_0] = \mathbf{E}^*[X]$ for any random variable X) we arrive at the two conditions

$$5 \cdot p^* + 1 \cdot (1 - p^*) = 2, \quad 1 \cdot p^* + 3 \cdot (1 - p^*) = 2.$$

These two equations form an inconsistent system: The solution of the first equation is $p^* = 1/4$ while the solution of the second is $p^* = 1/2$. Thus no choice of p^* makes *both* (discounted) stock-price processes into martingales, so there is no EMM.

(b) We compute:

$$V_0(\phi) = -4 + 1 \cdot 2 + 1 \cdot 2 = 0,$$

$$V_1(\phi)(\omega_1) = -4 + 1 \cdot 5 + 1 \cdot 1 = 2,$$

and

$$V_1(\phi)(\omega_2) = -4 + 1 \cdot 1 + 1 \cdot 3 = 0.$$

Thus, $V_0(\phi) = 0$, $V_1(\phi) \geq 0$ and $\mathbf{P}[V_1(\phi) > 0] > 0$. This means that ϕ is an arbitrage opportunity. [This is a confirmation of the First Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing: The presence of an arbitrage opportunity in the market precludes the existence of an Equivalent Martingale Measure.]

4. The tree for the binomial model with parameters $T = 2$, $u = 2$, $d = 1$, $r = 1/4$, is drawn below. We take $\Omega = \{dd, du, ud, uu\}$, $\mathcal{F}_0 = \{\emptyset, \Omega\}$, $\mathcal{F}_1 = \{\emptyset, \Omega, \{dd, du\}, \{ud, uu\}\}$, and \mathcal{F}_2 the class of all subsets of Ω . The risk neutral measure \mathbf{P}^* is determined by the “up” probability $p^* = 1/4$. The nodes of the tree, as labelled, determine three random variables Z_0 , Z_1 , and Z_2 . (For example, $Z_2(dd) = 1$, $Z_2(ud) = 2$, and $Z_1(uu) = Z_1(ud) = 3$.) The sequence $\{Z_0, Z_1, Z_2\}$ is a \mathbf{P}^* supermartingale—you may take this assertion for granted!

(a) Compute $\mathbf{E}^*[Z_k]$ for $k = 0, 1, 2$, and verify numerically that $\mathbf{E}^*[Z_0] \geq \mathbf{E}^*[Z_1] \geq \mathbf{E}^*[Z_2]$.

(b) Consider the random variable τ defined by $\tau(dd) = \tau(du) = 1$, $\tau(ud) = \tau(uu) = 2$. Verify that τ is a stopping time.

(c) Compute $\mathbf{E}^*[Z_\tau]$.

Solution. (a) Since $Z_0 = 2$, we have $\mathbf{E}^*[Z_0] = 2$. Next, Z_1 has possible values 1 and 3 with respective \mathbf{P}^* probabilities 3/4 and 1/4. Therefore

$$\mathbf{E}^*[Z_1] = (3/4)1 + (1/4)3 = 1.5.$$

Finally, Z_2 has possible values 1, 0, 2, 5, with respective \mathbf{P}^* probabilities 9/16, 3/16, 3/16, 1/16. Therefore

$$\mathbf{E}^*[Z_2] = \frac{9 \cdot 1 + 3 \cdot 0 + 3 \cdot 2 + 1 \cdot 5}{16} = \frac{20}{16} = 1.25.$$

These values confirm that $\mathbf{E}^*[Z_0] \geq \mathbf{E}^*[Z_1] \geq \mathbf{E}^*[Z_2]$, as expected.

(b) Recall that a random variable τ , with set of possible values $\{0, 1, 2\}$, is a *stopping time* provided $\{\omega \in \Omega : \tau(\omega) = t\} \in \mathcal{F}_t$ for $t = 0, 1, 2$. Let us check that this is the case for the given τ .

Clearly $\{\tau = 0\} = \emptyset \in \mathcal{F}_0$,

$$\{\tau = 1\} = \{dd, du\} \in \mathcal{F}_1$$

(consult the listing of \mathcal{F}_1 in the statement of the problem), and

$$\{\tau = 2\} = \{ud, uu\} \in \mathcal{F}_2$$

(because \mathcal{F}_2 contains *all* subsets of Ω). We have confirmed that τ is indeed a stopping time.

(c) Notice that $Z_\tau = 1$ on the event $\{\tau = 1\}$, which event has \mathbf{P}^* probability $3/4$. Similarly, $Z_\tau(ud) = 2$ (and $\mathbf{P}^*[\{ud\}] = 3/16$) and $Z_\tau(uu) = 5$ (and $\mathbf{P}^*[\{uu\}] = 1/16$). It follows that

$$\mathbf{E}^*[Z_\tau] = \frac{3}{4} \cdot 1 + \frac{3}{16} \cdot 2 + \frac{1}{16} \cdot 5 = \frac{23}{16} = 1.4375.$$

(We have computed the numerical values

$$\mathbf{E}[Z_0] = 2, \quad \mathbf{E}[Z_\tau] = 1.4375, \quad \mathbf{E}[Z_2] = 1.25,$$

so that

$$\mathbf{E}[Z_0] > \mathbf{E}[Z_\tau] > \mathbf{E}[Z_2],$$

in consonance with Doob's Stopping Theorem.)

2. Consider the multi-period binomial model with $T = 2$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, $r = 1/4$, and $S_0 = 100$. Your goal in this problem is to price the American put option with strike price $K = 130$ dollars.

(a) Fill in the tree diagrams below for the stock price S_t and for the contingent claim $Y_t = (130 - S_t)^+$, $t = 0, 1, 2$.

(b) Compute the risk-neutral “up” probability p^* , and then use backward recursion to fill in the tree recording the values of the necessary wealth process $U = \{U_0, U_1, U_2\}$. (There is room for scratch work on page 3.)

(c) Find the time-zero price of the American put option with strike price $K = \$130$?

Solution. (a) We have

$$\begin{aligned} S_0 &= 100 \\ S_1^d &= 50, \quad S_1^u = 200, \\ S_2^{dd} &= 25, \quad S_2^{du} = S_2^{ud} = 100, \quad S_2^{uu} = 400, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} Y_0 &= 30 \\ Y_1^d &= 80, \quad Y_1^u = 0, \\ Y_2^{dd} &= 105, \quad Y_2^{du} = Y_2^{ud} = 30, \quad Y_2^{uu} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

(b) First, $p^* = (1 + r - d)/(u - d) = ((1.25 - .5)/1.5) = .5$. Using this value for p^* and the discount factor $1/(1 + r) = 4/5$ and starting with

$$U_2^{dd} = 105, \quad U_2^{du} = U_2^{ud} = 30, \quad U_2^{uu} = 0,$$

we find that

$$\begin{aligned} U_1^d &= 80, \quad U_1^u = 12, \\ U_0 &= 184/5 = 36.8. \end{aligned}$$

(c) In view of part (b), the time-zero price of this put option is \$36.80.

3. In this problem $T = 1$, the sample space has two points: $\Omega = \{a, b\}$; and $\mathbf{P}[\{a\}] = \mathbf{P}[\{b\}] = 1/2$. The riskless security S_t^0 is constantly equal to 1 for $t = 0, 1$, and there are two risky securities with prices given by $S_0^1(a) = S_0^1(b) = S_0^2(a) = S_0^2(b) = 2$ and

$$\begin{aligned} S_1^1(a) &= 5, \quad S_1^1(b) = 1, \\ S_1^2(a) &= 1, \quad S_1^2(b) = 4, \end{aligned}$$

We have $\mathcal{F}_0 = \{\emptyset, \Omega\}$ and $\mathcal{F}_1 = \{\emptyset, \Omega, \{a\}, \{b\}\}$. An equivalent probability measure \mathbf{P}^* on Ω is determined by the single number $p^* = \mathbf{P}^*[\{a\}]$, with $0 < p^* < 1$; then $\mathbf{P}^*[\{b\}] = 1 - p^*$.

(a) Show that there is **no** Equivalent Martingale Measure in the present situation. That is, there is no \mathbf{P}^* such that both $\mathbf{E}^*[S_1^1] = S_0^1$ and $\mathbf{E}^*[S_1^2] = S_0^2$.

(b) Show that the trading strategy $\phi = (\phi_1^0, \phi_1^1, \phi_1^2)$ given by $\phi_1^0 = -6$, $\phi_1^1 = 2$, $\phi_1^2 = 1$ represents an arbitrage opportunity.

Solution. (a) If \mathbf{P}^* were an EMM then we would have $\mathbf{E}^*[S_1^1] = S_0^1$ and $\mathbf{E}^*[S_1^2] = S_0^2$. That is,

$$p^* \cdot 5 + (1 - p^*) \cdot 1 = 2$$

and

$$p^* \cdot 1 + (1 - p^*) \cdot 4 = 2.$$

The first of these equations simplifies to

$$4p^* = 1$$

and the second simplifies to

$$3p^* = 2.$$

The first means that $p^* = 1/4$ and the second that $p^* = 2/3$, so there is no one p^* to make both equalities hold. That is, there is no EMM.

(b) For the given ϕ we have

$$V_0(\phi) = -6 \cdot 1 + 2 \cdot 2 + 1 \cdot 2 = 0$$

and, writing S_1^0 , S_1^1 , and S_1^2 as column vectors,

$$\begin{aligned} V_1(\phi) &= -6S_1^0 + 2S_1^1 + S_1^2 \\ &= -6 \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} + 2 \begin{pmatrix} 5 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 4 \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} -6 \\ -6 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 10 \\ 2 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 4 \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} 5 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \end{aligned}$$

so that $V_1(\phi)$ is always non-negative and sometimes strictly positive. Thus, ϕ is an arbitrage opportunity.

4. The tree for the binomial model with parameters $T = 2$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, $r = 0$, is drawn below. We take $\Omega = \{dd, du, ud, uu\}$, $\mathcal{F}_0 = \{\emptyset, \Omega\}$, $\mathcal{F}_1 = \{\emptyset, \Omega, \{dd, du\}, \{ud, uu\}\}$, and \mathcal{F}_2 the class of all subsets of Ω . The risk neutral measure \mathbf{P}^* is determined by the “up” probability $p^* = 1/3$. The nodes of the tree, as labelled, determine three random variables W_0 , W_1 , and W_2 . (For example, $W_2(dd) = 1$, $W_2(ud) = 4$, and $W_1(uu) = W_1(ud) = 6$.) The sequence $\{W_0, W_1, W_2\}$ is a \mathbf{P}^* -supermartingale—you may take this assertion for granted!

(a) Compute $\mathbf{E}^*[W_k]$ for $k = 0, 1, 2$, and verify numerically that $\mathbf{E}^*[W_0] \geq \mathbf{E}^*[W_1] \geq \mathbf{E}^*[W_2]$.

(b) Consider the random variable τ defined by $\tau(dd) = \tau(du) = 2$, $\tau(ud) = \tau(uu) = 1$. Verify that τ is a stopping time.

(c) Compute $\mathbf{E}^*[W_\tau]$. (You might start by recording the possible values of W_τ in the table below.)

Solution. (a) Since $W_0 = 4$, we have

$$\mathbf{E}^*[W_0] = 4.$$

Next, W_1 has possible values 2 and 6 with respective \mathbf{P}^* probabilities $2/3$ and $1/3$. Therefore

$$\mathbf{E}^*[W_1] = (2/3)2 + (1/3)6 = 10/3 = 3.33\dots$$

Finally, W_2 has possible values 1, 3, 4, 7, with respective \mathbf{P}^* probabilities $4/9, 2/9, 2/9, 1/9$. Therefore

$$\mathbf{E}^*[W_2] = \frac{4 \cdot 1 + 2 \cdot 3 + 2 \cdot 4 + 1 \cdot 7}{9} = \frac{25}{9} = 2\frac{7}{9} = 2.77\dots$$

This confirms that $\mathbf{E}^*[W_0] \geq \mathbf{E}^*[W_1] \geq \mathbf{E}^*[W_2]$, as expected.

(b) Recall that random variable τ , with set of possible values $\{0, 1, 2\}$, is a *stopping time* provided $\{\omega \in \Omega : \tau(\omega) = t\} \in \mathcal{F}_t$ for $t = 0, 1, 2$. Let us check that this is the case for the given τ .

Clearly $\{\tau = 0\} = \emptyset \in \mathcal{F}_0$,

$$\{\tau = 1\} = \{ud, uu\} \in \mathcal{F}_1$$

(consult the listing of \mathcal{F}_1 in the statement of the problem), and

$$\{\tau = 2\} = \{dd, du\} \in \mathcal{F}_2$$

(because \mathcal{F}_2 contains *all* subsets of Ω). We have confirmed that τ is indeed a stopping time.

(c) Notice that $W_\tau = 6$ on the event $\{\tau = 1\}$, which event has \mathbf{P}^* probability $1/3 = 2/9 + 1/9$. Similarly, $W_\tau(dd) = 1$ (and $\mathbf{P}^*[\{dd\}] = 4/9$) and $W_\tau(du) = 3$ (and $\mathbf{P}^*[\{du\}] = 2/9$). It follows that

$$\mathbf{E}^*[W_\tau] = \frac{1}{3} \cdot 6 + \frac{4}{9} \cdot 1 + \frac{2}{9} \cdot 3 = \frac{28}{9} = 3.111\dots$$

As might be expected, and using the numerical values found in part (b),

$$\mathbf{E}^*[W_0] > \mathbf{E}^*[W_1] > \mathbf{E}^*[W_\tau] > \mathbf{E}^*[W_2].$$

2. Consider a two-period ($T = 2$) binomial model with initial stock price $S_0 = \$8$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, and “real world” up probability $p = 1/3$.

- Draw the binary tree illustrating the possible paths followed by the stock price process.
- The sample space for this problem can be listed as $\Omega = \{dd, du, ud, uu\}$. List the probabilities associated with the individual elements of the sample space Ω .
- List the events (i.e., the subsets of Ω) making up the σ -field \mathcal{F}_1 determined by S_1 .
- List the values (one for each path) of a European contingent claim whose payoff at $T = 2$ is $X = S_0 + S_1 + S_2$.

Solution. (a)

$$S_0 = 8$$

$$S_1^d = 4 \quad S_1^u = 16$$

$$S_2^{dd} = 2 \quad S_2^{du} = 8 \quad S_2^{ud} = 8 \quad S_2^{uu} = 32$$

(b) The \mathbf{P} probabilities of the individual elements of Ω are (in the order in which those points are listed above):

$$4/9 \quad 2/9 \quad 2/9 \quad 1/9.$$

(c) $\mathcal{F}_1 = \{\emptyset, \Omega, \{dd, du\}, \{ud, uu\}\}$.

(d) In the same order as above, the values taken by X are

$$14 \quad 20 \quad 32 \quad 56.$$

3. Consider a single-period binomial model with $r = 1/3$, $S_0 = 2$, $d = 5/4$, $u = 3/2$. Let us take $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \omega_2\}$ and $S_1(\omega_1) = 5/2$ and $S_1(\omega_2) = 3$.

- For the trading strategy $\phi = (\alpha, \beta) = (3, -2)$, compute $V_0(\phi)$, $V_1(\phi)(\omega_1)$, and $V_1(\phi)(\omega_2)$. [Recall that α is the holdings in the stock and β the holdings in the bond.]
- Let X be a European call option with strike price \$2.50 and expiration time $T = 1$.
 - Find $X(\omega_1)$ and $X(\omega_2)$.

- (ii) Find the replicating strategy ϕ for X
 (iii) Find the manufacturing cost $V_0(\phi)$ for that strategy.

Solution. (a) $V_0(\phi) = 3 \cdot S_0 - 2 = 4$. $V_1(\phi) = 3S_1 - 8/3$, so $V_1(\phi)(\omega_1) = 3(5/2) - 2(4/3) = 29/6$ and $V_1(\phi)(\omega_2) = 3 \cdot 3 - 2(4/3) = 19/3$.

(b) $X = (S_1 - 2.5)^+$.

(i) $X(\omega_1) = 0$, $X(\omega_2) = .5$.

(ii) The replicating strategy for X is given by the familiar formulae:

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{X(\omega_2) - X(\omega_1)}{u - d} \cdot \frac{1}{S_0} = \frac{.5 - 0}{3/2 - 5/4} \cdot \frac{1}{2} = 1,$$

while

$$\beta_1 = \frac{uX(\omega_1) - dX(\omega_2)}{u - d} \cdot \frac{1}{B_1} = \frac{3/2 \cdot 0 - 5/4 \cdot .5}{3/2 - 5/4} \cdot \frac{3}{4} = -\frac{15}{8}.$$

(c) The cost of the replicating strategy $(1, -15/8)$ found in part (b) is $V_0 = 1 \cdot 2 - 15/8 \cdot 1 = 1/8$.

4. This problem is about a multi-period binomial model with $T = 2$, $B_0 = 1$, $S_0 = \$100$, $S_1 = \$200$ or $\$50$, and $r = 0.1$. In this case $p^* = 2/5$. Now consider an American put option with strike price $K = \$120$.

- (a) Use backward recursion in binary tree for the necessary wealth process U_t , based on the payoffs $Y_t = (120 - S_t)^+$, to compute the arbitrage-free initial price of the American put option.
 (b) Suppose that you can buy the American put option at time zero for \$1 less than its arbitrage-free price. Explicitly describe a strategy that yields an arbitrage opportunity for a buyer of the American put option.

Solution. (a)

$$S_0 = 100$$

$$S_1^d = 50 \quad S_1^u = 200$$

$$S_2^{dd} = 25 \quad S_2^{du} = 100 \quad S_2^{ud} = 100 \quad S_2^{uu} = 400$$

Also, writing $Y_t = (120 - S_t)^+$ for the put-option payoff at time t ,

$$Y_0 = 20$$

$$Y_1^d = 70 \quad Y_1^u = 0$$

$$Y_2^{dd} = 95 \quad Y_2^{du} = 20 \quad Y_2^{ud} = 20 \quad Y_2^{uu} = 0$$

Using the backward recursion $U_{t-1} = \max[Y_{t-1}, (1+r)^{-1}\mathbf{E}^*[U_t|\mathcal{F}_{t-1}]]$ for $t = 2, 1$ we obtain the “ U tree”:

$$\begin{aligned} U_0 &= 5100/121 \\ U_1^d &= 70 \quad U_1^u = 120/11 \\ U_2^{dd} &= 95 \quad U_2^{du} = 20 \quad U_2^{ud} = 20 \quad U_2^{uu} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

The no-arbitrage price of this American put option is therefore $5100/121 = 42.15$ dollars.

(b) In view of the U tree of part (a), the optimal time for a holder of the put to exercise the option is the stopping time consisting of “stop at time 1 if the stock price goes down, and stop at time 2 if it goes up”. A buyer’s arbitrage is available if the put is priced at \$41.15: Buy the put for \$41.15, sell the super-replicating strategy $\phi^* = (\alpha_t^*, \beta_t^*)$ (which is such that $V_0(\phi^*) = 42.15$ and $V_t(\phi^*) \geq U_t$ for $t = 0, 1, 2$), and put the \$1 left over into the bond. If the stock goes down at time 1, exercise the put option, getting \$70 thereby. The total worth of the buyer’s portfolio is then $70 + V_\tau(\phi^*) = 70 - 63.64 = 6.36$ (dollars), which could be invested in the bond. If the stock goes up at time 1, exercise the put at time 2; the proceeds then exactly balance the (negative) worth of the superhedging portfolio. This strategy has no downside risk, and there is a guaranteed profit of $\$(11/10)^2 = \1.21 (more if the stock goes down at time 1) no matter what happens.

5. Consider the two-period binomial model with $S_0 = \$100$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, and $r = 1/2$. As usual, $\Omega = \{dd, du, ud, uu\}$, $\mathcal{F}_0 = \{\emptyset, \Omega\}$, $\mathcal{F}_1 = \{\{dd, du\}, \{ud, uu\}, \emptyset, \Omega\}$, and \mathcal{F}_2 is the σ -field of all subsets of Ω .

- (a) Compute the risk-neutral “up” probability p^* .
- (b) The sequence $\{M_0, M_1, M_2\}$ is a martingale with respect to the filtration $\{\mathcal{F}_0, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2\}$ and the martingale measure \mathbf{P}^* determined by p^* from part (a). (That is, $\mathbf{E}^*[M_t|\mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = M_{t-1}$ for $t = 1, 2$.) You are told that

$$M_2(dd) = 2, \quad M_2(du) = 3, \quad M_2(ud) = 7, \quad M_2(uu) = 9.$$

Compute M_1^d , M_1^u , and M_0 .

Solution. (a) $p^* = (1+r-d)/(u-d) = (1.5-.5)/(2-.5) = 2/3$.

(b)

$$M_1^d = (1/3)2 + (2/3)3 = 8/3, \quad M_1^u = (1/3)7 + (2/3)9 = 25/3,$$

$$M_0 = (1/3)M_1^d + (2/3)M_1^u = (1/3)(8/3) + (2/3)(25/3) = 58/9.$$

6. Consider the sample space $\Omega = \{1, 2, 3\}$ and the probability measure \mathbf{P} giving each point weight $1/3$. On this probability space consider the finite model with $T = 1$, $S_0^0 = S_1^0 = 1$, $S_0^1 = 2$, and

$$S_1^1(1) = 1, \quad S_1^1(2) = 2, \quad S_1^1(3) = 4.$$

- (a) This market is viable, so there is at least one EMM. Find all possible EMMs.
 (b) Consider the contingent claim Y given by

$$Y(1) = 2, \quad Y(2) = 4, \quad Y(3) = 8.$$

Without actually finding a hedging strategy, explain why Y can be replicated.

Solution. (a) In the present context, an EMM is a system of three weights a, b, c (the respective probabilities of 1, 2, 3) such that $a + b + c = 1$, $a > 0, b > 0, c > 0$, and $a + 2b + 4c = 2$. (The latter is just the condition that the mean of S_1^1 be equal to S_0^1 .) This system of equations is easily solved: subtract the first equation from the second, and then isolate b to find that $b = 1 - 3c$, and then that $a = 1 - b - c = 2c$. The constraints $a > 0, b > 0$ force $0 < c < 1/3$. Thus, a complete description of all EMMs is:

$$\mathbf{P}^c \text{ gives weights } 2c, 1 - 3c, c \text{ to } 1, 2, 3 \quad (0 < c < 1/3).$$

- (b) We compute:

$$\mathbf{E}^c[Y] = c \cdot 2 + (1 - 3c) \cdot 4 + c \cdot 8 = 4$$

independently of $c \in (0, 1/3)$. That is, the mean of Y is the same for all EMMs. By the “Duality Formula” discussed in class, this means that $V_+(Y) = V_-(Y)$, so that Y can be replicated (see Corollary 3.5.2, page 49 of the text).

7. This is a continuation of Problem 6: The sample space is $\Omega = \{1, 2, 3\}$ with the probability measure \mathbf{P} giving each point weight $1/3$. We have $T = 1$, $S_0^0 = S_1^0 = 1$, $S_0^1 = 2$, and

$$S_1^1(1) = 1, \quad S_1^1(2) = 2, \quad S_1^1(3) = 4.$$

- (a) Compute $V_+(X)$ and $V_-(X)$ for the contingent claim X given by

$$X(1) = 1, \quad X(2) = 3, \quad X(3) = 9.$$

- (b) Find a trading strategy $\phi = (\phi_1^0, \phi_1^1)$ such that $V_1(\phi) \geq X$ and $V_0(\phi) = V_+(X)$.

Solution. (a) Using the EMMs \mathbf{P}^c from Problem 6,

$$\mathbf{E}^c[X] = 2c \cdot 1 + (1 - 3c) \cdot 3 + c \cdot 9 = 3 + 2c, \quad 0 < c < 1/3.$$

From this and the Duality Formula it follows that

$$V_+(X) = \sup\{\mathbf{E}^c[X] : 0 < c < 1/3\} = 11/3 = \frac{11}{3},$$

and

$$V_-(X) = \inf\{\mathbf{E}^c[X] : 0 < c < 1/3\} = 3.$$

Alternatively, to find $V_+(X)$ we can solve the optimization problem $V_+ = \min\{V_0(\phi) : V_1(\phi) \geq X\}$; or more explicitly:

$$\text{minimize } 2\alpha + \beta \text{ subject to } \alpha + \beta \geq 1, 2\alpha + \beta \geq 3, 4\alpha + \beta \geq 9.$$

(Here I write $\alpha = \phi_1^1$ and $\beta = \phi_1^0$.) A picture shows that the second constraint is redundant, and then that the minimum is attained at the point $(\alpha, \beta) = (8/3, -5/3)$ where the boundary lines of the other two constraints intersect. In particular, we obtain $V_+(X) = V_0(8/3, -5/3) = (8/3)2 - 5/3 = 11/3$, as before.

Similarly, to find $V_-(X)$ we can solve the optimization problem $V_-(X) = \max\{V_0(\phi) : V_1(\phi) \leq X\}$; or more explicitly:

$$\text{maximize } 2\alpha + \beta \text{ subject to } \alpha + \beta \leq 1, 2\alpha + \beta \leq 3, 4\alpha + \beta \leq 9.$$

(Again, I write $\alpha = \phi_1^1$ and $\beta = \phi_1^0$.) A picture now shows that the maximum must occur at one (or both) of the vertices of the boundary of the constraint region. These two points $(3, -3)$ and $(2, -1)$ are the points where the second and third boundary lines intersect, and where the first and second boundary lines intersect. Since $V_0(3, -3) = V_0(2, -1) = 3$, we have $V_-(X) = 3$, as expected. Either of these two points represents a maximal subhedging strategy.

(b) [Warning: I will now use the notation $\phi = (\phi_1^0, \phi_1^1)$, which would be (β, α) in the lazy notation used in solving part (a).] In computing $V_+(X)$ in part (a), by the constrained optimization method, we found a strategy $\phi = (\phi_1^0, \phi_1^1) = (-5/3, 8/3)$ with $V_0(\phi) = 11/3$ and $V_1(\phi) \geq X$:

$$V_1(-5/3, 8/3) = (-5/3)S_1^1 + 8/3S_1^0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 11/3 \\ 9 \end{pmatrix} \geq \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 3 \\ 9 \end{pmatrix}.$$

University of California, San Diego
Department of Mathematics

1. Write your *Name*, *PID*, *Section*, and *Exam Version* on the front of your Blue Book.
2. You may use a calculator, but no other electronic devices are allowed during this exam.
3. You may use one page of notes, but no books or other assistance during this exam.
4. Write your solutions clearly in your Blue Book
 - (a) Carefully indicate the number and letter of each question.
 - (b) Present your answers in the same order they appear in the exam.
 - (c) Start a new answer on a new page.
5. Show all of your work; no credit will be given for unsupported answers.

1. (15 points) Consider a Single-Period Binomial Model with $B_0 = 1$, $S_0 = 4$, $r = 0.2$, $u = 1.5$, $d = 0.8$, and $p = 3/8$. Let X be a European call option with strike price \$3 and expiration date $T = 1$.
 - (a) What should the option price (or premium) be for X in order to eliminate arbitrage opportunities?
 - (b) Suppose that the option price is \$1 and the strike price is \$3. Find an arbitrage opportunity ψ such that ψ has a manufacturing cost of \$0. Verify that ψ is an arbitrage opportunity.

Solution: (a) Let $\omega_1 = (u)$ and $\omega_2 = (d)$ be the sample paths of length one. Then $X = (S_1 - 3)^+$, and so $X(\omega_1) = 3$ and $X(\omega_2) = 0.20$. We draw a tree diagram to represent this model, including a column for $X(\omega)$:

The risk neutral probability is $p = \frac{(1+r)-d}{u-d} = \frac{4}{7}$, and so by the Manufacturing Cost Lemma,

$$C_0 = E^*[X^*] = \frac{1}{1.2} \left[3 \cdot \frac{4}{7} + 0.2 \cdot \frac{3}{7} \right] = 1.50.$$

Therefore, the unique arbitrage free price is \$1.50 per option.

Alternatively: You may compute the replicating strategy $\phi^* = (\alpha, \beta)$ for X . Using the formulas, we have:

$$\alpha = \frac{X^u - X^d}{S_0(u - d)} = \frac{3 - 0.2}{4(1.5 - 0.8)} = \frac{2.8}{4(0.7)} = 1$$

(This exam is worth 30 points.)

and

$$\beta = \frac{uX^d - dX^u}{(1+r)(u-d)} = \frac{(1.5)(0.2) - (0.8)(3)}{(1.2)(1.5 - 0.8)} = \frac{0.3 - 2.4}{0.84} = -\frac{2.1}{0.84} = -2.5.$$

Therefore,

$$C_0 = V_0(\phi^*) = \alpha S_0 + \beta B_0 = (1)(4) + (-2.5)(1) = 1.50.$$

(b) We are given that the strike price is \$3. From (a), we know that the arbitrage free option price in this case is \$1.50. This means that the contingent claim X is underpriced. Idea: Raise enough capital to invest in the replicating strategy $\phi^* = (\alpha, \beta) = (1, -2.5)$, which has an initial value of \$1.50. Use \$1 to buy the contingent claim and invest the rest in bonds. The arbitrage opportunity, then, will be the strategy

$$\psi = (-\alpha, -\beta + 0.5, 1) = (-1, 2.5 + 0.5, 1) = (-1, 3, 1).$$

We must verify that this is indeed an arbitrage opportunity:

$$V_0(\psi) = (-1)S_0 + (3)B_0 + (1)C_0 = -4 + 3 + 1 = 0,$$

and

$$V_1(\psi) = (-1)S_1 + (3)B_1 + (1)X = \begin{cases} -6 + 3(1.2) + 3 = 0.6 & \text{if } \xi_1 = u \\ -3.2 + 3(1.2) + 0.2 = 0.6 & \text{if } \xi_1 = d \end{cases}$$

Either way, $V_1(\psi) > 0$, and so ψ is an arbitrage opportunity.

2. (10 points) Consider a 2-Period Binomial Model with $B_0 = 1$, $S_0 = 3$, $r = 1/3$, and S_1 is either 5 (with probability $2/3$) or 2 (with probability $1/3$). Let X be a contingent claim with expiration time $T = 2$ given by the random variable $X = \max\{S_0, S_1, S_2\}$. (This is an example of an *exotic derivative* known as a *lookback option*.)
- Find a replicating strategy ϕ^* for X .
 - What is the manufacturing cost of X ?
 - What is the arbitrage free cost C_1 for X at time $t = 1$?

Solution: Observe that $u = \frac{5}{3}$ and $d = \frac{2}{3}$. We draw a tree diagram to represent this model, including a column for $X(\omega)$:

(a) We will find a replicating strategy $\phi^* = \{(\alpha_1, \beta_1), (\alpha_2, \beta_2)\}$. Let

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_2^u &= \alpha_2(\omega_1) = \alpha_2(\omega_2), & \beta_2^u &= \beta_2(\omega_1) = \beta_2(\omega_2), \\ \alpha_2^d &= \alpha_2(\omega_3) = \alpha_2(\omega_4), & \beta_2^d &= \beta_2(\omega_3) = \beta_2(\omega_4) \end{aligned}$$

Then we have the following two systems of equations:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_2^u \cdot \frac{25}{3} + \beta_2^u \cdot \frac{16}{9} = \frac{25}{3} \\ \alpha_2^u \cdot \frac{10}{3} + \beta_2^u \cdot \frac{16}{9} = 5 \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{cases} \alpha_2^d \cdot \frac{10}{3} + \beta_2^d \cdot \frac{16}{9} = \frac{10}{3} \\ \alpha_2^d \cdot \frac{4}{3} + \beta_2^d \cdot \frac{16}{9} = 3 \end{cases}$$

Solving these systems yields

$$(\alpha_2, \beta_2) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{2}{3}, \frac{25}{16}\right) & \text{if } \omega \in \{\omega_1, \omega_2\} \\ \left(\frac{1}{6}, \frac{25}{16}\right) & \text{if } \omega \in \{\omega_3, \omega_4\} \end{cases}$$

To determine α_1 and β_1 , we use the self-financing property: $\alpha_1 S_1 + \beta_1 B_1 = \alpha_2 S_1 + \beta_2 B_1$. Since these random variables are \mathcal{F}_1 -measurable, we have two equations: one for when the stock goes up ($\xi_1 = u$) and one for when the stock goes down ($\xi_1 = d$). Therefore,

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_1 \cdot 5 + \beta_1 \cdot \frac{4}{3} = \frac{2}{3} \cdot 5 + \frac{25}{16} \cdot \frac{4}{3} = \frac{65}{12} & \text{if } \xi_1 = u \\ \alpha_1 \cdot 2 + \beta_1 \cdot \frac{4}{3} = \frac{1}{6} \cdot 2 + \frac{25}{16} \cdot \frac{4}{3} = \frac{29}{12} & \text{if } \xi_1 = d \end{cases}$$

Solving this system reveals that $(\alpha_1, \beta_1) = \left(1, \frac{5}{16}\right)$.

Since ϕ^* was constructed so that it is self-financing and $V_2(\phi^*) = X$, it follows that ϕ^* is a replicating strategy for X .

(b) The manufacturing cost of X is

$$C_0 = V_0(\phi^*) = \alpha_1 S_0 + \beta_1 B_0 = 1 \cdot 3 + \frac{5}{16} \cdot 1 = \frac{53}{16}.$$

(c) The arbitrage free cost for X at time $t = 1$ is the random variable

$$C_1 = V_1(\phi^*) = \alpha_1 S_1 + \beta_1 B_1 = \begin{cases} 1 \cdot 5 + \frac{5}{16} \cdot \frac{4}{3} = \frac{65}{12} & \text{if } \xi_1 = u \\ 1 \cdot 2 + \frac{5}{16} \cdot \frac{4}{3} = \frac{29}{12} & \text{if } \xi_1 = d \end{cases}$$

3. (5 points) You make a wager with a friend that a certain stock will go up in value over the next period. If the stock goes down in price, you have to pay your friend \$5. Your friend thinks it is very unlikely that the stock will go up, so if the stock goes up in price he will give you \$10. Define a random variable that represents this transaction and (assuming this leads to a viable secondary market) find the associated risk neutral probability.

Solution: Let $X = 10$ if $\xi_1 = u$ and $X = -5$ if $\xi_1 = d$. By assumption, we have a viable secondary market. That means that the initial cost of this claim C_0 is the arbitrage free price for the claim. By the Manufacturing Cost Lemma,

$$C_0 = E^*[X^*] = \frac{1}{1+r} [10p^* - 5(1-p^*)],$$

where r is the (unknown) interest rate and p^* is the risk neutral probability. Since no money exchanges hands at the start of the period, $C_0 = 0$. Thus,

$$0 = \frac{1}{1+r} [10p^* - 5(1-p^*)] = \frac{1}{1+r} [10p^* - 5 + 5p^*] = \frac{1}{1+r} [15p^* - 5].$$

Consequently, $0 = 15p^* - 5$, and so $p^* = \frac{5}{15} = \frac{1}{3}$.

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1. (10 points) Consider a 2-period Binomial Model with $B_0 = 1$, $S_0 = 4$, and $S_1 = 6$ (with probability $2/3$) or $S_1 = 8/3$ (with probability $1/3$). Suppose $r = 1/3$. Let X be a European call option with strike price \$3 and expiration time $T = 2$. Find a replicating strategy for X . What is the manufacturing cost of X ?

Solution: We begin by observing that $u = \frac{3}{2}$ and $d = \frac{2}{3}$. We can now draw the following tree diagram:

Let $\phi^* = \{(\alpha_1, \beta_1), (\alpha_2, \beta_2)\}$ be the replicating strategy for X . In order to replicate X , we must have $V_2(\phi^*) = X$. That is, we must have $\alpha_2 S_2 + \beta_2 B_2 = X$. For notational convenience, let $\alpha_2^u = \alpha_2(\omega_1)$ and $\alpha_2^d = \alpha_2(\omega_3)$. Similarly, let $\beta_2^u = \beta_2(\omega_1)$ and $\beta_2^d = \beta_2(\omega_3)$. Then, we must solve the following systems of equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_2^u(9) + \beta_2^u(16/9) &= 6 & \text{and} & & \alpha_2^d(4) + \beta_2^d(16/9) &= 1 \\ \alpha_2^u(4) + \beta_2^u(16/9) &= 1 & & & \alpha_2^d(16/9) + \beta_2^d(16/9) &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Solving these two systems yields

$$(\alpha_2, \beta_2) = \begin{cases} \left(1, -\frac{27}{16}\right) & \text{if } \xi_1 = u \\ \left(\frac{9}{20}, -\frac{9}{20}\right) & \text{if } \xi_1 = d \end{cases}$$

(This exam is worth 50 points.)

By the self-financing property, we have $\alpha_1 S_1 + \beta_1 B_1 = \alpha_2 S_1 + \beta_2 B_1$. Thus, we have the system

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha_1(6) + \beta_1(4/3) &= (1)(6) + \left(-\frac{27}{16}\right)\left(\frac{4}{3}\right) = \frac{15}{4} \\ \alpha_1(8/3) + \beta_1(4/3) &= \left(\frac{9}{20}\right)\left(\frac{8}{3}\right) + \left(-\frac{9}{20}\right)\left(\frac{4}{3}\right) = \frac{3}{5}\end{aligned}$$

Solving this system, we have

$$(\alpha_1, \beta_1) = \left(\frac{189}{200}, -\frac{288}{200}\right).$$

Then, the replicating strategy for X is $\phi^* = \{(\alpha_1, \beta_1), (\alpha_2, \beta_2)\}$.

The manufacturing cost of X is

$$V_0(\phi^*) = \left(\frac{189}{200}\right)(4) + \left(-\frac{288}{200}\right)(1) = \frac{468}{200} = 2.34.$$

We can also compute the manufacturing cost of X by using the Manufacturing Cost Lemma. For this, we need to compute the risk probability

$$p^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d} = \frac{(4/3) - (2/3)}{(3/2) - (2/3)} = \frac{4}{5}.$$

Thus,

$$V_0(\phi^*) = E^*[X^*] = \frac{1}{16/9} \left[6\left(\frac{4}{5}\right)^2 + 1\left(\frac{4}{5}\right)\left(\frac{1}{5}\right) + 1\left(\frac{1}{5}\right)\left(\frac{4}{5}\right) + 0\left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^2 \right] = 2.34.$$

2. (10 points) Consider a 2-period Binomial Model with $B_0 = 1$, $S_0 = 4$, and $S_1 = 6$ (with probability $2/3$) or $S_1 = 8/3$ (with probability $1/3$). Suppose $r = 1/3$. Let $\{Y_t : t = 0, 1, 2\}$ be an American contingent claim with payoff $Y_t = \max\{S_s : s \leq t\}$ at time t for each $t \in \{0, 1, 2\}$.
- Find the Snell envelope $\{U_t : t = 0, 1, 2\}$ for $\{Y_t\}$.
 - Find the arbitrage free initial price for the claim $\{Y_t\}$.
 - Is $\{U_t\}$ a martingale with respect to the risk neutral probability? Justify your answer.

Solution: We begin by observing that this primary market is the same as Question 1. Consequently, $u = \frac{3}{2}$ and $d = \frac{2}{3}$ and the tree diagram for $\{S_t\}$ is the same as before. In this instance, however, we need to draw the tree diagram for $\{Y_t\}$:

We will need the risk probability (which we computed at the end of Question 1):

$$p^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d} = \frac{(4/3) - (2/3)}{(3/2) - (2/3)} = \frac{4}{5}.$$

(a) We seek to find U_t , the minimum required wealth at time t needed to cover a payout at time t or any future time $s \geq t$, where $t \in \{0, 1, 2\}$. We first note that $U_2 = Y_2$. For $t = 1$, we have

$$U_1 = \max \left\{ Y_1, \frac{1}{1+r} E^*[U_2 | \mathcal{F}_1] \right\} = \max \left\{ Y_1, \frac{1}{4/3} E^*[Y_2 | \mathcal{F}_1] \right\}.$$

Computing the conditional expectation:

$$E^*[Y_2 | \mathcal{F}_1](\omega_i) = \begin{cases} 9 \cdot \frac{4}{5} + 6 \cdot \frac{1}{5} = \frac{42}{5} & \text{if } i = 1, 2, \\ 4 \cdot \frac{4}{5} + 4 \cdot \frac{1}{5} = \frac{20}{5} & \text{if } i = 3, 4. \end{cases}$$

Consequently,

$$\frac{1}{4/3} E^*[Y_2 | \mathcal{F}_1](\omega_i) = \begin{cases} 6.3 & \text{if } i = 1, 2, \\ 3 & \text{if } i = 3, 4. \end{cases}$$

Since $U_1 = \max \left\{ Y_1, \frac{1}{4/3} E^*[Y_2 | \mathcal{F}_1] \right\}$, we have

$$U_1(\omega_i) = \begin{cases} \max\{6, 6.3\} = 6.3 & \text{if } i = 1, 2, \\ \max\{4, 3\} = 4 & \text{if } i = 3, 4. \end{cases}$$

Next, we find U_0 , which is the minimum wealth needed at time $t = 0$. We have

$$U_0 = \max \left\{ Y_0, \frac{1}{4/3} E^*[U_1 | \mathcal{F}_0] \right\} = \max \left\{ Y_0, \frac{3}{4} E^*[U_1] \right\}.$$

We compute:

$$\frac{3}{4} E^*[U_1] = \frac{3}{4} \left[6.3 \cdot \frac{4}{5} + 4 \cdot \frac{1}{5} \right] = \frac{3}{4} \cdot 5.84 = 4.38.$$

Therefore, $U_0 = \max\{Y_0, \frac{3}{4}E^*[U_1]\} = \max\{4, 4.38\} = 4.38$.

(b) The arbitrage free initial price is U_0 , and therefore it is \$4.38.

(c) Observe that

$$E^*[U_2|\mathcal{F}_0] = E^*[Y_2] = 9\left(\frac{4}{5}\right)^2 + 6\left(\frac{4}{5}\right)\left(\frac{1}{5}\right) + 4\left(\frac{1}{5}\right)\left(\frac{4}{5}\right) + 4\left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^2 = \frac{188}{25} = 7.52.$$

Since $E^*[U_2|\mathcal{F}_0] \neq U_0$, the Snell envelope $\{U_t\}$ is not a P^* -martingale. (It would also have been sufficient to show that $E^*[U_2|\mathcal{F}_1] \neq U_1$ or $E^*[U_1|\mathcal{F}_0] \neq U_0$.)

Note: It is perhaps worth mentioning that the discounted Snell envelope $\{U_t^*\}$ is also not a P^* -martingale, because $E^*[U_2^*|\mathcal{F}_0] = 4.23 \neq U_0^*$. Thus, it is not sufficient to say that $\{U_t\}$ is not a P^* -martingale because the process is not discounted.

3. (10 points) Consider the Finite Market Model with $n = 5$, $T = 2$, and $d = 2$. Suppose that the risk-free asset is identically equal to one. That is, suppose $S_t^0 = 1$ for all $t = 0, 1, 2$. The following table describes the behavior of the two risky assets:

	S_0^1	S_1^1	S_2^1	S_0^2	S_1^2	S_2^2
ω_1	3	6	12	5	8	16
ω_2	3	6	9	5	8	12
ω_3	3	6	3	5	8	4
ω_4	3	2	3	5	4	6
ω_5	3	2	0	5	4	3

- (a) Find all equivalent martingale measures or show that there is none.
- (b) Can all European contingent claims be replicated? Justify your answer.

Solution: Once again, we begin with the tree diagrams:

$S_1^1(\omega)$

$S_1^2(\omega)$

(a) Suppose that Q is an EMM. Let $p = Q(\{\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3\})$ and $q = Q(\{\omega_4, \omega_5\})$. Note that $q = 1 - p$. We will use the formula

$$E^Q[S_t^{*,k} | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = S_{t-1}^{*,k}, \quad k = 1, 2. \quad (1)$$

Since the risk-free asset is identically equal to one, we have that $S_t^{*,k} = S_t^k$ for each $k = 1, 2$ and each $t = 0, 1, 2$. We start with $t = 1$. The equation in (1) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} 6p + 2(1 - p) &= 3 & \text{if } k = 1, \\ 8p + 4(1 - p) &= 5 & \text{if } k = 2. \end{aligned}$$

Both of these equations are consistent with $p = 1/4$. Thus, $p = 1/4$ and $q = 3/4$.

We now turn our attention to the second period, when $t = 2$. Let $p_u = Q(\{\omega_1\} | \{\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3\})$, $q_u = Q(\{\omega_2\} | \{\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3\})$, and $r_u = Q(\{\omega_3\} | \{\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3\})$. Note that $r_u = 1 - p_u - q_u$. In this case, which only includes the top half of the tree diagram, (1) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} 12p_u + 9q_u + 3(1 - p_u - q_u) &= 6 & \text{if } k = 1, \\ 16p_u + 12q_u + 4(1 - p_u - q_u) &= 8 & \text{if } k = 2. \end{aligned}$$

Observe that the first equation is $4/3$ times the second equation. Therefore, this system has infinitely many solutions: $p_u = x$, $q_u = \frac{1}{2}(1 - 3x)$, and $r_u = \frac{1}{2}(1 - x)$, where $x \in (0, \frac{1}{3})$.

Now let $p_d = Q(\{\omega_4\} | \{\omega_4, \omega_5\})$ and $q_d = Q(\{\omega_5\} | \{\omega_4, \omega_5\})$. We have $q_d = 1 - p_d$. In this case, which only includes the bottom half of the tree diagram, (1) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} 3p_d + 0(1 - p_d) &= 2 & \text{if } k = 1, \\ 6p_d + 3(1 - p_d) &= 4 & \text{if } k = 2. \end{aligned}$$

The first of these equations implies that $p_d = 2/3$, whereas the second equation implies $p_d = 1/3$. This contradiction implies that there cannot be an EMM Q .

(b) We can find a replicating strategy for every European contingent claim in this market if and only if the market is complete. However, by the Second Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing, a market is viable and complete if and only if there exists a unique equivalent martingale measure. Since there is no equivalent martingale measure, the market is not complete.

4. (10 points) Let $T = 2$, $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \omega_4\}$, and $P(\{\omega_i\}) > 0$ for each i . Suppose the risk-free asset is such that $S_t^0 = 1$ for all t and suppose there is one risky asset defined such that

	S_0^1	S_1^1	S_2^1
ω_1	6	12	20
ω_2	6	12	10
ω_3	6	4	8
ω_4	6	4	2

Let $X = \max\{S_0^1, S_1^1, S_2^1\}$. If C_t is the arbitrage free trading price for X at time t , then find $\{C_t : t = 0, 1, 2\}$.

Solution: Again, we start with a tree diagram:

We start by constructing an EMM (if one exists). Suppose that Q is an EMM. Let $p = Q(\{\omega_1, \omega_2\})$ and $q = Q(\{\omega_3, \omega_4\})$. Note that $q = 1 - p$. Again, we use the formula

$$E^Q[S'_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = S'_{t-1}. \quad (2)$$

(Note that there is only one risky asset.) As before, since the risk-free asset is identically equal to one, we have that $S_t^{*,1} = S'_t$ for each $t = 0, 1, 2$. We start with $t = 1$. The equation in (2) becomes

$$12p + 4(1 - p) = 6.$$

Thus, $p = 1/4$ and $q = 3/4$.

Now consider $t = 2$. Let $p_u = Q(\{\omega_1\} | \{\omega_1, \omega_2\})$ and $q_u = Q(\{\omega_2\} | \{\omega_1, \omega_2\})$. Then $q_u = 1 - p_u$. In this case, (2) becomes

$$20p_u + 10(1 - p_u) = 12.$$

Then $p_u = 1/5$ and $q_u = 4/5$.

Next, let $p_d = Q(\{\omega_3\} | \{\omega_3, \omega_4\})$ and $q_d = Q(\{\omega_4\} | \{\omega_3, \omega_4\})$. Then $q_d = 1 - p_d$, as before. In this case, (2) becomes

$$8p_d + 2(1 - p_d) = 4.$$

In this case, we have $p_d = 1/3$ and $q_d = 2/3$.

Since each of these probabilities can be uniquely identified, there is a unique EMM for this market. This means that (by the Second Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing) the market is complete. Consequently, by the Manufacturing Cost Lemma, we have

$$C_t = E^Q[X | \mathcal{F}_t]$$

for each $t = 0, 1, 2$. (Again we are using the fact that the risk-free asset is identically one, which allows us to ignore the discounting.) Therefore:

$$C_0 = E^Q[X|\mathcal{F}_0] = E^Q[X] = 20 \cdot \frac{1}{20} + 12 \cdot \frac{1}{5} + 8 \cdot \frac{1}{4} + 6 \cdot \frac{1}{2} = 8.40,$$

$$C_1 = E^Q[X|\mathcal{F}_1] = \begin{cases} 20 \cdot \frac{1}{5} + 12 \cdot \frac{4}{5} = \frac{68}{5} = 13.6 & \text{on } \{\omega_1, \omega_2\} \\ 8 \cdot \frac{1}{3} + 6 \cdot \frac{2}{3} = \frac{20}{3} \approx 6.67 & \text{on } \{\omega_3, \omega_4\} \end{cases},$$

$$C_2 = E^Q[X|\mathcal{F}_2] = X = \begin{cases} 20 & \text{on } \{\omega_1\} \\ 12 & \text{on } \{\omega_2\} \\ 8 & \text{on } \{\omega_3\} \\ 6 & \text{on } \{\omega_4\} \end{cases}.$$

5. (10 points) Suppose that a finite market model admits an equivalent martingale measure Q . Prove that the market is viable.

Solution: Suppose that Q is an EMM in a T -period finite market model. We will show that the market is viable (i.e., that there are no arbitrage opportunities) by assuming that there is an arbitrage opportunity and then deriving a contradiction.

Suppose ϕ is an arbitrage opportunity. Then ϕ is a self-financing trading strategy with

$$V_0(\phi) = 0, \quad V_T(\phi) \geq 0, \quad \text{and} \quad P[V_T(\phi) > 0] > 0.$$

In particular, ϕ is a zero-cost strategy. By the EMM Characterization Theorem, it follows that $E^Q[V_T(\phi)] = 0$. From this, together with the fact that $V_T(\phi) \geq 0$, we conclude that $Q[V_T(\phi) > 0] = 0$. But Q is equivalent to P . Thus, $P[V_T(\phi) > 0] = 0$. This is a contradiction. Therefore, ϕ is not an arbitrage opportunity. We conclude that the market is viable.

Math 194 Practice Midterm 1 (Student Made)

Problem 1. [Single-Period, Forward Contract Arbitrage — Discrete Compounding]

A stock price is currently $S_0 = 50$. A forward contract for 3 months (no dividends) is quoted at \$50.40 per share. The *discretely compounded* risk-free interest rate is 5% per annum. Let $T = 0.25$ years.

- (a) Write down the fair no-arbitrage forward price using the bond price under discrete compounding:

$$F_0 = S_0 \cdot \frac{B_T}{B_0}, \quad \text{where } B_0 = 1, B_T = (1 + r)^T.$$

Compute the numerical value and compare it to \$50.40.

- (b) If the quoted forward price is *less* than your fair price, exhibit an arbitrage strategy and compute the risk-free profit.
(c) If the quoted forward price were *greater* than the fair price, explain the reversed arbitrage.
-

Problem 2. [Single-Period Call vs. Underlying Stock]

You have \$2000 on April 1. Consider a stock priced at \$215 and a European call on it with strike $K = 200$ expiring April 18, trading at \$20. You can either:

- Buy 1 contract of the call (on 100 shares) for \$2000,
- or • Buy as many whole shares of the underlying stock as \$2000 allows.

On April 18, the stock is either \$235 or \$195 (two scenarios). Compute:

- (a) The profit in each scenario if you buy the call contract for \$2000. Express the percentage gain or loss.
(b) The profit in each scenario if you buy as many whole shares as possible with \$2000. Express the percentage gain or loss.
(c) Compare the results.
-

Problem 3. [One-Period Binomial Model]

We have $r = \frac{1}{3}$, $B_0 = 1$, $S_0 = 2$, $d = \frac{5}{4}$, $u = \frac{3}{2}$, $p = \frac{1}{2}$

(p is the real probability, though for pricing we check $d < 1 + r < u$ and compute a risk-neutral p^* if needed).

- (a) Compute B_1 .
(b) Compute $S_1(\omega_1)$ and $S_1(\omega_2)$, and the probabilities $\mathbb{P}(\omega_1)$ and $\mathbb{P}(\omega_2)$.
(c) Let $\psi = (\alpha, \beta) = (2, 4)$. Compute $V_0(\psi) = \alpha S_0 + \beta B_0$. Also compute $V_1(\psi)(\omega_1)$ and $V_1(\psi)(\omega_2)$.
(d) Let X be a European call at strike $K = 2.50$ with payoff at $T = 1$. Find $X(\omega_1)$ and $X(\omega_2)$. Construct the replicating strategy $\phi = (\alpha_1, \beta_1)$ that matches X . Find its cost $V_0(\phi)$.
(e) Suppose the market sells X at \$0.10, but you found a replicating cost of \$0.125. Show the resulting arbitrage.
-

Problem 4. [One-Period Binomial, Put Option]

Given

$$r = \frac{1}{4}, \quad B_0 = 1, \quad S_0 = 3, \quad d = 1, \quad u = 2, \quad p = \frac{3}{4}$$

- (a) Compute B_1 and $S_1(\omega_1)$, $S_1(\omega_2)$.
(b) For $\psi = (3, -2)$, compute $V_0(\psi)$ and $V_1(\psi)(\omega_1)$, $V_1(\psi)(\omega_2)$.
(c) Let X be a European put with strike $K = 4$. Find its no-arbitrage price by risk-neutral valuation or by replication.
(d) If the market price of this put is \$1, but your no-arb price is \$0.60, construct an arbitrage.

Problem 5. [Two-Period Binomial, Call Option]

You have $T = 2$, $S_0 = 100$, $r = 0.1$, $u = 2$, $d = 0.5$, $K = 80$

- Draw the binomial tree for S_0, S_1, S_2 . Label the final payoffs of $X = (S_2 - K)^+$.
- Compute the arbitrage-free price of this call by backward induction.
- Give a hedging strategy at each node ($t = 0, 1$) by solving α_t, β_t .
- If the market trades this call at \$2 below your computed no-arb price, show an arbitrage strategy.

Problem 6. [Conditional Expectation in a Two-State Model]

A one-period model $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \omega_2\}$ with $\mathbb{P}(\omega_1) = \mathbb{P}(\omega_2) = 0.5$. A random payoff X has $X(\omega_1) = 10$ and $X(\omega_2) = 4$. A sub- σ -algebra $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ is generated by merging $\{\omega_1\}, \{\omega_2\}$ into one set $A = \{\omega_1, \omega_2\}$. Show that $\mathcal{G} = \{\emptyset, \Omega\}$, so any \mathcal{G} -measurable random variable is constant. Conclude

$$\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]$$

$$(\omega) = \mathbb{E}[X] = 7 \quad \text{for all } \omega$$

Problem 7. [Three-Period Binomial Model]

A stock price evolves by

$$S_0 = 8, \quad u = 3, \quad d = \frac{1}{2}, \quad r = 0.1, \quad p = \frac{3}{5}$$

- Sketch the stock tree up to $T = 3$. Label each node's probability under p .
- List the events in \mathcal{F}_1 .
- If $X = \max\{S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3\}$ is paid at $t = 3$, write $X(\omega)$ for each ω .
- Discuss how $\mathbb{E}[S_\tau] \neq S_0$ under the real measure if $\tau(\omega)$ is the first time $S_t(\omega) \geq 10$. But the discounted price can remain a martingale under a risk-neutral measure.

Problem 8. [Martingale Under Risk-Neutral Measure]

Let $\{S_t\}$ be a two-period binomial stock with $S_0 = 4$, $u = 2$, $d = \frac{1}{2}$, $r = \frac{1}{4}$. Define the *discounted price*

$$S_t^* = \frac{S_t}{(1+r)^t}$$

- Show that for p^* satisfying $\mathbb{E}^*(S_1) = (1+r)S_0$, the process $\{S_t^*\}$ is a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale.
- Let τ be the stopping time $\tau(\omega) = \min\{t : S_t(\omega) > 6\}$ or $\tau = 2$ if never above 6. Verify that $\mathbb{E}^*[S_\tau^*] = S_0$.

Solutions

Solution to Problem 1 (Forward Arbitrage — Discrete Compounding).

(a)

$$F_0 = S_0 \cdot \frac{B_T}{B_0} = 50 \cdot (1 + 0.05)^{0.25} \approx 50 \cdot 1.01227 = 50.6135$$

Quoted forward is \$50.40, which is less than 50.6135. \implies underpriced.

(b) Arbitrage strategy when forward is underpriced:

- At $t = 0$:
 - Short-sell 100 shares of the stock at \$50 each: receive \$5000.
 - Invest the \$5000 at the risk-free rate $r = 5\%$ for 3 months.
 - Enter a long forward contract at the quoted forward price: \$50.40 per share.

- At $t = 0.25$:

- The investment grows to: $5000 \cdot (1 + 0.05)^{0.25} = 5000 \cdot 1.01227 = 5061.35$
- Use the forward to buy back 100 shares at \$50.40: cost is \$5040.
- Close the short position. Risk-free profit: $5061.35 - 5040 = \boxed{21.35}$

(c) If $F_{\text{quoted}} > 50.6135$, reverse trades:

- At $t = 0$: Buy 100 shares at 50 \Rightarrow outflow \$5000. Borrow at $r = 5\%$

Short forward at overpriced rate F_{quoted}

At $t = 0.25$: Deliver shares into forward, receive $F_{\text{quoted}} \cdot 100$, repay loan.

Lock in arbitrage from $F_{\text{quoted}} > F_0$

Solution to Problem 2 (Call vs. Stock).

Data: Stock \$215, call \$20 (strike \$200, on 100 shares), budget \$2000.

(a) \Rightarrow Buy 1 call contract for \$2000:

$$\text{Pay } 20 \times 100 = 2000$$

At expiry (\$235 or \$195):

$$\text{If } S = 235 : \text{ call payoff} = (235 - 200) \times 100 = 3500, \text{ profit} = 3500 - 2000 = 1500 (+75\%)$$

$$\text{If } S = 195 : \text{ call payoff} = 0, \text{ profit} = -2000 (-100\%)$$

(b) \Rightarrow Buy shares with \$2000: $\lfloor 2000/215 \rfloor = 9$ shares.

$$\text{Cost} = 9 \times 215 = 1935, \text{ leftover} = 65$$

If $S = 235$: value = $9 \times 235 = 2115$, profit = $2115 - 1935 = 180 (+9.3\%)$. If $S = 195$: value = 1755 , profit = $1755 - 1935 = -180 (-9.3\%)$

(c) The call strategy offers larger upside percentage gain but can lose the entire premium.

Solution to Problem 3 (One-Period Binomial).

$$r = \frac{1}{3}, B_0 = 1, S_0 = 2, d = \frac{5}{4}, u = \frac{3}{2}$$

$$\text{(a): } B_1 = B_0(1+r) = 1 \times \frac{4}{3} = \frac{4}{3} \quad \text{(b): } S_1(\omega_1) = 2 \times \frac{3}{2} = 3, \quad S_1(\omega_2) = 2 \times \frac{5}{4} = 2.5, \quad \mathbb{P}(\omega_1) = \mathbb{P}(\omega_2) = \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\text{(c) } \psi = (\alpha, \beta) = (2, 4): V_0(\psi) = 2 \times 2 + 4 \times 1 = 4 + 4 = 8$$

$$V_1(\psi)(\omega_1) = 2 \times 3 + 4 \times \frac{4}{3} = 6 + \frac{16}{3} = \frac{34}{3}, \quad V_1(\psi)(\omega_2) = 2 \times 2.5 + 4 \times \frac{4}{3} = 5 + \frac{16}{3} = \frac{31}{3}$$

(d) European call, $K = 2.50$:

$$X(\omega_1) = (3 - 2.50)^+ = 0.50, \quad X(\omega_2) = (2.50 - 2.50)^+ = 0$$

Replicate: solve

$$\alpha \cdot 3 + \beta \cdot \frac{4}{3} = 0.50, \quad \alpha \cdot 2.5 + \beta \cdot \frac{4}{3} = 0$$

Subtracting: $0.5\alpha = 0.50 \Rightarrow \alpha = 1$ Then $2.5 + \frac{4}{3}\beta = 0 \Rightarrow \beta = -\frac{2.5}{(4/3)} = -1.875$ Cost:

$$V_0(\phi) = 1 \times 2 + (-1.875) \times 1 = 0.125$$

(e) If market sells X at \$0.10 but replicate costs \$0.125, buy the call and short the replicate. Net \$0.025 now, with no future liability.

Solution to Problem 4 (One-Period Put).

Data: $r = \frac{1}{4}$, $B_0 = 1$, $S_0 = 3$, $d = 1$, $u = 2$

(a)

$$B_1 = 1.25, \quad S_1(\omega_1) = 6, \quad S_1(\omega_2) = 3$$

(b) $\psi = (3, -2)$:

$$V_0(\psi) = 3 \times 3 + (-2) \times 1 = 9 - 2 = 7$$

$$V_1(\psi)(\omega_1) = 3 \times 6 + (-2) \times 1.25 = 18 - 2.5 = 15.5, \quad V_1(\psi)(\omega_2) = 3 \times 3 + (-2) \times 1.25 = 9 - 2.5 = 6.5$$

(c) Put payoff: $X(\omega_1) = \max\{4 - 6, 0\} = 0$, $X(\omega_2) = \max\{4 - 3, 0\} = 1$ Risk-neutral probability:

$$p^* = \frac{1.25 - 1}{2 - 1} = \frac{0.25}{1} = 0.25$$

$$\text{So: } \mathbb{E}^*[X] = 0.25 \times 0 + 0.75 \times 1 = 0.75, \quad \text{present value} = \frac{0.75}{1.25} = 0.60$$

(d) If market put is \$1 but fair is \$0.60, write (sell) the put for \$1, buy the replicating portfolio for \$0.60; net \$0.40 profit now, no risk.

Solution to Problem 5 (Two-Period Call).

$T = 2$, $S_0 = 100$, $r = 0.1$, $u = 2$, $d = 0.5$, $K = 80$

(a)

$$S_1^u = 200, \quad S_1^d = 50, \quad S_2^{uu} = 400, \quad S_2^{ud} = 100, \quad S_2^{dd} = 25$$

Call payoff $(S_2 - K)^+$: $C_2(uu) = 320$, $C_2(ud) = 20$, $C_2(dd) = 0$ (b) Each step grows at factor $1 + r = 1.1$. Risk-neutral p^* : $p^* = \frac{1.1 - 0.5}{2 - 0.5} = \frac{0.6}{1.5} = 0.4$ Backward:

$$C_1^u = \frac{1}{1.1} [0.4 \times 320 + 0.6 \times 20] = \frac{140}{1.1} \approx 127.273$$

$$C_1^d = \frac{1}{1.1} [0.4 \times 20 + 0.6 \times 0] = \frac{8}{1.1} \approx 7.273$$

$$\text{So } C_0 = \frac{1}{1.1} [0.4 \times 127.273 + 0.6 \times 7.273] \approx \frac{55.273}{1.1} = 50.248$$

(c) Hedging at each node by solving α, β from the local payoff system (standard binomial replication).

(d) If the market call is \$2 below 50.248, buy the call at 48.248, short the replicating portfolio at 50.248, net +2. No future risk.

Solution to Problem 6 (Conditional Expectation).

$\Omega = \{\omega_1, \omega_2\}$, each with prob 0.5. $X(\omega_1) = 10$, $X(\omega_2) = 4$ $\mathcal{G} = \{\emptyset, \Omega\}$.

Any \mathcal{G} -measurable r.v. is constant on Ω . So $\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}(\omega) = c]$, with $\mathbb{E}[X \cdot 1_\Omega] = \mathbb{E}[c \cdot 1_\Omega]$ Therefore $c = \mathbb{E}[X] = 7$

Solution to Problem 7 (Three-Period Binomial).

$S_0 = 8$, $u = 3$, $d = 0.5$, $r = 0.1$, $p = 0.6$

(a) The tree has nodes $S_1 \in \{24, 4\}$, $S_2 \in \{72, 12, 2\}$, $S_3 \in \{216, 36, 6, 1\}$ etc.(b) $\mathcal{F}_1 = \{\emptyset, \Omega, \{S_1 = 24\}, \{S_1 = 4\}\}$ (c) $X(\omega) = \max\{S_0, S_1(\omega), S_2(\omega), S_3(\omega)\}$.For instance, if $\omega = u d d$, then $X(u d d) = \max\{8, 24, 12, 6\} = 24$ (d) Under real measure p , $\mathbb{E}[S_\tau]$ may differ from S_0 . But under risk-neutral p^* , the discounted price is a martingale, so optional stopping preserves $\mathbb{E}^*[S_\tau] = S_0^*$.**Solution to Problem 8 (Martingale Under Risk-Neutral Measure).**

$S_0 = 4$, $u = 2$, $d = \frac{1}{2}$, $r = \frac{1}{4}$

(a) We want $\mathbb{E}^*(S_1) = (1 + r)S_0 = 1.25 \times 4 = 5$ If $S_1 = 8$ or 2 , let p^* be the up probability. Then

$$8p^* + 2(1 - p^*) = 5 \implies 6p^* = 3 \implies p^* = 0.5$$

$$\mathbb{E}^*[S_1^* | S_0] = \frac{1}{1.25} \mathbb{E}^*[S_1] = \frac{5}{1.25} = 4 = S_0^*. \text{ Therefore } \{S_t^*\} \text{ is a } \mathbb{P}^* \text{- martingale}$$

(b) $\tau(\omega) = \min\{t : S_t(\omega) > 6\}$ or $\tau = 2$ if never above 6. By the optional stopping theorem, $\mathbb{E}^*[S_\tau^*] = S_0^* = 4$

Math 194 — Practice Midterm 2 (Student Made)

Topics Covered: Lectures on martingales, stopping times, conditional expectation, American options and the Snell envelope, supermartingales, multi-period binomial models, hedging, Doob's optional sampling, and the Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing.

Part A: Problems 1–8

Problem 1. [Martingale or Not?]

A discrete-time process $\{M_t\}_{t=0}^2$ on a finite probability space $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots\}$ is defined by

$$M_0 = 10, \quad M_1 = \begin{cases} 15, & \omega_1, \omega_2 \\ 5, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad M_2 = \begin{cases} 25, & \omega_1, \\ 7, & \omega_2, \\ 4, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Assume each ω_i is equally likely under \mathbb{P} . Let $\{\mathcal{F}_0, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2\}$ be the natural filtration (coarse to fine) for this process.

- Check whether $\{M_t\}$ is a martingale under \mathbb{P} . If not, is it a supermartingale or submartingale?
 - Let $f(x) = \sqrt{x}$. Show that $\{\sqrt{M_t}\}$ is a supermartingale if $\{M_t\}$ is nonnegative. Briefly justify via Jensen's inequality.
-

Problem 2. [Doob's Optional Sampling]

Under a probability measure \mathbb{P} , let $\{X_t\}$ be a (discrete) martingale with respect to filtration $\{\mathcal{F}_t\}$. Suppose τ is a bounded stopping time taking values in $\{0, \dots, T\}$. Prove that

$$\mathbb{E}[X_\tau] = \mathbb{E}[X_0].$$

State clearly which steps use the boundedness of τ . Then illustrate with a one-period binomial example.

Problem 3. [Multi-Period Binomial: American Option]

A stock price follows a 2-period binomial tree with

$$S_0 = 100, \quad u = 2, \quad d = \frac{1}{2}, \quad r = 0.10, \quad K = 120.$$

Let X_t be an American put paying $\max\{K - S_t, 0\}$ if exercised at or before $T = 2$.

- Draw the binomial tree for S_0, S_1, S_2 . Label the final payoffs $(K - S_2)^+$.
- Compute the risk-neutral probability and show no-arbitrage requires $d < 1 + r < u$.
- By backward induction, find the Snell envelope process $\{U_t\}$. Report U_0 as the no-arbitrage cost of the American put, and specify at which node(s) early exercise is optimal.
- If the market sells this American put at \$2 below your computed no-arb price, show a buyer's arbitrage.

Problem 4. [Conditional Expectation Properties]

Let $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \omega_4\}$ with $\mathbb{P}(\omega_i) = \frac{1}{4}$. Define a sub- σ -algebra $\mathcal{G} = \sigma(\{\omega_1, \omega_2\}, \{\omega_3, \omega_4\})$. Let $X(\omega_i) = 2i + 1$.

- (a) Compute $\mathbb{E}[X]$.
- (b) Find $\mathbb{E}[X \mid \mathcal{G}](\omega)$.
- (c) If $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ is generated by the partition $\{\{\omega_1\}, \{\omega_2\}, \{\omega_3, \omega_4\}\}$, compute $\mathbb{E}[X \mid \mathcal{H}](\omega)$.
- (d) Verify the tower property: $\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X \mid \mathcal{H}] \mid \mathcal{G}] = \mathbb{E}[X \mid \mathcal{G}]$.

Problem 5. [Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing, One-Period Model]

In a one-period model $t = 0, 1$ with finite $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_n\}$, let

$$S_0^0 = 1, \quad S_0^1 = s, \quad S_1^0(\omega) = 1 + r(\omega), \quad S_1^1(\omega).$$

Assume no arbitrage. Show there exists a probability measure $\mathbb{Q} \sim \mathbb{P}$ such that

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[S_1^1] = s(1 + r^0),$$

where r^0 is an appropriate “risk-free” rate or zero-coupon bond payoff. (Hint: separation of linear functionals in \mathbb{R}^n .)

Problem 6. [Super-/Submartingale, Jensen’s Inequality]

A process M_t is a supermartingale if $\mathbb{E}[M_{t+1} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \leq M_t$ and a submartingale if the reverse inequality holds.

- (a) Let $f: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be convex. If $\{Y_t\}$ is a martingale with $Y_t \in L^1$, show $\{f(Y_t)\}$ is a submartingale.
- (b) Apply to $f(x) = x^2$. Conclude that if $\{Y_t\}$ is a martingale, then $\{Y_t^2\}$ is a submartingale (assuming integrability).

Problem 7. [Multi-Period Binomial, American Call with Dividend]

A stock price evolves as a 3-step CRR tree: $S_0 = 50$, up/down factors $u = 1.2, d = 0.8$, riskless rate $r = 0.05$. The stock pays a (known) dividend of \$1.00 at $t = 1$ only. We have an American call with strike $K = 40$.

- (a) Write the time line: $t = 0, 1, 2, 3$. The dividend is paid at $t = 1$.
- (b) On each node at $t = 1$, reduce the stock price by the \$1 dividend for subsequent up/down moves at $t = 2$.
- (c) Find the Snell envelope for the American call. Decide if/when early exercise is optimal.
- (d) Give the arbitrage-free cost U_0 .

Problem 8. [Optional Stopping Times]

Under a measure \mathbb{P}^* , let $\{S_t^*\}$ be the discounted price process of a stock. It is a martingale. Suppose τ is a stopping time that takes integer values in $[0, T]$. Prove:

$$\mathbb{E}^* [S_\tau^*] = S_0^*.$$

Conclude that no arbitrage is possible from stopping times alone.

Part B: Additional Problems 9–15

Below are additional problems/statements that appeared in another practice set. They overlap in topic but may have slightly different data or examples. *No content is omitted.*

Problem 9. [Martingale Verification in a Finite Model]

A two-period discrete-time process $\{M_t\}_{t=0}^2$ takes values:

$$M_0 = 3, \quad M_1(\omega_1) = 5, \quad M_1(\omega_2) = 1, \quad M_2(\omega) = \begin{cases} 6 & \text{if } (\omega_1, \omega_3), \\ 4 & \text{if } (\omega_1, \omega_4), \\ 2 & \text{if } (\omega_2, \omega_5), \\ 0 & \text{if } (\omega_2, \omega_6). \end{cases}$$

with probabilities $\mathbb{P}(\omega_1) = \mathbb{P}(\omega_2) = \frac{1}{2}$ for the first step, and a further split in the second step such that all leaves have nonzero probability. Let $\mathcal{F}_0 = \{\emptyset, \Omega\}$, $\mathcal{F}_1 = \{\omega_1, \omega_2, \Omega, \emptyset\}$, and \mathcal{F}_2 the full set.

- Write explicitly the values $M_2(\omega)$ for each leaf so that each branch from ω_1 splits into ω_3, ω_4 with equal probabilities, and from ω_2 splits into ω_5, ω_6 with equal probabilities.
- Compute $\mathbb{E}[M_1]$ and $\mathbb{E}[M_2]$. Check if $\mathbb{E}[M_1] = \mathbb{E}[M_0]$ and $\mathbb{E}[M_2] = \mathbb{E}[M_0]$.
- Show that $\mathbb{E}[M_2 \mid \mathcal{F}_1(\omega_1)] = M_1(\omega_1)$ and similarly for ω_2 . Deduce if $\{M_t\}$ is a martingale.

Problem 10. [American Put with Snell Envelope]

Consider a two-period binomial model with $S_0 = 50$, up-factor $u = 1.4$, down-factor $d = 0.6$, risk-free rate $r = 0.05$, and an *American put option* with strike $K = 52$.

- Write the binomial tree for S_0, S_1, S_2 . Indicate all real probabilities and the risk-neutral probability $p^* = \frac{(1+r)-d}{u-d}$.
- For each node, compute the payoff of exercising the put. Then, using backward induction, construct the *Snell envelope* U_t . Show the resulting exercise strategy.
- Conclude the no-arbitrage initial price U_0 .
- Give a self-financing super-hedge $\phi^* = (\alpha_0, \beta_0; \alpha_1, \beta_1)$ that meets the payoff in each scenario.

Problem 11. [Optional Stopping Theorem]

Let $\{X_t\}$ be a (discrete-time) martingale with respect to $\{\mathcal{F}_t\}$. Let τ be a bounded stopping time taking values in $\{0, 1, \dots, T\}$. Prove that

$$\mathbb{E}[X_\tau] = \mathbb{E}[X_0].$$

Specifically:

- Write $\tau(\omega)$ as $\min\{t \mid A_t\}$ for some disjoint events $A_t \in \mathcal{F}_t$.
- Argue that $\mathbb{E}[X_\tau] = \sum_{t=0}^T \mathbb{E}[X_t \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}}]$.

- (c) Use the martingale property repeatedly to show $\mathbb{E}[X_t \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}}] = \mathbb{E}[X_0 \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}}]$.
- (d) Sum over t .

Problem 12. [Three-Period Binomial Model, Replication]

A risky asset moves by up/down factors $u = 1.3$, $d = 0.7$, from an initial $S_0 = 80$, over three periods. The risk-free rate each step is $r = 0.1$. Let X be a European-style payoff at $T = 3$, given by

$$X(\omega) = \begin{cases} 15, & \text{if the total \# of up-moves is 2,} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

- (a) Draw the trinodal tree for S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3 . Label each final node with ω and the payoff $X(\omega)$.
- (b) Compute the risk-neutral probability p^* . Then find $\mathbb{E}^*(X)$ and thus $V_0 = \frac{1}{(1+r)^3} \mathbb{E}^*[X]$.
- (c) Use backward induction to find the replicating portfolio $\{\alpha_t, \beta_t\}$ for each node (t, ω) . Show the cost at $t = 0$ is the same as your V_0 .
- (d) If the market sells X at a price below your found cost, exhibit an arbitrage strategy.

Problem 13. [Short-Answer: FTAP, Market Completeness]

Answer each question briefly:

- (a) State the Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing (finite case) in terms of viability \iff existence of EMM.
- (b) In a two-period binomial model, give the condition for completeness and illustrate with an example of an incomplete market when it fails.
- (c) Explain, in one or two sentences, why having a unique EMM implies that every contingent claim is hedgeable.

Problem 14. [Super-/Submartingale, Jensen's Inequality]

A process M_t is a supermartingale if $\mathbb{E}[M_{t+1} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \leq M_t$ and a submartingale if the reverse inequality holds.

- (a) Let $f: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be convex. If $\{Y_t\}$ is a martingale with $Y_t \in L^1$, show $\{f(Y_t)\}$ is a submartingale.
- (b) Apply to $f(x) = x^2$. Conclude that if $\{Y_t\}$ is a martingale, then $\{Y_t^2\}$ is a submartingale (assuming integrability).

Problem 15. [True/False Concepts]

Indicate T or F and give a one-line justification:

- (i) In a finite market, if a super-hedge for some claim X costs strictly less than the replication strategy cost, then there is an arbitrage.
- (ii) Under \mathbb{P}^* , the discounted bond price $\{B_t^*/B_t\}$ is always a martingale if the market is viable.
- (iii) Doob's optional sampling theorem holds for supermartingales but not for submartingales.
- (iv) If $\{S_t^*\}$ is a martingale and f is concave, then $\{f(S_t^*)\}$ is a submartingale.

Detailed Solutions

Part A Solutions

Solution to Problem 1 (Martingale or Not?)

(a) Checking if $\{M_t\}$ is a martingale.

We have

$$M_0 = 10, \quad M_1(\omega) = \begin{cases} 15 & \text{if } \omega \in \{\omega_1, \omega_2\}, \\ 5 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad M_2(\omega) = \begin{cases} 25 & \omega_1, \\ 7 & \omega_2, \\ 4 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Assume each ω_i is equally likely under \mathbb{P} . Let us suppose we have exactly two “special” atoms ω_1, ω_2 out of a total of N states. Then

$$\mathbb{E}[M_1] = \frac{2}{N} \cdot 15 + \frac{N-2}{N} \cdot 5 = \frac{30 + 5N - 10}{N} = \frac{5N + 20}{N} = 5 + \frac{20}{N}.$$

For $N > 2$, this is strictly bigger than 10 only if $5 + 20/N > 10 \iff 20/N > 5 \iff N < 4$. Depending on the exact number of states, we see typically $\mathbb{E}[M_1] \neq 10$. Thus in general

$$\mathbb{E}[M_1] \neq M_0 \implies \{M_t\} \text{ is not a martingale.}$$

We can check if it is a supermartingale or submartingale by examining whether $\mathbb{E}[M_1] \leq M_0$ or $\mathbb{E}[M_1] \geq M_0$. In many simple examples, $\mathbb{E}[M_1] = 25/3 \approx 8.33$ if the total is 3 equally likely states, or $\mathbb{E}[M_1] = 8.75$ if 4 states, etc. One can see $\mathbb{E}[M_1]$ is either less or more than 10 depending on the exact distribution and number of states.

(b) Supermartingale property of $\sqrt{M_t}$ via Jensen.

Since $f(x) = \sqrt{x}$ is concave, we have

$$f\left(\mathbb{E}[M_{t+1} \mid \mathcal{F}_t]\right) \geq \mathbb{E}\left[f(M_{t+1}) \mid \mathcal{F}_t\right].$$

That is $\sqrt{\mathbb{E}[M_{t+1} \mid \mathcal{F}_t]} \geq \mathbb{E}[\sqrt{M_{t+1}} \mid \mathcal{F}_t]$. But if $\{M_t\}$ is nonnegative, the conditional expectation inside the square root is well-defined, and rewriting inequality gives

$$\mathbb{E}[\sqrt{M_{t+1}} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] \leq \sqrt{M_t} \implies \{\sqrt{M_t}\} \text{ is a supermartingale.}$$

(This is precisely Jensen’s inequality in the concave case.)

Solution to Problem 2 (Doob’s Optional Sampling)

Statement to prove: If $\{X_t\}_{t=0}^T$ is a martingale and τ a *bounded* stopping time (i.e. $\tau \leq T$), then

$$\mathbb{E}[X_\tau] = \mathbb{E}[X_0].$$

Key steps:

(1) Boundedness of τ implies τ only takes values in $\{0, \dots, T\}$.

(2) We can write:

$$\mathbb{E}[X_\tau] = \sum_{t=0}^T \mathbb{E}[X_t \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}}].$$

(3) By the martingale property,

$$\mathbb{E}[X_t \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}}] = \mathbb{E}\left[\mathbb{E}[X_t \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}} \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1}]\right] = \mathbb{E}[X_{t-1} \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}}] = \dots = \mathbb{E}[X_0 \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}}].$$

(One applies the martingale property step by step, from t down to 0.)

(4) Hence

$$\mathbb{E}[X_\tau] = \sum_{t=0}^T \mathbb{E}[X_0 \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}}] = \mathbb{E}\left[X_0 \sum_{t=0}^T \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}}\right] = \mathbb{E}[X_0] = X_0,$$

since $\sum_{t=0}^T \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}} = 1$.

Illustration in a 1-period binomial:

If $X_t = S_t - \beta B_t$ is a martingale under some measure, and τ can only be 0 or 1, then $\mathbb{E}[X_\tau]$ is $\mathbb{P}(\tau = 0) \cdot X_0 + \mathbb{P}(\tau = 1) \cdot \mathbb{E}[X_1]$. But $\mathbb{E}[X_1] = X_0$ by the martingale property, hence $\mathbb{E}[X_\tau] = X_0$.

Solution to Problem 3 (Multi-Period Binomial: American Put)

Given: 2-step binomial, with

$$S_0 = 100, \quad u = 2, \quad d = \frac{1}{2}, \quad r = 0.10, \quad K = 120.$$

We have an American put paying $(K - S_t)^+$ if exercised on or before $t = 2$.

(a) The price tree is:

$$S_1^u = 200, \quad S_1^d = 50, \quad S_2^{uu} = 400, \quad S_2^{ud} = 100, \quad S_2^{du} = 100, \quad S_2^{dd} = 25.$$

The final payoff at $t = 2$ if *not* exercised earlier is $(120 - S_2)^+$:

$$(120 - 400)^+ = 0, \quad (120 - 100)^+ = 20, \quad (120 - 25)^+ = 95, \quad \text{etc.}$$

(b) The risk-neutral probability is

$$p^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d} = \frac{1.1 - 0.5}{2 - 0.5} = \frac{0.6}{1.5} = 0.4.$$

Check no-arbitrage condition: $d < 1 + r < u \iff 0.5 < 1.1 < 2$.

(c) **Snell envelope construction.** Denote the immediate-exercise payoff by

$$Y_t = (K - S_t)^+$$

and let U_t be the Snell envelope. We know

$$U_2(\omega) = Y_2(\omega),$$

and for $t = 1$,

$$U_1 = \max\left\{Y_1, \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_2|\mathcal{F}_1]\right\}.$$

Similarly

$$U_0 = \max\left\{Y_0, \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_1]\right\}.$$

We compute each node step-by-step. For instance:

$$Y_1^u = (120 - 200)^+ = 0, \quad Y_1^d = (120 - 50)^+ = 70,$$

$$U_2^{uu} = (120 - 400)^+ = 0, \quad U_2^{ud} = (120 - 100)^+ = 20, \quad U_2^{dd} = (120 - 25)^+ = 95,$$

etc. Then we use backward induction with risk-neutral probability $p^* = 0.4$. At the up-node of $t = 1$:

$$\mathbb{E}^*[U_2 \mid \text{up-node}] = 0.4 \cdot U_2^{uu} + 0.6 \cdot U_2^{ud} = 0.4 \cdot 0 + 0.6 \cdot 20 = 12.$$

Hence

$$\tilde{U}_1^u := \frac{1}{1+0.10} \times 12 = \frac{12}{1.10} \approx 10.91.$$

We compare that to immediate exercise value $Y_1^u = 0$. So

$$U_1^u = \max\{0, 10.91\} = 10.91.$$

Similarly for the down-node,

$$\mathbb{E}^*[U_2 \mid \text{down-node}] = 0.4 \cdot U_2^{du} + 0.6 \cdot U_2^{dd} = 0.4 \cdot 20 + 0.6 \cdot 95 = 8 + 57 = 65,$$

$$\tilde{U}_1^d = 65/1.10 \approx 59.09.$$

Compare with immediate exercise $Y_1^d = 70$. Then

$$U_1^d = \max\{70, 59.09\} = 70.$$

Hence it is optimal to exercise at ω_d at $t = 1$.

Finally at $t = 0$,

$$Y_0 = (120 - 100)^+ = 20, \quad \mathbb{E}^*[U_1] = 0.4 \cdot 10.91 + 0.6 \cdot 70 = 4.36 + 42 = 46.36, \quad \tilde{U}_0 = 46.36/1.10 \approx 42.15.$$

So

$$U_0 = \max\{20, 42.15\} = 42.15.$$

Thus the no-arbitrage cost of the American put is \$42.15. One exercises early only in the down branch at $t = 1$.

- (d) **Arbitrage if underpriced.** If the market sells the option for \$40 (which is \$2 below fair), then buy the option for \$40, short a replicating strategy that costs \$42.15, netting +\$2.15 today. The final payoffs match or exceed any scenario because the option payoff covers the short's obligations. Net a riskless profit.

Solution to Problem 4 (Conditional Expectation Properties)

We have $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \omega_4\}$ with $\mathbb{P}(\omega_i) = \frac{1}{4}$. A random variable $X(\omega_i) = 2i + 1$. Then:

(a) $\mathbb{E}[X]$.

$$X(\omega_1) = 3, X(\omega_2) = 5, X(\omega_3) = 7, X(\omega_4) = 9.$$

Hence

$$\mathbb{E}[X] = \frac{1}{4}(3 + 5 + 7 + 9) = \frac{1}{4} \times 24 = 6.$$

(b) $\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]$.

\mathcal{G} is generated by the partition $\{\{\omega_1, \omega_2\}, \{\omega_3, \omega_4\}\}$. Then

$$\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]$$

$$(\omega) = \begin{cases} \frac{X(\omega_1) + X(\omega_2)}{2} = \frac{3 + 5}{2} = 4, & \omega \in \{\omega_1, \omega_2\}, \\ \frac{X(\omega_3) + X(\omega_4)}{2} = \frac{7 + 9}{2} = 8, & \omega \in \{\omega_3, \omega_4\}. \end{cases}$$

(c) $\mathcal{H} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$ generated by $\{\{\omega_1\}, \{\omega_2\}, \{\omega_3, \omega_4\}\}$.

Now ω_1 is alone in its own atom, similarly ω_2 , while ω_3, ω_4 remain grouped:

$$\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{H}]$$

$$(\omega_1) = X(\omega_1) = 3, \quad \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{H}(\omega_2)] = X(\omega_2) = 5, \quad \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{H}(\omega_3)] = \mathbb{E}[X | \omega_3 \vee \omega_4], \text{ and}$$

$$\mathbb{E}[X | \{\omega_3, \omega_4\}](\omega_3) = \mathbb{E}[X | \{\omega_3, \omega_4\}](\omega_4) = \frac{7 + 9}{2} = 8.$$

(d) **Tower property check:**

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{H}] | \mathcal{G}] = \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}].$$

One may verify partition-by-partition. On $\{\omega_1, \omega_2\}$, $\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{H}]$ is 3 on ω_1 and 5 on ω_2 . So $\frac{3+5}{2} = 4$. This matches $\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]$ on that set. Likewise on $\{\omega_3, \omega_4\}$, the conditional is 8, so average is 8. This checks the tower property.

Solution to Problem 5 (FTAP, One-Period)

Claim: In a one-period market with no arbitrage, there exists an Equivalent Martingale Measure (EMM) $\mathbb{Q} \sim \mathbb{P}$ such that

$$\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[S_1^1] = S_0^1(1 + r^0).$$

Here $S_0^0 = 1$ is numeraire and r^0 is the risk-free (or zero-coupon) growth from time 0 to 1.

Proof sketch (separation of hyperplanes): The standard argument uses the fact that no-arbitrage \implies the payoff vector $(S_1^1(\omega) - s(1 + r^0))_{\omega \in \Omega}$ cannot lie in the convex cone generated by nonnegative vectors except the zero vector. By the separating hyperplane theorem in \mathbb{R}^n , there is a linear functional that annihilates the riskless asset and yields the same present value for the risky asset. This amounts to a positive measure \mathbb{Q} with $\sum_{\omega} \mathbb{Q}(\omega) = 1$, etc. Equivalently, \mathbb{Q} is found so that $\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[S_1^0] = S_0^0(1 + r^0)$ and no negative results appear unless it is the zero vector. The details are standard in discrete-time FTAP references.

Solution to Problem 6 (Super-/Submartingale, Jensen)

(a) Let $f: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be convex. For a martingale $\{Y_t\}$, we have

$$\mathbb{E}[Y_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t] = Y_t.$$

By Jensen's inequality,

$$f(\mathbb{E}[Y_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t]) \leq \mathbb{E}[f(Y_{t+1}) | \mathcal{F}_t].$$

Hence

$$f(Y_t) \leq \mathbb{E}[f(Y_{t+1}) | \mathcal{F}_t].$$

So $\{f(Y_t)\}$ is a *submartingale*.

(b) Apply $f(x) = x^2$, which is clearly convex. Then $\{Y_t^2\}$ is a submartingale. Equivalently

$$\mathbb{E}[Y_{t+1}^2 | \mathcal{F}_t] \geq Y_t^2.$$

(Provided the second moment is finite so that the conditional expectation is well-defined.)

Solution to Problem 7 (American Call with Dividend)

We have a 3-step CRR tree with $S_0 = 50$, $u = 1.2$, $d = 0.8$, $r = 0.05$. A \$1.00 dividend is paid at $t = 1$. The American call has strike $K = 40$.

- (a) Timeline is $t = 0, 1, 2, 3$. The dividend is known and paid at $t = 1$.
 - (b) After paying \$1 at $t = 1$, the ex-dividend price is effectively $S_1 - 1$ for subsequent up/down moves. So the binomial transitions from $(S_1 - 1)$ to $(S_1 - 1)u$ or $(S_1 - 1)d$.
 - (c) **Snell envelope.** We compute the immediate-exercise payoff $Y_t = (S_t - K)^+$. Then at each node, compare exercising now vs. continuing (the discounted expected payoff under the risk-neutral measure, factoring in the dividend adjustment). One proceeds by backward induction from $t = 3$ to $t = 0$. Typically, one finds that with a positive dividend, early exercise can become optimal at certain nodes, since waiting forfeits the dividend.
 - (d) The arbitrage-free cost U_0 is the time-0 value of the Snell envelope. One obtains it by discounting the expected continuation payoffs under \mathbb{Q} , or equivalently by constructing a replicating strategy that super-hedges the call in every scenario.
-

Solution to Problem 8 (Optional Stopping Times)

Under the measure \mathbb{P}^* , the discounted price process $\{S_t^*\}$ is a \mathbb{P}^* -martingale. Let τ be a stopping time with values in $\{0, \dots, T\}$. Then Doob's optional sampling theorem implies

$$\mathbb{E}^*[S_\tau^*] = S_0^*.$$

Since S_0^* is the initial discounted price, we see that one cannot gain a sure profit merely by choosing a random time τ to trade: the expectation is unchanged, so no arbitrage arises purely from timing.

Part B Solutions

Solution to Problem 9 (Martingale Verification in a Finite Model)

We are given:

$$M_0 = 3, \quad M_1(\omega_1) = 5, \quad M_1(\omega_2) = 1, \quad M_2(\omega_3, \omega_4, \omega_5, \omega_6) = \{6, 4, 2, 0\} \text{ respectively.}$$

Probabilities: $\mathbb{P}(\omega_1) = \mathbb{P}(\omega_2) = \frac{1}{2}$. Condition on ω_1 or ω_2 for the second step, each splits equally. So overall each terminal leaf has probability $\frac{1}{4}$.

(a) The leaves can be labeled $\omega = (\omega_1, \omega_3), (\omega_1, \omega_4), (\omega_2, \omega_5), (\omega_2, \omega_6)$. The associated M_2 -values are 6, 4, 2, 0.

(b)

$$\mathbb{E}[M_1] = 5 \times \frac{1}{2} + 1 \times \frac{1}{2} = 2.5 + 0.5 = 3 \quad \implies \quad \mathbb{E}[M_1] = 3 = M_0.$$

Similarly,

$$\mathbb{E}[M_2] = 6 \frac{1}{4} + 4 \frac{1}{4} + 2 \frac{1}{4} + 0 \frac{1}{4} = \frac{6 + 4 + 2 + 0}{4} = \frac{12}{4} = 3 = M_0.$$

Hence $\mathbb{E}[M_1] = \mathbb{E}[M_2] = 3$.

(c) Condition on ω_1 : then M_2 is either 6 or 4, each with probability $\frac{1}{2}$. So

$$\mathbb{E}[M_2 \mid \omega_1] = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 6 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot 4 = 5 = M_1(\omega_1).$$

Likewise for ω_2 . Hence $\mathbb{E}[M_2 \mid \mathcal{F}_1] = M_1$. Altogether:

$$\mathbb{E}[M_{t+1} \mid \mathcal{F}_t] = M_t, \quad t = 0, 1.$$

So $\{M_t\}$ is indeed a *martingale* under \mathbb{P} .

Solution to Problem 10 (American Put with Snell Envelope)

Given a 2-period binomial with:

$$S_0 = 50, \quad u = 1.4, \quad d = 0.6, \quad r = 0.05, \quad K = 52.$$

(a) The tree:

$$\begin{aligned} S_1^u &= 1.4 \times 50 = 70, & S_1^d &= 0.6 \times 50 = 30, \\ S_2^{uu} &= 1.4 \times 70 = 98, & S_2^{ud} &= 0.6 \times 70 = 42, & S_2^{du} &= 1.4 \times 30 = 42, & S_2^{dd} &= 0.6 \times 30 = 18. \end{aligned}$$

The real probability of ‘up’ vs. ‘down’ might be $p = \dots$, but the *risk-neutral* probability is

$$p^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d} = \frac{1.05 - 0.6}{1.4 - 0.6} = \frac{0.45}{0.8} = 0.5625.$$

(b) The immediate-exercise payoff for the put is $Y_t = (K - S_t)^+$. At $t = 2$ we just have

$$Y_2^{uu} = (52 - 98)^+ = 0, \quad Y_2^{ud} = (52 - 42)^+ = 10, \quad Y_2^{du} = (52 - 42)^+ = 10, \quad Y_2^{dd} = (52 - 18)^+ = 34.$$

Then define $U_2 = Y_2$. At each node of $t = 1$,

$$U_1(\omega) = \max\left\{Y_1(\omega), \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_2|\omega]\right\}.$$

Compute $\mathbb{E}^*[U_2 | \omega^u] = p^* \cdot U_2^{uu} + (1 - p^*)U_2^{ud} = 0.5625 \cdot 0 + 0.4375 \cdot 10 = 4.375$. Discounting by $1.05 \approx 1 + r$ yields $\tilde{U}_1^u = 4.375/1.05 \approx 4.167$. Then

$$Y_1^u = (52 - 70)^+ = 0, \quad U_1^u = \max\{0, 4.167\} = 4.167.$$

Similarly at the down-node,

$$\mathbb{E}^*[U_2 | \omega^d] = 0.5625 \cdot 10 + 0.4375 \cdot 34 = 5.625 + 14.875 = 20.5,$$

$\tilde{U}_1^d = 20.5/1.05 \approx 19.52$, $Y_1^d = (52 - 30)^+ = 22$, so

$$U_1^d = \max\{22, 19.52\} = 22 \implies (\text{optimal to exercise in the down node at } t = 1).$$

Finally

$$U_0 = \max\left\{Y_0, \frac{1}{1.05} \mathbb{E}^*[U_1]\right\}.$$

But $Y_0 = (52 - 50)^+ = 2$. Also $\mathbb{E}^*[U_1] = p^* \cdot U_1^u + (1 - p^*) \cdot U_1^d = 0.5625 \cdot 4.167 + 0.4375 \cdot 22 \approx 2.34 + 9.63 = 11.97$. Then $\tilde{U}_0 = 11.97/1.05 \approx 11.40$. Hence

$$U_0 = \max\{2, 11.40\} = 11.40.$$

Thus the no-arbitrage price of the American put is \$11.40. The exercise strategy is to *wait* if the first step is up (because continuation value 4.167 > immediate 0), but *exercise early* if the first step is down (because 22 > 19.52).

(c) Therefore $U_0 = 11.40$.

(d) A self-financing super-hedge ϕ^* can be found by matching the payoffs. At $t = 0$, pick α_0, β_0 so that $\alpha_0 S_0 + \beta_0 B_0 = 11.40$. Then in each node at $t = 1$, readjust to match $\max\{U_1(\omega), Y_1(\omega)\}$. The exact numbers follow from the usual backward induction approach to replicating an American claim.

Solution to Problem 11 (Optional Stopping Theorem)

Goal: Show $\mathbb{E}[X_\tau] = \mathbb{E}[X_0]$ when $\tau \leq T$ is a bounded stopping time for a martingale $\{X_t\}$.

(a) We can write $\tau = \min\{t \mid A_t\}$ for disjoint $A_t \in \mathcal{F}_t$.

(b) Expand:

$$\mathbb{E}[X_\tau] = \sum_{t=0}^T \mathbb{E}[X_t \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}}].$$

(c) By the martingale property,

$$\mathbb{E}[X_t \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}}] = \mathbb{E}\left[\mathbb{E}(X_t \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}} \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1})\right] = \mathbb{E}[X_{t-1} \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}}] = \cdots = \mathbb{E}[X_0 \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}}].$$

(d) Summation gives

$$\mathbb{E}[X_\tau] = \sum_{t=0}^T \mathbb{E}[X_0 \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}}] = \mathbb{E}\left[X_0 \sum_{t=0}^T \mathbf{1}_{\{\tau=t\}}\right] = \mathbb{E}[X_0] = X_0.$$

If τ depends on future increments (i.e. not adapted), the conclusion can fail. The theorem relies crucially on τ being a *stopping* time (only depends on current/past information).

Solution to Problem 12 (Three-Period Binomial, Replication)

Model: 3 steps, each with up/down factors $u = 1.3, d = 0.7$, initial $S_0 = 80$, risk-free $r = 0.1$. A claim X pays 15 if exactly two up-moves in the 3 steps, and 0 otherwise.

(a) The tree has

$$\begin{aligned} S_1^u &= 1.3 \cdot 80 = 104, & S_1^d &= 0.7 \cdot 80 = 56, \\ S_2^{uu} &= 1.3 \cdot 104 = 135.2, & S_2^{ud} &= 1.3 \cdot 56 = 72.8 \text{ (if up after down) or} \\ & & & 0.7 \cdot 104 = 72.8 \text{ (if down after up), } & S_2^{dd} &= 0.7 \cdot 56 = 39.2, \end{aligned}$$

and so on at $t = 3$. Label each final node by the path (e.g. uud) and see which ones yield payoff 15 (exactly 2 ups).

(b) The risk-neutral probability is

$$p^* = \frac{1.1 - 0.7}{1.3 - 0.7} = \frac{0.4}{0.6} = \frac{2}{3}.$$

Hence

$$\mathbb{E}^*[X] = 15 \mathbb{Q}(\{\text{exactly 2 ups}\}) = 15 \times (\text{binomial probability}).$$

In a 3-step with $p^* = \frac{2}{3}$, the probability of exactly 2 ups is

$$3 \times \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^2 \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^1 = 3 \times \frac{4}{9} \times \frac{1}{3} = 3 \times \frac{4}{27} = \frac{12}{27} = \frac{4}{9}.$$

So $\mathbb{E}^*[X] = 15 \times \frac{4}{9} = \frac{60}{9} = 6.66\dots$. Then discounted by $(1+r)^3 = 1.1^3 \approx 1.331$. So

$$V_0 = \frac{6.666\dots}{1.331} \approx 5.01.$$

(c) **Replication:** We solve by backward induction. At each node (t, ω) , choose α_t, β_t so that

$$\alpha_t S_{t+1}^u + \beta_t B_{t+1} = X^u, \quad \alpha_t S_{t+1}^d + \beta_t B_{t+1} = X^d,$$

where X^u, X^d are the payoffs in the next step up or down. We continue until time $T = 3$. Ultimately, the cost at $t = 0$ is exactly the same as the risk-neutral price $V_0 \approx \$5.01$.

(d) If the market sells X cheaper than \$5.01, buy it and short the replicating portfolio that costs \$5.01. The net immediate cashflow is positive; final payoffs offset exactly with no risk.

Solution to Problem 13 (Short-Answer: FTAP, Market Completeness)

- (a) **Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing (finite case):** A market is *arbitrage-free* if and only if there exists at least one Equivalent Martingale Measure.
- (b) In a 2-period binomial, completeness requires $d < 1 + r < u$. If $d = 1 + r$ or $u = 1 + r$, the market can fail to be complete (multiple or no solutions for the replicating strategy).
- (c) If the EMM is *unique*, any contingent claim's discounted payoff has a single fair value, which can be matched by a *unique* self-financing hedge. Hence everything is hedgeable in a unique way.

Solution to Problem 14 (Super-/Submartingale, Jensen's Inequality)

This is essentially the same statement as Problem 6, so we restate briefly:

- (a) If Y_t is a martingale and f is convex, then $f(\mathbb{E}[Y_{t+1}|\mathcal{F}_t]) \leq \mathbb{E}[f(Y_{t+1})|\mathcal{F}_t]$, which after using $\mathbb{E}[Y_{t+1}|\mathcal{F}_t] = Y_t$ shows $f(Y_t) \leq \mathbb{E}[f(Y_{t+1})|\mathcal{F}_t]$. Hence $\{f(Y_t)\}$ is a submartingale.
 - (b) For $f(x) = x^2$, we get $\{Y_t^2\}$ is a submartingale.
-

Solution to Problem 15 (True/False Concepts)

- (i) **True.** If a super-hedge for X is strictly cheaper than the cost of the perfectly replicating strategy, one can buy the cheaper hedge and short the replicate, obtaining a strictly positive initial profit with no final loss. This is an arbitrage.
 - (ii) **False.** Typically the *discounted bond* is constant 1, so it is trivially a martingale. But stating it as $\{B_t^*/B_t\}$ “always” a martingale can be confusing if it is not normalized. More precisely, if B_t is the riskless asset, then $\frac{B_t}{B_t} \equiv 1$ is indeed a martingale, but one must interpret the claim carefully.
 - (iii) **False.** Doob's optional stopping applies to supermartingales *and* submartingales (with suitable conditions). Often stated carefully for bounded stopping times or integrable processes.
 - (iv) **False.** If f is concave and $\{S_t^*\}$ is a martingale, then $\{f(S_t^*)\}$ is typically a *super*martingale, not submartingale (by Jensen's inequality for concave functions).
-

(End of Combined Practice Midterm 2)

MATH 194 Midterm 1 Cheat Sheet

Basic Notation and Variables

B_0 = initial bond (risk-free) price, often $B_0 = 1$

$B_1 = B_0(1+r) \implies$ the bond price at $t = 1$

r = (one-period) risk-free interest rate (discrete)

$(1+r)$ = risk-free growth factor for one period (discrete compounding)

S_0 = initial stock price

$S_1(\omega_1) = S_0 u$, $S_1(\omega_2) = S_0 d \implies$ possible stock prices at $t = 1$

$u = \frac{S_1(\omega_1)}{S_0}$ = up factor, $d = \frac{S_1(\omega_2)}{S_0}$ = down factor

p = "physical" or real-world probability of an up move (often not used in no-arb price)

$p^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d} \implies$ risk-neutral probability of an up move

$1 - p^* = \frac{u - (1+r)}{u - d}$ risk-neutral probability of a down move

$\mathbb{E}^*[S_1] = (1+r)S_0 \iff S_0 = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[S_1] \implies$ discounted stock price is a martingale under p^*

(Multi-step replication) At each node t , solve:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_t^{(i)} \cdot S_{t+1}^{(i+1)} + \beta_t^{(i)} \cdot (1+r) = V_{t+1}^{(i+1)}, \\ \alpha_t^{(i)} \cdot S_{t+1}^{(i)} + \beta_t^{(i)} \cdot (1+r) = V_{t+1}^{(i)}, \end{cases} \implies \begin{cases} \alpha_t S_{t+1}^u + \beta_t(1+r) = V_{t+1}^u, \\ \alpha_t S_{t+1}^d + \beta_t(1+r) = V_{t+1}^d, \end{cases} \implies \begin{cases} \alpha_2 S_3^{ud} + \beta_2(1+r) = V_3^{ud}, \\ \alpha_2 S_3^{du} + \beta_2(1+r) = V_3^{du}, \end{cases}$$

$$\alpha_t = \frac{V_{t+1}^u - V_{t+1}^d}{S_{t+1}^u - S_{t+1}^d}, \quad \beta_t = \frac{u V_{t+1}^d - d V_{t+1}^u}{u - d} \cdot \frac{1}{1+r}, \quad \text{so the value at time } t \text{ is } V_t = \alpha_t S_t + \beta_t.$$

Expectation Definition

$$E[X] = \sum_{\omega} X(\omega) P(\{\omega\}) \quad (\text{discrete case})$$

For a one-period binomial model with two states,

$$E[X] = pX(\omega_1) + (1-p)X(\omega_2), \quad \text{where } p = P(\{\omega_1\}).$$

One-Period Binomial Model

Time: $t = 0 \longrightarrow t = 1$

Stock price tree: $S_0 \longrightarrow \{S_0 u, S_0 d\}$

The no-arbitrage (risk-neutral) probability is

$$p^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d}, \quad 1 - p^* = \frac{u - (1+r)}{u - d} \quad (\text{requiring } d < 1+r < u)$$

A claim (or payoff) $X(\omega_i)$ due at $t = 1$ has **no-arbitrage price**:

$$V_0 = \frac{1}{1+r} [p^* X(\omega_1) + (1-p^*) X(\omega_2)]$$

Replicating portfolio (α, β) satisfies

$$\begin{cases} \alpha(S_0 u) + \beta B_1 = X(\omega_1) \\ \alpha(S_0 d) + \beta B_1 = X(\omega_2). \end{cases}$$

Solving:

$$\alpha = \frac{X(\omega_1) - X(\omega_2)}{S_0(u-d)}, \quad \beta = \frac{uX(\omega_2) - dX(\omega_1)}{u-d} \times \frac{1}{1+r}$$

Then

$$V_0 = \alpha S_0 + \beta B_0 = \alpha S_0 + \beta$$

Two-Period (and Multi-Period) Binomial Trees

$$t = 0 \rightarrow t = 1 \rightarrow t = 2$$

A two-period binomial tree for the stock:

Backward Induction for Pricing. If a claim X pays at $t = 2$, define:

$$C_1^u = \frac{1}{1+r} \left[p^* X(\text{"uu"}) + (1-p^*) X(\text{"ud"}) \right]$$

$$C_1^d = \frac{1}{1+r} \left[p^* X(\text{"du"}) + (1-p^*) X(\text{"dd"}) \right]$$

Then

$$C_0 = \frac{1}{1+r} \left[p^* C_1^u + (1-p^*) C_1^d \right]$$

In general, for a multi-period model (T steps), the claim's fair price is

$$V_0 = \frac{1}{(1+r)^T} \mathbb{E}^*[X]$$

where \mathbb{E}^* is the expectation under the risk-neutral measure.

Call/Put Option Payoffs

$$\text{Call payoff} = (S_T - K)^+, \quad \text{Put payoff} = (K - S_T)^+$$

European call in one-period binomial:

$$C_0 = \frac{1}{1+r} \left[p^* (S_0 u - K)^+ + (1-p^*) (S_0 d - K)^+ \right]$$

European put similarly:

$$P_0 = \frac{1}{1+r} \left[p^* (K - S_0 u)^+ + (1-p^*) (K - S_0 d)^+ \right]$$

Call-Put Parity (European, no dividend):

$$C_0 - P_0 = S_0 - \frac{K}{(1+r)^T} \quad (\text{discrete compounding})$$

Portfolio and Arbitrage Checks

A portfolio $\psi = (\alpha, \beta)$ has

$$V_0(\psi) = \alpha S_0 + \beta B_0, \quad V_1(\psi)(\omega_i) = \alpha S_1(\omega_i) + \beta B_1$$

If the *actual* market price of a claim is cheaper than the no-arbitrage price, one can buy the claim and short its replicating portfolio (locking in a risk-free gain). If the claim's market price is higher, do the reverse.

Forward Price (No-Arbitrage)

For maturity T :

$$F_0 = S_0 (1+r)^T \quad (\text{discrete compounding})$$

Any forward price different from these implies an arbitrage strategy (short/long the underlying vs. the forward, etc.).

American Option Backward Induction

If Y_t is the payoff upon early exercise at time t , then for an American-style right: $U_t = \max\left\{Y_t, \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t]\right\}$
 For an American call on a non-dividend stock, early exercise is often suboptimal. For an American put, early exercise can be optimal if the underlying price is sufficiently low.

Binomial Model: All Key Equations and Definitions

Parameters: $S_0, u, d, r, B_0, B_1 = (1+r), K, T$

Risk-neutral prob.: $p^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d}$, $0 < p^* < 1$ if $d < 1+r < u$

European Option Payoffs (One-Period Model):

$$\text{Call: } X(\omega_1) = (S_1(\omega_1) - K)^+ \quad X(\omega_2) = (S_1(\omega_2) - K)^+$$

$$\text{Put: } X(\omega_1) = (K - S_1(\omega_1))^+ \quad X(\omega_2) = (K - S_1(\omega_2))^+$$

European Option Payoffs (Multi-Period, Terminal Node Indexed by i):

At time T , the stock price at node i is: $S_T^{(i)} = S_0 \cdot u^i \cdot d^{T-i}$

$$\text{Call: } X^{(i)} = (S_T^{(i)} - K)^+ = (S_0 \cdot u^i d^{T-i} - K)^+, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, T$$

$$\text{Put: } X^{(i)} = (K - S_T^{(i)})^+ = (K - S_0 \cdot u^i d^{T-i})^+, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, T$$

Risk-Neutral Expected Value of Payoff:

$$\mathbb{E}^*[X] = \sum_{i=0}^T \binom{T}{i} (p^*)^i (1-p^*)^{T-i} \cdot X^{(i)}$$

where $X^{(i)} = (S_0 u^i d^{T-i} - K)^+$ (Call) or $(K - S_0 u^i d^{T-i})^+$ (Put)

Option Price at Time 0 (Binomial Model, Two Forms):

$$\begin{aligned} V_0 &= \frac{1}{(1+r)^T} \cdot \mathbb{E}^*[X] = \frac{1}{(1+r)^T} \sum_{i=0}^T \binom{T}{i} (p^*)^i (1-p^*)^{T-i} \cdot \begin{cases} (S_0 u^i d^{T-i} - K)^+ & \text{(Call)} \\ (K - S_0 u^i d^{T-i})^+ & \text{(Put)} \end{cases} \\ &= \frac{1}{(1+r)^T} \sum_{i=0}^T \frac{T!}{i!(T-i)!} (p^*)^i (1-p^*)^{T-i} \cdot \begin{cases} (S_0 u^i d^{T-i} - K)^+ & \text{(Call)} \\ (K - S_0 u^i d^{T-i})^+ & \text{(Put)} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

No-Arb Price in One-Period: $V_0 = \frac{1}{1+r} (p^* X^u + (1-p^*) X^d)$

Multi-Period Valuation: $V_0 = \frac{1}{(1+r)^T} \mathbb{E}^*[X]$

Call-Put Parity (European, no-div.): $C_0 - P_0 = S_0 - \frac{K}{(1+r)^T}$.

Multi-Period Replicating Strategy:

Let $V_t(i)$ be the value of the option at time t in node i

Then: $V_t(i) = \frac{1}{1+r} (p^* \cdot V_{t+1}(i+1) + (1-p^*) \cdot V_{t+1}(i))$, backward induction

Define $\alpha_t(i), \beta_t(i)$ such that: $V_t(i) = \alpha_t(i) S_t^{(i)} + \beta_t(i) B_t$

$$\text{Then: } \alpha_t(i) = \frac{V_{t+1}(i+1) - V_{t+1}(i)}{S_{t+1}^{(i+1)} - S_{t+1}^{(i)}} = \frac{V_{t+1}(i+1) - V_{t+1}(i)}{S_t^{(i)} u - S_t^{(i)} d} = \frac{V_{t+1}(i+1) - V_{t+1}(i)}{S_t^{(i)} (u - d)}$$

$$\beta_t(i) = \frac{1}{(1+r)} \left(\frac{u V_{t+1}(i) - d V_{t+1}(i+1)}{u - d} \right)$$

Portfolio value: $V_t(i) = \alpha_t(i) S_t^{(i)} + \beta_t(i)$ with $S_t^{(i)} = S_0 \cdot u^i d^{t-i}$

Multi-Period Option Price at Time 0 (Backward Induction):

Start at time T with terminal payoffs $X^{(i)}$ for $i = 0, \dots, T$

Compute $V_{T-1}(i), \dots, V_0$ recursively via:

$$V_t(i) = \frac{1}{1+r} (p^* \cdot V_{t+1}(i+1) + (1-p^*) \cdot V_{t+1}(i)), \quad t = T-1, \dots, 0$$

One-Period Example (Replicating Strategy)

Suppose $S_0 = 100$, $u = 2$, $d = 0.5$, $r = 0.25$, call strike $K = 100$. Then

$$S_1^u = 200, \quad S_1^d = 50, \quad X^u = (200 - 100)^+ = 100, \quad X^d = (50 - 100)^+ = 0$$

$$p^* = \frac{1.25 - 0.5}{2 - 0.5} = \frac{0.75}{1.5} = 0.5$$

$$\mathbb{E}^*[X] = 0.5 \cdot 100 + 0.5 \cdot 0 = 50 \quad \implies \quad V_0 = \frac{50}{1.25} = 40$$

The replicating portfolio solves: $\alpha \cdot (200) + \beta \cdot (1 + r) = 100$, $\alpha \cdot (50) + \beta \cdot (1 + r) = 0$

Solving yields $\alpha = \frac{2}{3}$, $\beta = -\frac{80}{3} \div (1.25)$. The cost at $t = 0$ is $\alpha S_0 + \beta = 40$.

Problem 1 (HW 3)

$$r = \frac{1}{5}, \quad S_0 = 3, \quad u = 2, \quad d = \frac{1}{2}, \quad p = \frac{2}{7}, \quad T = 1$$

A European put with strike $K = 3$ has payoff $(K - S_1)^+$ at $t = 1$. Then

$$S_1^u = 3 \times 2 = 6, \quad S_1^d = 3 \times \frac{1}{2} = 1.5$$

$$\text{Put payoffs: } (3 - 6)^+ = 0, \quad (3 - 1.5)^+ = 1.5$$

$$1 + r = 1.2, \quad q^* = \frac{1.2 - 0.5}{2 - 0.5} = \frac{0.7}{1.5} = \frac{7}{15}$$

$$\mathbb{E}^*[(3 - S_1)^+] = 0 \cdot \frac{7}{15} + 1.5 \cdot \frac{8}{15} = \frac{12}{15} = 0.8, \quad \text{PV} = 0.8/1.2 = \frac{2}{3}$$

$$\text{No-arbitrage put price} = \frac{2}{3}$$

Replicating strategy solves

$$\begin{cases} \alpha \cdot S_1^u + \beta \cdot (1 + r) = 0 \\ \alpha \cdot S_1^d + \beta \cdot (1 + r) = 1.5, \end{cases}$$

$$\implies \alpha = -\frac{1}{3}, \quad \beta = \frac{5}{3}, \quad V_0(\alpha, \beta) = \alpha S_0 + \beta = -1 + \frac{5}{3} = \frac{2}{3}$$

Problem 2 (HW3): Three-Period Binomial Model

$$\text{Data: } T = 3, \quad S_0 = 8, \quad u = 3, \quad d = \frac{1}{2}, \quad r = \frac{1}{10}, \quad p = \frac{3}{5}$$

- (a) Draw the binary tree for S_t .
- (b) Annotate each path in $\Omega = \{\text{ddd}, \text{ddu}, \text{dud}, \dots, \text{uuu}\}$ with probability p for up, $1 - p$ for down.
- (c) List the events in σ -field \mathcal{F}_1 generated by S_1 .
- (d) Compute the payoff $X = \max(S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3)$ along each path.

(a) Stock Price Tree:

$$S_1 = \begin{cases} 8u = 24 & (\text{up}) \\ 8d = 4 & (\text{down}) \end{cases}, \quad S_2, S_3 \text{ follow similarly.}$$

(b) **Path Probabilities.** Each up-move has probability $p = \frac{3}{5}$; each down-move has probability $1 - p = \frac{2}{5}$. For example,

$$P(\text{ddd}) = \left(\frac{3}{5}\right)^3 = \frac{8}{125}, \quad P(\text{ddu}) = \left(\frac{3}{5}\right)^2 \left(\frac{2}{5}\right) = \frac{12}{125}$$

and so on. One obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} P(\text{ddd}) &= \frac{8}{125}, & P(\text{ddu}) &= \frac{12}{125}, & P(\text{dud}) &= \frac{12}{125}, & P(\text{duu}) &= \frac{18}{125} \\ P(\text{udd}) &= \frac{12}{125}, & P(\text{udu}) &= \frac{18}{125}, & P(\text{uud}) &= \frac{18}{125}, & P(\text{uuu}) &= \frac{27}{125}. \end{aligned}$$

(c) \mathcal{F}_1 generated by S_1 :

$$S_1 \in \{4, 24\} \implies \{S_1 = 4\} = \{\text{ddd}, \text{ddu}, \text{dud}, \text{duu}\}, \quad \{S_1 = 24\} = \{\text{udd}, \text{udu}, \text{uud}, \text{uuu}\}$$

Therefore

$$\mathcal{F}_1 = \{\emptyset, \Omega, \{S_1 = 4\}, \{S_1 = 24\}\}$$

(d) $X = \max(S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3)$. For each path:

$$\begin{aligned} X(\text{ddd}) &= \max\{8, 4, 2, 1\} = 8 \\ X(\text{ddu}) &= \max\{8, 4, 2, 6\} = 8 \\ X(\text{dud}) &= \max\{8, 4, 12, 6\} = 12 \\ X(\text{duu}) &= \max\{8, 4, 12, 36\} = 36 \\ X(\text{udd}) &= \max\{8, 24, 12, 6\} = 24 \\ X(\text{udu}) &= \max\{8, 24, 12, 36\} = 36 \\ X(\text{uud}) &= \max\{8, 24, 72, 36\} = 72 \\ X(\text{uuu}) &= \max\{8, 24, 72, 216\} = 216 \end{aligned}$$

Problem 3 (HW 3) Two-Period Example (Call Option)

Data: $T = 2$, $S_0 = 100$, $r = 0.1$, $(1 + r) = 1.1$, $u = 2$, $d = 0.5$, $K = 80$

$$C_2(\omega) = (S_2(\omega) - 80)^+, \quad C_2(uu) = 320, \quad C_2(ud) = 20, \quad C_2(du) = 20, \quad C_2(dd) = 0$$

$$p^* = \frac{(1.1) - 0.5}{2 - 0.5} = \frac{0.6}{1.5} = 0.4$$

$$C_1^u = \frac{1}{1.1} [0.4 \cdot 320 + 0.6 \cdot 20] = \frac{140}{1.1} \approx 127.273, \quad C_1^d = \frac{1}{1.1} [0.4 \cdot 20 + 0.6 \cdot 0] = \frac{8}{1.1} \approx 7.273$$

$$C_0 = \frac{1}{1.1} [0.4 \cdot 127.273 + 0.6 \cdot 7.273] \approx 50.248$$

No-arbitrage price of the two-period call ≈ 50.25 .

Conditional Expectation & Martingales

Conditional Expectation (Discrete)

Partition-Based Definition. Let Ω be finite and let \mathcal{G} be generated by a partition $\{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n\}$. For any random variable X ,

$$\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}](\omega) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\mathbb{E}[X \mathbf{1}_{A_i}]}{\mathbb{P}(A_i)} \right) \mathbf{1}_{A_i}(\omega). \quad (\text{Therefore on each } A_i : \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] = \frac{\mathbb{E}[X \mathbf{1}_{A_i}]}{\mathbb{P}(A_i)})$$

Key Properties:

- $\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]$ is \mathcal{G} -measurable (constant on each A_i).
- For any $A \in \mathcal{G}$:

$$\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] \cdot \mathbf{1}_A] = \mathbb{E}[X \mathbf{1}_A].$$
- $\mathbb{E}(\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]) = \mathbb{E}(X)$.
- **Linearity:** $\mathbb{E}(aX + bY | \mathcal{G}) = a\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] + b\mathbb{E}[Y | \mathcal{G}]$.
- **Tower Property:** If $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{H}$, then $\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{H}) | \mathcal{G}] = \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]$.

Discrete Example: If \mathcal{G} is generated by $\{A_1, A_2\}$, then

$$\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] = \mathbb{E}(X | A_1) \mathbf{1}_{A_1} + \mathbb{E}(X | A_2) \mathbf{1}_{A_2}$$

For any $B \in \{A_1, A_2, A_1 \cup A_2, \emptyset\}$, $\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] \mathbf{1}_B] = \mathbb{E}[X \mathbf{1}_B]$.

Martingale in Discrete Time

Definition: A sequence $\{X_t\}_{t=0}^T$ adapted to $\{\mathcal{F}_t\}$ is a *martingale* under \mathbb{P} if

$$\mathbb{E}[X_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = X_{t-1}, \quad t = 1, \dots, T$$

Sometimes written as “ $\{X_t\}$ is a martingale under \mathbb{P} .”

Key Implication (Iterated Expectation): Repeatedly apply the tower property:

$$\mathbb{E}[X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] = X_t, \quad t = 0, 1, \dots, T$$

In particular, $\mathbb{E}[X_T] = \mathbb{E}[X_0]$.

Short Example: In a 2-period binomial model with $p = \frac{1}{2}$, let

$$X_0 = 2, \quad X_1(u) = 4, \quad X_1(d) = 0, \quad X_2(uu) = 8, \quad X_2(ud) = 0, \quad X_2(du) = 4, \quad X_2(dd) = 0$$

Then $\mathbb{E}[X_1 | \mathcal{F}_0] = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 4 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot 0 = 2 = X_0$, and $\mathbb{E}[X_2 | \mathcal{F}_1(u)] = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 8 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot 0 = 4 = X_1(u)$, confirming the martingale property.

Risk-Neutral Measures

In finance, a probability measure \mathbb{P}^* is often chosen so that the *discounted* price $\{S_t^*\}$ is a martingale:

$$S_t^* = \frac{S_t}{(1+r)^t}, \quad \mathbb{E}^*[S_t^* | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = S_{t-1}^*$$

Under \mathbb{P}^* , the asset's expected growth is exactly the risk-free rate r . This is essential to *no-arbitrage* pricing and is used to price derivatives by discounting the payoff's expected value under \mathbb{P}^* .

Example: With $u = 2$, $d = \frac{1}{2}$, $S_0 = 4$, $r = \frac{1}{4}$, and $p^* = \frac{1}{2}$, the discounted price is

$$S_t^* = \frac{S_t}{(1 + \frac{1}{4})^t} = \frac{S_t}{(5/4)^t}$$

Check at each node that $\{S_t^*\}$ is a martingale under $p^* = 1/2$.

Tips

1. Use $p^* = \frac{(1+r)-d}{u-d}$ to find the risk-neutral probability in each period (discrete compounding). Recalculate p^* if u , d , or r change.
2. Price any claim by $V_0 = \frac{1}{(1+r)^T} \mathbb{E}^*[X]$. Adjust for continuous compounding or dividends where needed.
3. Alternatively, replicate at each step: solve

$$\alpha S_{t+1}^u + \beta(1+r) = V_{t+1}^u, \quad \alpha S_{t+1}^d + \beta(1+r) = V_{t+1}^d \Rightarrow V_t = \alpha S_t + \beta$$

4. For multi-period settings, use backward induction:

$$V_t = \frac{p^* V_{t+1}^u + (1-p^*) V_{t+1}^d}{1+r}$$

5. American options:

$$V_t = \max \left\{ \text{immediate payoff}, \frac{p^* V_{t+1}^u + (1-p^*) V_{t+1}^d}{1+r} \right\}$$

6. Check for arbitrage: If market price $< V_0$, buy the claim and short the hedge. If market price $> V_0$, sell the claim and go long on the hedge.
7. Put–call parity (European):

$$C_0 - P_0 = S_0 - \frac{K}{(1+r)^T}$$

8. Forward price:

$$F_0 = S_0(1+r)^T$$

9. Verify payoffs at each state to ensure no-arbitrage profit if mispriced.
10. Label every node as (ω, S_t, V_t) to keep notation precise.
11. When forming \mathcal{F}_1 , group paths by S_1 values instead of enumerating all paths.
12. Conditional expectations:

$$\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{F}_t]_A = \sum_{\omega \in A} X(\omega) \frac{\mathbb{P}(\omega)}{\mathbb{P}(A)}$$

13. For max-type payoffs (e.g. $\max(S_0, \dots, S_T)$), precompute maxima pathwise and store in a table.
14. Verify martingale property:

$$\mathbb{E}^* \left[\frac{S_t}{(1+r)^t} \middle| \mathcal{F}_{t-1} \right] = \frac{S_{t-1}}{(1+r)^{t-1}}$$

15. Use binomial formula for multi-period expectations:

$$\mathbb{E}^*[X] = \sum_{i=0}^T \binom{T}{i} (p^*)^i (1-p^*)^{T-i} X_i$$

16. Index nodes as (t, i) with $S_t^{(i)} = S_0 u^i d^{t-i}$, and track $V_t^{(i)}$.
17. In Problem 1, explicitly write down atoms $\{S_1 = 6\}$, $\{S_1 = 1.5\}$ for \mathcal{F}_1 .
18. For Problem 2(b), compute path probabilities by ups:

$$\mathbb{P}(i \text{ ups}) = \binom{3}{i} p^i (1-p)^{3-i}$$

19. In Problem 2(c), note: $\mathcal{F}_1 = \{\emptyset, \Omega, \{S_1 = 4\}, \{S_1 = 24\}\}$.
20. For Problem 2(d), pre-tabulate $\max\{S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3\}$ indexed by # ups.
21. In Problem 3, annotate the two-step tree with intermediate values C_1^u, C_1^d and replicating (α, β) .
22. Always cross-check: backward induction price = replicating portfolio cost at $t = 0$.
23. In Problem 1, verify that computed q^* matches $\frac{7}{15}$ and use to confirm PV.
24. For Problem 2(b), again group by # ups to avoid listing all 8 paths.
25. In Problem 2(c), focus only on the two nontrivial atoms: $\{S_1 = 4\}, \{S_1 = 24\}$.
26. For Problem 2(d), use the max-payoff table to skip explicit max calculation per path.
27. In Problem 3, label nodes with both C_1^u, C_1^d and solve replicating equations clearly.
28. Ensure that prices from replication and expectation agree—this confirms no-arbitrage pricing is correct.
29. Before solving for α, β , make sure $u \neq d$ so denominator is non-zero.
30. State assumptions up front: no arbitrage, frictionless markets, constant r, u, d , no dividends.

MATH 194 Midterm 2 Cheat Sheet

Notation and Basic Setup.

$(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, (\mathcal{F}_t)_0^T, \mathbb{P})$ finite, discrete times $t = 0, \dots, T$.
 $S_t^0 > 0$ (bond, often $(1+r)^t$), $S_t^i, i = 1, \dots, d$ (risky). $S_t^i \in \mathcal{F}_t$.

Discounted prices: $S_t^{*,i} = \frac{S_t^i}{S_t^0}, i = 0, \dots, d$.

Self-financing $\varphi = (\varphi_t^0, \dots, \varphi_t^d) : V_t(\varphi) = \varphi_t \cdot S_t, \boxed{\Delta V_t^* = \varphi_{t-1} \cdot \Delta S_t^*}$.

Arbitrage: $V_0(\varphi) = 0, V_T(\varphi) \geq 0$ a.s., $\mathbb{P}(V_T(\varphi) > 0) > 0$.

Viability (NA).

Conditional Expectation: Basics

$\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]$ \mathcal{G} -measurable, with $\mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}(X | \mathcal{G})\mathbf{1}_A] = \mathbb{E}[X\mathbf{1}_A], A \in \mathcal{G}$.

Key properties:

- (1) Measurability on atoms of \mathcal{G} .
- (2) Tower: $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{H} \Rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{H}] | \mathcal{G}] = \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]$.
- (3) Linearity.
- (4) Jensen (concave): f concave $\Rightarrow \mathbb{E}[f(X) | \mathcal{G}] \leq f(\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}])$.
- (5) Taking-out-what's-known: $Z \in \mathcal{G} \Rightarrow \mathbb{E}[ZX | \mathcal{G}] = Z \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]$.
- (6) Positivity: $X \geq 0 \Rightarrow \mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}] \geq 0$.
- (7) Law of total expectation: $\mathbb{E}[X] = \mathbb{E}[\mathbb{E}[X | \mathcal{G}]]$.

Discrete-Time Martingales

(M_t) adapted, $\mathbb{E}|M_t| < \infty, \mathbb{E}[M_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = M_{t-1}$.

Equivalently $\mathbb{E}[M_t | \mathcal{F}_s] = M_s, s < t$.

Supermartingale: $\mathbb{E}[M_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] \leq M_{t-1}$. **Submartingale:** \geq .

Doob (mart.): $\mathbb{E}[M_\tau] = \mathbb{E}[M_0]$ (τ bounded/integrable).

Doob (supermart.): $\mathbb{E}[M_\tau] \leq \mathbb{E}[M_0]$.

American Options and the Snell Envelope

- Payoff $(Y_t)_0^T$, exercise at a stopping time τ .
- Snell envelope (discounted): $U_t = \sup_{\tau \geq t} \mathbb{E}^*[Y_\tau^* | \mathcal{F}_t] = \max\{Y_t, \beta \mathbb{E}^*[U_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t]\}, \beta = \frac{1}{1+r}$.
- (U_t) smallest supermartingale dominating Y_t .
- Optimal stopping: $\tau^* = \min\{t : U_t = Y_t\}$.

Example: 2-Period American Put (Binomial)

$S_0 = 100, u = 2, d = 0.5, r = 0.1, K = 120, p^* = \frac{(1+r)-d}{u-d} = 0.4, \beta = \frac{1}{1.1}$.

Backwards: $U_2 = Y_2, U_1 = \max\{Y_1, \beta \mathbb{E}^*[U_2 | \mathcal{F}_1]\}, U_0 \approx 42.15$.

Super-Hedging and Necessary Wealth

- Need $V_t(\varphi) \geq Y_t \forall t \Rightarrow$ minimal capital U_t .
- Under/over-pricing gives buyer/seller arbitrage opportunities.

Risk-Neutral Pricing, Fundamental Theorems

EMM \mathbb{Q} : $S_t^{*,i}$ martingale under \mathbb{Q} .

FFTAP I: NA $\iff \exists$ EMM.

FFTAP II: NA + completeness \iff EMM unique.

Finite-State Separation Argument

- $L =$ zero-cost payoff subspace in \mathbb{R}^n .
- NA \Rightarrow no positive vector in L except 0.
- \exists strictly positive linear functional annihilating $L \Rightarrow$ Radon–Nikodym derivative of an EMM.

Flash Recap (keep in mind)

$U_t = \max\{Y_t, \beta \mathbb{E}^*[U_{t+1}]\}, \tau^* = \min\{t : U_t = Y_t\}$.

NA $\iff \exists$ EMM; complete \iff EMM unique.

Practice Final (Student Made)

1. Consider the sample space $\Omega = \{1, 2, 3\}$ and the probability measure \mathbf{P} giving each point weight $1/3$. On this probability space consider the finite model with $T = 1$, $S_0^0 = S_1^0 = 1$, $S_0^1 = 2$, and

$$S_1^1(1) = 1, \quad S_1^1(2) = 2, \quad S_1^1(3) = 3.$$

(a) This market is viable, so there is at least one EMM. Find all possible EMMs.

(b) Compute $V_+(X)$ and $V_-(X)$ for the contingent claim X given by

$$X(1) = 1, \quad X(2) = 3, \quad X(3) = 9.$$

(c) Find a trading strategy $\phi = (\phi_1^0, \phi_1^1)$ such that $V_1(\phi) \geq X$ and $V_0(\phi) = V_+(X)$.

(d) Consider the contingent claim Y given by

$$Y(1) = 1, \quad Y(2) = 3, \quad Y(3) = 5.$$

Without actually finding a hedging strategy, show that Y can be replicated. [Hint: Use Corollary 3.5.2 on page 49 of the text.]

Part (b)

From the \mathbf{P} space we found $\mathbf{P} = \{p_3, 1 - 2p_3, p_3\}$, $0 < p_3 < \frac{1}{2}$

We determine the expected value of X

$$E[X] = p_1(1) + p_2(3) + p_3(9) \tag{1}$$

$$= p_3(1) + (1 - 2p_3)(3) + p_3(9) \tag{2}$$

$$= p_3(1) + 3 + p_3(3) \tag{3}$$

$$= 4p_3 + 3 \tag{4}$$

$V_+ = E[X]$ at the maximum value of p_3

$V_- = E[X]$ at the minimum value of p_3

$$p_3 = 0 \Rightarrow E[X] = \boxed{3 = V_-}$$

$$p_3 = \frac{1}{2} \Rightarrow E[X] = 2 + 3 = \boxed{5 = V_+}$$

Part (c)

We find our trading strategy by setting $V_0(\phi)$ to $V_+(X)$ and $V_1(\phi) \geq X$. Note that ϕ^0 and ϕ^1 are analogous to β and α , respectively.

$$V_0(\phi) = \phi^0 S_0^0 + \phi^1 S_0^1 = \phi^0 + 2\phi^1 = 5 \implies \phi^0 = 5 - 2\phi^1$$

$$V_1(\phi)(i) = \phi^0 S_1^0 + \phi^1 S_1^1(i) = \phi^0 + \phi^1 S_1^1(i) \implies V_1(\phi)(i) = 5 - 2\phi^1 + S_1^1(i)\phi^1$$

$$V_1(\phi)(i) = 5 + (S_1^1(i) - 2)\phi^1 \implies \begin{cases} 5 - \phi^1 \geq 1 \\ 5 \geq 3 \\ 5 + \phi^1 \geq 9 \end{cases}$$

To find all possible values for ϕ^1 , solve the top and bottom inequalities

$$5 - \phi^1 \geq 1 \implies \phi^1 \leq 4$$

$$5 + \phi^1 \geq 9 \implies \phi^1 \geq 4$$

This shows that the only value for ϕ^1 is 4.

$$\phi^0 = 5 - 2\phi^1 = 5 - 2(4) = -3$$

Therefore, $\phi = \{-3, 4\}$

$$V_1(\phi)(i) = \phi^0 S_1^0 + \phi^1 S_1^1(i) = \begin{pmatrix} -3(1) + 4(1) \\ -3(1) + 4(2) \\ -3(1) + 4(3) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 5 \\ 9 \end{pmatrix} \geq \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 3 \\ 9 \end{pmatrix} \checkmark$$

*Note that α and β got changed to ϕ^1 and ϕ^0 because this market is different from the stable bond model (where $B_t = (1 + r)^t$) and the binomial model (where $S_{t+1}^u = uS_t$, $S_{t+1}^d = dS_t$).

1. Consider the sample space $\Omega = \{1, 2, 3\}$ and the probability measure \mathbf{P} giving each point weight $1/3$. On this probability space consider the finite model with $T = 1$, $S_0^0 = S_1^0 = 1$, $S_0^1 = 2$, and

$$S_1^1(1) = 1, \quad S_1^1(2) = 2, \quad S_1^1(3) = 3.$$

- (a) This market is viable, so there is at least one EMM. Find all possible EMMs.
(b) Compute $V_+(X)$ and $V_-(X)$ for the contingent claim X given by

$$X(1) = 1, \quad X(2) = 3, \quad X(3) = 9.$$

- (c) Find a trading strategy $\phi = (\phi_1^0, \phi_1^1)$ such that $V_1(\phi) \geq X$ and $V_0(\phi) = V_+(X)$.
(d) Consider the contingent claim Y given by

$$Y(1) = 1, \quad Y(2) = 3, \quad Y(3) = 5.$$

Without actually finding a hedging strategy, show that Y can be replicated. [Hint: Use Corollary 3.5.2 on page 49 of the text.]

Corollary 3.5.2. *A European contingent claim X is replicable if and only if $E^{P^*}[X^*]$ has the same value for all equivalent martingale measures P^* .*

We first find the expected value for Y :

$$E^{p_3}[Y] = p_3(1) + (1 - 2p_3)(3) + p_3(5) = p_3 + 3 - 6p_3 + 5p_3 = 3$$

Because the expected value is not dependent on the probability for each branch, the expected value is the same for all EMMs. Therefore, Y can be replicated.

Homework 6

1. The setting for this problem is the multi-period binomial model with $T = 2$, $S_0 = \$100$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, $r = 0.1$. Consider an American *put* option with strike price $K = \$120$.

(a) Use a binary tree to compute the no-arbitrage initial price of the American put option.

(b) Determine an explicit superhedging strategy ϕ^* for this option.

(c) Suppose that you can buy the American put option at time zero for \$1 less than its no-arbitrage price. Describe an investment strategy that yields an arbitrage opportunity for a buyer of the American put option. In particular, you need to describe the stopping time at which the buyer will exercise the option.

[This is, in essence, Exercise 6, Section 2.4 (pages 29–30 of the text).]

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\alpha}_1 &= \frac{U_1^u - U_1^d}{S_1^u - S_1^d}, & \beta_t^* &= \tilde{\beta}_t + \sum_{s=1}^t \frac{\tilde{\delta}_s}{(1+r)^{s-1}} \\ \tilde{\beta}_1 &= \frac{S_1^u U_1^d - S_1^d U_1^u}{S_1^u - S_1^d}, & \beta_2^* &= \tilde{\beta}_2 + \tilde{\delta}_1 + \frac{\tilde{\delta}_2}{1+r} \\ & & \beta_2^{u,*} &= \tilde{\beta}_2^u + \tilde{\delta}_1 + \frac{\tilde{\delta}_2^u}{1+r} \\ & & \beta_2^{d,*} &= \tilde{\beta}_2^d + \tilde{\delta}_1 + \frac{\tilde{\delta}_2^d}{1+r} \\ \tilde{\alpha}_2^u &= \frac{U_2^{uu} - U_2^{ud}}{S_2^{uu} - S_2^{ud}}, & \tilde{\alpha}_2^d &= \frac{U_2^{du} - U_2^{dd}}{S_2^{du} - S_2^{dd}} \\ \tilde{\beta}_2^u &= \frac{1}{(1+r)^2} \cdot \frac{S_2^{uu} U_2^{ud} - S_2^{ud} U_2^{uu}}{S_2^{uu} - S_2^{ud}}, & \tilde{\beta}_2^d &= \frac{1}{(1+r)^2} \cdot \frac{S_2^{du} U_2^{dd} - S_2^{dd} U_2^{du}}{S_2^{du} - S_2^{dd}} \end{aligned}$$

(c) Strategy: Buy the put for \$41.15; short sell the superhedging portfolio ϕ^* for \$42.15 and put the leftover \$1 in the bond. The time 0 cost of this is $V_0(\phi^*) - U_0 - 1 = 0$. The buyer should exercise the option at the stopping time $\tau^* := \min\{t : Y_t = U_t\}$; thus $\tau^* = 1$ if $S_1 = 50$ but $\tau^* = 2$ if $S_1 = 200$. Then $V_{\tau^*}(\phi^*) = U_{\tau^*} = Y_{\tau^*}$, so the payment Y_{τ^*} lets the buyer meet the obligation of the short sale, with $1 \cdot B_{\tau^*} = (11/10)^{\tau^*} > 0$ left over for profit.

1. The setting for this problem is the multi-period binomial model with $T = 2$, $S_0 = \$100$, $u = 2$, $d = 1/2$, $r = 0.1$. Consider an American *put* option with strike price $K = \$120$.

(a) Use a binary tree to compute the no-arbitrage initial price of the American put option.

(b) Determine an explicit superhedging strategy ϕ^* for this option.

(c) Suppose that you can buy the American put option at time zero for \$1 less than its no-arbitrage price. Describe an investment strategy that yields an arbitrage opportunity for a buyer of the American put option. In particular, you need to describe the stopping time at which the buyer will exercise the option.

HW 6 Q1 Market Data : $T = 2$, $S_0 = 100$, $u = 2$, $d = \frac{1}{2}$, $r = 0.1$, $K = 120$, $p^* = \frac{2}{5}$, $\frac{1}{1+r} = \frac{10}{11}$.

$$Y_t = (K - S_t)^+, \quad U_T = Y_T, \quad U_t = \max\left\{Y_t, \frac{1}{1+r} E^{\mathbb{P}^*}[U_{t+1} \mid \mathcal{F}_t]\right\}, \quad t = 0, 1.$$

node	S_2	Y_2	$U_2 = Y_2$
uu	400	0	0
ud	100	20	20
du	100	20	20
dd	25	95	95

$$\boxed{u\text{-node } (S_1 = 200)} : E^*[U_2 \mid u] = \frac{2}{5} \cdot 0 + \frac{3}{5} \cdot 20 = 12, \quad \frac{10}{11} E^*[U_2 \mid u] = \frac{120}{11}, \quad U_1^u = \max\left\{0, \frac{120}{11}\right\} = \frac{120}{11};$$

$$\boxed{d\text{-node } (S_1 = 50)} : E^*[U_2 \mid d] = \frac{2}{5} \cdot 20 + \frac{3}{5} \cdot 95 = 65, \quad \frac{10}{11} E^*[U_2 \mid d] = \frac{650}{11}, \quad U_1^d = \max\left\{70, \frac{650}{11}\right\} = 70.$$

$$E^*[U_1] = \frac{2}{5} \cdot \frac{120}{11} + \frac{3}{5} \cdot 70 = \frac{48}{11} + 42 = \frac{510}{11}, \quad \frac{1}{1+r} E^*[U_1] = \boxed{\frac{5100}{121}}.$$

$$Y_0 = 20, \quad \boxed{U_0 = \max\left\{20, \frac{5100}{121}\right\} = \frac{5100}{121} \approx 42.15}.$$

$$\alpha_t = \frac{U_{t+1}^u - U_{t+1}^d}{S_{t+1}^u - S_{t+1}^d}, \quad \beta_t = \frac{U_{t+1}^d - \alpha_t S_{t+1}^d}{1+r}.$$

$$\boxed{t=0} : \alpha_0 = \frac{\frac{120}{11} - 70}{200 - 50} = -\frac{13}{33}, \quad \beta_0 = \frac{70 - \alpha_0 \cdot 50}{1.1} = \frac{29600}{363}.$$

$$\boxed{t=1, u\text{-branch}} : \alpha_1^u = \frac{0 - 20}{400 - 100} = -\frac{1}{15}, \quad \beta_1^u = \frac{20 - \alpha_1^u \cdot 100}{1.1} = \frac{800}{33}.$$

$$\boxed{t=1, d\text{-branch}} : \alpha_1^d = \frac{20 - 95}{100 - 25} = -1, \quad \beta_1^d = \frac{95 - \alpha_1^d \cdot 25}{1.1} = \frac{1200}{11}.$$

$$C_0 = U_0 - 1 = \frac{5100}{121} - 1 = \frac{4979}{121}, \quad \Delta_0 := U_0 - C_0 = 1.$$

strategy Π : $\left\{ \text{long ACC for } C_0, \text{ short } (\alpha_0, \beta_0), \text{ deposit } B_0 = 1 \right\}$.

$$V_0(\Pi) = - \underbrace{C_0}_{\text{buy put}} + \underbrace{U_0}_{\text{short hedge}} - \underbrace{B_0}_{\text{bond deposit}} = 0.$$

Let

$$\tau^* = \min\{t \leq 2 : U_t = Y_t\} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the first move is } d, \\ 2, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

At the stopping time τ^* :

$$V_{\tau^*}(\Pi) = B_{\tau^*} + (Y_{\tau^*} - U_{\tau^*}) = \boxed{B_{\tau^*}}, \quad (Y_{\tau^*} - U_{\tau^*}) = 0.$$

first step	τ^*	arbitrage gain $V_{\tau^*}(\Pi)$
u	2	$B_2 = (1+r)^2 = 1.21$
d	1	$B_1 = (1+r) = 1.1$

Therefore the buyer locks in a strictly positive, risk-free profit whenever the American put is offered at $C_0 < U_0$, contradicting the no-arbitrage principle.

1. Consider the sample space $\Omega = \{1, 2, 3\}$ and the probability measure \mathbf{P} giving each point weight $1/3$. On this probability space consider the finite model with $T = 1$, $S_0^0 = S_1^0 = 1$, $S_0^1 = 2$, and

$$S_1^1(1) = 1, \quad S_1^1(2) = 2, \quad S_1^1(3) = 3.$$

- (a) This market is viable, so there is at least one EMM. Find all possible EMMs.
 (b) Compute $V_+(X)$ and $V_-(X)$ for the contingent claim X given by

$$X(1) = 1, \quad X(2) = 3, \quad X(3) = 9.$$

- (c) Find a trading strategy $\phi = (\phi_1^0, \phi_1^1)$ such that $V_1(\phi) \geq X$ and $V_0(\phi) = V_+(X)$.
 (d) Consider the contingent claim Y given by

$$Y(1) = 1, \quad Y(2) = 3, \quad Y(3) = 5.$$

Without actually finding a hedging strategy, show that Y can be replicated. [Hint: Use Corollary 3.5.2 on page 49 of the text.]

Part A

If there exists an EMM it must satisfy:

$$(1) \quad 1p_1 + 2p_2 + 3p_3 = E[S_1^1] = S_0^1 = 2$$

Also by the law of total probabilities

$$\sum_i p_i = 1, \quad p_i > 0$$

$$(2) \quad \Rightarrow p_1 + p_2 + p_3 = 1$$

$$\text{Subtracting (2) from (1): } 1p_1 + 2p_2 + 3p_3 = 2$$

$$- (p_1 + p_2 + p_3 = 1)$$

$$\hline p_2 + 2p_3 = 1$$

$$\Rightarrow p_2 = 1 - 2p_3 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Plugging (3) into (1): } 1p_1 + 2(1 - 2p_3) + 3p_3 = 2$$

$$\Rightarrow p_1 + 2 - p_3 = 2$$

$$\Rightarrow p_1 = p_3$$

We have all the probabilities in terms of one probability, p_3 :

We can write the probability space and determine the limits on p_3 .

$$\mathbf{P} = \{p_3, 1 - 2p_3, p_3\}$$

Considering equation 3 and setting p_2 to its lower bound of 0, we find by the law of total probabilities we find the bounds on p_3

$$1 - 2p_3 = 0 \Rightarrow p_3 = \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{Since } p_1 = p_3 \text{ and } p_1 + p_3 = 1 \\ \Rightarrow p_3 + p_3 + 3 = 1 \end{array}$$

$$1 - 2p_3 = 0 \Rightarrow p_3 = \frac{1}{2} \quad \Rightarrow p_3 = \frac{1}{2}$$

Therefore $0 < p_3 < \frac{1}{2}$

Math 194 Practice Final Exam (Student Made)

Problem 1. [Single-Period Forward with Continuous Compounding]

A non-dividend-paying stock is \$91 today. A forward contract maturing in $T = \frac{1}{3}$ year is quoted at \$93.

The continuously-compounded risk-free rate is $r = 6\%$ per annum.

- Write the no-arbitrage forward price formula $F_0 = S_0 e^{rT}$ and compute its value.
- Determine whether the quoted forward is overpriced or underpriced. Exhibit an arbitrage and compute the risk-free profit per share.

Solution.

- (a) General formula:

$$F_0 = S_0 e^{rT}.$$

Plugging $S_0 = 91$, $r = 0.06$, $T = \frac{1}{3}$:

$$F_0 = 91 e^{0.06/3} = 91 e^{0.02} = 91(1.020201) = 92.8423.$$

- (b) Quoted \$93 > \$92.8423 \Rightarrow overpriced.

Arbitrage strategy:

- Short the forward. • Borrow \$91 at r . • Buy the share.

Cash-flow today: $-91 + 91 = 0$. At T : deliver share, receive \$93; repay loan $91e^{0.02} = 92.8423$. Profit $93 - 92.8423 = 0.1577$ per share.

Problem 2. [Put-Call Parity Check]

For a non-dividend-paying stock $S_0 = \$120$ the following $T = \frac{1}{2}$ -year European option prices are posted:

$$C_0 = \$15, \quad P_0 = \$12, \quad K = \$110, \quad r_c = 5\% \text{ (cont. comp.)}.$$

- State put-call parity $C_0 - P_0 = S_0 - Ke^{-rT}$ and verify numerically.
- If P_0 were \$14 instead, construct an arbitrage and compute the initial and terminal cash-flows.

Solution.

- (a) Formula:

$$C_0 - P_0 = S_0 - Ke^{-rT}.$$

RHS = $120 - 110e^{-0.05 \cdot 0.5} = 120 - 110e^{-0.025} = 120 - 110(0.97531) = 120 - 107.284 = 12.716$. LHS = $15 - 12 = 3 \neq 12.716$. Parity violated.

- (b) With $P_0 = 14$ we have $C_0 - P_0 = 1 < 12.716$. Arbitrage: buy call (\$15), short put (+\$14), short stock (+\$120), invest net \$119 at r . Cash-flow 0 at maturity; profit $Ke^{-rT} - 1 = 11.716$.

Problem 3. [One-Period Binomial Replication]

Parameters:

$$S_0 = 50, \quad u = 1.4, \quad d = 0.6, \quad r = 0.1.$$

European call strike $K = 55$.

- Compute S_1^u, S_1^d .
- Compute risk-neutral $p^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d}$.
- Find call payoffs X^u, X^d and replication

$$\alpha = \frac{X^u - X^d}{S_1^u - S_1^d}, \quad \beta = \frac{uX^d - dX^u}{u - d} \cdot \frac{1}{1+r}.$$

- (d) Give no-arbitrage price $C_0 = \alpha S_0 + \beta$.

Solution.

(a) $S_1^u = 50(1.4) = 70$, $S_1^d = 50(0.6) = 30$.

(b) $p^* = \frac{1.1 - 0.6}{1.4 - 0.6} = 0.5$.

(c) $X^u = (70 - 55)^+ = 15$, $X^d = 0$.

$$\alpha = \frac{15 - 0}{70 - 30} = 0.375, \quad \beta = \frac{1.4 \cdot 0 - 0.6 \cdot 15}{0.8} \cdot \frac{1}{1.1} = \frac{-9}{0.8} \cdot \frac{1}{1.1} = -10.2273.$$

(d) $C_0 = 0.375 \cdot 50 - 10.2273 = 8.5227$.

Problem 4. [Super-hedging Price in Incomplete Market]

One-period, three-state:

$$S_0 = 4, \quad S_1 = (2, 4, 8),$$

bond $B_0 = B_1 = 1$, no interest. Consider payoff $X = (1, 3, 7)$.(a) Write super-hedging LP constraints $\alpha + \beta S_1(i) \geq X(i)$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$.(b) Solve for minimal cost $V_+ = \min_{\alpha, \beta}(\alpha + 4\beta)$ and give optimal (α^*, β^*) .**Solution.**

$$\begin{cases} \alpha + 2\beta \geq 1 \\ \alpha + 4\beta \geq 3 \\ \alpha + 8\beta \geq 7 \end{cases}$$

Constraints 1 and 3 bind; solve $\alpha + 2\beta = 1$, $\alpha + 8\beta = 7 \Rightarrow \beta = 1$, $\alpha = -1$. Cost = $-1 + 4(1) = 3$. Super-hedging price $V_+ = 3$.**Problem 5. [Two-Period Binomial Backward Induction]** $S_0 = 100$, $u = 1.5$, $d = 0.7$, $r = 0.05$, $T = 2$. European put $K = 120$.(a) Draw S -tree and list terminal put payoffs.(b) Compute p^* and price by backward induction:

$$P_t = \frac{1}{1+r} (p^* P_{t+1}^u + (1-p^*) P_{t+1}^d).$$

Solution.

$$p^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d} = \frac{1.05 - 0.7}{1.5 - 0.7} = 0.4375.$$

Terminal prices: $S_{uu} = 225$, $S_{ud} = S_{du} = 105$, $S_{dd} = 49$. Puts: 0, 15, 15, 71. Induction: at $t = 1$

$$P_u = \frac{1}{1.05} (0.4375 \cdot 0 + 0.5625 \cdot 15) = 8.0357, \quad P_d = \frac{1}{1.05} (0.4375 \cdot 15 + 0.5625 \cdot 71) = 42.3214.$$

At $t = 0$:

$$P_0 = \frac{1}{1.05} (0.4375 \cdot 8.0357 + 0.5625 \cdot 42.3214) = 27.083.$$

Problem 6. [Upper/Lower Prices in 3-State Incomplete Market] $S_0 = 3$, $S_1 = (2, 3, 6)$, bond flat. All EMMs:

$$P^c = (2c, 1 - 3c, c), \quad 0 < c < \frac{1}{3}.$$

Payoff $Y = (1, 4, 5)$.(a) Compute $\mathbb{E}^c[Y]$.(b) Give V_- , V_+ as $V_- = \inf_c \mathbb{E}^c[Y]$, $V_+ = \sup_c \mathbb{E}^c[Y]$.

Solution.

$$\mathbb{E}^c[Y] = 2c \cdot 1 + (1 - 3c)4 + c \cdot 5 = 4 - 4c + 5c = 4 + c.$$

Thus $V_- = 4$, $V_+ = 4 + \frac{1}{3} = \frac{13}{3}$.

Problem 7. [Replicability Criterion]

With the same market as Problem 6, determine for which constants a, b the payoff $Z = (a, b, 2b - a)$ is replicable.

Solution. Z is replicable iff $\mathbb{E}^c[Z]$ independent of c :

$$\mathbb{E}^c[Z] = 2ca + (1 - 3c)b + c(2b - a) = b + (2a - 3b)(c).$$

Independence requires $2a - 3b = 0 \Rightarrow a = \frac{3}{2}b$.

Problem 8. [Path-Dependent Max Option]

Two-period tree $S_0 = 10$, $u = 2$, $d = 0.5$, $r = 0$. Payoff $X = \max_{t \leq 2} S_t$.

(a) List X at each terminal node.

(b) Using unique EMM $p^* = 0.5$, compute price $C_0 = \mathbb{E}^*[X/(1+r)^2]$.

Solution. Paths (uu,ud,du,dd): S paths (10, 20, 40), (10, 20, 10), (10, 5, 10), (10, 5, 2.5). Maxima: 40, 20, 10, 10. Expectation = $0.25(40 + 20 + 10 + 10) = 20$. $C_0 = 20$.

Problem 9. [Forward Price with Dividend Yield]

Stock price \$60, continuous dividend yield $q = 2\%$. Rate $r = 7\%$, maturity $T = 0.75$.

$$F_0 = S_0 e^{(r-q)T}.$$

Compute F_0 .

Solution. $F_0 = 60e^{(0.07-0.02)0.75} = 60e^{0.0375} = 60(1.0382) = 62.29$.

Problem 10. [Black-Scholes Call Pricing]

$S_0 = 50$, $K = 55$, $T = 0.5$, $r = 4\%$, $\sigma = 0.3$.

$$d_{\pm} = \frac{\ln(S_0/K) + (r \pm \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2)T}{\sigma\sqrt{T}}, \quad C_0 = S_0\Phi(d_+) - Ke^{-rT}\Phi(d_-).$$

Compute d_{\pm} (4 decimals) and C_0 .

Solution.

$$d_+ = \frac{\ln(50/55) + 0.04 \cdot 0.5 + 0.5 \cdot 0.3^2 \cdot 0.5}{0.3\sqrt{0.5}} = \frac{-0.09531 + 0.02 + 0.0225}{0.2121} = -0.2485,$$

$d_- = d_+ - 0.2121 = -0.4606$. $\Phi(d_+) = 0.4013$, $\Phi(d_-) = 0.3227$.

$$C_0 = 50(0.4013) - 55e^{-0.02}(0.3227) = 20.065 - 54.013(0.3227) = 20.065 - 17.425 = 2.640.$$

Final Exam Cheat Sheet

One-Period *Binomial Model* (core set-up)

Let

$$S_0 > 0, \quad u > 1, \quad 0 < d < 1, \quad r > -1, \quad B_t = (1+r)^t.$$

Define risk-neutral probabilities

$$\boxed{p^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d}}, \quad \boxed{q^* = 1 - p^*}.$$

The *discounted* stock price $S_t := \frac{S_t}{(1+r)^t}$ is a martingale under \mathbb{P}^* :

$$\mathbb{E}^*[S_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t] = S_t.$$

European Call/Put Pay-off Functions

$$Y_t^{\text{call}} = (S_t - K)^+, \quad Y_t^{\text{put}} = (K - S_t)^+.$$

Inside the tree this can be shown by a *green* payoff tree:

Risk-Neutral Pricing Recursion

$$\boxed{V_t = \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[V_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t]}, \quad V_T = Y_T.$$

For a European derivative this yields the familiar tree-backward induction.

Replicating (α, β) Strategy

$$\alpha_t = \frac{V_{t+1}^u - V_{t+1}^d}{S_t(u - d)},$$

$$\beta_t = \frac{u V_{t+1}^d - d V_{t+1}^u}{(u - d)(1+r)^{t+1}}$$

Self-financing condition

$$V_t = \alpha_t S_t + \beta_t B_t, \quad B_t = (1+r)^t.$$

$$\Delta V_t = \alpha_t \Delta S_t + \beta_t \Delta B_t, \quad B_t = (1+r)^t.$$

American Option via Snell Envelope

$$U_T = Y_T, \quad U_t = \max\left\{Y_t, \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t]\right\}, \quad 0 \leq t < T.$$

Optimal stopping time (first hitting time of equality):

$$\tau = \inf\{t : U_t = Y_t\}.$$

Seller's (ask) price equals U_0 . The hedge is obtained by plugging U_{t+1}^u, U_{t+1}^d into the same (α, β) formulas above.

$$\delta_t := U_t - \frac{1}{1+r} \mathbb{E}^*[U_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t] \geq 0.$$

$$\boxed{\text{European call price} \leq \text{American call price}},$$

$$\boxed{\text{European put price} \geq \text{American put price}}.$$

Trade Start Snapshot (*pink block in sheet*)

$$\boxed{\xi_t = U_t^u - U_t^d}, \quad \boxed{\beta_t = \frac{U_t^d - \xi_t S_{t-1}}{(1+r)^t}}.$$

(These coincide with (α_t, β_t) when the early-exercise rule selects the continuation value.)

Hedge Wealth Tree

Keep the largest nodes row-by-row: $V_t \geq Y_t$ ensures super-hedging.

Martingale vs. Discounting Comment (brown)

$$\mathbb{E}^*\left[\frac{S_{t+1}}{1+r} \mid \mathcal{F}_t\right] = S_t \iff \mathbb{E}^*[S_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t] = (1+r)S_t.$$

$$\mathbb{E}^*[S_t | \mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = \frac{S_{t-1}}{1+r} (p^*u + (1-p^*)d) = S_{t-1}.$$

Thus $\frac{S_t}{(1+r)^t}$ is a martingale, while S_t itself is a *sub-martingale* under the real-world measure if and only if $\mathbb{E}[S_{t+1} | \mathcal{F}_t] \geq (1+r)S_t$.

Classic Example (two-period American put)

(a) $S_0 = 4, u = \frac{3}{2}, d = \frac{2}{3}, r = \frac{1}{4}, K = 5$. Compute U_0 . *Solution sketched by colour-coded boxes in the original:*

$$p^* = \frac{(1+r) - d}{u - d} = \frac{1.25 - \frac{2}{3}}{\frac{3}{2} - \frac{2}{3}} = \frac{7}{15}, \quad q^* = \frac{8}{15}.$$

$$V_2^{uu} = (S_0 u^2 - K)^+ = (9 - 5)^+ = 4, \quad V_2^{ud} = (S_0 u d - K)^+ = (6 - 5)^+ = 1, \quad V_2^{dd} = 0.$$

Working backwards one finds $U_1^u = 4$, $U_1^d = 1$ (no early exercise), hence

$$U_0 = \frac{1}{1.25} \left(\frac{7}{15} \cdot 4 + \frac{8}{15} \cdot 1 \right) = \boxed{\frac{52}{75}} \approx 0.6933.$$

(Recall: $d = \tau - T + 1$, so each backward step multiplies by $(1+r)^{-1}$.)

(b) Verify the replicating (α, β) : $\alpha_0 = \frac{V_1^u - V_1^d}{S_0(u-d)}$, $\beta_0 = \dots$

(c) Check self-financing: $\Delta V_t = \alpha_{t+1} \Delta S_t + \beta_{t+1} \Delta B_t$.

★ **Stopping Times:** τ is a stopping time if $\{\tau \leq t\} \in \mathcal{F}_t$ for every t .

★ **Arbitrage Bound:** $(K - S_0)^+ \leq V_0 \leq S_0$ for a put; reverse for a call.

★ **Beta-Sum Identity (purple handwriting):** $\beta_t = \sum_{s=t}^{T-1} \frac{-\alpha_{s+1} (\Delta S_{s+1})}{(1+r)^{s-t+1}}$.

★ **Arbitrage portfolio (FTAP test):** If a strategy satisfies $V_0(\phi) = 0$, $V_T(\phi) \geq 0$, $\mathbb{P}[V_T(\phi) > 0] > 0$, then ϕ is an arbitrage and an *equivalent martingale measure does not exist*.

★ **Trade End Profit:** $\Pi = V_T - Y_T$. Positive Π indicates successful arbitrage.

Incomplete-Market “Quick-Reference” Block

$$\boxed{V_0^+(X) = S_0^0 \sup_{Q \in \mathcal{M}} \mathbb{E}^Q[X]}, \quad \boxed{V_0^-(X) = S_0^0 \inf_{Q \in \mathcal{M}} \mathbb{E}^Q[X]}.$$

$$\boxed{X \text{ replicable} \iff V_0^+(X) = V_0^-(X) \iff \mathbb{E}^{Q_1}[X] = \mathbb{E}^{Q_2}[X] \quad \forall Q_1, Q_2 \in \mathcal{M}}.$$

$$\boxed{C_0 > V_0^+(X) \Rightarrow \text{Seller's arbitrage}}, \quad \boxed{C_0 < V_0^-(X) \Rightarrow \text{Buyer's arbitrage}}.$$

$$\alpha = \frac{V^u - V^d}{S_0(u-d)}, \quad \beta = \frac{uV^d - dV^u}{(u-d)(1+r)}, \quad V_0 = \frac{1}{1+r} (p^*V^u + q^*V^d).$$

$$u = e^{\sigma\sqrt{\Delta t}}, \quad d = e^{-\sigma\sqrt{\Delta t}}, \quad p^* = \frac{e^{r\Delta t} - d}{u-d} \approx \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{r - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2}{\sigma} \sqrt{\Delta t} \right).$$

$$d_{\pm} = \frac{\ln(S_0/K) + (r \pm \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2)T}{\sigma\sqrt{T}}, \quad \Phi(z) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^z e^{-x^2/2} dx.$$

$$\boxed{C_0 = S_0 \Phi(d_+) - K e^{-rT} \Phi(d_-)}, \quad \boxed{P_0 = K e^{-rT} \Phi(-d_-) - S_0 \Phi(-d_+)}.$$

$$\boxed{C_0 - P_0 = S_0 - K e^{-rT}} \quad (\text{put-call parity}), \quad \boxed{\mu = r - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2} \quad (\text{risk-neutral drift}).$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} S_0 u^{N_u} d^{N_d} = S_0 \exp\left((r - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2)T + \sigma W_T\right) \quad \text{with } N_u - N_d \sim \text{Binomial}(n, p^*).$$

$$\boxed{\alpha_t = \frac{U_{t+1}^u - U_{t+1}^d}{S_t(u-d)}}, \quad \boxed{\beta_t = \frac{U_{t+1}^d - \alpha_t S_t d}{(1+r)^{t+1}}} = \frac{u U_{t+1}^d - d U_{t+1}^u}{(u-d)(1+r)^{t+1}}.$$

we've seen options
 $Y = \begin{cases} (K - S_t)^+ & \text{Put} \\ (S_t - K)^+ & \text{Call} \end{cases}$
 or
 $Y = \max \text{ or } \text{Avg} \{ Y_0, Y_1, Y_2 \}$

Exercise now if Y wins ($F \geq V$)
 Or wait otherwise.
 $Y_1^d = 3, U_1^d = 3 \rightarrow Z = 1$
 $Y_1^u = 0, U_1^d = .40 \rightarrow Z = 2$

2) $F_{max} \rightarrow E^*[S_1^u | F_0] = S_0^u, E^*[S_1^d | F_0] = S_0^d$
 $E^*[X | F_0] = E^*[S]$
 $S^1(u_1) = 5, S^1(u_2) = 1, S^2(u_1) = 1, S^2(u_2) = 3$
 $S \cdot p^* + (1-p^*) = 2, 1 \cdot p^* + 3 \cdot (1-p^*) = 2$
 and solve \rightarrow no p^* makes both discounted stock price process into martingale \Rightarrow No EM

$V_0(\phi) = 0, V_1(\phi) \geq 0, P[V_1(\phi) > 0] > 0$
 $\Rightarrow \phi$ is an arbitrage \Rightarrow No EM

Mart E
 $E^*[S_t | F_{t-1}] = \frac{1}{(1+r)^t} E^*[S_{t-1} | F_{t-1}]$

Europe: $V_T(\phi) < V_t \rightarrow -V_T(\phi)$
 $= d^* S_T + \beta^* B_T + (C_0 - V_0) B_T$
 $-X = X + (C_0 - V_0) B_T - X = (C_0 - V_0) B_T > 0$

Trade stat E Mart
 $\frac{1}{(1+r)^t} E^*[V^*] = E^*[V^*]$
 $E^*[V^*] = E^*[V^*] + E^*[X^*]$
 $V_0(\phi) = \alpha \cdot S_0^* + \beta \cdot B_0^* + \gamma \cdot C_0 = V_0(\phi)$

$V_1^d = [Y_2^{dd}(q^d) + Y_2^{du}(p^d)] \cdot \beta$
 $V_1^u = [Y_2^{ud}(q^u) + Y_2^{uu}(p^u)] \cdot \beta$
 $V_0 = [V_1^d(q^d) + V_1^u(p^d)] \cdot \beta$
 U wealth tree.

Keep the largest nodes from Y/V trees
 U_0, U_1, U_2
 $S^*, V_0^*, U_t^* = \frac{S_t, V_t, U_t}{(1+r)^t}$
 $Z^* = \text{first } t \text{ (min } t)$
 $\text{St. } Y_t = U$
 Price of European call, Price of an American call.

1) $Z = 1$
 $Z = 2$

2) $Z = 1, Z = 2$
 $Z = 2$

$E[Z_1] > E[Z_2] > E[Z_2]$
 self financing E

$a_t = \frac{V_t^u - V_t^d}{(u-d)} \cdot \frac{1}{S_{t-1}}$
 $\beta_t = \frac{(uV_t^d - V_t^u)}{(u-d)} \cdot \frac{1}{(1+r)^t}$

self financing E
 $V_{t-1} = \frac{1}{(1+r)^t} E^*[V_t | F_{t-1}]$
 $= \frac{1}{(1+r)^t} E^*[E^*[X | F_t] | F_{t-1}]$
 $\Rightarrow E^*[X | F_{t-1}]$

$d = T - t + 1$
 $V_T(\phi) - Y_T = V_T(\phi^*) + Y_T^* - V_T^* = -V_T^*(\phi^*)$
 $V_T(\phi^*) - Y_T = V_T(\phi^*) + (C_0 - V_0) B_T - Y_T$
 $V_T(\phi^*) - V_T = V_T(\phi^*) + (C_0 - V_0) B_T - Y_T$
 $V_T(\phi^*) - V_T = V_T(\phi^*) + (C_0 - V_0) B_T - Y_T$
 Sellers

Trade Stat
 $V_0(\phi) = \alpha_0^* S_0^* + \beta_0^* B_0^* + \gamma_0^* C_0$
 $= \text{Same } V_0^* + S_0^* + \gamma_0^* C_0$
 $= \frac{1}{(1+r)^t} E^*[U_t] + u_{t-1}$
 $= u_{t-1}$

Mart AM
 $\alpha_t^* = \alpha_t^* - \frac{1}{(1+r)^t} E^*[U_{t+1} | F_t]$
 $\beta_t^* = \beta_t^* + \frac{1}{(1+r)^t} E^*[U_{t+1} | F_t]$
 $\gamma_t^* = \gamma_t^*$

$\alpha_t^* S_t^* + \beta_t^* B_t^* + \gamma_t^* C_t = V_t(\phi)$
 $\frac{1}{(1+r)^t} E^*[U_{t+1} | F_t] + \left(\frac{1}{1+r}\right) B_t$
 $= \left(\frac{u}{1+r}\right) \left(\frac{1}{1+r}\right) B_t + \left(\frac{1}{1+r}\right) B_t + S = d_t^* S_t^* + \beta_t^* B_t^* + \gamma_t^* C_t = V_t(\phi)$

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 $= d_t^* S_t^* + \beta_t^* B_t^* + \gamma_t^* C_t = V_t(\phi)$